

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC POLICIES ON MIGRANTS IN EUROPE

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

COVID-19 - Coronavirus Disease

CS - Case Study

IT - Information Technology

LAU - Local administrative unit

NUTS - Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques

MATILDE - Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance Integration and Local Development in European Rural and Mountain Regions

TCN - Third Country National

WP - Working Package

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE POLICY BRIEFS

This document presents the impact assessments of a range of policies on migrants' interaction with the social and economic structure of the remote and rural areas in the MATILDE countries – Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Italy, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and in the United Kingdom.

Each report includes firstly a systematic gathering of information on existing policies that have a direct/indirect impact on migrants' interaction with the social economic structure of remote and rural areas. This includes also those policies that were not designed for this purpose but nonetheless contribute to shape such an interaction. The information for this task has been collected by means of desk research and informants' interviews.

Secondly, for each country we carried out a meta-analysis/literature review on the existing literature/research that has focused on assessing traditional and foundational economics as well as social migrants' impact in rural and remote areas in their country of settlement. The overall purpose of the meta-analysis was to pick up those elements that extant studies have indicated as drivers or barriers to social/economic integration and development. This review focuses on recent research – notably those produced in the last 10years – however it may include relevant research produced outside that period.

Thirdly, each report includes an assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of the policies and services explored through semi-structured interviews. A range of stakeholders has been consulted in gathering this information on the migration-related policies and governance in the socio-economic realm – policy makers and public officers, public service providers, practitioners and organizations working on migration related fields, social policies and territorial planning, experts/scholars, (social) entrepreneurs (both TCN and native) and other relevant stakeholder (e.g. unions' representatives, employers' organization leaders, etc.).

Finally, each country report includes two separate conclusions, describing if and how policy related factors act on the one side on the migrants' impact into the country economy and on the other on their social inclusion/impact. This final section also includes an inventory of good practices.

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2. AUSTRIA

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1.1 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC RELATED POLICIES REGARDING TCNS INTEGRATION AND IMPACT IN THE COUNTRY AND ITS SELECTED REMOTE AREA(S)

To give a thorough overview of the most relevant policies regarding TCN integration and impact in the country this description focusses on four main policy areas in Austria: i) residence & asylum, ii) integration (with a focus on language support) iii) labour market, and iv) social welfare (social protection, housing, health).

RESIDENCE & ASYLUM

IMMIGRATION AND RESIDENCE

Entry into Austria is regulated by the **Aliens Police Act** (FPG 2005¹). The **Security Police Act** (SPG²) includes i.e. the passport system and the surveillance of entry into/exit from Austria. If TCNs aim to stay in Austria for more than six months, they require a residence permit (**NAG**³). For their initial application, they have to give proof of elementary German language skills at the simplest level in the form of a language diploma (speaking German before immigrating to Austria) (§21a para. 1 NAG) (comparable with A1-level of Common European Framework of Reference for Languages – CEFR; this proof is according to §21 para. 3 NAG not required for artists in certain fields of art). The possibilities of immigration to Austria are precisely regulated and very limited. A temporary residence permit (the first residence permit is issued only for a certain time) is issued basically for reasons of

¹ BGBl. I Nr. 100/2005.

² BGBl. Nr. 566/1991.

³ BGBl. I Nr. 100/2005.

labour migration (employed or self-employed activities, for artists and researchers) or family reunion (§ 8 par. 1 NAG). In addition, there is also the possibility of obtaining a residence permit as a pupil or student (§ 63 and § 64 NAG). In Austria, the first issue of a residence permit is regulated by a quota system. A residence permit (Red-White-Red - Card) will only be issued if the following conditions are met: proof of income in the amount of (according to the equalisation supplement reference rates since 1.1.2021) € 1,000.48 for single persons and € 1,578.36 for married couples, health insurance, accommodation, proof of no threat to public order or security. In order to be able to apply for a Red-White-Red - Card as a "skilled worker in a shortage profession", a binding job offer in Austria must already be presented; as a "particularly highly qualified person", a TCN can enter Austria for the purpose of seeking work by means of a visa; as soon as a suitable job has been found, the Red-White-Red - Card can be applied for (migration.gv.at 2021a). In the case of labour market migration by the mean of a so-called Red-White-Red - Card, a positive statement of the regional labour market service is required (§41 par. 1 NAG). Immigration as a skilled worker in a shortage profession (for the list of shortage professions that addresses regional labour market needs, see Skilled Workers Directive 2021⁴) is one of the few possibilities for non-highly qualified persons to migrate legally to Austria. Moreover, immigration regulations have been repeatedly tightened over the years (see the act amending the law on aliens, **FräG2018**⁵), Asylum & asylum procedure

The granting or withdrawal of asylum is regulated by the **Asylum Act**, the asylum procedure by the **BFA-VG**⁶. Court of Appeal is the Federal Administrative Court (**BVwGG**⁷), which replaced the Asylum Court (**AsylGHG**, **Asylgerichtshof-Einrichtungsgesetz**⁸). Over the years, the Asylum Acts have been tightened: **Asylum Act**

⁴ BGBl. II Nr. 595/2020.

⁵ BGBl. I Nr. 56/2018.

⁶ BGBl. I Nr. 87/2012.

⁷ BGBl. I Nr. 10/2013.

⁸ BGBl. I Nr. 4/2008.

1991⁹ made reception more difficult, **Asylum Act 1997**¹⁰ introduced rapid asylum procedures (within ~5 working days) to sort out where it is clear that the application has to be rejected, **Asylum Act amendment 2003**¹¹ implemented the "prohibition of new information" in a later interview or the possibility of refolement at the border, if entering from a secure country. Further tightening was made in 2005¹² (**Aliens Law Package 2005**, representing the most comprehensive reform of foreigners' law since 1945; Schumacher 2005, 2), 2014 and **2016**¹³: now, asylum status is granted only for three years. If the evaluation of the political situation in the country of origin shows a positive change, a procedure to withdraw the right to asylum is initiated, otherwise the asylum title becomes indefinite.

The provision of basic care during the asylum procedure is regulated by the Federal Law on Basic Services (**GVG-B 2005**¹⁴). Moreover, the agreement between Federal Government and Federal States (**Grundversorgungsvereinbarung – Art. 15a B-VG**¹⁵) secure a nationwide uniform basic care provision and should avoid regional overloading (considering the relation of asylum seekers to the resident population). Each Federal State has a separate basic care provision law (e.g. **Kärntner Grundversorgungsgesetz**¹⁶; **Art. 15a B-VG – Grundversorgungsvereinbarung Vorarlberg**¹⁷). 2015-2018 the **Federal Constitutional Law on the**

⁹ BGBl. Nr. 8/1992.

¹⁰ BGBl. I Nr. 76/1997.

¹¹ BGBl. I Nr. 101/2003.

¹² BGBl. I Nr. 100/2005.

¹³ BGBl. I Nr. 70/2015.

¹⁴ BGBl. Nr. 405/1991.

¹⁵ BGBl. I Nr. 80/2004.

¹⁶ LGBl Nr 43/2006.

¹⁷ LGBl.Nr. 39/2004.

Accommodation and Distribution of Foreigners in Need of Assistance and Protection¹⁸ was in force obliging municipalities (districts) to accommodate asylum seekers in the amount of 1.5% of the resident population.

With the Federal Act on the Establishment of the Federal Agency for Care and Support Services (Bundesagentur für Betreuungs- und Unterstützungsleistungen GmbH, **BBU-G**¹⁹) which is assigned to the Ministry of the Interior, from 2020 onwards the agency took over the basic care for foreigners in need of help and protection, as well as starting by 2021, the legal advice, return counselling and return assistance, the provision of human rights observers to monitor deportations and, the provision of interpreters in proceedings. So far, legal and return counselling for asylum seekers has been provided by external service providers, primarily non-profit organizations, and the initial care of refugees by private companies in federal institutions. Under this law, both areas are provided by a state agency. Following nationalization, opposition parties (Republik Österreich 2019a) and NGOs (ORF 2020) have questioned the independence of legal counselling. However, the law states that the legal advisers can work independently and without being bound by instructions.

INTEGRATION

The legal basis for integration policies is the **Integration Act** (IntG²⁰), introduced in 2017. The Integration Act regulates the central framework conditions for the integration of persons entitled to asylum, subsidiary protection and legally settled TCNs, in the areas of language and orientation. The attendance and participation in German language courses and “values and orientation” courses (WOK) are mandatory and non-attendance is sanctioned. Either a “declaration of integration” (persons entitled to asylum, subsidiary protection) or an

¹⁸ BGBl. I Nr. 120/2015.

¹⁹ BGBl. I Nr. 53/2019.

²⁰ BGBl. I Nr. 68/2017.

“integration agreement”_(TCNs) is signed. The **implementing regulation** of the Integration Act (IntDV) (Durchführungsverordnung²¹) regulates the uniform quality standards.

For young people of more than 15 years of age (end of compulsory school age) up to 18 years of age the **“Mandatory Training Act”** (Ausbildungspflichtgesetz²²) has been implemented in 2016, which demands compulsory training up to the age of 18. Another important education and training opportunity for teenagers and adults involves the “lifelong learning initiative” which is already in its third period (2018-2021). It focusses on two main program areas: basic education and basic skills training for educationally disadvantaged adults (starting at the age of 16) and the catch up of the compulsory school leaving certificate.

Language training in compulsory education in schools is regulated in the **Education Reform Act** (Bildungsreformgesetz²³), which came into effect in 2017. Since the beginning of the school year 2018/19 pupils in compulsory schools (primary and lower secondary level) who are classified as ‘extraordinary pupils’ due to a lack of knowledge of the teaching language have been taught in German support classes and German training courses.

LABOUR MARKET

The Aliens Employment Act (**AuslBG**²⁴) regulates the employment of foreigners who only can be employed if the employer has obtained an employment permit (valid for one year or the apprenticeship duration). The foreign employees must not be treated worse than domestic employees (wages, working conditions).

Austria has introduced a system of criteria-based labour immigration for TCNs, which supports the immigration of highly qualified TCNs and professionals in professions with a shortage of skilled workers in order to cover

²¹ BGBl. II Nr. 286/2019.

²² BGBl. I Nr. 62/2016.

²³ BGBl. I Nr. 138/2017.

²⁴ BGBl. Nr. 218/1975.

domestic labour requirements. Depending on the group of persons willing to immigrate, there are different criteria that must be fulfilled. For the groups mentioned below, which are particularly needed on the labour market, the criteria-based, transparent system is intended to facilitate immigration for these groups of persons: particularly highly qualified persons, skilled workers in shortage professions, other key professionals, graduates of an Austrian university, self-employed key professionals, and start-up founders (migration.gv.at 2020). For each of these groups of labour migrants, criteria have been defined which, depending on the extent to which they are met, increase the chance of immigration opportunities. The fulfilment of the criteria is assessed with points. Every person willing to immigrate can use this points calculator (scoring system) available online to find out how many points he/she would receive and whether an application for immigration could be successful. The following criteria, among others, are assessed (based on the example of skilled workers in shortage professions): qualification (completed vocational training in the shortage profession, qualification for university entrance, graduation at Bachelor level), years of adequate work experience (also in Austria), German language skills (5 points for A1-level, 10 points for A2-level, 15 points for B1-level), English language skills (5 points for A2-level, 10 points for B1-level), and age of person (15 points for under 30 years-old, 10 points for over 30 years-old). The person has to reach at least 55 out of 90 points (migration.gv.at 2021b).

ACCREDITATION OF QUALIFICATIONS

The Recognition and Assessment Act (**AuBG**²⁵) aims to simplify and regulate procedures for the recognition of foreign educations or professions and set up counselling centres.

VOLUNTARY INTEGRATION YEAR

For people granted asylum and subsidiary protection the entry to the labour market is often very difficult. In order to promote the integration of refugees and subsidiary protection beneficiaries, the voluntary integration

²⁵ BGBl. I Nr. 55/2016.

year was established to strengthen the inclusion in social life, to foster the learning of “Austrian values” as well as the German language by gaining first work experience. Furthermore, it should help to provide career orientation and deepen previous educational skills, promote personality development, the expansion and application of knowledge for various occupational fields, the strengthening of social and intercultural skills and the social commitment of the participants (§27c **FreiwG**²⁶). Through the work in public welfare and non-profit organizations (§27d para. 1 **FreiwG**) during the voluntary integration year the people granted asylum and subsidiary protection gain not only work experience and improve their German language skills, but also get in contact with colleagues and natives and perhaps even make friends.

INTEGRATION YEAR BASED ON THE INTEGRATION YEAR ACT

The integration year based on the Integration Year Act (IJG²⁷) aims to accelerate the labour market integration of recognized refugees, people entitles to subsidiary protection and asylum seekers who, according to experience, are very likely to be granted asylum, by offering measures that foster the acquisition of German language skills and improve the chances of sustainable integration into the labour market. The target group, mentioned above, who have been in Austria since 31 December 2014 and are still registered as unemployed can participate in the integration year. The measures provided by the public employment service (AMS) include competence clearing, German language courses (beginning at A2-level), clarification and support in the recognition of qualifications and certificates, values and orientation courses in cooperation with the Austrian Integration Fund, vocational orientation and job application training, job preparation measures, and work trainings (§5 para. 3 IJG). During the one-year training, refugees and people entitles to subsidiary protection get an allowance to cover living expenses and to cover course costs, asylum seekers are further provided by basic care (AMS 2020a).

²⁶ BGBl. I Nr. 17/2012.

²⁷ BGBl. I Nr. 75/2017.

EMPLOYMENT OF ASYLUM SEEKERS

During the first three months of the asylum procedure there is an absolute ban on employment. Afterwards, asylum seekers can be employed as seasonal workers (in agriculture or in tourism) for a maximum of six months (“**Bartenstein-Erlass**”²⁸), for domestic services in private households (e.g. cleaning, mowing the lawn, supervising children) or become self-employed. In order not to lose basic care (i.a. accommodation, food, clothing, 40 € monthly pocket money, health care, information on orientation in Austria and voluntary return, costs of school attendance for children, costs for structuring of the daily routine (Art. 6 para. 1 Grundversorgungsvereinbarung – Art. 15a B-VG), asylum seekers are not allowed to earn more than €110/month (AMS 2020b; Fonds Soziales Wien 2020). Furthermore, they can become volunteers to expand knowledge and skills, carry out charitable work for public authorities (e.g. maintenance of parks and sports facilities for a low recognition fee) or support activities directly related to their accommodation (e.g. cleaning, kitchen operations, maintenance) (GVG-B 2005²⁹).

APPRENTICESHIPS FOR YOUNG ASYLUM SEEKERS

A decree in 2012³⁰ made it possible for asylum seekers up to the age of 18 years to start an apprenticeship during their asylum procedure. With the decree in 2013³¹ the age limit was raised up to 25 years for starting an apprenticeship. With decree of the year 2015³² apprenticeships are possible in all professions recorded in the

²⁸ GZ 435.006/6-II/7/2004.

²⁹ BGBl. I Nr. 100/2005.

³⁰ GZ: BMASK-435.006/0005-VI/AMR/7/2012.

³¹ GZ: BMASK-435.006/0005-VI/B/7/2013.

³² GZ: BMASK-435.006/0009-VI/B/7/2015.

list of shortage professions. In 2018³³, the decree from 2015, covering also the regulations of 2013, was repealed, argued by the large number of domestic and foreign young people looking for a job. Hence, since autumn 2018, young asylum seekers are not allowed to start an apprenticeship any longer.

SOCIAL WELFARE

In the policy area of social welfare, the focus is on the legal basis of minimum income and housing. Starting with the **needs-based minimum benefit** (Bedarfsorientierte Mindestsicherung, BMS) this social welfare scheme instrument was introduced in September 2010 by means of a Federal-State Agreement between the Federal Government and the Federal States throughout the country³⁴. It has replaced the social welfare regulations that previously were decided by each Federal State. The BMS serves to support subsistence and housing cost and also covers access to health care provision. The agreement expired at the end of 2016 and since then it has been referred back to the Federal States as the responsible administrative scale. In order to change this situation, a basic federal law was created, which came into force on 1 June 2019. The implementation of the **Basic Act on Social Assistance** (Sozialhilfe-Grundsatzgesetz 2019³⁵) under Article 12 of the Federal Constitution (B-VG) includes a binding framework as well as a number of so-called "optional provisions". Implementation of the Basic Act on Social Assistance has not yet taken place in all Federal States, in the Austrian MATILDE regions the **law on guaranteed minimum income** in Vorarlberg and in Carinthia is still in force (until 2021).

Housing policy lies by constitution with the **competence of the Federal States**. Here we will focus on the legal approach for Vorarlberg that includes also TCNs and persons of asylum or subsidiary protection in its welfare

³³ GZ: BMASGK-435.006/0013-VI/B/7/2018.

³⁴ Federal state laws based on agreement between Federal government and Federal states (Art. 15a B-VG).

³⁵ BGBl. I Nr. 41/2019.

schemes. The **Housing Subsidy Act** (Wohnbauförderungsgesetz³⁶) of 1989 regulates the promotion of the construction and renewal of housing and the granting of housing assistance in Vorarlberg. In 2014, the provincial government of Vorarlberg adopted the **provincial Housing Allocation/Procurement Directive** (Wohnungsvergaberichtlinie³⁷), which is the first binding provincial directive. It regulates the target groups who can register for a rented flat or for "assisted living" and how housing supply is allocated to applicants via the municipalities. Persons entitled to asylum and subsidiary protection are also eligible. While the **New Building Subsidies Directive for public housing 2020/2021** (Neubauförderungsrichtlinien für den privaten/öffentlichen Wohnbau³⁸) regulates how the housing subsidy is awarded and calculated (Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung 2020b), the **Directive for Housing Allowance (Wohnbeihilferichtlinie 2019)**³⁹ supports the cost of housing. Apart from other groups it is eligible for long-term TCNs and beneficiaries of asylum and subsidiary protection.

³⁶ LGBl.Nr. 31/1989.

³⁷ Amt der Vorarlberger Landesregierung, Wohnungsvergaberichtlinie 2015.

³⁸ Vorarlberger Landesregierung, Neubauförderungsrichtlinie 2020/2021 für den privaten Wohnbau, 6.11.2019.

³⁹ Vorarlberger Landesregierung, Wohnbeihilferichtlinie 2019, 20.11.2018.

1.2 OVERVIEW ON EXISTING ANALYSES AND ASSESSMENTS OF ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL POLICIES

RESIDENCE & ASYLUM

Residency and citizenship, the necessary permits and the associated legal and administrative framework and their development and impact have been the main focus of previous research efforts in connection with migration policy in Austria. The efforts have been conducted by various actors, including public authorities, academic institutions, private research actors and NGOs. The National Contact Point Austria in the European Migration Network, which is the country office of the International Organization for Migration (IOM), can be mentioned as a particularly active research actor.

The distinction between temporary residence and long-term settlement in Austria takes the form of various residence permits and the associated rights and obligations represent an important aspect of Austrian migration policy (Kratzmann et al. 2011, p. 62). Special focus was often placed on the group of TCNs who came to Austria as asylum seekers, especially from 2015 onwards. The attempt to assess and further forecast the economic impact of this immigration has also resulted in the recognition that there is a need for better intersection management, since the basic care, which includes the accommodation of asylum seekers, is a complex system that requires the cooperation of many actors (Berger et al. 2016).

This interplay of actors was also critically reviewed with a focus on residence permits, as the often long processing times are considered as a hindrance for TCNs aiming at studying at an Austrian University (Bassermann 2019). Differences per Federal State in the official procedures for citizenship were found not only in terms of the duration of the procedures, but also in terms of the documents that are accepted as proof of the many requirements. Furthermore, knowledge of the German language, in particular, increased in importance in policies over time. While in 1985 a mere "knowledge of the German language" was still considered as a prerequisite to acquire citizenship, actually, level B1 was set according to the European standard (Stiller 2019).

In order to support start-up founders to establish their company in Austria, a separate residence permit (Red-White-Red - Card for start-up founders) was created, which is, however, difficult to obtain due to the underlying criteria-based scoring system (Spiegelfeld 2019).

INTEGRATION (INCLUDING EDUCATION AND LANGUAGE TRAINING)

The Integration Act (IntG), introduced in 2017, is for the first time a nationwide uniform basis for integration efforts in the direction of values and orientation, and language training. The target group of the act are persons entitled to asylum and subsidiary protection from the age of 15, attendance and participation in German language course and values and orientation courses (WOK) are mandatory. Asylum seekers, “with a high probability to stay”, (which is not clearly defined) are eligible to participate in language courses. The obligation of the attendance to values and orientation courses is seen to be two-fold: although, it might be important to teach and “learn” the values, which is appreciated by most of the course participants as an evaluation confirms (Güngör 2017) critique goes, that “values are not teachable, but are the nonenforceable result of the reflection process of personal experience” (Friesl et al. 2009, 33). It is the acceptance of the values, that is crucial to create a link to a community. A stereotypical exam on values is not considered helpful for achieving community (Fritz 2017) and deploys a “conviction that our values and institutions are superior to others’, and may, or even should, be imposed on them to their benefit” (Hobsbawm 2007: 77). It is doubted whether a test can shed light on this (Hofer-Robinson 2018). Moreover, the discourse about values evokes the image of a homogenous community that agrees on a concerted set of values to organise everyday life, different from those of immigrants (Hofer 2016) and presenting a stereotypical image of the Austrian society (Boeckmann 2018).

The **Education Reform Act** came into effect in **2017** and focuses in particular on language training in compulsory education in schools. Since the beginning of the school year 2018/19 pupils in compulsory schools (primary and lower secondary level) who are classified as extraordinary pupils due to a lack of knowledge of the teaching language have been taught in **German support classes and German training courses**. This separation in specific German learning classes is justified by the government with the argument that the knowledge of teaching language is a prerequisite for integration. German support classes are contested by language experts (Rosenberger and Gruber 2020, SOS Mitmensch 2018) who argue that peer to peer German language learning is aggravated, a sufficient scope of action for schools and regions is missing, and threat of

discrimination and segregation increases. Ableidinger (2019) concludes that the model is only partially integrative and advocates the need to achieve the fastest possible transition from separated German classes to regular classes. Teaching in separate classes furthers a vague role attribution and unclear feelings of belonging of the eligible pupils. According to tests at the end of each term (DerStandard 2020) about half of the pupils in German support classes improved their German skills moderately which implies that they change to regular classes albeit still as pupils who are not included into the regular grading system and with additional German language learning support needs (6 hours per week). About one third improved considerably, they are enabled to change to regular classes and achieve the status of regular pupils, however 16% of the pupils did not improve sufficiently and have to stay for another term in the German support classes.

The knowledge of German has also been demanded as a precondition for school readiness. In order to qualify for school entrance children need not only the physical and mental requirements, but also the (tested) knowledge of the German teaching language (Bundesministerium für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung 2018) despite wide-spread contrasting expert findings on the need to keep “low-performing” and children with language weaknesses in mainstream education (Herzog-Punzenberger 2017). Gomolla (2013) argues that linking school readiness with the knowledge of the teaching language constitutes indirect discrimination. Further, the sufficient knowledge of German as a criterion for school readiness may result in denying these children a school education appropriate to their age and development (Netzwerk Sprachen Rechte 2018). With the introduction of the German support classes the knowledge of German is officially no longer a criterion for school readiness (Österreichs digitales Amt, 2021).

Other regulations, not focused explicitly on persons entitled to asylum or subsidiary protection are reported to have positive effects, like the “Mandatory Training Act” (Ausbildungspflichtgesetz) (Steiner et al. 2019), or education and training for teenagers and adults within the “lifelong learning initiative” with two main program areas: basic education and basic skills training for educationally disadvantaged adults (starting at the age of 16) and the catch up of compulsory school leaving certificate (Jenewein 2018).

LABOUR MARKET

A study by Biffi (2011) showed to what extent migrants from EU and third countries contribute to meet the labour demand since 2004. Different qualification levels are considered. It is explained that a reorientation of migration policy towards highly qualified people is expected to reduce the pressure on the public budget, which is burdened by an ageing population.

That the focus on highly qualified migrants, as in Biffi (2011), leaves out a significant group of migrants is possibly shown by the study by Bock-Schappelwein and Huber (2016). In their contribution they explain that in Austria, in line with international studies, even after taking into account other factors important for labour market integration, a worse labour market integration success of asylum seekers who have only been in Austria for a short time and a particular disadvantage of asylum-seeking women is shown.

The international literature shows, “depending on the institutional circumstances of the respective recipient country, a combination of particularly unfavourable migration conditions (hasty and traumatising departure from the home country) with particular problems of recognition of formal training (lack of documents), long periods outside the labour market during the asylum procedure and settlement during the asylum procedure in regions where their specific qualifications are not in demand on the labour market” (ibid: 167).

The importance of employees with foreign citizenship in the Austrian labour market, especially for tourism, was analyzed by Walch et al. (2012). The experts interviewed in this study emphasized the diversity of employment opportunities for people with a migration background in tourism.

Taking this up, TourIK pilot project, analyzed by Gruber et al. (2019) aimed the pre-training and labour market integration of 30 young asylum seekers in tourist professions. For the hotel and gastronomy companies participating in the project the trainees and later apprentices represented an important personnel bridging aid because of the lack of skilled workers.

Furthermore, the study by Ortlieb et al. (2020) investigates two programs aimed at integrating refugees into the Austrian labour market – a short-term skills assessment and the integration year, which includes internship and training. The integration year, on the other hand, has a positive effect on employment, but this effect was

only shown by refugee women. The study emphasizes that cultural and social capital must be made available for successful integration programs.

SOCIAL WELFARE

In Austria the social welfare scheme has been reoriented towards a system of “**needs-based minimum benefit**” (Bedarfsorientierte Mindestsicherung - BMS) which was introduced in 2010 and at that time replaced the previous, more comprehensive “social assistance” scheme, which was regulated regionally by the provinces. Therefore, the intention of the BMS was to harmonize the benefits nation-wide. Furthermore, people should be ensured a certain quality of life in order to prevent marginalization in society (Pfeil & Wöss 2016). At federal level a minimum rate of monetary benefits has been set. In 2014, the minimum rate for persons living alone or single parents was € 814 per month (Statistik Austria 2015), which is the highest total amount of the needs based minimum benefit. Other groups of persons get only a certain percentage of this amount (e.g. adults living together in the same household obtain only 75%). The agreement expired at the end of 2016 and since then the implementation of a minimum benefit has been referred back to the Federal States. Particularly after 2015 the uptake of BMS was particularly high by persons entitled to asylum and subsidiary protection and people with migration background (up to 60%) (DerStandard 2018), which led to a tightening of access to BMS in several provinces.

In 2019 a basic federal law (**Basic Act on Social Assistance**) came into force in order to recreate national equal standards. It comes into effect either in 2020 or 2021, depending on the implementing regulations by provinces. The new law provides maximum rates of benefits instead of minimum standards. Further, the allocation of social assistance will increasingly take place in the form of benefits in kind (e.g. housing benefits) (Bundesministerium für Soziales, Gesundheit, Pflege und Konsumentenschutz 2019). Even if this “retrenchment of the welfare state” was criticized by some policy groups and NGOs, observers analyse that contesting activities against this trend and mobilization for justice and respective discourses was rather weak in Austria (Meier and Tiefenbacher 2019). This can be accounted to a strong tendency towards right-wing parties and policy convictions that were originally inspired directly from the dominant (and steadily increasing) national

right-wing party in the country (Wodak 2018) but have then been adopted by the Austrian People's Party (Gruber 2017; Liebhart 2020).

In the original version of the Basic Act of Social Assistance the full entitlement to benefits for immigrants was linked to a monetary “incentive” to improve language level of German. Sufficient language skills (level B1 of German or C1 of English) and the “completion of vocational qualification measures” were the prerequisites for employability on the Austrian labour market and simultaneously requested as precondition for full entitlement to the minimum benefit. Only if those prerequisites were met, immigrants should receive 100% of the BMS (Stelzer-Orthofer & Woltran 2019).

This law was passed by center-right coalition of the Austrian People's Party and the Austrian Freedom Party and reflects its social policy, which is mainly oriented towards performance and focused on Austrian citizens (Atzmüller 2019). On 12th December 2019 the Constitutional Court declared this part of the **Basic Act on Social Assistance** as unconstitutional and repealed it.

HOUSING

In Austria, Housing Subsidy (Wohnbauförderung) plays a key role in housing policy as well as housing construction policy, which are characterized by rent control in subsidized multi-floor residential buildings and in the historic housing stock (built before 1953 according to the rent law⁴⁰ and by allocating contracts to non-profit developers (Matznetter 2002). Direct subsidies, like Housing Assistance (Wohnbeihilfe), which support rent cost can be requested by eligible persons (Wenk 2017). Since 1988 the Housing Subsidy is regulated at Federal State level and is a crucial policy instrument in terms of social, economic and environmental policy (Matznetter 2020). In Vorarlberg, an annual amendment of the regulations enables the government to react to current challenges and to sharpen the instruments (Amann & Oberhuber 2019). The decentralization of Housing Subsidy has led to a wide range of different regional laws by pursuing separate priorities in each of the

⁴⁰ BGBl. Nr. 520/1981.

provinces (Amann & Oberhuber 2019), which has, according to a study of Amann & Mundt (2017) positive effects in the area of competition well-designed and effective funding models.

However, there are also significant differences in terms of eligibility conditions and requirements between Federal States, with some applying stricter requirements than others. While people with an EU, EEA or Swiss citizenship are treated on an equal footing with Austrians other TCNs are treated very different in different provinces. In terms of Housing Assistance asylum seekers are equal to nationals in all Federal States except in Upper Austria. By contrast, people entitled to subsidiary protection are only given equal access in six Federal States, including Vorarlberg and Carinthia. Further, TCNs require a certain time of main residence in Austria and in some Federal States, such as Upper Austria and Vorarlberg, TCNs need a regular minimum income in order to allocate Housing Assistance (Amann & Oberhuber 2019).

1.3 ASSESSMENT OF THE STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF POLICIES THROUGH SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

Although the long tradition of immigration in Austria has been evident since the 1970s, based on the statistical evidence, Austria can be viewed and is termed as a “reluctant immigration country” that either passively or actively confronts newcomers with various sets of conditions, legal restrictions and requirements (Heiss and Rathkolb 1995). In 2010, a more active approach with the “national action plan for integration” has been introduced which represents a balanced representation of the positive and negative aspects of migration. It is deemed as founding document for the Austrian integration policy (Rosenberger & Gruber 2020). To accompany and advise integration policy, an Expert Board for Integration has been established with the aim to discuss and summarize main issues of integration in the annual integration reports, starting with a first integration report in 2011 (Expertenrat für Integration 2019), and to critically reflect on the integration monitoring (e.g. Statistik Austria & BMEIA 2019). In the past 20 years the instrument of “**integration monitoring**” has been a valuable and reliable outcome of the Expert Board, who has “only an advisory and suggesting role” (as mentioned by an expert on migration and integration, WP3WP4AT002).

Experts confirmed the shift from a pronounced cultural perspective, which was increasingly dominated by catchphrases and valuations of the right-wing party, to the narrative of “integration by performance” with the establishment of the State-Secretary for Integration in 2011. This narrative is still in place and has acquired a dominant role in the current government program (Austrian People’s Party and Green Party) and in public discourse as well. The current policy concept is characterized by the principles of “promoting (migrants) and demanding (integration)” and is directed primarily towards migrants. The general understanding described by experts goes that the Federal Government enables integration while it simultaneously demands an active contribution from the newcomers. Sufficient knowledge of the German language is seen as key for successful integration that would eventually “achieve” labour market integration in the long run.

Integration as a two-way process is presented as the main principle of the Integration Act in 2017, which, however, unilaterally focusses on **mandatory orientation and language courses** for TCNs and persons entitled for asylum and subsidiary protection. Language development (Sprachförderung) through language courses provided through a national-wide effort and achievement of a minimum standardised level by the Austrian

Integration Fund (ÖIF) is now at the foreground of integration activities. However, funding for activities in a broader and more holistic, integrative way on a regional level are less valued and were subsequently curtailed. In contrast to the promotion of local and municipal integration competence as a priority measure in the field of integration policy in the first integration report of 2011 (Expertenrat für Integration 2011) interviewed experts (WP3WP4AT002, WP3WP4AT003) perceive a **centralisation of integration measures**, which is seen either as a logic consequence of the current organization of integration policy or as on-going considerable loss of local community action. As civil society had a very active role in the reception and care of asylum seekers and refugees as well as in support with language learning at a very low threshold in 2015 and the immediate period thereafter, the later centralization of language course provision and concentration on language training induced narrowing the many ways of integration at the local level. This is particularly true for a lot (not all) of rural areas, which had been successful in welcoming asylum seekers and other newcomers, giving them a new home, where they intended to stay, also in a longer perspective (WP3WP4AT002). A regional expert describes the reaction of the Federal State in the situation of the increased refugee movement in 2015:

“Here in Vorarlberg, the aim was that all 96 municipalities should take in asylum seekers. [...] Of course, he [the regional minister] made the mayors very aware of their responsibilities. This has led to an increased focus on this target group [asylum seekers] in society. So it is also important that society supports this integration process and resources are provided to do so. [...] The broad support of civil society has resulted in people still living in these municipalities where they first arrived. I also heard that people moved to the city, but came back after a short time.” (WP3WP4ATV002)

A strong focus on language training is also revealed through the Education Reform Act (2017) (WP3WP4AT001) concentrating on **German support classes** where pupils who are classified as pupils who are not included in the regular grading system of schools due to a lack of knowledge of the teaching language German. They are taught in separate classes during most lessons. One of the main points of critique, which has been expressed by various statements of language teaching experts (SOS Mitmensch 2018), was the missing integrative element of the peer group, when pupils with extraordinary status are assembled in separate classes with defined German language thresholds and examinations. An evaluation of this new approach is planned only for 2023.

Additionally, many measures financed by the Federal Government, with a previously more integrative focus have been adapted or eliminated. In particular the following measures have been mentioned by the expert from the Ministry of Education (WP3WP4AT001), which would have considerable positive impact, not only for the respective pupils, but also for parents, schoolteachers as well as the actual school location: a doubling of permanent posts for teachers dedicated to teaching extraordinary pupils in compulsory education with a special focus on language training. The creation of additional permanent posts for so called “**Mobile Intercultural Teams**” consisting typically of a psychologist, a social worker and a social pedagogue, who should also speak the language of the respective children. These teams would work on the interface of schooling psychologists and the teachers and focus on children with experience in displacement, to help them find their way into a positive schooling experience. Experts referred also to the recently established option of a “**transition training for young refugees** who are above compulsory school age” through which particularly unaccompanied minor refugees got a chance to enter the Austrian school system or later on the vocational system, including a focus on German language training.

However, the **German support classes** have been quite well received by pupils and teachers as the regional education expert in Vorarlberg argued (WP3WP4ATV003). As these classes have only started two years ago no valid evaluation is available yet. The main challenge, though, is seen in the transition from German support classes to regular classes, which will need to be accompanied by further support from the Federal state authorities in the case of Vorarlberg. A transfer of subsidies to schools “more in need of additional resources than others” (Brennpunktschulen) with many children with a mother tongue other than German is planned.

Integration into the labour market is also a major area where recent policy reforms had specific impact, either through creating targeted support for TCNs or increasing already existing obstacles. Refugees often find themselves confronted with the need to prove availability of financial resources and the need to find employment quickly in order to secure their own livelihood and that of their family members, since often **debts** exist already at the time a residence permit is granted. The debts occur, for example, due to money loaned to carry out the escape from their country of origin (WP3WP4ATK002). This burden, together with the fact that Austria has high standards of formal proof for the recognition of education or other qualifications forces many of this group of TCNs into the **low wage sector**, since needed documents to pursue certain professions and/or training and education are oftentimes not sufficiently notarized or translated or, especially in the case of

refugees, no longer available to them (WP3WP4ATK002). A particularly vulnerable group is that of 15–18-year-olds refugees, who have no vocational training. They are particularly exposed to exploitation and poor pay (WP3WP4ATK002). Doing auxiliary work and pursuing a career in the tourism and gastronomy sector are very prevalent occupational activities, which not only have a low wage level, but are also not valued very highly by the population (WP3WP4ATK002). Important employers in the case study region Villach are the IT-sector with its suppliers, the regional hospital, the Austrian Federal Railways (ÖBB) and also tourism and gastronomy (WP3WP4ATK003). Similarly, for the other case study region Vorarlberg big enterprises, partly with global networks (e.g. in tool production, tourism infrastructure, construction and food systems) as well as small and medium commercial operations at regional scale, play a significant role in labour market integration processes (WP3WP4ATV002).

Policy measures to counteract this trend were, for example, the **”voluntary integration year”**, which was introduced in 2016 as a deliberate measure to raise integration chances of young migrants. Although participants and experts analysed it as a successful measure (de Silva 2018) because it both offered young jobseekers the opportunity to participate, show and refine their own skills and opened employers up to this group of potential employees (WP3WP4ATK002, WP3WP4ATK003) it was not extended. On the contrary, despite the positive uptake and findings funds for this scheme were soon curtailed and, in 2019, discontinued. Other support made available by the Integration Fund, which comprise training offers and further education through various Austrian institutions for TCNs, which was also very well received nationwide (WP3WP4AT001, WP3WP4ATK002, WP3WP4ATK003). However, according to the experts, both measures are no longer actively pursued. The **”cancellation of the apprenticeship possibility for asylum seekers”** was perceived particularly negatively (WP3WP4ATK002). In recent years, the so-called **”Initiative 20,000”** was in force, which offered older, unemployed workers or workers who were difficult to place on the labour market, the opportunity to integrate into the primary labour market. Refugees and other TCNs have also benefited from this initiative (WP3WP4ATK002). The last centre-right oriented Federal Government abolished this initiative [initially, it was suspended as of 31.12.2017 (Republik Österreich 2018) and then expired completely at the end of June 2019 (APA-OTS 2019)] under heavy criticism, but additional funds for unemployed people over 50 years were later decided by an interim government (Republik Österreich 2019b).

The discontinuation of these support measures means that individual initiatives will have to be launched. As an exemplary initiative, one of the interviewed experts mentioned the project where **farmers opened their farms** to give interested TCNs an insight into the work and could hire them for harvest work (WP3WP4AT003). In general, the creation of such opportunities for exchange supports a first meeting and prevents the emergence of fears, which are often stirred up by the media or members of right-wing political movements. As the interviewee argues: "Wherever there are opportunities for interaction with other cultures, there is less fear of the foreigners". Hence, this project not only supports integration into the labour market, but also fosters interaction with natives and thereby integration into society, as well as provides new impulses which, as experience shows, enrich social life (WP3WP4ATK002).

Self-employment plays only a marginal role for TCNs in Carinthia, even though the opening of stores, hairdressers or restaurants is increasing in frequency and there is a demand for it especially in certain communities. As the interviews with experts in this area show, TCNs in Austria are often confronted with the fulfilment of the general strict criteria and guidelines (which apply to all people interested in setting up and running a business) if the step into self-employment is to be dared. Information regarding official procedures, necessary permits and the duration of procedures to be followed is often not available in a low-threshold form, which makes the process of founding and self-employment in the particularly bureaucratic administrative system in Austria even more difficult (WP3WP4ATK002).

Global political events such as disputes and armed conflicts are often provided as reasons why TCNs migrate to Europe and thus also to Austria. Their occurrence therefore influences which groups apply for asylum in Austria. Often, asylum seekers do not specifically plan to migrate to Austria, but has been stopped in Austria during their journey. Others may have heard about Austria as a welfare state. Arrived in Austria, asylum seekers cannot choose the place they will come to. They are often assigned to asylum shelters in rural areas. However, they then often get to know the rural area as a place that offers peace and quiet, a high level of security and good living and educational conditions for themselves and their children (Gruber 2014).

But, one expert interviewed noted that not only conflicts can be the trigger for flight, but that existential hardship can be so severe (e.g. in economically weak regions) that people have to leave their homes. This type of migration, as well as that influenced by climate change, is estimated to be the most prominent in the future

(WP3WP4ATK002). Many of the refugees do not stay in the rural areas but move to cities, in particular to the capital Vienna, as in some cases the urban environment is more similar to what they are accustomed to from their home country, or they already have friends and family or at least a community there that makes it easier for them to connect with social life (WP3WP4ATK002).

In the community of asylum experts, there is particular criticism in connection with **basic care and social benefits** indicating that, following the reform of the needs-based minimum protection scheme, beneficiaries of subsidiary protection will in future only receive financial benefits at the level of basic care, which will signify for people major difficulties to meet basic needs, e.g., in terms of financing housing. Further wide-spread critique concerns the unequal treatment of unaccompanied minors. Under the slogan "There are no half children", SOS Kinderdorf (2020; WP3WP4ATK002) and many other NGOs and welfare organizations demand that unaccompanied minors have the same right to education, health care and welfare as other children who grow up without parents. This is not the case due to restrictive regulations of the provided basic care services, as there is often a lack of psychological care and therapy places for trauma. Furthermore, experts pick at the constant tightening of asylum law. The **time limit for asylum status** was also viewed very critically by one expert interviewee, as it makes integration more difficult (WP3WP4ATK002).

With regard to the COVID-19 pandemic, it could be soon observed that those areas in which TCNs are often professionally active are particularly hard hit by the economic effects and there are comparatively more job cuts for this population group (WP3WP4ATK002, WP3WP4ATK003). In this sphere, the example of positive action is particularly useful, but largely dependent on individuals and institutions favourable to such an approach. For example, the municipal government of the Carinthian City of Villach, which has a politically unanimously agreed integration program since 2012, has adopted already the fourth "**CORONA Aid Package**" to support the city's economy: The program also bolsters pupils by offering laptops for free, provides assistance to affected families by paying a deposit for a flat (incl. deferral of rents; no evictions) and has reduced kindergarten fees in the crisis (Stadt Villach 2020a). In addition, the municipality has increased the budget for social assistance (BMS) (WP3WP4ATK003). In Vorarlberg **Corona Emergency Funds** have been introduced. They are aimed at supporting employees and businesses facing serious economic difficulties due to the pandemic. However, despite all the aid measures, there are social restrictions which have complicated the situation for many people. There is concern that especially refugees who are newcomers to the region and are

in need of urgent assistance are finding it difficult to obtain information. Due to the restrictions, social contacts and low-threshold services at community level no longer function as they used to (WP3WP4ATV001).

“My colleague told me that before the pandemic, the refugees just came to see her at the town hall if they needed support or information, but now it’s not possible.” (WP3WP4ATV001).

During the first lockdown, the refugees could only be advised via telephone and received homework to study German. However, in the second lockdown mandatory courses such as German language and “values and orientation” courses may also be held in person under protective measures (WP3WP4ATV002).

1.4 CONCLUSION

SOCIAL POLICY-INTEGRATION CONCLUSION. POLICY RELATED FACTORS ON THE MIGRANTS' INCLUSION

A host of policies imply profound effects on the opportunities for socio-structural and socio-cultural integration and their opportunities to be included in societal institutions of all kinds. In 2015/2016 with the sudden increase of asylum seekers migration, integration issues have dominated many political debates and led to a heightened awareness for the issue and, later, a general change of attitudes towards newcomers. This included enhanced considerations on opportunities for migrants in rural regions, discussions of local development action focusing on “integration” and community engagement extending towards newcomers, and reflection of the beneficial effects in cultural and economic terms of increasing levels of migrants in small remote municipalities, including mountain valleys. Albeit the general feeling towards asylum seekers was considered friendly and welcoming at the beginning of that ‘migration peak’, the atmosphere changed to a restrictive narrative advancing hostile arguments against immigration processes, nourished by conservative and right-wing policy discourses and media amplification. It was postulated that the increasing number of migrants would lead to rising challenges of accommodation and care, fuelling a more hostile attitude with a growing general scepticism against integration (Rosenberger & Gruber 2020, 79). Although perspectives on community life probably did not alter so promptly among individuals, political discussion, media coverage and available support drifted gradually towards more conservative and stereotypical views of ideological preservation of hegemonic (right-wing) views. These changing attitudes showed themselves up in a massive rise of the right-wing party in Austria, and their subsequent participation in government (starting from the end of 2017) together with a conservative party that had already incorporated and was boasting itself of the realization of a restrictive migration and integration policy as their main political achievement.

The amendment of the Aliens Act in 2018 (FräG2018⁴¹) can be seen as one expression of mainstreaming and tightening of migration regulation. This policy amendment particularly aimed at extending the possibility of implementing a fast-track procedure for withdrawing the granted asylum status from refugees in the event of voluntary recourse to protection in their country of origin or acquisition of lost nationality. However, the history of the aggravation of immigration regulation can be dated back much further, also in 1991 the Asylum Act was largely adopted. A major novelty at that time was the introduction of the “third country-clause”, under which an asylum seeker entering Austria from a safe third country is not granted asylum. Major amendments increased restrictions, in particular through the entering into force of the Dublin Convention in 1997, the amendment of 2003 addressing the increasing number of asylum seekers by streamlining and simplifying procedures, legal adjustments in 2005 because parts of the 2003 amendments were repealed as being unconstitutional and the most recent amendment of 2016 by introducing a time limit for asylum entitlement. Since then, granted asylum status is in the first instance only valid for three years and is extended for an indefinite period if there has been no lasting change in the political situation of the state of origin. Concerning this tightening, experts on foreigners’ law and human rights activists warned against the difficulties for refugees in the labour market integration or in finding accommodation. It was also feared that this law will make it more difficult for refugees to integrate (Republik Österreich 2016). This process encompassed all aspects of policy and social life and severely hampered any endeavour for working towards community integration so that analysts speak of a “politics of fear” (Wodak 2020). The empirical research study by Ratheiser et al. (2019) on the integration process of recognized refugees and persons entitled for subsidiary protection show in different interviews with integration experts, migrant counselling organisations and refugees i.a. the strong negative psychological effects of the temporary nature of the protection title and the possible reopening of the asylum procedure, which puts a lot of stress on people and thus also hinders them in the integration process.

In 2019 a strong, more symbolic signal of re-naming the “reception centres” into “departure centres” showed the intention of the right-wing party being in governmental responsibility at that time to prove immigration in Austria as very difficult (DerStandard 2019). Main aim was to stem against entry of possible asylum seekers and

⁴¹ BGBl. I Nr. 56/2018.

not show any sign of pull incentives. With the new conservative-green government the term was removed again.

In the past few years, in certain areas of integration an increase of duties for TCNs and a focus on sanctions, if duties are not fulfilled, can be observed. This notion is (theoretically) connected with the perception of integration as a two-way process. In the Integration Act of 2017 (§2 para. 1 IntG) “integration” is defined as a process whose success depends on the participation of all people living in Austria and is based on personal interaction. It states that in particular, integration requires that immigrants actively participate in this process, take advantage of the integration measures offered and recognize and respect the values of a European democratic states. The Integration Act foresees for TCNs the obligatory signing of an integration agreement comprising two modules, including mandatory orientation and language courses for TCNs and persons entitled to asylum and subsidiary protection. If the integration agreement and its obligation for language and orientation courses (which is a necessary proof for the prolongation of the residence permit) is not fulfilled within two years, a financial penalty of 500€ or a prison sentence for two weeks at the most is the consequence (§23 para. 1 IntG).

With the Education Reform Act the pressure on successfully and fast language learning for pupils with a lack of knowledge of the teaching language German has been intensified. Only with a positive result in the language test they are allowed to proceed in regular classes. Otherwise, they are obliged to continue in the German support classes. After two years of particular school courses the transfer to regular classes is obligatory, however further language training for pupils in need is not foreseen in the national proposal but has to be provided by the federal states on a voluntary basis.

A centralization of integration measures is recognized as dominant and adverse trend within the implementation of integration measures. While accommodation and care for asylum seekers as well as language and orientation courses for all newcomers have been provided at a regional and local level before, often through low-threshold activities, the provision of language and orientation courses has to be (according to legal prescriptions) provided by the Austrian Integration Fund (ÖIF) since the Integration Act in 2017. The ÖIF implements language and values courses, organizes public events and creates information materials. At the same time, the same institution is also responsible for certification and for handling German language courses.

If there are still activities at the local or regional level, they have to be supported by the Federal States or by NGOs through their own funds, e.g. language courses for asylum seekers are organized and financed by the Federal States, activities of the ÖIF focuses on recognised refugees and other TCNs. However, with the centralization of language and orientation courses there is the threat that integrative activities of NGOs and volunteers at the regional and local level may not or be less supported than before.

INVENTORY OF GOOD PRACTICES ON SOCIAL IMPACT

A series of relevant initiatives have been elaborated across the country, extending to rural regions as well, and providing numerous examples from the two Austrian MATILDE case study areas. Good practices seeking to contribute migrants' inclusion in the local society are led to a substantial part by local actors (community organizations), voluntary associations and individual volunteers, associations and NGOs, and social-sector institutions, partly supported by public funds and administration. By curtailing “public services” the bulk of integration efforts is hence entrusted in this private field of social groups enhancing effective integration pathways. Many of these initiatives are short-termed, project-funding dependent and conditionally approved as long as political support is not withdrawn. The long-term challenges of integration can therefore hardly be met in a sustained and empowering way by these structures and fragile conditions. The following inventory of selected initiatives highlights examples from the two regions representative for the diversity of themes, approaches and actors:

- Both in Carinthia as well as Vorarlberg an **integration prize** has been adopted by the Federal State Government. The aim is to honour civil society engagement as well as active communities and companies in the area of integration achieving an important contribution to social cohesion, providing visibility of good practice examples and raising their appreciation and recognition in the course of an award ceremony (Land Kärnten 2019a; Land Vorarlberg 2020).
- Located at the intersection of lowland and mountain areas in Vorarlberg, a **Regional Coordination Office for Integration** aims at combining integration efforts of 11 municipalities. Since 2016, this office provided a regional anchor point for advice and support for migrants and refugees in this area,

supported by public funds (Verein Region Vorderland-Feldkirch n.d.). Many support projects addressed issues like “Refugees and Integration”, one of the sub-activities of a small municipalities called Röthis, oriented at integration of local refugees (about 20) there (Gemeinde Röthis 2020).

- The **Integration Pass of the City of Villach** has been offered since 2016 and is aimed at asylum seekers in order to explain the rules and customs in Villach and Austria and to facilitate their entry into society. It is divided into 7 modules in which the conditions for living together in Villach are explained and people are given the opportunity to exchange ideas with specialists. At the end, i.e. when all modules have been completed, the participants receive a certificate from the city of Villach (City of Villach 2020).
- A specific project targeting at a local welcoming society in a rural context was advocated in the project “**vorankommen**”, which is the German verb for “progressing”, indicating the aim to advance with integration objectives at this level. The project was carried out as a LEADER initiative in the period 2015-2018 in the mountain municipality of Alberschwende, representative for many remote parts of Vorarlberg (Regionalentwicklung Vorarlberg eGen n.d.). Through “institutionalizing” the approach it should provide an incentive to shift attention and acceptance towards newcomers in the small community. The target was to address five neighbouring municipalities, with about 150 enterprises, local partners and actors to instigate change in perceiving migrants and refugees.
- The **ASPIS** association is an independent institution and offers a wide range of help for traumatized people, which is highly needed as there are too few places for trauma therapy available especially for children; DerStandard 2018). People who have experienced violence often suffer psychological, psychosomataical and physical stress from the consequences of the “extreme situation”. The multi-professional team is specialized in psychotherapeutic work and in the implementation of accompanying measures. There is also close cooperation with other professional groups and treatment institutions (doctors, social workers, counselling for foreigners, UNHCR etc.) (ASPIS 2020).
- In some projects the focus was explicitly on one social group to address their needs with more detail and effectiveness. As the age structure of migrants shows particularly high shares of young people, youth is often a specific target group. The project “**Youth, Culture, Labor in Walgau**”, located in the municipality of Nenzing is a characteristic example (Regio Im Walgau n.d.). It further underpins that social capital enhancement should be seen as foundational to employment creation and an effective

strategy to enhance labour market performance and integration objectives. Though, initially it was a local action in one municipality. Since 2008, it was applied to seven municipalities through a LEADER project in 2017-2020. The specific target group are young refugees with their traumatic experiences and individual desire for trust-building action, enhanced partly by dedicated recreation offers. However, here a careful planning and informal support is required which seeks to promote, gradually, acceptance with local associations and population.

- Since 2013, activities have been carried out in the rural Hermagor region to support the permanent settlement and integration process of national and international migrants. The project “come to stay” **((ge)kommen, um bleiben)** aimed at raising the awareness of the public administration and the population towards migration process and raising pluralization of society. It was intended to create a service offer for immigrants according to regionally agreed quality criteria and thus make an important contribution to diversity and quality of life in the region (including a welcome handbook and checklist for the administration in order to be able to support the immigrants in their first steps in the region) (Region Hermagor n.d).
- Different religious beliefs, linked-cultural traits and cultural symbols are a further field of concern which is often neglected as understanding for these crucial issues tends to be limited. An inspiring example in Vorarlberg is the planning, preparation and creative realization of the cemetery for Muslims in that federal state. On account of the distinct rites and rules for burial sites an introductory study argued for the need of an “**Islamic Cemetery**” in Vorarlberg (Dörler 2004) and its feasibility. Being realized in a very specific architectural manner, addressing the contexts of religion and migration, the actual cemetery in Altsch received several architectural prizes between 2012-2014 for its exemplary design and evocation of these topics (okay.zusammen leben 2013).
- The Day of Encounter (**Tag der Begegnung**) in Carinthia is an annual event designed to strengthen polylogue and inter-religious understanding between Catholic, Protestant and Muslim religious communities. Other participants include the Federal State of Carinthia and representatives of the Carinthian Slovenian ethnic group (Land Kärnten 2019b).
- Access and use of public spaces and communication facilities are a more fluid aspect, but highly interesting to achieving new relationships, open dialogue and acceptance from diverse partners in this process. In Carinthia, a project called “Cariola-Community Gardens” runs **intercultural**

community gardens. These spaces are intended to create possibilities for joint gardening, encounters and intercultural exchange and to support the acquisition of the German language and integration process (Land Kärnten 2020).

The projects, offers and initiatives mentioned represent a selection of many supporting offers for asylum seekers, refugees and TCNs in the two Federal States Vorarlberg and Carinthia. On behalf of all the others, they provide an overview of what is mostly provided by NGOs, associations and volunteers.

ECONOMIC POLICY-INTEGRATION CONCLUSION. POLICY RELATED FACTORS ON THE MIGRANTS' IMPACT INTO THE ECONOMY

Participation in the labor market is considered the key to social integration. When refugees were asked in a study, when they feel “integrated”, they answered “when having a job” (UNHCR 2013, p. 76). Paid employment creates the basis for the self-sustaining ability of individuals, families and relatives and is acknowledged as foundation for integration in other fields. Household income affects housing options and quality, as well as education, qualification and skill development opportunities. Thus, the (legal) permission of (sufficiently paid) employment for TCNs is crucial.

On the one hand, labour market integration is highly regulated for TCNs in Austria, on the other hand citizens from the EU member states and the EEA states who make up of more than two thirds of the yearly immigrants, have free access to the Austrian labour market. As they enjoy free movement of workers, they do not need a labour market authorization to take up work. Legal regulations are focused on TCNs and may be divided into policies for (high-skilled) working migrants and policies for asylum seekers and persons entitled for asylum as well as subsidiary protection.

Austria has introduced a system of criteria-based labour immigration in 2011, which was adapted in 2017 and 2018 (Red-White-Red card). In the frame of these criteria labour market migration from third countries is geared to cover domestic labour requirements, provided that the applicant falls into one of the following groups (migration.gv.at 2020):

- Particularly highly qualified persons (e.g. persons with a university degree, preferably in mathematics, computer science, natural sciences or technology, and persons in a management function with a correspondingly high gross salary or research and innovation activity, and with sufficient German or English language skills); persons in this category can apply for a Red-White-Red card and do not have to show a job prior to entering the country, thus can come to Austria to look for a job;
- Professionals in professions with a shortage of skilled workers²² (completed apprenticeship in an occupation where there is a shortage of skilled workers; other criteria such as German and English language skills are also assessed);
- Other key professionals (criteria such as a university degree or minimum gross salary per month must be fulfilled and minimum salary levels must be proven);
- Graduates of an Austrian higher education institution (a job must be found in Austria within one year after graduation with a minimum salary of € 2,416.50 plus special payments (year 2020));
- Self-employed key professionals (possible, if employment involves a transfer of investment capital of at least €100,000 to Austria or if employment creates new jobs or secures existing jobs or involves a transfer of know-how or the introduction of new technologies or if the company is of major importance for a whole region);
- Start-up entrepreneurs (possible, e.g. when a new company to be set up develops innovative products, services or technologies and launches them on the market).

Although these criteria for labour-market-led immigration are still very demanding and can therefore only be met by a very limited number of people wishing to immigrate to Austria, the amended laws aimed at opening up the labour market and raise attractiveness for a skilled and qualified labour force.

While every TCN needs an employment permit in order to take up work in Austria, asylum seekers face additional obstacles and their possibility to work are very limited. During the first three months of the asylum procedure there is an absolute ban on employment. After these three months, an employment permit can be applied for, however employment opportunities and activities open to asylum seekers are very restricted:

- According to a decree from 2004, access to the labour market for asylum seekers has been regulated in such a way that after the first three months, they may only be employed as seasonal workers (e.g. in

agriculture as harvest workers or in tourism) for a maximum of six months (Arbeitsmarktservice Österreich 2020b).

- In addition, after the first three months of the asylum procedure, asylum-seekers may be employed for domestic services in private households (e.g. cleaning, mowing the lawn, supervising children, shopping) and may be remunerated by the so-called "service cheque". The service cheque is a means of payment and a wage for people who work in private households. In order not to lose basic care services, asylum seekers are allowed to earn a maximum of €110 additional per month (AMS 2020b; Fonds Soziales Wien 2020).
- Asylum seekers may become self-employed after the first three months. However, becoming self-employed means that asylum seekers lose the right to basic care, have to pay health insurance, chamber levy and income tax, and observe the other provisions relating to the exercise of the trade (Fonds Soziales Wien 2020).
- Asylum seekers are also allowed to become volunteers, so to be employed for up to three months for the purpose of expanding and applying the own knowledge without the obligation to work and without remuneration. Volunteering or work training must be registered with the Public Employment Service (AMS) and the General Accident Insurance Institution (AUVA) and has to be approved by them (Fonds Soziales Wien 2020).
- In addition, asylum seekers can carry out charitable work for Federal Government, federal states, municipalities and municipal associations (e.g. maintenance of parks and sports facilities). They may receive a minimum recognition fee of a few euros per hour, which must not exceed the possible additional income limit, as basic care is reduced or gets lost completely otherwise (Fonds Soziales Wien 2020).
- Finally, asylum seekers may be used for support activities directly related to their accommodation (e.g. cleaning, kitchen operations, transport, maintenance).

In 2012, an easement for young asylum seekers took place, enabling them an access to apprenticeship during their asylum procedure (with an extension of the age threshold from 18 to 25 years since 2014). The concept of this forward-looking integration instrument argues that young asylum seekers should be offered the opportunity to acquire professional qualifications during the asylum procedure which would facilitate their career entry after a positive asylum decision or, in the case of a negative outcome of the asylum procedure,

could be useful for their professional advancement in their country of origin. In 2018 the decree was repealed with immediate effect. The reason given was the current labour market development and, in particular, the large number of domestic and foreign young people who are registered with the Public Employment Service (AMS) as looking for a job. Furthermore, any pull factor for potential asylum seekers should be eliminated. Since then, it has no longer been possible for young asylum seekers to start an apprenticeship.

Another supportive integration instrument, the “integration year”, directed towards persons entitled to asylum and subsidiary protection, is no longer pursued since 2019, despite its high utilization and success. The aim of this policy was to strengthen inclusion into Austrian social life, to familiarize with “Austrian values” and to learn the German language. It was intended to provide career orientation and deepen previous school education, as well as to promote personality development, the expansion and application of knowledge for various occupational fields, the strengthening of social and intercultural skills and the social commitment of the participants.

INVENTORY OF GOOD PRACTICES ON ECONOMIC IMPACT

The economic aspects are tightly interwoven with the development of social integration and thus a strict separation of good practices is rather difficult. Moreover, many renowned enterprises and migrants don't stress their origin or even tend to downplay that aspect of their biographies in business communication. The following inventory exemplifies activities that enhance work integration through service and advice, skills development and approval, linking migrants and local people and entrepreneurs, the role of associations and needs of specific groups.

- The **Refugee and Migrant Support** by Caritas Carinthia (2020) encompasses all aspects of social and labour integration. With its accompanying support it provides guidance which is similar to many mentoring projects (that are more tightly focused on specific personal and job advice). The department “**Flight and Inclusion**” by Diakonie de La Tour in Carinthia (2020a) support asylum

seeker, refugees and migrants. They i.e. organize and operate accommodation for asylum seekers, run labour integration projects (like TourIK or A:life) or project on sexual education for refugees.

- A comprehensive assessment of the labour market effects of integration action was carried out by “arbeit plus” (2017), the Austrian network of community-oriented social enterprises. It lists a number of interesting examples, including several activities in the study area Vorarlberg. One of it, the project “**start2work - labour integration of migrants**” is supported by Caritas Vorarlberg (arbeit plus 2017, 18). Up to 400 approved refugees are supported year by year in their search for labour and/or skills development.
- A further example is the “**Youth College INTEGRA**” in Vorarlberg which was conceived in 2015 due to the strong increase of immigration, and the large number of young migrants (arbeit plus 2017, 22). The target is to achieve an “ability check” for young migrants (15-19 years) and to suggest subsequently appropriate courses and institutions for further skill improvement or work according to their interests and affinities. The situation is particularly challenging as most (more than 80% of them were unattended refugees with negative psychological effects due to their refugee biography). In the first phase more than 200 persons were included in the programme and most could be integrated to either the school system or vocational training, with a drop-out rate of just 16%.
- “**TourIK - Tourism and Integration in Carinthia**” is about the “pre-apprenticeship” for young refugees as a cooperative support model against the lack of skilled workers in Carinthian tourism. The aim of the project was to enable 30 motivated asylum seekers (including unaccompanied minors, UMFs) and recognized refugees to complete a one-year training programme (“pre-apprenticeship”) at the Villach vocational tourism school after a comprehensive potential analysis (clearing). After completion of the preliminary training in tourism in mid-November 2018, the prospective tourism professionals have been placed in the Carinthian economy, where many of them had the chance to start their regular apprenticeship (KWF 2017). A follow-up project is “**A:Life - Asylum & Apprenticeship**” in Carinthia, which aims to establish a commitment to dedicate apprenticeship places from industry or from hotel and gastronomy based in Carinthia as well as to support recognized asylum seekers during the socialization phase in Austria, prepare them for an apprenticeship with a training programme and offer socio-pedagogical follow-up support during an apprenticeship (Diakonie de La Tour 2020b).

- Reference should also be made to the **Institute for Labour Migration in Carinthia (IAM)**, which provides counselling and support to help migrants integrate into the labour market through job placement or further training. IAM is an association whose activities are funded by the Public Employment Service and the Carinthian Government and which offers the “competence check” (IAM 2020).
- The joint initiative of the Austrian Integration Fund, the Austrian Chambers of Commerce and the Public Employment Service, “**Mentoring for female migrants**”, aims to bring together experienced people from the domestic economy (mentors) and well-qualified people with a migration background (mentees) in order to support their integration into the Austrian labour market (Österreichischer Integrationsfonds 2020).

It should be noted that despite of the successful projects mentioned here, a thorough investigation of the demand differentiated by age groups and reflecting specific needs would be required. However, current policy trends focus on the costs of these activities and argue on short-term failures and difficulties, without considering “social cost” and deficiencies in public community development.

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3. BULGARIA

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1.1 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC RELATED POLICIES REGARDING TCNS

METHODOLOGICAL REMARKS

The objective of the Policy brief is twofold: 1/to analyse the policies impacting the economic and social integration of TCNs and refugees; 2/to examine the practices and actors of integration. This second perspective is important because a major specificity of the Bulgarian case is that inclusion is not so much the outcome of policies, but of migrants' integration strategies.

The methodology of Matilde is conceived to grasp mainly the specificities of regions with mass migration. All tools - templates, questionnaires for interviews, etc. - follow the same logic. They are, therefore, only partially applicable to the Bulgarian case. The contribution of the Bulgarian case is fruitful in three regards: to illustrate the diversity of European regions in regard to migration; to represent a case that is more defined by fluidity and in which transit, the dynamic nexus of arrivals and departures predominates on stock; to analyse the multifaceted change provoked by the opening of a new Reception centre in a small town without experience in migration management and its economic, social, political, cultural impact on local society.

BULGARIAN MIGRATION PROFILE

The Bulgarian migration profile is forged by two transitions: from the close communist society with almost no migration to a more open post-communist society with significant emigration and increasing migration at the beginning of the 90-es; the integration to the EU in 2007.

During the last three decades, an asymmetrical tri-polar migration profile has crystallised which is characterized by high emigration, low immigration and a very low number of refugees. The number of Bulgarians who have emigrated abroad after the democratic transition in 1989 is approximately 1.3 million overall. Immigrants in

Bulgaria are few in number, approximately 150,000 or around 2% of the population⁴² (Krasteva 2019, p. 15-16). Most immigrants are from non-EU countries – 93,200 were born in non-member countries, while 52,200 were born in other EU Member States.⁴³

The number of refugees with international protection status who have settled in Bulgaria is very low in comparison to other EU member states. The refugee community is characterised by a big difference between the number who have been granted international protection status – 25,075 – and the number of those with refugee status who have settled in Bulgaria, which is estimated at no more than 2,000. For refugees, as well as for numerous immigrants, Bulgaria is a transit country.

A large number of ‘old’ economic immigrants is relatively well-integrated in terms of labour market participation, linguistic, cultural and social integration. Contrary to the immigrants, most of refugees need social, economic, housing and other policies to facilitate and support their integration.

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The aim of this part of the policy brief is to present the major laws, policies and strategies in the key areas of migration and integration, economic, social and territorial development. They will be analysed, critically reflected upon and assessed in the next part.

MIGRATION, ASYLUM AND INTEGRATION POLICIES

Adoption of Geneva Convention. In Bulgaria, the Geneva Convention was adopted after the democratic transition in 1993. The same year the State Agency for Refugees (SAR) was set up as a key step to the institutionalization of asylum policy.

⁴² The data on (im)migrant stock numbers vary between 145,000 according to Eurostat, 150,000 according to the Pew Research Centre, and 154,000 according to the International Migration Report (2017).

⁴³ Eurostat. Migration and Migrant Population Statistics

The *National Strategy of the Republic of Bulgaria on Migration and Integration (2008-2015)*. The first migration strategy was adopted almost two decades after the transition from communism to democracy. The Strategy is the first comprehensive document in which the Bulgarian State formulated its vision about an optimal migration profile. A central focus was the permanent return of new emigrants and attraction of foreign citizens of Bulgarian origin. The document defined two strategic goals: to attract persons with Bulgarian citizenship living in other countries, as well as of persons of Bulgarian origin with foreign citizenship – for permanent return and settlement in the Republic of Bulgaria; to implement an adequate integration policy, and efficient control of the migration processes (Krasteva 2014a:619). The Strategy also defined the key economic migrant groups which it prioritised: workforce from other Member States of the EU, EEA and Switzerland; foreigners of Bulgarian origin; students, researchers and highly qualified specialists who have been educated and graduated in Bulgaria (Krasteva 2014a: 621). The Strategy reflect the predominant emigration character of the Bulgarian migration profile and the priority assigned to the policy of return of emigrants and of attracting representatives of the Bulgarian diaspora.

The latest *National Strategy on Migration, Asylum and Integration (2015-2020)* formulates the priority of “transforming migration and mobility into positive factors for development in demographic and economic terms,” which it expounds in the section on “Policies in the field of migration, development, integration.” In line with the Global Approach to Migration and Mobility, the Strategy envisages cooperation with countries of origin and transit, and the promotion of Mobility Partnerships:

Until now, Bulgaria has placed the main emphasis in these policies on the Eastern dimension of the European Neighbourhood Policy and, accordingly, we have identified as our partners the Eastern Partnership countries. Considering, however, the events in recent years and the significant diversification of the migration flows connected to the Middle East and the Mediterranean region and along the Silk Road, Bulgaria ought to take steps to identify possible areas of higher cooperation with potential partners identified among countries with which the EU is conducting dialogue and applying some of the instruments of the Global Approach to Migration and Mobility (National Strategy on Migration, Asylum and Integration).

REFUGEE INTEGRATION – FROM NATIONAL TO LOCAL LEVEL

An important integration policy change has been introduced that shifted the integration from national to local government – mayors and municipalities. On 12 August 2016, the Council of Ministers issued a decree on the adoption of an Ordinance on the Terms and Procedure for Concluding, Implementing, and Terminating an Integration Agreement for Foreigners Granted Asylum or International Protection. On 31 March 2017, the Ordinance was repealed. On 19 July 2017, the government adopted a new Ordinance on the Terms and Procedure for Concluding, Implementing, and Terminating the Integration Agreement for Foreigners Granted Asylum or International Protection.

The decentralisation of integration, the shift from national to local level is per se a positive policy change, but the conditions for successful implementation such as preparedness and political will of local authorities, as well as preparedness of local population have not been granted. The Ordinance was largely criticised by scholars (Krašteva 2019), international organisations (UNHCR Bulgaria 2017), human rights organisations (BHC 2014), human rights lawyers (Ilareva 2017). “The new Ordinance does not foresee any activities to inform the local population about refugee issues and integration principles. Awareness-raising campaigns, run by municipalities together with civil society and the private sector, are needed to create a favourable environment for the integration of refugees” (UNHCR Bulgaria 2017). Another argument is related to the refusal of towns like Elin Pelin and Belene to register recognised refugees. Lawyer Ilareva underlines that to address registration is “the key to access to all other rights – EGN [Personal Identification Number], ID document, health insurance, registration at labour offices, etc.” (Ilareva 2017). Concerns about access to housing have been raised: “The UNHCR regrets that the Ordinance does not fill gaps in refugee access to social housing and family benefits for children, which the law currently does not allow. This creates a significant risk of homelessness among recognised refugees.” (UNHCR Bulgaria 2017).

The Bulgarian Helsinki Committee emphasized the lack of political will of national and local authorities to enhance integration that demotivates refugees to stay in the country (BHC 2014, p.71). The main reason for the reluctance of local authorities and local population to accept refugees in several towns is connected to the raising national populism.

POLITICISATION OF IMMIGRATION

The reasons for the lack of significant success of some integration policies and practices of the most disadvantaged migrants and refugees are rooted not in legislation, but in the political context of populist securitization of immigration and mainstreaming of anti-migration discourses. They undermines the conditions for integration policies and forges a negative public opinion. Several trends converge: increasing of anti-migration discourses even in the situation of post-migration crisis; mainstreaming of anti-migration rhetoric; negative impact on public opinion and on migration and integration policies. The first one is illustrated by the Eurosceptic MEP Angel Dzhambazki who claimed that “Sofia was flooded by thousands of aliens... crowds of people who had illegally entered into Bulgarian territory” (Mitov 2018) in a situation of no migration pressure and of almost empty refugee camps.⁴⁴ The mainstreaming of anti-immigration discourses is exemplified by the increasing number of politicians of all colours – not only from the far right, but also from mainstream parties. Among the most outspoken speakers of anti-migrant discourses are Bulgarian Socialist Party (BSP) leader Kornelia Ninova (Krasteva 2018a) and President Rumen Radev. One of the popular slogans of his presidential campaign⁴⁵ was the refugee crisis: refugees threaten a change in the ethnic and religious composition of the Bulgarian people (“Our children leave for Europe, the ruling parties replace them with refugees.”). These trends impact negatively both the public opinion and the migration and integration policies – president Rumen Radev, in the spirit of his campaign, repealed the Ordinance on refugee integration,⁴⁶ Bulgaria did not join the Global Compact for Migration. Bulgaria occupies one of the last positions—along with Hungary, the Czech Republic, Estonia and Latvia—in terms of portion of the population open to accepting migrants from outside EU. Bulgarians who are positive about migration are twice as few as Europeans as a whole: 15% vs. 37% (Public opinion in EU. Bulgaria 2016). These data seem paradoxical, given that Bulgaria has one of the lowest

⁴⁴ According to the Deputy Prime Minister: “The capacity of migrant camps is only 11% full. There have been no new admissions to the camps” (Mitov 2018).

⁴⁵ in 2016

⁴⁶ The paradox is that soon after that, a new Ordinance, similar to the repealed one – showing that Bulgaria’s European commitments as an EU member country can correct some of the major governmental deficiencies. (Krasteva 2019).

percentages of migrants per capita (2%), was never a major destination of the refugee flow in 2015 and 2016, and has been a transit country since the beginning of the crisis. They illustrate the performative power of mainstreamed anti-migration discourses and policies to forge negative representations of migration. These trends are relevant for understanding the deficiencies and paradoxes of integration. One of them is the invisibilization of good practices of integration. A case in point was reported at a workshop organised by UNHCR Bulgaria at the end of 2018: two Sofia municipalities had accepted refugees, but did not want this to be made public. The anti-immigrant discourse and the invisibility of the cases of good practices of integration delay and impede refugee integration in Bulgaria.

ECONOMIC POLICY. LABOUR MARKET INTEGRATION. LEGISLATION ON LABOUR MIGRATION

The last few years have seen progress in developing legislation on labour migration and mobility. A series of amendments to the Labour Migration and Labour Mobility Act, adopted in 2018, have eased access to the Bulgarian labour market for third-country nationals.

The Ordinance Laying Down the Conditions and Procedure for Issuing, Refusal and Withdrawal of Work Permits for foreigners. Art. 4 was adopted in 2002 and amended in 2016. It stipulates that employment for asylum seekers without a work permit is allowed only within SAR centers. For labour outside SAR centers, asylum-seekers can apply for a work permit 3 months after submitting their application while they are waiting for a decision. It has been amended multiple times: Up until October 2015, the minimum stay required before receiving a work permit used to be 1 year. Then this requirement was reduced to 3 months. In May 2016 the minimum stay was extended to 9 months. In December 2016, the Law on foreigners was changed again and the minimum stay went back to 3 months (Gumnishka 2017, p. 29). Despite the formal recognition of the right to work, refugee employment levels in Bulgaria are low.

The *Labour Migration and Labour Mobility Act* (LMLMA) (promulgated in *State Gazette*, No. 33, 26 April 2016) has played a key role in easing access of third-country nationals to the Bulgarian labour market. The LMLMA regulates all types of access of third-country nationals to the Bulgarian labour market: single work permit; EU

Blue Card; work permit for intra-corporate transfer; work permits for seasonal workers; registration of the employment of students and researchers (EMN 2018b: 11). The LMLMA has been amended twice (*State Gazette*, No. 97/2017 and No. 24/2018) to reduce the administrative burdens for employers in hiring migrant workers. Of the many provisions easing procedures for access to the Bulgarian labour market, the following are the most notable:

The limitation on the number of third-country workers employed in Bulgarian enterprises has been increased from 10% of their average size in the previous 12 months to 20% for large enterprises, and 35% for small and medium-sized enterprises.

The opportunity has been provided for third-country nationals of Bulgarian origin to work without permission, after registration in the Employment Agency, until obtaining the residence permit.

The introduction of equal treatment of researchers, trainees, students and volunteers, as well as family members of Bulgarian, European and foreign citizens, including asylum seekers or beneficiaries of international protection (EMN 2018b:12-13).

Among the other legislative amendments easing access to the Bulgarian labour market, it is also important to note those added to the Recognition of Professional Qualifications Act (promulgated in *State Gazette*, No. 13, 8 February 2008, last amended by *State Gazette* No. 85, 24 October 2017).

This Act regulates the terms and procedure for recognition of professional qualifications acquired in other EU Member States and in third countries, with the aim of access to and practice of regulated professions in Bulgaria, as well as the terms and procedure for partial access to practice of a regulated profession and recognition of length of service for mastering the profession in another Member State (Zareva 2018b:72).

Blue Card Directive (Council Directive 2009/50/EC of 25 May 2009 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purposes of highly qualified employment), OJ 2009 L 155/17. The labour market needs highly qualified labour force. Bulgaria follows the EU regulations in the legislation, but is unable to transform them into efficient policy for attracting talents.

The Law for Employment Promotion (2013) addresses the un/employment services and policies especially for migrants, refugees and asylum seekers. The implementation involves the Employment Agency and its regional labour offices. In 2014 the number of registered unemployed migrants was 24, in 2015 – 192; in 2016 – 162. Zvezda Vankova analyses the reasons for the relatively limited use of these services and identifies a lack of motivation because of uncertain duration of the stay in the country, and lack of documents (Vankova 2013).

The Ordinance №2 on the validation of professional knowledge, skills and competence (2014) aims at facilitating the access to the labour market and applies to both EU citizens and TCNs.

The program for refugees' employment and training (2014) provides Bulgarian language classes for 200 unemployed persons who have been granted refugee or humanitarian status, professional training for 100 of them and subsidized employment of 100 persons for a period of 6 months. At the beginning the program remained on paper and in 2014 no refugees took part in it. In 2018, 129 people were employed through the program.

National Plan of Action on Employment (2020) is quite concise concerning TCNs. It addresses TCNs in two regards:

the implementation of the bilateral agreements on labour migration between Bulgaria and Armenia, Moldova and Israel and the preparation of future agreements with Albania, Azerbaijan, Belarus and other countries.

The legal framework for the TCNs integration to the labour market, such as Blue card of EU, Work permit, etc. (National Plan of Action on Employment 2020, p. 53). The Plan does not include specific policy measures for TCNs.

Bulgaria attracts a very small number of non-EU citizens. The government does not invest efforts in developing integration policies responding to the needs of new-comers (MIPEX 2015, p. 82). The labour market mobility is assessed 50 out of 100 – half way favourable policies for new comers,' that create slightly more obstacles than opportunities for non-EU immigrants to quickly and fully participate in society' (MIPEX 2015, p. 83).

According to the Employment Agency, third-country nationals are employed predominantly in tourism, services, manufacturing and education, as well as in construction and commerce. For comparison, Bulgarian nationals are employed predominantly in manufacturing, commerce and construction (EMN 2018b:14-15).

HOUSING POLICY

The housing policy is key for integration (Gabova 2020), yet in Bulgaria there are few measures concerning migrants and refugees.

The National Housing Strategy of Bulgaria is adopted in 2004. An interesting provision is a measure of regulating and encouraging the creation of “housing associations” (social housing), but it has not been implemented. The Strategy lacks a differentiated approach to the housing needs of the different groups of the population. The needs of migrants and refugees are not specifically addressed. A recent UNHCR study of the municipal housing policy (Gabova 2020) identifies several lacks and deficiency of the housing policy in relation to the beneficiaries of international protection (BIP):

- Public institutions still lack significant experience and practices to meet the short- and long-term housing needs of BIP.
- A major structural challenge in the provision of housing for beneficiaries of international protection is the shortage of public housing stock which is insufficient to meet the needs even of the local population, while a large number of dwellings across the country are empty.
- The municipal housing policies have been given a lower priority, little information is available on them, and new housing units are built only with the support of projects funded from the EU operational programs.
- Unlike the other European countries, the state and municipal housing stock in Bulgaria has been reduced to the symbolic level of 2.4%. The municipal housing stock in most cities and municipalities has been assessed as insufficient for the adequate provision accommodation for those in need; it is poorly maintained and inefficiently managed.
- The legislation does not address the BIPs. There are no precise legal provisions regulating the roles and responsibilities of the state and local authorities in terms of ensuring the right to affordable housing (Gabova 2020, pp.7-8).

EDUCATION POLICY

The education policy is among the most developed policies of integration with relatively good results for enrolment of refugee children at both national level and in the Matilde region.

Ordinance № 3 on the terms and conditions for admission and training of persons, seeking or obtaining international protection (6.04.2017). The aim is to facilitate the access of refugee children to public schools and kindergartens. The program does not provide governmental funding for municipalities to implement integration activities. For 2017/2018, 205 students seeking or receiving international protection were enrolled in the educational system. (Report on the action plan for the implementation of strategy for poverty reduction 2020, p. 57). 29 students are enrolled in the Haskovo region. The Matilde Haskovo region ranks second after Sofia-city, where 135 students are enrolled.

National Reform Program 2012 – 2020, amended in 2019. The program adopts provisions for the inclusion of refugee and migrant children in schools through learning of the Bulgarian language.

TERRITORIAL POLICY. REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT.

National Strategy for Regional Development of the Republic of Bulgaria 2012 – 2020. It adopts the Europe 2020 Strategy for Smart, Sustainable and Inclusive Growth, based on a knowledge-based and innovation-based economy. One of the aims is to increase the employment of the population through (not only) better integration of migrants into the labour force. The interim report on the implementation of the strategy does not provide information on the progress of the measure.

1.2 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING ANALYSES AND ASSESSMENTS OF ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL POLICIES

Migration studies are a relatively new field in the Bulgarian social and economic sciences, which is developing rapidly after the transition from communism to democracy, from a closed to an open society.

MAPPING THE MIGRATION STUDIES FIELD

The map of the migration research could be presented by two logical and one paradoxical characteristics. The first two are theoretical expressions of the migration profile, the last one is an important research zoom on a relatively minor migration phenomenon. The research reflects the specificity of the migration profile by a significant number of publications on emigration. They focus on Bulgarian emigration and diaspora in numerous countries, the push factors – the economic and social reasons for emigration in relation to regional socio-economic disparities (Minchev et al 2016). An increasing cluster of studies analyses return – causes for return migration, reintegration, incentives and motivation for re-emigration (Nonchev and Hristova 2018, Minchev 2016, Hristova 2018). Negative phenomena such as trafficking are also object of numerous PhDs (Stamenkov 2020) and projects.

The immigration research started with the study of the various communities – Russians, Arabs, Chinese, Africans, etc. (Krasteva 2005). Numerous publications detailed and deepened the knowledge and understanding of the immigration phenomenon in Bulgaria in terms of politics and policies, of social and economic integration, of the migration and development nexus, of social representations, etc. (OSI 2010 and 2014, Vladimirova 2009 and 2019, Economic Institute 2008, Maeva 2019, Mantarova 2018, Krasteva numerous years).

The paradoxical characteristic of the Bulgarian migration studies is the interesting asymmetry between very small number of refugees and the rapidly growing field of refugee research (Tsankov 2016, Ilareva 2017, Vankova 2013, Hristova, Maystorovich, Petkova 2019, Tcholarova 2012). This positive paradox is due to two major factors: participation of Bulgarian scholars in European and international projects, and also to the very active

policy of UNHCR-Bulgaria. UNHCR funds numerous projects on labour, social, educational integration and increases the visibility of all refugee research activities through the Academic Bulletin, numerous stakeholder workshops, etc.

STATE OF THE ART IN FIELDS RELEVANT FOR MATILDE

ASSESSMENT OF MIGRATION AND INTEGRATION STRATEGIES AND POLICIES

The assessments of foreign analysts on Bulgaria's integration policy are polarised. From the positive side, the European Migration Network (EMN) notes that: "In the field of integration, Bulgaria has modern, well-developed and effective legislation in the area of equal opportunities, social inclusion and non-discrimination, which is in line with EU standards" (EMN 2018a: 2). From a more critical position, the Migrant Integration Policy Index (MIPEX) notes that: "Immigrant integration is still not a priority for the Bulgarian government." (MIPEX Bulgaria 2015). Bulgarian scholars develop the critical perspective. A human rights lawyer (Interview 6) criticises EMN interpretation:

This is a wrong and misleading conclusion. We definitely have national regulations and procedures on protection against discrimination. But with regard to our refugee-migration system, there is a zero level of implementation of integration policy for the 6th consecutive year. The latest version of the AIDA Report for Bulgaria of February 2020 (p. 13) reads: "Integration: No integration activities are planned, funded or made available to recognized refugees or subsidiary protection holders; thus marking the sixth consecutive year of the national" zero integration "Policy" (Interview 6)

The lack of political will in this direction, the fragmentary addressing of individual groups and issues, the lack of a long-term vision for migration and integration is part of this problem.' In the same vein of thought, another prominent human rights lawyer, also very critically assesses the lack of refugee integration: 'Regarding integration, unfortunately, not only for several consecutive years we have a "zero year of integration", but also with the latest amendments to the LAR, SG. No. 89 of October 16, 2020, the possibility for support with shelter

by the SAR of those who received the status was eliminated, and at the same time the obligations for the refugees were increased. That is, there is no integration support, but there are more obligations' (Interview 5)

The paradoxes and discontinuities in Bulgaria's migration and integration policies can be summarised in several points (Krasteva 2019):

Late inclusion into government priorities: migration was assigned the status of a public policy, on which the State has a strategic vision, almost two decades after the beginning of the transition. It was not until 2008 that the first strategy for migration and integration was adopted. The strategy covers emigration, immigration and refugees. Its late adoption expresses the discrepancy between the migration policy and the migration phenomena - the huge emigration, the new phenomenon of refugees after the adoption of the Geneva Convention in 1993 and the increasing immigration.

Abrupt, unclear and unexplained discontinuities: in 2010, at the very beginning of the implementation of the first strategy for migration and integration, and without public information about the grounds for revision, work began on the elaboration of a new strategy, which entered into force in 2011. Less than halfway through the planned timeline, a third strategy entered into force in 2015.

Redefinition of the main priorities in migration policy: if the main focus of the 2008 Strategy was on economic emigration and integration of third-country nationals, the 2011 Strategy focused mainly on (in)security issues.

Lack of sustainability in policy implementation: in 2011, action plans for implementation of the 2011-2020 Strategy stopped being adopted, and then the Strategy itself was repealed without a public debate (Krasteva 2014a:618-619). The 2015-2020 Strategy was left for a long time without an Action Plan - it was not until 2018 that the plan was adopted.

MIGRATION AND DEVELOPMENT NEXUS. LABOUR MARKET INTEGRATION

The labour migration is conceptualised and analysed positively as a resource in the framework of the migration and development nexus (Krasteva 2019). This approach is a theoretical and normative alternative to the securitization of migration.

TCNs' labour market integration is studied in regard to the differentiated labour market profile of the various migrant communities and the economic sectors attracting migrant labour force.

A major characteristic of the migration profile of TCNs from the Near and Middle East and China is that a majority of them are self-employed and own small, medium-sized or large businesses. Most of them are occupied in the typical ethnic niches - restaurant industry and retail. The labour integration of Russians is the most varied and diversified. Unlike most other immigrant communities in Bulgaria - who are employed primarily in the private sector - first, second and third-generation Russian immigrants are employed in public administration, media, and education at all levels. There is also a new wave of Russians who have invested in property on the Black Sea coast which they use for holidays and rent out without settling permanently in Bulgaria. The African community in Bulgaria is very small. In the last decade, call centres - where fluency in French and English is highly appreciated - have provided the chance and impetus for their labour integration. Britons illustrate another category of TCNs whose migration project is not necessarily aimed at labour integration, insofar as some of them are retirees and settle in spa and small villages and towns. Some of them start small businesses - for example, as real estate brokers for compatriots interested in buying houses in Bulgaria, intermediaries or investors in health/dental tourism, etc.

Another type of TCNs are the seasonal and temporary workers. Third-country nationals are employed predominantly in tourism, services, manufacturing and education, as well as construction and commerce (EMN 2018b:14-15).

The integration of refugees through labour market is a relatively new, but rapidly developing, field with contribution from young scholars: Albena Tcholakova in her comparative PhD analysed the refugee labour integration in Bulgaria and France; Stana Iliev (2017) is a pioneer of another type of comparison - between the two most disadvantaged groups of Roma and refugees. Stana Iliev's study of the business community engagement in refugee integration is particularly interesting. She focusses on success stories, as well as on difficulties. The business initiatives on refugee integration are still few in number, but the study differentiates three different types: Bulgarian companies, companies of migrant entrepreneurs, and innovative forms of social entrepreneurship. - *TELUS International Europe* (a business process outsourcing and information technology outsourcing provider) is an interesting example of a Bulgarian company that employs 100 refugees and

humanitarian status holders. In addition to work, the company offers a wide range of social services as well as cultural, sporting and other events for its employees (Iliev 2017: 18). One of the main difficulties for companies is the mobility of refugees. Bulgaria is a transit country for most refugees (Iliev 2017:17). The company Convoy, based in the town of Novi Iskar, is a typical example: of the twenty people hired originally, one refugee woman and two men remain in the company (Iliev 2017:16). A similar example is that of Pirin Tex in Gotse Delchev (Iliev 2017:12). Recent studies confirm and develop Tcholakova's and Iliev's findings (Catro Bulgaria 2018, UNHCR Bulgaria, The Bulgarian Council on Refugees and Migrants (2021).

1.3 ASSESSMENT OF THE INTEGRATION AT LOCAL LEVEL THROUGH SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

METHODOLOGICAL COMMENTS

Six interviews were conducted. The interviewees introduce three perspectives: the civil society's understanding of integration, represented by a NGO and a humanitarian organisation, the one of a refugee with successful integration, and the legal and human rights one of two lawyers. These perspectives are rather close and do not cover the variety of viewpoints and assessments. Our local partner invested efforts to organise an interview with a representative of the municipality. They failed so far for a variety of reasons, the pandemic being an important one, but also the claim 'that they [the Municipality employees] are incompetent'. We take this claim very seriously – a municipality with a new refugee centre is not willing or able or both to develop expertise in managing migration issues. We are continuing our efforts to schedule this interview. These limitations of the empirical study are mitigated through three analytical provisions: 1/the perspective of business will be examined at the later stage of the project; 2/the local authorities will be interviewed if they accept to be interviewed; 3/the impact of populist discourses and policies is mainly produced by national actors – populist leaders and politicians, nationalist parties in government, etc. and are studied on a regular basis by the CERMES team of political scientists. The representativeness of qualitative methods relies on their internal coherence and wide external knowledge of the researchers, as specified during a Matilde methodological debate.

The respondents are as follow: Founder and president of a NGO dealing with vulnerable groups, incl. refugees and migrants; A refugee from Iran, member of the Advisory Refugee Board; Representative of a local branch of a humanitarian organisation; Team leader of a local branch of a humanitarian organisation; Human rights lawyer; Human rights lawyer.

The interviewees have been informed of the project, first, by email with the Matilde Participant Information Sheet, and second, orally at the beginning of the interview. They all signed the Consent form. They agreed for a high-level visibility of their participation. The atmosphere of the interviews was very cordial. All the interviewees were willing to participate in the research. The duration of the conducted interviews varied from

45 to 90 minutes. All the interviews were conducted online, using Zoom. There were some small technical issues, because of not very good internet connection at moments, but these were rather exceptional. The interviews with the Bulgarian citizens were conducted in Bulgarian, the interview with the refugee – in English. The two representatives of the humanitarian organisation expressed a wish to participate in the interview together, but easily accepted to give separate interviews.

As mentioned in the Introduction, several questions from the questionnaire were not applicable to the Bulgarian case. All interviewees have experience in working with migrants and refugees.

DIFFERENTIATED IMPACT OF TCN AND REFUGEES IN A REGION IN MIGRATION TRANSITION

The migration profile of Harmanli, the Matilde region under study, is the profound change brought with the construction of the Registration and Reception centre, the rapid increase of migrants, the change of their profile from economic to refugee. This change happened in a context defined by three factors – the refugee crisis of 2015-16, the unpreparedness of the local population and local authorities for this transition and the impact of anti-immigration rhetoric on social representations and attitudes.

The region of Harmanli experiences the transition from a diversified, but relatively small and well integrated migration to a rapid increase of new arrivals – mainly asylum seekers and refugees. The first group is represented by Turks, Russians and Britons. According to the 2018 annual report of the National Statistical Institute on the population and demographic processes in Haskovo district, 29.559 people have changed their place of residence from abroad to Bulgaria. This includes Bulgarian citizens, as well as foreigners with a residence permit or status. The highest share of immigrants is from Turkey (25.9%), Russian Federation (11.%) and Germany (7.2%) (NSI Territorial Bureau South 2019). The impact on local economy and society of the various group depends on the duration of the settlement, the size of the group, the integration to the labour market, and national specificities. The interviews detailed the differentiated impact of the migrant communities, the various forms and levels of integration and specific integration needs.

ECONOMIC AND LABOUR MARKET INTEGRATION

The structure of the Haskovo district economy is as follows: 32% - primary sector, 24% - secondary sector, 45% - tertiary sector (Bogomilova, Krasteva, Spenger, Staikova 2020). Most TCNs are employed in the secondary and tertiary sector. The economic integration is assessed in three regards: integration into the labour market, migrant entrepreneurship and migrants' impact on the local economy:

The labour market integration follows different paths. The major one is through employment in local enterprises. The study has identified a few companies hiring migrants and refugees, e.g. a factory in the confectionary industry producing baklava in Haskovo (Interview 1,2,3,4). One of the interviewees together with other refugees used to work in a factory for blankets and bed linen in Harmanli (Interview 2).

A second path is through upskilling. An informant exemplifies the policy of qualification with a free qualification course for refugees and its beneficial outcome: *'The state covers the tuition fees, per diems and accommodation for a 3-month course. This opportunity fits to the ambition of a young Afghan refugee to become welder in the very specialized field of underwater welding'* (Interview 1). Another interviewee mentions that this good opportunity is not well known in the region (Interview 2)

A third path of labour market integration starts with humanitarian assistance. An interviewee reported an interesting example of an African family: *'The man is from Côte d'Ivoire. The woman is from Nigeria. They received humanitarian statutes for religious reasons. He used to work in the local Orthodox Church, and now he is working on a program for the municipality of Svilengrad. They live in Svilengrad and work there and do not want to go anywhere.'* (Interview 1). While most immigrants are employed in the private sector, this example illustrates a positive case of employment by a program of the local authorities.

Labour market integration is hampered by two factors - low salaries and relatively limited labour and entrepreneurial opportunities in a small town. *'There are cases where employers are looking for labour, but some refugees do not want to work for low wages. They prefer to be unemployed than to take BGN 20 per day'* (Interview 3) This peculiarity should be understood in the perspective of the predominantly transit character of migration. An informant stresses that Harmanli can't address the employment need of the increased number of refugees: *'We have right now 400 or more refugees living in the camp [in Harmanli] and there is only one*

factory that can accept maximum 15 of them. From Harmanli some of them will go to Haskovo, Plovdiv and the majority will go to Sofia'(Interview 2). *'In Haskovo and Dimitrovgrad people manage to find a job because they are bigger cities, in Harmanli it is more difficult.'* (Interview 1) Bigger cities are assessed as more favourable for starting a business: Syrian father and son decide to settle in Bulgaria and choose Plovdiv: *'We want to stay in Bulgaria, in Plovdiv, the city is very nice. The father opens a Syrian restaurant. Then the little brother and mother arrive, so the whole family reunites - a dream comes true.'* (Interview 3)

The economic crisis provoked by the pandemic impacted employment and increased labour insecurity. 'Most of refugees lost their jobs and after [the first wave of] the pandemic finished some of them restarted working, some of them did not. The factory for pillows and blankets closed but after it started working people went back to work.' (Interview 2). A similar example is reported with another factory: *'A refugee from the baklava factory has been out of work for some time, but yesterday she returned to work'* (Interview 3). These quotes illustrate an important peculiarity of the labour market integration in the region – several migrants, especially refugees, do not have full time contracts.

Migrant entrepreneurship. Several immigrants are self-employed or entrepreneurs. Several cases of the latter have been reported in the interviews: *'The Syrian guy with a fast-food restaurant here is a very successful example of integration because he has a job, most of his clients are Bulgarians so they accept him as part of their society and he is still living in Harmanli and he didn't leave for Sofia or abroad.'* (Interview 2). The bigger the community, the more visible and significant their economic impact is. A case in point are the Turkish entrepreneurs: *'There are many Turks in Harmanli. In some sectors such as construction and maintenance, they predominate'* (Interview 4). Numerous entrepreneurs in various spheres are from the Turkish community: *'A Turkish owner of a factory for blankets in Harmanli hired initially 3 refugees, 'now they are more than 15. The good thing about this factory is that even Roma work there'* (Interview 2). The same trend is identified in housing: A Turkish speaking owner of 5-6 flats in Harmanli is open to rent them to refugees (Interview 1). Migrant entrepreneurship is characterised by national and gender diversity. Russian women entrepreneurs are a case in point: *'Two Russian women have business. One of them has a cloths store, the other - a chain of stores - grocery and stores for household goods.'* (Interview 4).

Impact on the local economy. A case in point are Britons: *'Most are retirees, but not all of them'* (Interview 4). They settle in small villages and boost the local economy by buying real estate, consuming goods and services. Other European citizens, such as Dutch and Finns (Interview 4), have the same profile and a similar positive impact. This type of (mainly) retirement migration is assessed as a win-win game *'They have adapted to life there, communicate with everyone. Local people accept them as part of the community already. They integrate well'* (Interview 4). The positive impact of migrants on the local economy is appreciated also in urban context. The local business and services welcome and target the new clientele: *'In a restaurant, you can see the inscriptions in Bulgarian and Arabic. Local people recognized the benefit because refugees are customers of various services, buy goods...'* (Interview 1)

HOUSING REMAINS A PROBLEM

Housing remains a problematic aspect of integration. Two risks have been identified, as well as a few good practices.

The *first risk is of temporary homelessness for refugees: 'I personally saw, for example how H. who received refugee status, on the day he took his documents from the refugee camp and left, he stayed on the street. He lived in our office for 22 days because he was homeless. Nobody cared, the State I mean. The Stay Agency for Refugees does not help them to find a job or house. If the refugees decide to stay in Bulgaria, they are absolutely homeless without any support. The only ones who help are the NGOs.'* (Interview 1). The interviewee emphasizes that the lack of housing policy of responsible authorities may result in a temporary homelessness.

A second risk is to overcome the negative attitude among part of the population that complicate and hinder the access to accommodation: *'When we were looking for apartment for H. (a refugee) it was a nightmare, as well as the search for an office for our organisation helping refugees.'* (Interview 1). The anti-migrant attitudes forged and boosted by populist rhetoric hamper both the accommodation of some refugees, as well as renting offices for NGOs working with refugees.

Good practices are provided by civic society actors, especially NGOs and churches. The NGO Mission Wing has a program 'Mom and baby' that offers shelter for vulnerable migrants, e.g. single mothers with small children: *'We have a woman from Iraq with two children. According to the methodology of the 'Mom and Baby' Unit, she*

can stay for a maximum of six months. She has been in our institution for two years now... (Interview 1). These humanitarian actors often unite efforts for granting continuity of support for housing. A single mother from Guinea has been accommodated initially in the housing facilities 'Mom and baby', then she moved to external address and a church helped her with the rent. The NGO continued their support with food, diapers. (Interview 1).

The local real-estate market also reacts positively to the new clientele. Some real-estate entrepreneurs and dealers get specialized in the new niche and offer flats for rents to foreigners. Housing in villages is rather cheap – Britons prefer to buy houses and restore them thus revitalizing the outlook of the small settlements.

EDUCATION POLICY – A SMALL SUCCESS STORY

Matilde region of Haskovo ranks second after the capital for the enrolment of migrant children is school which makes the educational integration a small success story. The key factors for this results are the combined and complementary efforts of national and local education authorities, from one side, and NGOs education activities in informal education⁴⁷, from another side.

Education integration of refugee children has been problematic at the beginning, especially because of rejection attitudes of a few parents of Bulgarian children: *'Mothers were rather hostile and unwilling to accept the refugee kids in the classes of their own children but gradually the situation calmed down'* (Interview 3). This tended initial situation after the arrival of the refugees in Harmanli has been slowly overcome thanks to the efforts of educators with intercultural sensitivity. An interviewee emphasized the crucial positive role for building trust and intercultural understanding of *'cool teachers who do their best for refugee children in their class. They educate Bulgarian parents, support other children to accept them'* (Interview 1).

⁴⁷ Included in Good practices

1.4 CONCLUDING REMARKS AND GOOD PRACTICES

CONCLUDING REMARKS ON SOCIAL POLICIES WP3

The migration profile of Harmanli is defined by three major characteristics – the change and the structure of the migration panorama, as well as the policy which implemented this change:

- The change in the migration profile was introduced by the new Registration and Reception Centre with a significant impact on the social, economic and political life.
- The structure of the migration profile has two poles – ‘old’ and ‘new’ migrants. The ‘old’ migrants are well integrated economically, linguistically, culturally, as well as in housing and education. The new foreigners are mainly refugees, most of them temporary. They face difficulties in integration and need targeted policies.
- This policy change was not initiated at a local level, but at a central governmental level. The rationale lies in the political will to decentralize asylum reception and not so much meet local needs – mitigate depopulation and revitalize local development through migration as a resource. Local migration and integration policies remain under institutionalized. A recommendation for an integration centre, formulated by an informant, would be a valid tool for local authorities: ‘I have been talking to UNHCR for a long time that an integration centre should be set up in Harmanli to support with information, consultation, accompaniment, guidance all those who leave the refugee centers in the area and seek some help, whether they want to stay or depart. These people need help because they are left on the street.’ (Interview 1).

Education policy is positively assessed because of the complementarity of factors and actors: governmental policy for enrolment of refugee children; active commitment of teachers for working with both the foreign and Bulgarian children for an inclusive education, as well as with parents who fear the migrants; active support of local NGOs.

Housing policy is less successful. The main actors are real estate entrepreneurs and NGOs supporting the most vulnerable migrants. Targeted local policies are lacking.

Three types of actors contribute to migrants' inclusion in local society:

- Local and national NGOs with complementary expertise. A very good practice is the fruitful collaboration among NGOs, e.g. the local 'Mission Wings' and Sofia-based 'Voice in Bulgaria' with excellent human rights lawyers (Interview 1)
- Churches are an important humanitarian actor. 'Some churches – catholic and protestant, unfortunately not the Orthodox ones – try to help, e.g. a catholic ones in Haskovo and Stara Zagora, a few protestant churches in the region'. (Interview 1).
- Migrant communities in the region play the typical role of mediators: 'Migrants have their own community, inform and help each other.' (Interview 4) Migrant communities and networks are a social capital – foreigners from Middle East profit largely, while migrants who are only a few such as Africans can't count on such a support at the local level.

GOOD PRACTICES

Migrant empowerment. One interviewee represents an exemplary story of successful He was homeless, despite his education and qualifications, his first job was in a factory. He omits these difficult periods in his personal story and highlights the present where he works for two NGOs and is member of the Refugee Advisory Board: 'I am a translator and coordinator for the "Mission Wings" foundation. I am a translator for Legal Aid center - Voice and I am working with UNHCR in the Refugee Advisory Board. (Interview 2) He considers his work at Missing Wing both as a job and a mission: 'There are a lot of NGO here but for me what is important are their intentions and the personality of the people. I saw humanity in 'Mission Wings' and this is what I was searching for - to do humanitarian things to fulfil my human duties'. H. does not speak of his own empowerment, but aspired to make change: 'The Refugee Advisory Board – we are a chance for change.' (Interview 2)

NGO 'Mission Wing' is set up in 2008 in the city of Stara Zagora with the aim to support vulnerable groups, especially children and families. They run a 'Centre for social support', as well as a Unit 'Mom and baby' with a

variety of social services. One of their target groups are refugees and migrants. They accommodate refugees and migrant families in their facilities, including single mothers with children. In March 2020 the NGO opens a branch in Harmanli. They identified vulnerable refugees and migrants in five municipalities – Harmanli, Svilendrag, Dimitrovgrad, Lubimetz and Nova Zagora. They offer services to the refugees in the reception centres in Harmanli, Pastrogor and Lubimetz, as well as to those living outside the camps. The weekly health consultations are appreciated and visited – sometimes about 60 refugees and migrants take part in. (Interview 1).

Charity events raise awareness and succeed sometimes in converting hatred into solidarity: I had an interesting case with a 20-year-old young man from Afghanistan. He was almost blind because of a group that wanted to recruit him. He needed glasses. We announced a campaign for 300 BGN on the Internet, we started collecting BGN 10, BGN 20. It is more important for us when 30 people give BGN 10, not one giving the whole amount, because this means that 30 are sensitive to the issue. A woman had given a friend of mine BGN 20 for this boy. My friend said, “How come you give BGN 20 to a young Afghan, he can be a terrorist. Aren’t you against the refugees, aren’t you constantly writing against them?” The woman replied that yes, she was against the refugees, but this story moved her. So we try to touch the soft part of people’ (Interview 1). Similar cases are reported by other respondents: ‘a person who organised anti-refugee protests, later participated in humanitarian actions bringing cloths to the refugees.’ (Interview 3)

Caritas – Harmanli. Caritas has offices in two towns in the Matilde region – Harmanli and Lubimetz. The main target of Caritas activities in Harmanli are children and women, but they contribute also to labour integration by mediating the relations among employers and refugees: ‘When an employer is looking for workers, s/he contacts us and we transfer that information to refugees’ (Interview 4). The main activity is intercultural mediation for educational integration: ‘We work actively with refugee parents, and our main goal is to convince them to enrol their children in school. We help with the communication with the principals, with the school management, with the host society. We work with our host society to accept refugee children in schools. The first year a child went to school, [Bulgarian] mothers organized a protest. So there is a lot to do with the host society. At the moment the situation is better’ (Interview 4). Bridging moms is crucial for intercultural understanding: ‘We organize meetings with mothers. We usually choose mothers from classes with children from the camp. We make meetings on the topic of culture, cooking, exchange recipes, someone cooks.

Bulgarian mothers see that refugees are not what they imagined them to be, but are the same people as them - mothers.' (Interview 4).

Art and sport are powerful tools for intercultural dialogue and Caritas practice them in variety of forms: 'art for women, sports for women, sport for children, sport for men.' (Interview 3) Bulgarian folklore dances, theatre performances are organized on various occasions, (Interview 3) A very nice initiatives for bridging generations, as well as refugees and local society are the activities with senior citizens: 'Refugee children with folklore costumes, offered by the municipality or the chitalishte [cultural club], sing Bulgarian songs and perform traditional rituals and the seniors in retirement clubs are very happy and welcoming.' (Interview 4) Local authorities collaborate with the NGO for enhancing intercultural exchanges: 'We visited the village of Dositeevo at the invitation of the municipality on the occasion of St. Nicholas Day. They recreated the customs, the traditional food. The first time we were just guests, on the next visit we took an active part - women from Iraq, Iran and Afghanistan cooked, all joined in the songs and dances.' (Interview 4). The result is mutual joy and satisfaction: 'The people in the villages greet us warmly, they, as well as refugees have a sincere desire to communicate.' (Interview 4).

CONCLUDING REMARKS ON ECONOMIC AND LABOUR INTEGRATION POLICIES WP4

Bulgaria's integration in the European Union is a key impetus for harmonising legislation in the sphere of labour migration. Amendments to the Labour Migration and Labour Mobility Act, adopted in 2018, have eased access to the Bulgarian labour market for third-country nationals. In the decade after 2008, several national strategies on migration, asylum and integration were adopted, offering opportunities for enhancing migrant and refugee contributions to development. The National Strategy for the Integration of Beneficiaries of International Protection in the Republic of Bulgaria (2014-2020) redefined Bulgaria's refugee integration policy from centralised to decentralised approach in which municipalities have the leading role.

The migration profile of the Matilde region changed significantly the last years: if before it was characterised by a non-numerous, yet well integrated migrants, the setting up of a Registration and reception centre during the crisis of 2015-16 increased the migration presence. The economic impact of the increased migration is

positive and visible. It contributes to boost services, real estate - local shops and businesses target the new clientele.

The labour market integration does not follow the economic structure of the region: the agricultural sector represents one third of it (32%), but migrants are employed mainly in the tertiary and secondary sectors. The potential of migrant labour force for agriculture is underutilised.

Several trends at the national level are also characteristic for the Matilde region:

- Several migrants are self-employed and/or entrepreneurs which enhances their contribution to local economy and society through taxes, entrepreneurial culture, role model for new migrants and local residents.
- Upskilling and acquiring new qualifications facilitate the access to better qualified jobs. Policies for qualification of refugees do exist and bring positive results in Matilde region, but are not very well known.
- More migrants and refugees are being employed by institutions and NGOs as interpreters/translators, social workers and mediators, which allows them to actively contribute to the integration of the newly arriving migrants and refugees. This practice at national level especially during and after the migration crisis, is already also introduced in the Matilde region. One of our interviewees is a good example.
- Foreign owners of companies are (more) open to migrant labour. The profile of the owners hiring migrants is diverse, but it is worth noting that some are foreigners, specifically Turks.
- The employability fluctuates and Covid-19 impacted it negatively - several refugees lost their jobs. The positive aspect of this negative trend is that when enterprises started to reopen they hired again their old employees.

The difficulties and obstacles for labour market integration in the Matilde region can be summarized in three regards:

- Lack of efficient policies for refugee integration. The ‘integration zero years’, according to the unanimous diagnosis of national and international experts and human rights organisations, as well as of interviewees, demonstrate the lack of strategic vision for new migrants as a resource for revitalizing this remote region.
- Relatively low salaries which discourage some of the migrants and refugees who prefer to head to western countries. The major factors for the transit migration of several migrants in the Matilde region and in the country are: 1/Bulgaria is the poorest EU member state; 2/There are no policies aimed at transforming the transit migration into a permanent one; 3/On the opposite, populist discourses discourage most migrants to settle permanently.
- Relatively limited labour and entrepreneurial opportunities in a small town which that motivate some migrants to transform the international migration into an internal one and to leave Harmanli for bigger cities. The internal migration of TCNs is an alternative to transit migration. The policies for local development do not sufficiently take into account the possible contribution of migrants for revitalizing the local economy.

GOOD PRACTICES

Immigrant entrepreneurs. Several cases of migrant entrepreneurs have been reported (Interview 1.2.3.4). A Chinese store and Turkish entrepreneurs illustrate the widespread entrepreneurial activities among ‘old’ migrants (Interview 3). Some new migrants also start small businesses: ‘a Syrian guy is a barber’ (Interview 2), ‘a few refugees have a phone accessories store selling phone parts’ (Interview 3). A similar case of entrepreneurship as inclusion in the local society is reported with another migrant from Syria: ‘A man from Syria has a second-hand clothing store in the city center. Many people go shopping there. They don’t mind he is Syrian and doing business.’ (Interview 3). The potential for entrepreneurship is illustrated by an asylum seeker from Iran, father of 4 children, who, even before the refugee status was granted, opened a hair-dressing salon. Another refugee from Syria did the same (Interview 1). Some migrant entrepreneurs target migrant customers: ‘An Iraqi refugee opened an Internet café. This internet cafe is mainly used by refugees’ (Interview 4). Women are also active in entrepreneurship: ‘An Iraqi refugee opened a beauty salon for painting eyebrows with thread.’ (Interview 3).

Business engagement in refugee integration. Business initiatives on refugee integration are still few in number, but it is important to note three types of business actors engaged in this field: Bulgarian companies, companies of migrant entrepreneurs, and forms of social entrepreneurship. Among migrant businesspersons, the best known for its humanitarian and integration activities is the Syrian-born entrepreneur Aladin. At the beginning of the refugee crisis, representatives of his company, Aladin Foods, started visiting the RRC-Harmanli every two or three months and offered employment to men and women, as well as free-of-charge accommodation in a well-furnished house. Most of the refugees and humanitarian status holders stayed in the house for five to seven months before leaving Bulgaria, heading for Western Europe (BCRM 2014:43). Aladin has also funded the higher education of one of his refugee employees.

Labour integration as a path to housing and education and social integration. A very good practice is when the employers offer not only jobs, but also housing and help refugees to other forms of integration – education of kinds, access to institutions: ‘The owner of the ‘Spring’ factory for bags and other leather products in Plovdiv offered a flat to a big Afghan family with nine kids (they pay the rent), helped the children to enrol in a local

school; he treats them very well' (Interview 1). Another interview tells the continuation of the story: 'They have different work now. The better you get to know the language the better opportunities you have. (Interview 2)

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MATILDE

4. FINLAND

Country: Finland

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1.1 INTRODUCTION AND BRIEF BACKGROUND

In a large scale, Immigration to Finland is still a comparatively recent phenomenon. Finland has traditionally been a country of emigration. Thus, for long, the impact of migration was considered in these terms; the impact of migration has first and foremost stemmed from emigration. During the past one hundred years more than a million people have moved to other countries⁴⁸, most notably to Sweden and USA in search of a better life, opportunities and higher levels of well-being. Emigration has occurred largely in specific waves: from the 1860's to the 1930's mainly towards for North America, and from the 1950's until the 1970's to Sweden.

While examples of mobility to the territory of what is today the Republic of Finland can be traced far back in history, it is hard to assess these mobilities the way immigration is discussed today. Even after Finland gained its independence in 1917, the number of people immigrating to Finland remained low. After World War I and the Russian revolution immigrants consisted mainly of a limited number of refugees from Eastern Europe, many of whom were Russians.⁴⁹ From World War II up to the early 1970s Finland remained as a rather closed society attracting very few immigrants.⁵⁰ Those who did arrive tended to stay only for a short period of time, usually for study or temporary work-related purposes. During the late 1970s and 1980s, marriage and family related immigration become more common. Until the end of the 1980s, some 85 % of the immigrants to Finland were return migrants, mostly from Sweden.⁵¹ Only notable group of foreign origin was formed by approximately

⁴⁸ Korkiasaari, 1998.

⁴⁹ Nylund-Oja et al. 1995

⁵⁰ Korkiasaari & Söderling, 2003

⁵¹ Ibid.

200 refugees from Chile, following the 1973 Chilean coup d'état, and then by some 800 refugees from Vietnam in the early 1980s, who immigrated to Finland.

In 1990, the share of foreign citizens in Finland was still less than one percent⁵², a lower percentage than in any other country in Europe at that time. Since then, the figure increased, yet it can still be considered as very low. The first two major groups of immigrants to Finland were asylum seekers and refugees from Somalia and migrants from Soviet Union and former Soviet territories. The collapse of the socialist countries, civil war in the former Yugoslavia as well as the developments in Asia and Africa can be mentioned as the key push factors to Finland and shortage of domestic labour as a characteristic pull factor of the era.⁵³

A specific form of immigration relates to the Russian Finns (also known as Ingrian Finns or Ingrians), who are descendants of the Finns who settled in the lands around the present-day St. Petersburg (when it was a part of the Kingdom of Sweden) in the 17th century. Following the Right to Return policy initiated by the Finnish President Mauno Koivisto in April 1990, more than 10,000 Ingrians moved to Finland within the first couple of years and another 25,000 followed later on. The share of immigrants from the former Soviet Union as whole has increased steadily ever since then, the current count of Russian speakers being close to 82,000.⁵⁴ It is noteworthy that while before, a vast majority of the immigrants were return migrants (of Finnish origin), in the 1990s already more than half of the immigrants were of foreign origin. Overall, in the 90s, immigration to Finland was mainly humanitarian, work and family based.

Finland joined the EU in 1995, which enabled freedom of movement, and the Schengen Area in 2001, which made immigration to Finland easier. Accordingly, most of the immigrants arriving to Finland are Europeans. The number, share and origin of the immigrant population has, nevertheless, not only grown but diversified. In 2019, the number of foreign-born persons was approximately 423,494, or 7,7% of the total population of Finland. Evidently, immigration has greatly increased the diversity of the Finnish society. The number of languages

⁵² Statistics Finland, 1980–1999.

⁵³ Korkiasaari & Söderling, 2003.

⁵⁴ Statistics Finland, 2020a.

spoken in Finland has tripled since 1990 (being now more than 160). There are 412,700 foreign language speakers in Finland, the Russian speakers forming the largest foreign language group (81 606), followed by Estonian speakers (49 427) Arabic speakers (31 927). There are now approximately 180 different foreign citizenship groups living in Finland. By far the largest group is formed by Estonians, followed by Russian citizens, the Iraqi citizens being on the third place. The top three is followed in the citizenship statistics by the Chinese, Swedes, and Thais. Other groups of importance remain under seven thousand persons. The motives to move to Finland have also become more varied. Currently, most immigrants move to Finland for family reasons, to work or to study. The recent influx of rapidly increased refugee and asylum seeker arrivals has, however, changed the customary immigration profiles remarkably.⁵⁵ Given the focus of the MATILDE project, it is important to note that, as a rule, immigrants settle overwhelmingly in cities and their surroundings. Only some 11% of immigrants are in the countryside, with most of them being Europeans.⁵⁶

Finland is a Nordic Welfare State, where the distribution of welfare benefits and services is based on the idea of universalism. The right to welfare benefits is based on municipal placement and all the benefits and services are aimed for residents of the country, who have legal municipal place in one of the Finnish municipalities⁵⁷. Those who move to Finland in work, family or study purposes get the municipal place and right to welfare state benefits in equal terms with Finnish citizens. Those who come to Finland based on humanitarian reasons are divided in two categories: *asylum seekers*, who are still applying/pending for the formal right to stay in Finland and *refugees*, who have already obtained that right. If an asylum seeker receives a positive decision on her/his application, s/he will no longer be a client of the Finnish Immigration Service, but a formal resident of a municipality. This assigned home municipality will be responsible for organising the basic services (e.g., health care, schooling, etc) and specific integration services that the municipality organises for immigrants.

⁵⁵ Laine & Rauhut, 2018.

⁵⁶ Juopperi, 2019.

⁵⁷ Municipality of Residence (Act 201/1994)

The material used in this briefing was collected from the different governmental, regional and local public organizations, representatives of civil society organisations (CSOs), and statistical offices. The main general sources are the site of Ministry of Interior, the Ministry of Economic Affairs, and the Finnish Immigration Service. Regional sources mainly consist of municipal websites, as well as the websites and the officials in the Centre for Economic Development, Transport (CEDTE), and the Environment and the Regional Councils of our two case study regions. Municipal integration program documents were retrieved either from their own websites or through the approached municipal employees. The legislation as well as the official translations were retrieved from Finlex Data bank, a governmental online service containing up-to-date Finnish legislation⁵⁸. We also included the current and three previous government programs of Finnish governments.

LEGISLATION, RIGHTS, AND SERVICES

The highest authority in charge of the Finnish immigrant policy and legislation is the Ministry of Interior. In addition to legislating immigration, the ministry also governs the Finnish Immigration Service (MIGRI), the police and the border guard. The latter two organizations oversee accepting of asylum applications and carrying out deportations. The Police also oversees the compliance of the Aliens Act (301/2004) and the border guard controls legal entry into the country. MIGRI, which was founded in 1995⁵⁹, handles residence permits, asylum, and citizenship applications, manages reception centres⁶⁰ and provides research data to assist in policy making⁶¹.

⁵⁸ Finlex is an online database of up-to-date legislative and other judicial information of Finland. Finlex is owned by Finland's Ministry of Justice, <https://www.finlex.fi/en/>

⁵⁹ Immigration Service Act (156/1995)

⁶⁰ Since 2016, Amendment of the Immigration Service Act section 2 (1160/2016)

⁶¹ i.e. country safety reviews

Integration processes together with the matters concerning labour, student and researcher migration are governed by the ministry of economic affairs⁶². These processes are regionalized through the Centres for Economic Development, Transport, and the Environment (CEDTEs) and Local Employment and Economic Development Offices (TE Offices). Other ministries and governmental organizations⁶³ also play their part in institutional proceedings concerning immigration. On the most practical level this mainly means the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health.

The first act to legislate specifically the immigrant affairs in Finland was the Aliens Act of 1991⁶⁴ which was passed to regulate entry, departure, residence permits and labour market testing in Finland. It was amended multiple times in late 1990s and early 2000s, especially to react and better match with the changing needs deriving from the increasing levels of humanitarian migrants. The current Aliens Act⁶⁵ replaced the old legislation in 2004. The first legislation which established national policies for integration and asylum seeker reception was not passed into law until 1999⁶⁶; prior to this humanitarian migration was governed mainly through international treaties which Finland was part of. The most recent integration legislation was issued in

⁶² INTERMIN (2020)

⁶³ i.a. Non-discrimination Ombudsman

⁶⁴ Aliens Act (378/1991)

⁶⁵ Aliens Act (301/2004)

⁶⁶ Act on the Integration of Immigrants and Reception of Asylum Seekers (493/1999)

late 2010⁶⁷ and the current act managing international protection and reception of asylum seekers⁶⁸ in the mid-2011. These acts were made to separate the integration and humanitarian migration into their own legislations.

Residence permit for TCN immigrants can be either fixed term or permanent⁶⁹. The first permits are always granted only for a fixed term, yet they may be either temporary (fixed term) or continuous (extendable)⁷⁰. Permanent permits can only be granted after four years of continuous stay in the country if the conditions for the original temporary permits are met. In most cases labour migrants are required to earn an income that is over the limit of social assistance to receive a residence permit. Nevertheless, any person⁷¹ residing in Finland is eligible to receive at least temporary social assistance if the need arises.⁷² Immigrants are eligible for unemployment benefits if they have a continuous or permanent residence permit in Finland and fulfil the other requirements.⁷³ While asylum seekers are not eligible for other forms of social security before they receive their

⁶⁷ Act on the Promotion of Immigrant Integration (1386/2010)

⁶⁸ Act on the Reception of Persons Applying for International Protection and on the Identification of and Assistance to Victims of Trafficking in Human Beings (746/2011)

⁶⁹ Aliens Act (301/2004), Chapter 4, Section 33

⁷⁰ Depending on the nature of the stay. The first permit is usually granted for one year. Continuous residence permits can be extended for a maximum of three years at a time. Temporary permit is given to migrants who do not intend or cannot stay in the country permanently.

⁷¹ Including undocumented migrants

⁷² Social Assistance Act (1412/1997)

⁷³ Act on Unemployment Benefits (1290/2002)

permit, they are eligible for reception allowance or spending allowance and other services provided by the reception centre.⁷⁴

The current act regulating citizenship was issued in 2003,⁷⁵ abolishing the outdated 1968 act.⁷⁶ The new act modernized the legislation and took in to account the diversified reasons and situations of the people applying for a citizenship. However, it also lengthened the time of residence needed in certain cases, which in turn caused a two-year slump in the granted citizenships in 2005 and 2006. The legislation was laxed and simplified in 2011 by shortening the time of residence it takes to be able to apply for citizenship in most cases, reflecting the general EU-wide trend. As a result, the number of granted citizenships almost doubled from 2011 to 2012.⁷⁷ The current act is still quite strict particularly when it concerns refugees and asylum seekers without proper identifying documentation as it requires 10-year residence to be recognized and to be able to apply for a citizenship.

The status of a migrant dictates his/her right to political participation. Participation, voting and running for a seat, in parliamentary and presidential elections is possible for every 18-years-old who is a Finnish citizen and participation in the EU elections is possible for those with EU citizenship⁷⁸. In municipal elections, EU citizens⁷⁹

⁷⁴ Act on the Reception of Persons Applying for International Protection and on the Identification of and Assistance to Victims of Trafficking in Human Beings (746/2011), Chapter 3, Section 13

⁷⁵ Nationality Act (359/2003)

⁷⁶ Nationality Act (401/1968)

⁷⁷ MIGRI (24.1.2013).

⁷⁸ Finnish Constitution (731/1999), Section 14

⁷⁹ Also applies to Icelandic and Norwegian citizens

who have been registered in the municipality in question, for 51 days, can take part⁸⁰. Other nationalities can participate when they have had a permanent residence in a Finnish municipality for the past two years and have been registered for 51 days in their current municipality.⁸¹

Since the beginning of 2020, the Ministry of the Interior has no longer been responsible for the administration of labour migration matters, but the Ministry of Economic Affairs has overseen all matters related to labour migration, international students, and researchers as well as integration service processes⁸². This transfer of duties was agreed on in the Government Programme with the objective to link labour migration more closely to employment, industrial, innovation, education and training policies. In shorth, the roles and responsibilities of different administrative branches in the permit procedure are as follows⁸³:

- Ministry for Foreign Affairs: Finnish missions abroad accept applications and personal documents, and interview applicants.
- Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment: TE Offices are responsible for partial decisions included in the employee's residence permit. This step involves an assessment of the availability of labour, terms of the employment, and the employer's and employee's ability to meet specific criteria.
- Ministry of the Interior: The Finnish Immigration Service makes the decisions in all permit matters.

Labour migration for TCNs into Finland is still strongly regulated through the permit system and labour market testing. Residence permit for an employed person allows the migrant to work only on the fields the permit is

⁸⁰ And are over 18-year-old

⁸¹ Local Government Act (410/2015), Chapter 5, Section 20

⁸² Government Rules of Procedure (262/2003), statute 1467/2019

⁸³ Ministry of the Interior, 2020, <https://intermin.fi/en/areas-of-expertise/migration/labour-migration>

given for⁸⁴. In the recent years, there have been multiple attempts to remove the labour market testing entirely, the latest of which was in 2017⁸⁵, but thus far the proportions have not gained enough support. The Aliens Act was amended in 2019 to remove labour market testing from those immigrants who had already worked in the Finnish labour market for a year⁸⁶. The last government to actively push for, at least gradual, removal of testing was the Vanhanen/Kiviniemi centre-right government of 2007-2011⁸⁷. All the governments that have followed since then have stated in their programs that they want to keep the labour market testing and sought other ways to ease labour migration, most notably by improving and speeding up the handling of permits. Aliens act also sets the livelihood precondition, which determines the minimum income migrant needs in order to receive a permit⁸⁸. The livelihood precondition is family-specific and dependent on the collective agreement in the sector where the migrant is applying for work.

The first regulation guiding refugee reception was the Act on the Integration of Immigrants and Reception of Asylum Seekers of 1999⁸⁹. The legislation concerning refugees and asylum seekers have been amended multiple times during the last decade. For example, during the unforeseen rates of asylum seeker arrivals in 2015-2016, the different acts regulating forced migration were amended multiple times. The amendment with the greatest impact was the abolishment of the ability to grant asylum through humanitarian protection⁹⁰. Humanitarian protection had been used as way to grant asylum if the conditions for asylum (i.e., the country of

⁸⁴ Aliens Act (301/2004), Section 74

⁸⁵ Bill on the repeal of Aliens Act section 73, subsection 1, paragraphs 1 and 2 (LA 41/2017)

⁸⁶ Amendment on the Aliens Act (437/2019)

⁸⁷ Prime Minister's Office (19.4.2007)

⁸⁸ Aliens Act (301/2004), Chapter 4, Section 39

⁸⁹ Act on the Integration of Immigrants and Reception of Asylum Seekers (493/1999)

⁹⁰ Amendment of the Aliens Act (332/2016)

origin was defined as safe) could not be met otherwise but the applier was still deemed to need protection. The reasoning given by the Sipilä government was that it should not be easier to get international protection from Finland than the other EU member states. Concurrent with this amendment, MIGRI announced that it had defined Iraq, Afghanistan, and Somalia safe⁹¹. This basically meant that MIGRI could reject most of the asylum application it received during 2015 and 2016. In 2016, MIGRI was also given power over founding and shutting down of reception centres⁹² and in 2017 most migrant permit bureaucracy was transferred from the Police and the Border Guard to MIGRI⁹³. These changes gave MIGRI the chief role it has today in the handling of forced migration.

THE ROLE OF REGIONAL AND LOCAL ADMINISTRATORS

Finnish municipalities are in central role when it comes to integration practices and immigrant services. The municipalities are the main actors in Finnish welfare state operations being responsible for organizing the welfare services and benefits. The Act on the Promotion of Immigrant Integration⁹⁴ made it statutory for municipalities to prepare an integration program⁹⁵ either by themselves or in municipal partnerships. These plans must be reviewed at least every four years. It is necessary for a municipality to have a plan in order to receive compensation from the state for the reception of refugees⁹⁶. These documents function as the guiding

⁹¹ MIGRI (17.5.2016)

⁹² Amendment of the Immigration Service Act section 2 (1160/2016)

⁹³ Amendment of the Aliens Act (501/2016)

⁹⁴ 1386/2010

⁹⁵ Not to be mixed with National Integration Programs, which are more of a guideline and a policy plans for the prevailing governments. The current government is yet to release its plan.

⁹⁶ 1386/2010, Section 44

plan for the local integration process, containing provisions for example on immigrant education, social services and integration services like translation and recreational guidance. The creation of these documents is guided by the CEDTEs. In practice, these documents range from brief 15-page documents covering the basic liabilities the legislature demands from the municipalities to extensive strategic programs with detailed elaborations. In our research regions, there were three general types of integration programs in use:

1. Models used by the bigger cities (Joensuu and Vaasa), which have clear strategic goals and are presented in visually simple and “presentable” packages.
2. Programs made by the K5⁹⁷ and Jakobstad municipal consortiums and the Korsholm and Vörå municipalities in Ostrobothnia, which cover only the basics but do so in a very detailed and thorough manner
3. Programs made by the Finnish language municipalities in Ostrobothnia and most of the municipalities in North Karelia, which contain the bare minimum of what is required.

These programs also reflect on the size of the migrant population in the areas. The larger cities have the highest number of immigrants in the regions. Some municipalities in the second group⁹⁸ have relationally some of the highest shares of migrants in entire Finland. In most of the small municipalities in North Karelia as well as the two unilingually Finnish municipalities in Ostrobothnia the number of migrants is often less than 4% of the population, which in actual numeric terms can equal to very few individuals. The municipalities or their partnerships in the types 1 and 2 have separate integration / immigrant services. Generally, these services are provided through standard municipal services, except in the municipality of Lieksa in North Karelia, where a specific immigration coordinator has been appointed. Lieksa has been active in taking refugees and until recently there was also a reception centre for asylum seekers in the town.

⁹⁷ Consortium of Malax, Korsnäs, Närpes, Kaskö and Kristinestad municipalities

⁹⁸ i.e. Närpes, Korsnäs and Jakobstad

Municipalities are responsible for the provision of basic services such as healthcare⁹⁹ and primary education. These services are to be equal for all permanent residents; in terms of healthcare, to those with international healthcare insurances¹⁰⁰. The municipalities are obliged to give immediate healthcare for asylum seekers and equal care if the applicant is a minor or pregnant¹⁰¹. For undocumented migrants, the municipalities must provide immediate care¹⁰² although some of the larger cities have made the decision to expand on them by providing the undocumented migrants more extensive services¹⁰³. Primary education has to be provided to every municipal resident within the compulsory education age, no matter of his or her legal status¹⁰⁴. Municipalities are also required to organize preparatory education for the newly arrived migrants for the duration of a full school year syllabus.¹⁰⁵

Together with operationalizing labour market testing through the TE services, the CEDTEs also supervise the municipalities in the process of integration. The Centres help municipalities in making their integration programs and make refugee settlement contracts with them. In Ostrobothnia, 8/15 municipalities have an

⁹⁹ Although many municipalities organize healthcare through larger consortiums such as *Siun Sote*, which covers the entirety of North Karelia

¹⁰⁰ Health Care Act (1326/2010)

¹⁰¹ THL (28.2.2020)

¹⁰² Self-financed

¹⁰³ THL (30.6.2020)

¹⁰⁴ Basic Education Act (628/1998), Section 4

¹⁰⁵ Basic Education Act (628/1998), Section 9

ongoing contract on settlement¹⁰⁶. In North Karelia, 7/12 municipalities have signed a contract but only six of them have taken in refugees¹⁰⁷.

Regional councils do not have governing role in migrant affairs, but their strategies and programs contain information on the desires and plans for the development of migration in the region. The role of these councils is in a transition as the provincial level might get increased liabilities and responsibilities in the future due to the restructuring of the healthcare and social services¹⁰⁸. The reform that is supposed to happen within the next three years.

THE ROLE OF NGOS AND BUSINESSES

In the last decade, the different governments have pushed more responsibilities concerning integration and refugee management on the municipalities and NGOs. Largest single actor outside of the public institutions the Finnish Red Cross which runs almost half (16 of 33) of the reception centres and two out of seven facilities for underage refugees who have arrived without a parent. There are also five adult centres and one underage facility run by other NGOs and businesses¹⁰⁹. It is to be noted though, that the role of these organizations in policy making and governing are limited with MIGRI supervising their operations and the government paying them for the refugee upkeep. Other notable nationwide associations are Startup Refugees, Finnish Refugee

¹⁰⁶ Provided by an official from Ostrobothnia CEDTE

¹⁰⁷ Provided by an official from North Karelia CEDTE

¹⁰⁸ Health and social services reform website: <https://soteuudistus.fi/en/frontpage>

¹⁰⁹ MIGRI (3.8.2020)

Council, The Finnish Refugee Advice Centre and Moniheli ry. Most of these work with migrants from humanitarian background.

Social enterprises are not a major factor in Finnish society in general. In legal terms¹¹⁰ social enterprises are mostly founded to help those with physical or mental disabilities to get into the labour market. Many regular businesses are still an important part in economic integration of migrants. For example, the EU-funded KIITO-project¹¹¹ had over 40 companies participating in helping migrants find work and integrate through their jobs.

¹¹⁰ Act on Social Enterprises (1351/2003)

¹¹¹ The website: <https://kiitohanke.wordpress.com/>

1.2 OVERVIEW ON EXISTING ANALYSES AND ASSESSMENTS OF ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL IMPACT

The core concept of Finnish migration research has been that of integration. The Act on the Promotion of Integration (1386/2010) sees integration as an interactive development of an immigrant and society, the aim of which is to enable the immigrant to develop skills in society and working life while supporting the maintenance of his or her own language and culture¹¹². Hiitola et al.¹¹³ state that integration is primarily an administrative concept, the purpose of which is to promote equality and positive social interaction. They also continue that, although integration is loose as an administrative concept, in the social policy debate it is often narrowed down to learning of the local language, educational matters and integration into the work life¹¹⁴. In a broad sense, the concept of integration refers to the whole process by which an immigrant finds his or her place in society¹¹⁵. However, integration is strongly associated with the idea of guiding and helping immigrants to adapt and settle from the outside¹¹⁶.

The migration research in Finland is – in relative terms – a rather recent phenomenon, as is its subject of study, international migration, in itself. The research began to gain momentum in the early 2000's, most of the research at the time concentrating on migrants' labour market integration and migrant's position at the Finnish labour markets. The labour market integration was long seen as the main object of migration studies in Finland.

¹¹² Yijälä & Luoma (2018), page 48

¹¹³ Hiitola et al. (2018) page 14

¹¹⁴ See also Saukkonen (2016)

¹¹⁵ Saukkonen (2013); Hiitola et al. (2018), page 16

¹¹⁶ cf. Hiitola et al. (2018); Sotkasiira (2018a); (2018b); Haverinen (2018)

Migrants were also studied in the framework of their ethnical background. In the beginning, many studies focused on the major migrant groups, such as the Russian speakers and Somalian migrants.¹¹⁷

Different forms of humanitarian migration played major roles in the short history of immigration to Finland. Arrival of asylum seekers and refugees peaked in the 1990s with the crises in Somalia and the Balkans and again in mid 2010s with the culmination of the Middle East crises. These periods have been greatly influential on the migration legislation as well as the broader socio-political discussion on migration in Finland. The influence of asylum seekers and refugees were also recognized in migration research following the event of 2015 “refugee crisis”, following which the focus on asylum seekers and refugees have been particularly evident. The studies have mainly been conducted in the context of urban areas, yet there are also exceptions. Rural localities as asylum seekers’ and refugees’ destinations have also been studied in the Finnish context recently.¹¹⁸

There are currently 33 reception centres for adults and families together with seven facilities for lone underage arrivals. Reception centres for refugees and asylum seeker are governed by MIGRI, but it only operates three of them. The others are run mainly by municipalities and NGOs as well as a few through the private sector. During the peak of the asylum seeker arrivals in the late 2015 and early 2016 there were as many as 227 operational reception centres in the country, many of which were newly founded (in 2015). From the second half of 2016 onwards, the number of centres has steadily gone down.¹¹⁹ In the beginning of 2021, there will be only 25 adult centres left with many of them seeing capacity cuts¹²⁰. This is occurring mainly due to the decrease in the

¹¹⁷ See e.g., Forsander 2002; Davydova 2009; Liebkind et al. 2004.

¹¹⁸ See e.g., Haverinen 2018; Sotkasiira 2017; 2018a; 2018b

¹¹⁹ MIGRI (3.8.2020)

¹²⁰ MIGRI (3.8.2020)

number of asylum seekers arriving in the country. One of the recent research strands have been concentrating on asylum seekers everyday life in reception centres¹²¹.

When discussing the political participation of migrants, the research has concentrated on the lack of it. While many of the migrants could vote, at least in municipal elections, very few do actually practice the right¹²². In the last municipal election in 2017, only roughly 20% of TCNs eligible to vote casted their ballots. Also, while TCNs represented 4,4% of the total electorate, the number of candidates and, finally, those elected remained very low. It is to be noted, however, that election participation among TCNs has been rising since 1996¹²³ and between 1996 and 2017, the number of eligible TCNs almost quadrupled¹²⁴. Voting activity has increased especially among the Somalis. One reason given to the low voter participation among migrants is simple the lack of information about eligibility¹²⁵.

To sum up, research on immigration in Finland has covered the themes of labour market integration and integration in wider sense. Currently, the studies have been concentrating on urban area and the rural context is less studied and need to be studied more.

¹²¹See e.g., Haverinen 2018; Pöllänen 2020

¹²² Kestilä-Kekkonen, Sipinen, Borg, Tiihonen & Wass (2018)

¹²³ From 16,7% to 20,0%

¹²⁴ From 44 569 to 176 661

¹²⁵ Kaleva (24.02.2017)

1.3 STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS

A total of 11 interviews were conducted (with 13 different stakeholders; in one of the interviews there were three persons to be interviewed from the same organization): four interviews were conducted in the region of Ostrobothnia, five interviews in North Karelia and two at the national level (ministries). All interviews were conducted virtually due to the COVID-19 restrictions. In the regional and local interviews, we intended to get parity between the stakeholders we interviewed between the two regions under scrutiny. We tried to find people from same or similar organizations from both areas and had moderate success in achieving it. This said, as we will point out later in the briefing, there are differences, for example, in NGO activity between the two provinces and thus we could not reach exact parity. All interviews were conducted by researcher Pirjo Pöllänen and research assistant Lauri Havukainen. All the interviews were conducted in Finnish language. In the Swedish speaking area, the interviewees were given the option to speak in Swedish, yet all the interviewees preferred to talk in Finnish. At the beginning of each interview, respondents were asked to fill in the consent form in their own language (Finnish) and they had the opportunity to ask questions about the project and the consent form. The interviews were recorded upon permission, in addition to which the researchers took notes during the interviews. The notes were analyzed using the framework provided by MATILDE. The interview summaries have been prepared.

The two studied regions in Finland are remarkable different (cf. the D2.1 regional reports). In North Karelia, a vast majority of the population is Finnish speaking, while in Ostrobothnia both Finnish and Swedish languages, both being official languages in Finland, are equally common. The economic structures of regions are also different: in North Karelia is service sector oriented while in Ostrobothnia export industry plays a decision role. North Karelia is a very homogenous region with many rural municipalities similar to each other, the only notable exception being the regional capital, the city of Joensuu. In Ostrobothnia the structure of municipalities differs more decisively from each other (see the D2.1 regional report for details). North Karelia has also a rather homogenous migration population: Russian speakers constituting the evidently dominant migrant group. Many Russians are moving to the region for family and educational reasons, clearly less so because of work. Mixed

(Finnish/Russian) marriages are also common. In Ostrobothnia, the migrant population of region is more diverse and many TCNs are moving into the region as labour migrants.

ECONOMIC INTEGRATION AND IMPACT IN THE VERY DIFFERENT LABOUR MARKETS

According to the interview data collected in Finland the situation of migrant's integration and migrant's impact in economic development is highly dependent on regions' economic situation. This is also noticed in previous research as for example Reini¹²⁶ points out that migrant's impact to local economy is more substantial in economically well-off regions. This can also be verified through the Finnish data collected for this project. All the informants from Ostrobothnia region were pointing out the significant impact of migrant labour force in the region's economic development and international trade while in the case of North Karelia the situation is more grievous. The strategic importance of migration, for example when it comes to challenges brought by the ageing of the native population, is still emphasized in both regions. The prospect of increased migration to mitigate the problems in the demography is underlined both in the interviews and the programs and documents of public institutions and organizations. Even in the now-struggling region of North Karelia there have been speculations of labour shortage in the future, and immigrants are seen as a valuable future resource to alleviate the situation.

As noted, the two studied regions are very different when it comes to the economic conditions. While Ostrobothnia has one of the lowest unemployment rates (5,9% in 2019) in the country, North Karelia has the highest (12,9% in 2019). In Ostrobothnia, this has been one of the largest factors in the growth of the migrant population. The ability of a migrant to stay in the region seems to vary greatly between different immigrant groups. Humanitarian migrants cannot choose freely where they are located upon arrival. Often, after receiving the permit to stay, they end up moving elsewhere in the county. It came apparent in our interviews that without possibilities in the labour market and without co-ethnic community in the area, most of those who came as asylum seekers (or refugees) move out of the region to bigger cities in the south of the country. This phenomenon is especially apparent in North Karelia, but it also happens in Ostrobothnia – yet it is not specific

¹²⁶ See Reini (2012)

to immigrants only, as the tendency to move south has been commonplace for long among the general population as well.

In addition to better job opportunities, an important factor that can be seen to “help” the migrants to stay in Ostrobothnia is the language. According to our interviews, particularly in the Jakobstad area, most migrants who enter the integration process choose Swedish (also an official language in Finland) as their language of integration. Swedish is, to me many, an easier language to learn than Finnish, and helpful in finding work in the area. Not knowing Finnish may, however, hinder possibilities to move and acquire a job elsewhere in the country, as most of the country (especially the rural areas) outside of Ostrobothnia and the rest of the narrow coastal region are in practice almost monolingually Finnish, with few exceptions.

The informants from Ostrobothnia were highlighting that TCN's input in the region is significant. The labour migrants namely from the East and Southeast Asia, Balkans as well the Post-Soviet territories are considered as the most important for the agricultural sector (such as vegetable farms and fur farming). In Ostrobothnia, the agricultural sector is highly dependent on the migrant labour force. The significance of labour migrants is also pointed out in the secondary sector of economy. These labour migrants are now permanently living in the area having moved there with an existing job during past three decades. According to informants the region has strong demand for labour migration in future as well.

“Of course, work based [migrants come] because we have a lot employment where the employer provides the training and also lot of jobs in the primary sector. Before the Corona we had made a projection that we will be needing 600-800 new employees to the area within the next two years.” (Municipal integration coordinator, Interviewee FI007)

In the case of highly educated migrants the situation in both regions can be regarded as two-fold. The main population hubs of the provinces (Vaasa and Jakobstad in Ostrobothnia and Joensuu in North Karelia) have all attracted a significant number of student migrants into their tertiary education institutions. At the beginning of 2019 autumn semester Ostrobothnia had about 1400 TCN students while the number in North Karelia was

roughly 600¹²⁷. Still, the customary tendency is that many students stay in the region only to study and move elsewhere after graduation in looking for better or more diverse work opportunities. There have also been problems with finding internships, co-ethnic build ups, and language acquisition. It was noted that even in with international companies it is hard to acquire a job without knowing either of the native languages. This is in contrast to bigger cities, most notably the capital Helsinki, where it is considerable easier to acquire a job even without knowing Finnish or Swedish.

In both of the studied regions, the service sector migrant labour is largely concentrated in cleaning, nursing, and food production. Ethnic restaurants are particularly common in both areas. However, migrant entrepreneurship is lower in both regions compared to the national average. This can, at least partly, be contributed to the availability of pre-existing jobs, which in turn mitigates the, so called forced entrepreneurship among migrants. In Ostrobothnia there is also a vibrant manufacturing industry which has been actively seeking migrant labourers to fill job openings. Although it is to be noted that many of these immigrants are from the EU and thus out of scope of this briefing. The main manufacturing jobs that employ migrants are in the metal industry, especially in welding.

It is obvious, based on the conducted interviews, that in North Karelia migrant integration and especially integration to labour market is framed by the lack of job opportunities. The region of North Karelia is suffering from high unemployment rates and for the situation is particularly challenging for the immigrants. The informants from North Karelia were clearly talking more about various social issues and the aspects of socio-cultural integration of migrants than about the migrant impact in local labour markets or economic development, even if so guided by the interviewer. According to the interviewees, agriculture is the only sector in North Karelia that is highly dependent on migrant labour, but even here the situation is different to that of Ostrobothnia. While in the latter region the agricultural sector employs people year around, in North Karelia the employment occurs mostly on seasonal basis (necessitating seasonal migration). These differences can largely be explained by the differences in the farming produce. In Ostrobothnia, there are major consolidations

¹²⁷ Vipunen, Education Statistics Finland (2020a/b)

of both greenhouse farming and fur farming which need labour year-around while the agricultural sector in North Karelia is mostly based on livestock farming and more traditional forms of production, which are much less labour intensive or have a limited harvesting season.

The stakeholders in North Karelia were in general more cynical about the possibilities of migrants in finding work in the region. It must be said, though, that this was included in the general notion about the region in general as the labour market situation has been frail even for the native Finns. All the local interviewees pointed out this difficulty and one was even sceptical about the hopes for more labour migration as there were not a lot of regional pull factors. There was some hope when it came to future projections, as most thought that without more labour migration, the situation will be even more dire when it comes to demographics and employers finding employees.

POLICIES AND SERVICES TOWARDS SOCIAL INCLUSION

According to the stakeholder's interviews, public-sector resources for integration are not sufficient and are focused too much on those arriving for humanitarian reasons. The interviewed public officials see that services should be made more equal between the different groups. Work-related migrants, whose numbers have increased in recent years, also need integration services and this has produced a situation where most of the people in need of these services do not have access to them. It was also pointed out that the permits for both humanitarian and labour migrants take far too long to be processed. This has been seen to be a major hindrance on the integration process and thus diminishing its potential. One of the stakeholders talked about the need for dual interpretation when comes to migrants trying to cope with the Finnish bureaucracy; simply knowing the language is often not enough when the documents and instructions are written in a formal and complicated manner.

The work permit process was taken as an example of the policy, which is not working as smoothly as it could. The practice of labour market testing is currently managed through the TE services, which in turn are under

instruction of the CEDTEs¹²⁸. These centres operate on a regional level, mostly on the same sphere of operation as the provinces. Seasonal labour and some sectors can be regionally exempt from labour market testing¹²⁹. Despite the ambiguity over labour market testing, every government program at least from 2007 onwards has stated that the government seeks to increase labour migration.

It was also mentioned in the interviews that the work permit process is not only slow, but also too restrictive. The system in use where the availability of labour defines the possibilities of migrants moving or staying in Finland or a particular region restricts the labour migration to Finland. Also, the official integration policy which is, in practice, aimed for refugees is limiting the work and study-based migrants' possibilities to acquire access to language courses and thus slowing down the integration process.

Multiple interviewees mentioned the need for a renewed legislation on integration processes that would make the services more broadly available and simplify the permit processes. According to one of the national level stakeholders the new Act on the Promotion of Immigrant Integration will begin to take shape in the spring of 2021. The details on how the legislation will change is still under consideration. Immigrants, including labour migrants, are often not very active politically, so their voice in decision making is not being fully heard.

Based on the interviews it became obvious that the impact of the third sector actors (most notably the Red Cross, church etc.) is very different in the two studied regions. It is evident that in North Karelia, the third sector organisations are vigorous and take an active role in assisting migrants' social integration. There are many active organisations, such as the Multicultural Association of Joensuu Region (Jomoni), the Somali Family association of Lieksa region and the North Karelian Society for Social Security, which are organizing and offering various social and cultural services for migrants – both formally and informally. Both Jomoni and the Somali Family association in Lieksa can be considered as sorts of migrants' bottom-up associations, in which migrants themselves pay a key role in organizing the services and activities for their peers. The North Karelian

¹²⁸ Aliens Act (301/2004), Section 73

¹²⁹ Aliens Act (301/2004), Section 77

Society for Social Security is seeking to coordinate all the migrant related NGO-based integration services in the region; their role as one of the key actors in migrant integration were well recognized in interviews. However, the role of NGO's in Ostrobothnia appears very different in comparison. The informants could only rarely name any specific NGOs working with or assisting migrants. The most commonly the church (Referring predominantly to the Protestant Evangelical Lutheran Church of Finland) was mentioned as key player in social integration service provider for migrants. It is likely that as in the case of Ostrobothnia TCN's are in many cases moving to the area following the available exciting jobs, the NGO-based work and the demand for that is less needed and recognised in the region than in North Karelia where family/marriage as well as study related migration is more common.

Furthermore, several interviewees brought up in the interviews that there are differences between ethnic groups about how well they are integrated in the surrounding society. In Ostrobothnia for example some ethnic groups were seen as largely invisible in the everyday life of the region, even if they are well integrated into the labour markets.

COVID-19 AND THE UNCERTAIN FUTURE

The uncertainties brought in by the current Covid-19 pandemic were evident in every single interview conducted. Here, the immediate impacts of the pandemic are very similar to the migrants as they are to the rest of the population, yet its severity is likely to be higher to those in more precarious positions and/or without proper safety and support structures. Locking down inside homes, getting furloughed or laid-off and socially distancing from all non-immediate people are all concerns shared by all, yet the ability to cope with these uncertainties may differ greatly.

Nevertheless, the interviewed stakeholders also highlighted difficulties that can be seen as more specific to migrants. Challenges with the availability and particularly accessibility of correct, up-to-date, information in an understandable format (language) amidst the rapidly changing circumstances was highlighted as a particularly pertinent to migrants. Much of the integration services, such as language courses, were suddenly moved online, requiring adjustment from both the teacher and students. The abrupt disappearance of social life has been

especially hard on migrants who might already suffer from lack of social interaction and networks in general. These issues have raised anxieties and fear among those who are already in a volatile situation, most notably refugees and asylum seekers. While the pandemic is still in full swing, it is impossible to predict what the aftereffects of this pandemic will be for the economy in general and the situation of migrants, especially.

1.4 CONCLUSION

The two studied regions in Finland appear seemingly different in this first step of our analysis. The conducted interviews confirmed that the nationwide legislation on integration policy is applied quite differently in Ostrobothnia than what it is in North Karelia. In Ostrobothnia, integration of migrants is more based on and aimed at finding work and contributing the society through labour, whereas in North Karelia social integration seems to be prioritised over the economic one. This is of course logical because the economic surface of Ostrobothnia region is more dependent on migrant's labour force than the North Karelia. The social aspects of integration are highlighted in North Karelia, which is suffering from a high level of unemployment in general. Migrant's well-being and welfare is supported by public policies in both regions. The municipalities are offering counselling for migrants, although in North Karelia these are rarely present as separate and specific services. The municipalities organize immigration courses, including language teaching, in co-ordination with the private sector and various NGOs. These services have seen a hit recently due to the on-going Covid-19 pandemic.

SOCIAL POLICIES

In North Karelia, the role of NGO's and the third sector as a whole in TCNs' integration is more significant than in Ostrobothnia. In North Karelia, social, cultural, and family networks of migrant play a crucial role in integration for many migrants. The third sector has an important role in organizing services and activities for migrants, especially for the TCNs. When regional economy and labour markets are weaker, social aspects of inclusion and integration, as well as the significance of NGOs in these terms, tends to get in turn emphasized. In the Ostrobothnia case study region, the TCNs integration is evidently more based on labour market integration, which is the most valued form of migrant integration according to the public policy discussion as well. Still, the previous research has emphasized that too often the discussion about migrant integration is limited on labour market activity and language skills while the social and cultural aspect are dismissed as less important and beneficial.

According to the interviews the other weakness of Finnish integration policy in practice is that integration is too often target only for refugees and other non-working migrants, even though training and services regarding language skills and other socio-cultural skills should also be offered also for those who work or study in Finland. Integration must be considered as a wide process, which should not cover only the language teaching and labour market integration. Flexibility should be taken in account when organizing integration courses to migrants. The labour migrants should also have access to integration services in equal terms with refugees and other non-working migrants.

Working towards and organising social inclusion and integration services and opportunities in the municipalities where there are only a very small number of migrants can be very challenging. The Finnish welfare state functions in a way that the responsibility of basic service provision rests largely on the shoulders of individual municipalities. The rural municipalities in the two studied regions are different with regards to migrant population, but also in terms of several other aspects, such the size and population of the municipalities. Based on the municipalities' integration programs, it seems that the way integration is conceptualised and the related services prepared for in a particular municipality depends greatly on the size of migrant population in that municipality. In small municipalities, where also the number of migrants tends to be lower, the municipal integration programs are generally very simple and basic, suggesting migration and migrants' integration not be high on the agenda and that the time and resources invested on the related concerns are scarce. However, in the interviews, migrants are seen predominantly as having a positive impact in addressing the demographic challenges in rural areas. There is thus a mismatch between the perceived impact and the investments made towards migrants' integration and well-being in the local communities. The integration should be seen as a holistic process which involves different kinds of migrant groups, not just refugees. The integration instruments should be diverse (language teaching, mentoring on labour market issues, organizing hobbies etc.). An effective integration process also demands the public, private and third sector actors to work flexibly together. There are things which need to be organized through public sector such as labour market counselling, but there are also activities which could be organized by NGOs such as sports, cultural event, networking, and other hobbies.

In the integration process the involvement of the third sector actors, such as the Red Cross, different congregations and local (multicultural) associations should be given more resources to organize integration

and other type of socio-cultural activities for migrants. The third sector actors can be important in improving the social and health services for migrants. They could play an even larger role as actors and mediators in enhancing migrant networking with each other as well as with the rest of the population, but also as organizers of leisure time activities. Resources are scarce, and while there is a need to rethink the financial premises and allocations for those organizations involved in service provision, other options for gaining further resources should be considered as well. The opportunities, which practices of social entrepreneurship, for example, could provide, are seldom considered. Despite the positive results of the few existing examples thereof, the customary trust on state being the primary resource provider remains strong. Another challenge having to do with the resources is that many NGO activities are based on project-based funding, which makes the inclusion and integration work of NGOs fragile, porous and non-persistent. This created further uncertainty and disruptions in organizing the required services.

On the national level, migrant issues are in a constant mode of adjustment, with the recent changes in the governance structure and the now beginning process of crafting of the new integration regulation to replace the old 2010 act¹³⁰. These national processes will have both a social and economic impact on migrants and their integration. Hopes for possible changes in the structure of integration services and laxation on permit provision were evident in the conducted interviews. It is however difficult to say what the final impact of the new act will be as it is still in its early stages and we are not yet aware of all the effects of the on-going pandemic. When talking about the national policy making, we also must take into consideration the fluctuating governments and their policy preferences. While the current government can be considered to be very much a pro-immigration government it is still hard to assess the level of which they can and will implement the desired policies.

GOOD PRACTICES

As a good practice stemming from the Finnish integration policy, its multicultural orientation can be mentioned. While expected to learn the local language and habits migrants are simultaneously also encouraged to

¹³⁰ 1386/2010

maintain and keep developing their native language and cultural skills. In primary education, the municipalities are obligated to provide teaching in the first languages, as well as religious education based on one's conviction if there are enough pupils of the same language group or religious group in the school. In North Karelia, for example, Russian speaking pupils can have teaching in their mother tongue in their own schools. The two-dimensional integration is a good tool to foster a multicultural society, where both local/regional inhabitants are welcoming newcomers and migrants can integrate into a new society without abandoning their own cultural capital. Multiculturalism can provide a strong positive impact for the increasingly international labour force and the society as whole.

The practice of organizing integration services together in larger municipal consortiums has been growing, and become, especially in Ostrobothnia, also a common custom. Municipal consortiums allow sharing of resources, and avoiding any overlaps, by extending the organization of services aimed for immigrants beyond the borders of a single municipality, which gives the service provision much broader shoulders. This practice is still in development in North Karelia, though it has been in consideration already for years.

In North Karelia, the network of several NGOs working in migrant related issues, compiled together by the North Karelian Society for Social Security, can be seen as successful example of pooling knowhow and expertise. The North Karelian Society for Social Security is an association which coordinates various kinds of migrant-related activities from social issues to anti-racist work. The network also covers public actors such as municipalities and the police. It was also recognized in interviews that it is important to involve migrants themselves in the local and regional integration process and as members and leaders of associations. When migrants themselves are actors in the integration work, potential problems of migrant objectification can be better avoided.

ECONOMIC POLICIES

The impact of migrants for the regional economy was well recognized in the interviews conducted in Ostrobothnia, while in North Karelia the migrants' impact in these terms was seen clearly more moderately. In the latter, the impact on the labour market was limited mostly to seasonal agricultural work, conducted mostly

by seasonal migrants. In North Karelia, the migrant's possibility for finding work is evidently limited due to the high levels of general unemployment rate in the region. As there is a shortage of job opportunities in North Karelia, many TCNs seek to move away to southern and western parts of the country as soon as the opportunity arises. In addition to better job opportunities, this decision is usually further driven by social and co-ethnic contacts and networks. The same phenomenon occurs also in Ostrobothnia, but in lesser extent than in North Karelia. It is obvious that without possibilities in the labour market and without co-ethnic community in the region, migrants tend to move out of their original regions to larger cities.

In addition to better and more versatile job opportunities, another factor keeping migrants in Ostrobothnia is the language. Many migrants who enter the integration process choose Swedish as their language of integration. On the one hand this means that in many cases it is easier to find job in the area, but on the other hand it can limit one's possibilities elsewhere in the country. Knowledge of either of the local language in finding employment outside of the primary sector is evident in both areas. In the interviews conducted in Ostrobothnia, it was noted that even finding internships as a migrant studying in tertiary education can be difficult without proper knowledge of either Finnish or Swedish, even as many of the companies in the manufacturing sector are multinational and export oriented.

Supporting the previous research, it was also emphasized in the interviews that in Ostrobothnia labour migration is a significant factor for the region's economic growth. The economic structure of the region is dependent on foreign trade and the industry is dependent on migrant labour force, even though much of it comes from within the EU. According to the interviews, the TCN's impact on local and regional economy in both regions could be more substantial if the work-based residence permit process was more efficient, straightforward and relevant in terms of the determination of the availability of labour. A more efficient process would also increase the number of entrepreneurs. The contemporary system is perceived to frame and restrict the possibilities of migrants moving or staying in Finland or within the region. The collected material suggests that if this system could be made more efficient, it could also increase the numbers of entrepreneurs in both studied regions, which would be especially beneficial for North Karelia, which is suffering from high unemployment.

It seems, based on the interviews, that due to the lack of existing jobs available in North Karelia, the number of entrepreneurs among migrants is higher than in Ostrobothnia. In both studied regions the migrants' impact as entrepreneurs was restricted mainly to the food production industry: the ethnic restaurants and grocery store selling ethnic food produce. During the interviews some of the informants were pondering that TCN's possibilities and chances of setting up companies to other sectors should be encouraged, but no-one really knew how this should be done. It seems that many migrant entrepreneurs are working in sectors where they can in one way or the other benefit from their ethno-cultural capital e.g., use languages they know (for example, as an interpreter) or prepare food they are familiar with. In future it should be taken into account that TCNs have in many cases wide networks in Finland and beyond. TCNs' networks, skills and know-how should be better estimated and taken in use in the labour market both as workers and entrepreneurs. This would need more resources and educated employees in TE services¹³¹ and networking of migrant associations and local associations would be important in reaching the task.

In labour market integration, the effective collaboration among NGO's, the public and private sector is key for well-functioning migrant labour markets in both of the study regions. It seems that in North Karelia, where the economic situation is weaker, the measure of support is more needed than in Ostrobothnia, which has a better general economic situation. The integration work in North Karelia should be concentrating on finding the work opportunities for migrants. It is a well-known fact that both regions need working age migrants to be able to cope for future challenges related with demography and care poverty, which means that more care resources (workers) will be needed in the future.

While the labour market testing has been lax with CEDTE's already allowing many sectors of work to simply by-pass it, it is still possible that future legislation could remove it entirely. It is to be noted, however, that the political debate on it is still strong with both the current parliament and the government being split in half¹³².

¹³¹ The unemployment services

¹³² Duunitori (3.4.2019)

Even within some of the key parties there are major differences on the topic. Work-based residence permits could be eased. More resources should be invested handling of the permits as the process is considered to simply take for too long. One section that could also be looked into is the livelihood precondition in the Aliens Act. There are cases¹³³ where the family-specific minimum livelihood expectation has caused expulsion of spouses and children of migrant labourers, as while the salary has been determined enough for a single person, the permit for the family has been cancelled because it was deemed insufficient for them as a whole. Both issues mentioned above can cause unnecessary stress for families who are already dealing with stress of integrating into a new country and culture.

In North Karelia, the seasonal migrant workers opportunities to work in region year-around could also be evaluated. The local farming could change its character and start producing more goods needing all year employment and the possibility of seasonal workers working on other sectors during the winter seasons could be looked into. At the moment, the latter is diminished by the stiff permit provision caused by labour market testing. These are of course major hurdles to overcome, but North Karelia would also benefit from mentoring given by Ostrobothnia and other regions, where more of the migrants working in agriculture are employed all year around. The rural areas in North Karelia are demanding surroundings for anyone to work but forestry and farming could employ more families as independent entrepreneurs as well as through existing jobs. Many TCN's are also migrating from countries or regions where they have learned to do agricultural work, so this opportunity needs to be studied further. This would, once again, need effective co-operation with different actors, public sector, private sector, and NGO's. For it to be possible for migrants to set up farms or farming related businesses they would need economic resources and know-how.

GOOD PRACTICES

¹³³ Mattila & Björklund (2013), pages 77-79.

While it is evident that labour migration and integration into the Finnish labour market is difficult because of the stiff labour market testing and inefficient permit provision, a few good practices can also be found. Many industries and sectors have received an exemption from labour market testing. In the most recent CEDTE alignment¹³⁴, in Ostrobothnia this includes for example work in green houses, most agricultural work, a lot of the manufacturing jobs and most of the positions in healthcare, nursing and cleaning. In North Karelia there is a smaller list of exemptions¹³⁵ with it covering manufacturing jobs such as welding, forestry, and nursing among others.

One good practice in integrating TCN's better for the labour markets is the practice where language teaching and on-the-job training are linked together. Migrants can learn the language simultaneously with practicing their occupation creating everyday surroundings where language skills can be used in the real life context. The mentoring for entrepreneurs given by local Chamber of Commerce and members of local entrepreneurs' association is also important in improving TCN's capability to start working as entrepreneurs.

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¹³⁴ Ostrobothnian CEDTE, (20.12.2019)

¹³⁵ Northern Savonian CEDTE, (19.6.2018)

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MATILDE

5. GERMANY

Country: Germany

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

BGL	- Rural district Berchtesgadener Land
COVID-19	- Coronavirus Disease 2019
GAP	- Rural district Garmisch-Partenkirchen
LAU	- Local Administrative Units
NEA	- Rural district Neustadt a.d.Aisch-Bad Windsheim
NUTS	- Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques
OA	- Rural district Oberallgäu
TAT	- Tür an Tür – miteinander wohnen und leben e.V.
TCN	- Third-Country National
VIA	- VIA Bayern – Verband für Interkulturelle Arbeit e.V.

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Figure 1: Priority areas in the IQ Network Bavaria 176

1.1 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC RELATED POLICIES REGARDING TCNS INTEGRATION AND IMPACT IN GERMANY IN GENERAL AND RURAL BAVARIA IN PARTICULAR

In the governance system of the Federal Republic of Germany, multilevel governance is a major principle. While the federal level (NUTS0) is responsible for migration policy, including citizenship and immigration legislation as well as labour market and welfare policies¹³⁶, the implementation is processed by the Federal States, i.e. the *Länder* (NUTS1, SVR 2017). The latter are given ample scope regarding the interpretation of legal documents, which may result in differing administrative practices between the Federal States. Federal States are also able to shape integration policies, in particular in the realms of education, cultural policy, and inner security (Gesemann & Roth 2015; Münch 2016) and can promote and offer additional subsidies programmes or action plans (ibid.). Moreover, they decide on the legal terms which regulate the self-government of rural and city districts (*Landkreise, kreisfreie Städte*, NUTS3) as well as municipalities (*Gemeinden*, LAU) and provide respective funding. The rural and city districts as well as municipalities, finally, are responsible for implementing economic and social policies, being processed by, e.g. the local foreigners' registration offices, social welfare departments or job centres (*Jobcenter*), and organise the communal life by virtue of their self-government (SVR 2017). While residence and livelihood issues are compulsory tasks for the rural and city districts as well as municipalities, many other tasks of integration are voluntary ones. Here, the rural and city districts as well as municipalities can decide for themselves whether and how they want to act (Schammann 2020).

The table provided in the Annex (Annex I) contains selected social and economic policies of various types on different administrative levels, affecting, but not exclusively, foreigners and migrants in general and TCNs in particular. Thus, general social and economic policies are included, but also those commonly termed migration

¹³⁶ The Federal States (NUTS1), however, can influence legislation processes via the Federal Council (*Bundesrat*).

and integration policies. According to their different degree of legal enforcement capacity and in terms of their temporal dimension, we distinguish between:

- regularly reworked and adjusted laws,
- regularly reworked and adjusted (funding) regulations and directives about how to implement laws, and
- strategic roadmaps and visions that provide the frame for future activities and intended adjustments of laws in the long run.

The social and economic policies mentioned in the table have developed historically between the conflicting priorities of liberalisation and restriction (SVR 2019). Critical junctures, identified by Hess and Green (2016), are firstly based on historical events and resulting responsibility, e.g. the end of World War II with millions of expellees from Central and Eastern Europe, or the German reunification in the 1990s (see also MATILDE D2.1 Country report Germany, Weidinger & Spenger 2020). Secondly, junctures stimulating a change in social and economic policies and migration legislation include times of economic transformation, such as the post-war “economic miracle” (*Wirtschaftswunder*) from the 1960s, associated to an increasing labour demand as well as various economic crises leading to more restrictive measures (e.g. termination of recruitment of guest workers in 1973). Thirdly, transformations in the government participation and the positioning and self-understanding of political parties had an influence. The change to a social-ecological coalition between Social democrats (SPD) and Green Party (*Bündnis 90/Die Grünen*) in 1998, for instance, resulted in the recognition of Germany as a country of immigration and a reform of the Citizenship and Immigration Law. Most of the legislations and regulations illustrated in the table in the Annex (Annex I) as well as in the text below were adopted or modified from 2005 on, following the implementation of the Immigration Act (*Zuwanderungsgesetz*)¹³⁷. These were accompanied by many substantial and symbolic measures such as the installation of a Commissioner of the

¹³⁷ The Immigration Act of 2005 originates from the discussions of the Independent Commission Immigration (*Unabhängige Kommission Zuwanderung / Süßmuth-Kommission*) that was implemented by the Federal Government in 2000 and which became known by the name of its chairwoman, the former presiding officer of the German parliament Rita Süßmuth (Kolbe 2020).

Federal Government for Migration, Refugees and Integration (*Beauftragte*r der Bundesregierung für Migration, Flüchtlinge und Integration*) in the Federal Chancellery, the establishment of an annual Islam Conference (*Deutsche Islamkonferenz*) and an annual Integration Summit (*Deutscher Integrationsgipfel*) or the negotiation of a National Integration Plan / National Action Plan Integration (*Nationaler Integrationsplan / Nationaler Aktionsplan Integration*).

In the following, recent changes in selected legislations and regulations that can be seen to have (had) an impact on the presence and impact of TCNs in rural and mountain areas will be sketched drawing on the compilation of SVR (2019), Chemin and Nagel (2020a, 2020b) as well as Gomes and Doomernik (2020), whilst the evaluation of selected legislations and regulations will take place in chapter 2:

In terms of **education policies**, access to integration courses for asylum seekers with a good prospect of staying¹³⁸ and individuals with toleration was facilitated in the Asylum Package I (*Asylpaket I*, 2015), whilst work-related German language promotion and the Recognition Act (*Anerkennungsgesetz*, including the Professional Qualifications Assessment Act, *Berufsqualifikationsfeststellungsgesetz*, 2012) aimed at facilitating foreigners' access to employment. In order to safeguard the coordination of educational offers for new immigrants on the level of rural and city districts (NUTS3), coordinators were implemented in 2016 and, today, are installed across the whole country.

In terms of **migration and employment-related policies**, in 2012 and 2013, several new bilateral recruitment programmes between the Central Placement Office (*Zentrale Auslands- und Fachvermittlung*) of the Federal Employment Agency (BA) and countries from the Balkan, North Africa and Asia tried to attract nurses to Germany in order to fill the demand for labour (SVR 2018; Kordes et al. 2020). In 2012, in addition, Germany implemented the EU Blue Card directive for High-Skilled Individuals¹³⁹. The asylum compromise (2014), then, classified Bosnia and Herzegovina, Ghana, Macedonia, Senegal and Serbia as so-called “safe countries of origin”

¹³⁸ Their countries of origin are recognised as being “unsafe Third Countries”. For a discussion on this, see Schultz (2020).

¹³⁹ From 2000 to 2004, there was also a so-called “Green Card” for ICT professionals (Přivara & Rievajová 2019; Kolbe 2020).

allowing for accelerated asylum procedures. Simultaneously, however, it was decided that asylum seekers and individuals with toleration are allowed to work already three months upon arrival. Due to rising numbers of asylum seekers from the Western Balkan with low chances of receiving asylum, the Asylum Package I (2015) also classified Albania, Kosovo and Montenegro as so-called “safe countries of origin”. Simultaneously, however, the Western Balkan Regulation (*Westbalkanregelung*, 2016-2023) offered citizens of Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Macedonia, Montenegro and Serbia, who did not receive benefits for asylum seekers according to Asylum Seekers’ Benefits Act (*Asylbewerberleistungsgesetz*, AsylbLG) in the past 24 months, the opportunity to enter the German labour market with a valid job offer by a German employer only. To better manage the influx of refugees, the Asylum Package II (*Asylpaket II*, 2016) encompassed the suspension of family reunification for individuals with subsidiary protection status for two years¹⁴⁰ as well as accelerated asylum procedures for individuals from so-called “safe countries of origin”. In light of a prospering labour market, the Integration Act (*Integrationsgesetz*, 2016) then further improved forced migrants’ access to the labour market by abolishing priority checks for individuals with a good prospect of staying. To offer planning security for companies who employ forced migrants by means of a three-year vocational training, the 3+2-rule (*3+2-Regelung*) was implemented, saying that forced migrants with a negative decision on asylum can finish the vocational training and even continue to work in the company up to two years after. The 2019 Migration Package (*Migrationspaket*), then, included the Toleration for Education and Employment Act (*Gesetz über Duldung bei Ausbildung und Beschäftigung*) on the one hand. It extended the opportunities for a tolerated stay for the purpose of vocational training and offered a new type of tolerated stay permit, i.e. the so-called Tolerated Stay for Working Professionals (*Beschäftigungsduldung*). The Migration Package, on the other hand, entailed the Skilled Labour Immigration Act (*Fachkräfteeinwanderungsgesetz*, FEG), which was put in effect in 2020. While until this date, working permits were issued in a very limited scope, e.g. for high skilled employees, scientists, understaffed professions or seasonal/temporary employment only, since then, fully trained specialists with a vocational training and university graduates are treated as equal, i.e. they are allowed to enter the country independent from trained profession. This went hand in hand with a reduction of administrative

¹⁴⁰ In 2018, the family reunification to individuals with subsidiary protection status was limited to 1.000 persons per month.

burdens for companies and migrants, a speeding up of the recognition of foreign credentials and a better access to structured language training support.

In terms of **societal and welfare-related policies**, existing social policies, either affecting all people reliant on social welfare (Social Act Second Book, SGB II) or focussing exclusively on forced migrants such as the Asylum Seekers' Benefits Act (AsylbLG), were adjusted in manifold ways in the last couple of years. The migration counselling for adult immigrants and the Youth Migration Services provided by the state were already developed in the course of the Immigration Law, while additional support mechanisms funded by the Federal States, e.g. the integration guides¹⁴¹ in Bavaria, were often introduced not before the mid-2010s. Newly emerging refugee relief groups and individual volunteers, however, represent a backbone of local integration activities. Therefore, their coordination and professional support was addressed as crucial. The Federal Integration Act (2016), finally allowed the Federal States to enact their own integration acts, from which for instance Bavaria made use (Bavarian Integration Act, 2016).

In terms of **housing and mobility policies**, Germany applies a dispersal mechanism and distributes asylum seekers between the Federal States according to the distribution key *Königsteiner Schlüsse*, which was introduced in 1974 to respond to the rising influx of asylum seekers (see Kordel & Weidinger 2019). In the last couple of years, the duration of the obligation to live in first reception centres was changed several times and differs, e.g. between families with minor children and individuals from so-called safe countries of origin. For subsequent accommodation, asylum seekers are further distributed within the Federal States, whereby the states draw on their own distribution keys (in Bavaria, for instance, the quota is based on population figures of the rural and city districts). During their first months in Germany, in addition, a geographic restriction to the

¹⁴¹ During the pilot phase (2015-2017), they were either termed coordinators of volunteers in the context of asylum (*Ehrenamtskoordinatoren Asyl*) or integration guides (*Integrationslotsen*). After that, the ministry did not differentiate according to migration status anymore, while the funding regulations for integration guides were published even together with the ones of refugee and integration counsellors (*Flüchtlings- und Integrationsberatern*).

responsible foreigners' registration office (NUTS3) is applied as part of the Asylum Act. For recognised refugees reliant on social welfare, the Integration Act (2016) implemented a three-year Residence Rule (*Wohnsitzregelung*) that was extended for an indefinite period of time in 2019. It reduces the freedom of movement at least to the Federal State, where the refugee lived during the asylum procedure. Federal States are allowed to issue even stricter regulations and prescribe the place of residence in a city or rural district (NUTS3) or municipality (LAU) even ("positive residence obligation")¹⁴². The driving permit regulation (*Fahrerlaubnisverordnung, FeV*), finally, regulates that, in case of long-term stays, TCNs need to transform their driving licenses issued in Third Countries to a German one.

¹⁴² In contrast, the Federal States can also impose a ban to move to a specific municipality or city in order to prevent social or societal exclusion ("negative residence obligation").

1.2 OVERVIEW ON EXISTING ANALYSES AND ASSESSMENTS OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC POLICIES

The “**complete programme language**” (see p. 9), including both the integration courses (language levels A1 to B1, Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community, BMI) and the work-related German language promotion (B2 to C2, Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs, BMAS) was evaluated by both the Institute for Employment Research (IAB), a research institute of the Federal Employment Agency, and the Friedrich Ebert Foundation (FES), a political foundation related to the Social Democratic Party (SPD). The IAB found that refugees who have completed integration courses tend to have higher employment rates (Brücker et al. 2017). With regard to rural specificities, the FES detected that the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF), which develops the courses, certifies public and private language course providers and contracts out the implementation of courses to them, faces only a limited number of providers in rural areas (Scheible & Schneider 2020). On site, adult education centres (*Volkshochschulen*), mostly sponsored by rural and city districts as well as municipalities, play a crucial role. Most recently, the course providers massively expanded their activities and hired personnel. While the local level is of particular importance (Schammann & Kühn 2016) – foreigners’ registration offices and Jobcentres provide entitlements and obligations for the participation in the courses – the authors recommend a transfer of competence to the local level (Scheible & Schneider 2020). They also plea for a stronger regionalisation of integration courses in order to react faster and better to the local and regional constellations and challenges (ibid.; see also Opinion Paper of Ohliger & Schweiger 2019). In order to meet specific challenges in rural areas, e.g. the low number of potential participants in language courses, the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees introduced a minimum reward for teachers in such regions. Moreover, a reimbursement of travel costs to places where courses take place is foreseen, yet bureaucratic burdens for its accounting were identified. Finally, the seamless connection between official language and integration courses and internships as well as between official language and integration courses and lay language courses provided by volunteers is in need of further improvement (Scheible & Schneider 2020).

The Expert Council of German Foundations on Integration and Migration (*SVR*), a politically independent think tank, the employer-oriented German Economic Institute (*iW*), the Institute for Employment Research (IAB), and

the Migration Strategy Group (MSG) on International Cooperation and Development, an initiative by the German Marshall Fund of the United States (GMFUS), the Bertelsmann Foundation and the Robert Bosch foundation (RBS), discussed and evaluated the **Western Balkan Regulation** as a potential alternative to asylum applications and legal trajectory for TCNs without prospects of staying (see p. 10). The evaluations conclude that the eased entry to the German labour market foreseen for individuals from the Western Balkan was able to reduce the number of asylum seekers from these countries, which are not considered unsafe. However, the number of working permits issued by the employment authorities and the number of visas issued by the embassies differed largely between the countries of origin depending on the regional demand, and already established diasporic networks with Germany. Simultaneously, long waiting times were common due the overload of embassies in the respective countries (Bither & Ziebarth 2018; SVR 2018). The most work permits were issued for the economically prospering Federal States of Bavaria and Baden Württemberg, which already had established migration systems with the Western Balkan, not least due to their geographic proximity. Immigration, to a certain extent, was sector-specific, i.e., the construction (42% of all issued allowances), hospitality industry (16%) and healthcare (10%) benefitted the most (Burkert & Haase 2017; Geis-Thöne 2018). The iW-Study adds that mostly skilled workers profited from the regulation, while less qualified people, e.g. from the minority of Roma, to a larger extent, have not made use of it (Geis-Thöne 2018). However, data are lacking to identify a potential over-qualification of employees (Bither & Ziebart 2018). In addition, SVR and MSG identified strategic shortcomings of the regulation, i.e. lacking incorporation of countries of origin and a lacking proactive communication strategy. As a consequence, the German Information Centres for Migration, Training and Career (DIMAK) that were established in Albania, Kosovo and Serbia already before the implementation of the regulation, were not used according to their original aim to assist the labour market integration of returning migrants in their countries of origin, but for the purpose to enter Germany instead, mostly. According to SVR and MSG, lessons learned from the Western Balkan Regulation with regard to both forced and labour migration are the call for a clear-cut migration policy with sector specific programmes considering the needs of the country of origin instead of a general opening and liberalisation based on a “best friends” approach (Bither & Ziebarth 2018, 38; SVR 2018). Due to the high acceptance among employers and potential foreign employees, the SVR recently opted for its extension until 2023.

Following an evaluation published by legal scholar Funke (2017) and SVR (2017), the **Bavarian Integration Act** (BayIntG), introduced in 2016, distinguishes between promotion of and an obligation to integration (Art. 1) (SVR

2017, see also p. 11). However, the expectations are merely addressing immigrants in general and refugees as the core target group in particular, e.g. with regard to their acculturation to the local culture and acceptance of a leading culture (*Leitkultur*, see also Bendel & Funke 2016). The law, thus, has an assimilative character, follows principles of order and security and can be considered protective by tendency. In general, the law includes only programmatic principles for integration policies and is a balancing act between legally non-binding nature and vague legal force (Funke 2017). Similarly, political scientist Zuber (2019) highlights the law's focus on restrictive and culturally monist measures in socio-economic and cultural-religious terms, which was found typical for regions characterised by sub-state nationalism.

Volunteers were recently addressed as crucial actors in the implementation of integration policies in rural areas, as reported in case studies, conducted, for instance, by the Robert Bosch Foundation (RBS, Ohliger et al. 2017; see also Kordel & Weidinger 2020; Schweiger & Veyhl 2020). Their specific local knowledge and networks support immigrants' access to housing, employment, education and many other realms of everyday life. As a consequence, **integration guides** (*Integrationslots*innen*) were hired in 86 of the 96 Bavarian rural and city districts to support and coordinate the work of volunteers, who mostly have a full-time position and are allocated to the rural and city district offices or to Third Sector Organisations such as Caritas (see p. 11). For many rural districts, the opportunity to hire integration guides was an important step into an active integration policy. In light of the renewal of the funding guidelines 2021-2023, an evaluation was conducted by social scientist Wegner (2020). Drawing from an online survey among integration guides, she concludes that integration guides have to cover a wide range of tasks, including, for instance, coordination of volunteers and projects, networking, knowledge transfer with regard to integration, organisation of events and PR activities (Wegner 2020), but have scope of discretion to set priorities according to local needs. In rural areas, integration guides evaluate their work as positive for integration on site, while 89%, for instance, agree that they are an important contact point for volunteers. On the other hand, however, they can rarely rely on adopted integration concepts and recognise a decrease in people who are willing to volunteer (ibid.).

In the realm of housing and mobility, the three-year **Residence Rule** (§12a AufenthG) introduced in 2016, is crucial for the settlement of recognised refugees reliant on social welfare as it limits the freedom of movement at least to the Federal State, where the refugee lived during the asylum procedure (see p. 12). Despite a scientific evaluation of its effects was claimed many times by various organisations, it is still lacking to date (SVR 2016;

BBSR 2017). Yet, the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF) monitors the regulation internally. Regarding implications on rural areas, a qualitative study conducted by the BAMF research branch points to a positive effect from the perspective of providers of integration measures and education infrastructures. However, respondents on NUTS3-level favoured an application of the regulation towards a local allocation (LAU) even (Rösch et al. 2020). The Institute for Employment Research (IAB) and the BAMF research branch also assessed the implications of the Residence Rule in terms of effects on labour and housing market integration. Comparing refugees among whom the regulation is applied with those, who are free to move, Brücker et al. (2020) estimate a reduced probability among the former group. In addition, results indicate that for the former group also access to private housing is hampered. However, no differences could be detected for access to language and integration courses (ibid.). In a nationwide panel survey, Tanis (2020) found that 25% among those refugees where the regulation is applied want to move on to cities afterwards, especially from Eastern Germany and rural areas. To sum up, the aims of the Residence Rule to foster integration, i.e. refugees' access to housing, to integration and language courses as well as to the labour market, may not be fulfilled, instead, it could have quite the reverse effect.

Considering immigration for labour purposes, the legislative procedure of the Skilled Labour Immigration Act (FEG) was critically accompanied by SVR. Its introduction was supported as it was a farewell to the “academic arrogance” of German labour immigration legislation (SVR 2019, 45) and especially eased the access of non-academics from Third Countries (Graf & Heß 2020). In light of the structure of the employment market in Bavarian MATILDE districts with SMEs and small handicraft businesses predominating, we expect the law to represent an important pillar. However, an in-depth evaluation is still missing. Apart from that, areas for further research encompass the evaluation of the role of specific legislations and regulations such as the Western Balkan Regulation or the Bavarian Integration Act and the role of different mediators (coordinators of educational offers for new immigrants; integration mentors, job mentors, welcome guides, canvassers of vocational training for refugees, migration counsellors for adult immigrants, youth migration services, refugee and integration counsellors) for the social and economic impact of TCNs in rural and mountain areas in Germany in general and in the MATILDE region Bavaria in specific.

1.3 ASSESSMENT OF THE STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF POLICIES THROUGH SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

METHODS AND ETHICS ASPECTS RELATED WITH THE INTERVIEWS

To assess the strengths and weaknesses of policies with regard to the integration and impact of TCNs in the country and its selected remote areas, the policy brief draws on five semi-structured interviews with seven actors that were conducted in October and November 2020. In addition, participatory observation was undertaken in an online meeting of the Bavarian State Ministry of the Interior, for Sport and Integration (StMI) with volunteers working in refugee relief (03.11.2020). The stakeholders for the interviews were chosen to represent the different political levels of the federal system with their respective legislative competencies (see chapter 1), i.e. the federal level (1 person), the *Länder* level, in this case one of the administrative districts within the Federal State of Bavaria (1 person), and the local level, i.e. the rural districts and municipalities (5 persons). Applying purposive sampling, interview persons were selected based on their competence regarding the themes of the policy brief and comprised policy makers, public officers and representatives of professional associations as well as practitioners and organisations working on migration-related fields, social policies and territorial planning. Due to on-going travel restrictions as well as for preventive reasons in the course of the COVID-19 pandemic, all interviews were conducted audio-visually using the conferencing tool Zoom (for a critical methodological reflection, see Nehls et al. 2015) or via telephone. After having received the interviewees' consent, all interviews were audio-recorded. Afterwards, they were transcribed verbatim and were analysed using thematic analysis.

RESULTS

EDUCATION POLICIES

With regard to education policies, Germany always considered language acquisition core for integration. The newly established **complete programme language** with its modular concept is considered adequate and based on the needs of TCNs. However, stakeholders are aware that rural peculiarities have to be considered more consequently for planning of courses (WP3WP4DE001). These include the low number of potential participants associated to a low number of TCNs in the rural catchment areas of the course providers, resulting in difficulties to meet the minimum number of participants for different levels of learning. Besides, since courses are often located in central small towns or, in case of advanced courses, in metropolitan areas, long travel distances are reported as a further challenge (WP3WP4DE001, WP3WP4DE003, WP3WP4DE004). During the COVID-19 pandemic, it has become also obvious that the internet infrastructure in certain rural areas was not sufficient enough to safeguard virtual learning (WP3WP4DE001). Apart from that, interviewees noticed a lacking availability of technical equipment and insufficient technical capacities among low-income households in general and TCN households in particular (WP3WP4DE001, WP3WP4DE002, WP3WP4DE004). In addition to the public language and integration courses provided by state authorities, volunteers offered and still offer **lay language courses** for those who are not eligible due to their legal status or aim at bridging the time until official courses start on-site (WP3WP4DE002, WP3WP4DE003). Nevertheless, rural district administrations foster **access to language and integration courses** for all TCNs irrespective of their origin or on a case-by-case decision (WP3WP4DE002, WP3WP4DE003, WP3WP4DE005), but face scarce availability of courses and places due to the fact that the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees does not foresee granting permissions to more language course providers (WP3WP4DE002).

For young people in particular, the rural district of OA and the city of Immenstadt offer **exterior school learning support** in the family and the education house of the Islamic cultural association. For employees, companies provide self- or third party-funded language courses. For apprentices, in particular, companies had the idea of a **language-learning app**, which was developed by the Association of Bavarian Chambers of Crafts to foster work-related language acquisition (WP3WP4DE004). Finally, the Bavarian State Ministry for Education and

Cultural Affairs (StMK) reimburses costs for **interpreters** used in the educational context, which is hardly known though (WP3WP4DE003).

The **Professional Qualifications Act** generally provides an easier and faster process for the recognition of foreign credentials (WP3WP4DE003; WP3WP4DE004). However, despite a tightening of the process, procedures are still extensive in duration and expensive (WP3WP4DE003). Only if salaries are below a certain threshold, a subsidy for the recognition process can be granted (WP3WP4DE004). While counselling in rural areas is hampered due to the fact that potential users are scarce (WP3WP4DE001), a better flow of information towards TCNs is seen as the approach to a solution (WP3WP4DE003).

MIGRATION AND EMPLOYMENT-RELATED POLICIES

Due to the fact that many national policies in this field were implemented only recently, experts considered it too early to conclusively evaluate implications. In addition, structural changes of the policies in rural areas may even be visible later due to structural constraints or traditional mindsets. However, the same interviewee admitted that the federal level only recently focused on rural specificities with regard to employment-related policy-making (WP3WP4DE001):

“For a long time, we looked at the fact if they arrived in East or West Germany, [...] because conditions were so much different there [in Dresden] than in the Ruhr area. [...] Therefore, our core focus was not on the conditions in the rural space.” (WP3WP4DE001)

The intention behind the **Western Balkan Regulation** was a political signal effect to reduce the number of asylum seekers from the countries of the Western Balkan and provide a legal alternative for immigration to Germany. However, when the programme was extended in 2020, labour market-related aspects were considered more crucial (WP3WP4DE001). Interviewees reported quite positive experiences with employees from these countries, especially in the hospitality industry and in the care sector in rural areas (WP3WP4DE001, WP3WP4DE003, WP3WP4DE005). Nevertheless, applicants still have to wait long to receive appointments or documents from the embassies, while the recruitment of non-qualified workers was made more difficult due to prior recognition processes that were implemented following a decision of the regional coordinator of the Federal Employment Agency (WP3WP4DE004).

Resulting from the huge demand for skilled labourers – not least in the health sector of rural regions, the **Skilled Labour Immigration Act** provides one of the most liberal immigration regulations for TCNs at the moment as compared to international standards (WP3WP4DE001). So far, however, the effect of this law is only marginal due to the COVID-19 pandemic (WP3WP4DE001, WP3WP4DE003, WP3WP4DE005):

“The COVID-19 pandemic has shot it to pieces for us, honestly spoken. We were prepared and, before it came into force on the 1st of March, we had an incredible number of enquiries. [...] But until now, we still have no case where a contract was concluded and someone actually entered the country.” (WP3WP4DE003_2).

Generally speaking, advantages are reported in terms of the accelerated procedures, the pre-audit of the working contract and the eased family reunification (WP3WP4DE004). To warrant “fair” migration that provides advantages for the sending countries as well as a long-term integration perspectives for TCNs and their families in (rural) Germany, **bilateral agreements** could complement the Skilled Immigration Act in the long run (WP3WP4DE001).

The other part of the Migration Package, i.e. the **Toleration for Education and Employment Act**, is evaluated positively so far (WP4WP4DE003, WP3WP4DE004). However, due to high obstacles especially for the Toleration for Employment, numbers of residence permits issued are considerably low (WP3WP4DE003). The Foreigners’ Office in one district, however, exhausts all possibilities to issue working permits for TCNs (WP3WP4DE002), reflecting the high demand for labour among employers before the COVID-19 pandemic (WP3WP4DE001). Moreover, it has a social effect in the society, since employment of immigrants goes along with increasing prestige among local population.

As part of the pre-existing **Asylum Seekers’ Benefits Act**, the rural districts offered “refugee integration measures”, i.e., low-paid, unskilled employment, for instance at the local builder’s yards (WP3WP4DE002, WP3WP4DE003). While it was subsumed that this measure fostered their access to the regular labour market in the past (WP3WP4DE002), today, it became less important due to the above mentioned eased regulations in terms of access to the labour market (WP3WP4DE003). Access to the labour market is also facilitated by the **Temporary Employment Act**. However, due to the temporal restriction of contract work to 18 months and the warranty of equal pay after 9 months, termination of contracts are reported for the industry – but not the crafts

sector (WP3WP4DE004). Terminations in turn resulted in bureaucratically elaborate registrations at the *Jobcenter* (WP3WP4DE003).

It was acknowledged that **migrant entrepreneurship** was not considered as a political priority so far (WP3WP4DE001). Yet, the Chamber of Crafts and MigraNet/IQ provide consultation for interested parties, while recognition processes of foreign credentials include an exception check regarding the obligation to hold a master craftsman's certificate (WP3WP4DE003, WP3WP4DE004).

For the specific group of refugees, finally, **welcome guides** (funded by the Federal Ministry of Economy and Energy, BMWi, as well as the economy) and **canvassers of vocational training for refugees** (funded by the Bavarian State Ministry of the Interior, for Sport and Integration, StMI) are evaluated as valuable support and contact persons especially for small and medium-sized enterprises. In favour of existing regular structures, funding for the canvassers of vocational training for refugees, is not used anymore (WP3WP4DE004).

Nevertheless, **negative attitudes** among employers **to hire TCNs** are reported. These stem from different salary expectations in the context of vocational training (WP3WP4DE002) or prejudices against foreigners (WP3WP4DE001). Regarding the former, mediation was provided by the Chamber of Crafts, while for the latter, a rural district administration set a good example and explicitly addressed foreigners when advertising a vacancy (WP3WP4DE003). With regard to private enterprises, already existing funding opportunities for companies to hire TCNs as well as measures to foster intercultural competencies among the workforce should be strengthened in the future (WP3WP4DE001). Experiences from the *Länder* level, however, show that the demand for such courses is low (WP3WP4DE004).

SOCIETAL AND WELFARE-RELATED POLICIES

All five rural districts make use of the funds provided by the Bavarian state in terms of **refugee and integration counsellors** as well as **integration guides**. The funding regulations for counselling and integration (BIR) applying to both kind of posts facilitated TCN's access to relevant realms of integration. Integration guides, for instance, qualified **lay interpreters** among TCNs, whose services are organised and accounted for by Third Sector Organisations such as non-statutory welfare providers using the volunteering fixed rate (*Ehrenamtspauschale*) (WP3WP4DE002):

“For languages, such as Arabic or Tigrinya, we had the problem (in 2015) to get interpreters. From CITY IN AUSTRIA we couldn’t get them most of the times. From Munich it took a few weeks, until someone came, however, with the problem, we couldn’t wait this long. [...] Therefore, we qualified 24 people, especially in the languages spoken by refugees. [...] Back then, we could use funds of the coordinator of volunteers in the context of asylum, i.e. state funding. And in 2019, when we applied for it again, we took it from the budget of the integration guide.” (WP3WP4DE002)

Most recently, these lay interpreters prepared translations of the “general ruling” regarding the COVID-19 pandemic in the rural district and expressed gratitude by showing local inhabitants that they are willing to “give something back” (WP3WP4DE002). The integration guide in the same district cooperates with local Third Sector Organisations or draws on Euregio funds for civic engagement (WP3WP4DE002). While the two posts and the funding regulations are generally evaluated positively, it is criticised that after 2015 the state all of a sudden “found money for integration” and seemed to neglect already established structures such as Commissioners for integration or lay integration guides (WP3WP4DE003).

To safeguard a socially inclusive environment for TCNs in rural areas, it is considered necessary to **combat right-wing extremism and reduce prejudices against foreigners among the local population** in general (WP3WP4DE001) and among earlier arrived immigrants in particular (WP3WP4DE003). The Federal Government is aware that it cannot govern integration by means of regulations. Therefore, its focus instead is on information campaigns, the provision of counselling services and funds that aim at empowering migrant organisations to act on eye level and at reducing prejudices (WP3WP4DE001). Regarding the latter aspect, also the German Sport Association and the Soccer Association provide funds to foster intercultural opening in sports clubs (WP3WP4DE003). In one of the rural districts, for instance, the integration guide organised a 3-day workshop on assuming a firm attitude against right-wing extremism in association with the Bavarian Working Group of Volunteering Agencies (IAGFA Bayern e.V.) after volunteers and their fosterlings faced a billboard campaign and negative experiences in restaurants (WP3WP4DE002). In a second district, instead, intercultural opening was and is envisaged by means of English language courses for employees of the rural district administration and their nomination as ad-hoc interpreters as well as by letting the ones of the Foreigners’ Office attend the annual “naturalization events” of “their” clients (WP3WP4DE003). To reduce prejudices,

interactions between TCNs and local inhabitants are crucial. The prerequisite to act on eye-level is reflected in the example of migrant associations partaking in the annual festival of a small town:

“Many towns have their inter-cultural festivals. We take part in the city festival, we are part of SMALL TOWN, so to speak [...]. We don't want any extra sausage. And this has developed from a small market stall to a 'global village', where we now occupy a huge space. We have different stalls from different continents, offering food from their culture, and even have our own stage programme. [...] And that is where encounters really happen, and that is what's really great. The migrants can present their culture and the [...] Germans, who are world champions in travelling, can have the world trip on their doorstep.” (WP3WP4DE003_1)

HOUSING POLICIES

Rural districts aim at providing housing for asylum seekers in (small) decentralised accommodation instead of (big) communal accommodation as it is envisaged in the **Asylum Act**. They also tried and try to spread the accommodation over the district to as many municipalities as possible or at least to the most accessible ones to make use of vacancies or take pressure from the housing market (WP3WP4DE002, WP3WP4DE003, WP3WP4DE005). With regard to the **Residence Rule** for recognised refugees reliant on social welfare, the Foreigners' Office in one of the rural districts expounds it very liberal and exhausts all possibilities to avoid its imposition, allowing migrants to move away from the district or allowing them to at least choose a place of residence within the district (WP3WP4DE002).

Due to the vicinity to bigger cities such as Salzburg (in the case of MATILDE district BGL) or the touristic character of the region resulting in the presence of second homes and seasonal migration (in GAP and OA) as well as the overall structure of the rural housing markets, housing for recognised refugees and their families is scarce¹⁴³. While recognised refugees were often allowed to continue to live in the flats provided for asylum

¹⁴³ The access to the housing market for recognized refugees was eased partly during COVID-19 pandemic due to the impossibility of entry of seasonal migrants (WP3WP4DE003).

seekers (WP3WP4DE002, WP3WP4DE005), where they occupied places for newly assigned asylum seekers as a consequence, the rural districts of NEA and OA, used funding of the **emergency programme** to even construct 7 respectively 2 new apartments dedicated to recognised refugees (Bayerischer Landtag 2020). To foster refugees' access to housing, rural districts offer **courses for tenant qualification**¹⁴⁴ (WP3WP4DE002, WP3WP4DE003). While the Bavarian State Ministry of the Interior, for Sport and Integration (StMI) offers course materials, the integration guide in one of the districts organises and implements courses based on previous local experiences (WP3WP4DE002). In the meanwhile, the other district offered to provide this course to all foreigners – however, with a low demand until now (WP3WP4DE003). The same district also grants refugees holding a certificate to this course a priority access to apartments owned by the rural district's housing association (WP3WP4DE003). Apart from that, access to the housing market is fostered by means of **mediators**, i.e. volunteers, entrepreneurs and employees of the rural district administration (WP3WP4DE003; WP3WP4DE004).

MOBILITY POLICIES

To foster economic and societal inclusion of TCNs in rural areas, mobility is considered a core determinant (WP3WP4DE002, WP3WP4DE003, WP3WP4DE004). Due to the fact that mobility in the countryside is primarily car-mobility, difficulties arise as driving licenses of TCNs expire 6 months after entering Germany. Following the driving permit regulation (*Fahrerlaubnisverordnung*) they need to complete a driving test before getting renewed their license at the rural district administration (WP3WP4DE003). If the driving license is a prerequisite of a job offer, the *Jobcenter* is able to provide **subsidies for the acquisition of a driving licence and a car**. Additionally, companies allow TCNs to privately use **company cars** or provide them **bikes** (WP3WP4DE004). Apart from that, social **events are dispersed** to different municipalities of the district to reduce driving distances (WP3WP4DE003), while **volunteers provide lifts** using busses from a charitable organisation, drawing on **travel cost reimbursements** by Third Sector Organisations (WP3WP4DE002).

¹⁴⁴ The course known as “Neusäss Concept” started off as a project of volunteers in the Bavarian town of Neusäss (rural district Augsburg). Later, the course materials developed were used all over Bavaria and even beyond.

In terms of mobility, one of the interviewees reported implications of the **Geographic Restrictions for Foreigners** (Asylum Act), which are applied to asylum seekers during their first months in Germany in the specific contexts of border regions. Asylum seekers, for instance, cannot legally make use of the shorter and better (public transport) connections via Salzburg in Austria to get from the southern to the northern part of the district – or vice versa.

1.4 CONCLUSION

CONCLUSION FOR SOCIAL POLICIES

EFFECT OF POLICY RELATED FACTORS ON MIGRANTS' IMPACT INTO THE GERMAN SOCIETY

Generally, the statutory social security system does not differentiate between Germans, EU-migrants and TCNs. However, the reception of basic security benefits for job seekers can be detrimental to the extension of a temporary residence permit (Müller et al. 2014). Recently, a variety of policies on federal, *Länder* and municipal level was implemented, which initially aimed at the integration of TCNs. Yet, in a broader understanding of integration, i.e., inclusion into the society and participation, those measures had an indirect effect on migrants' impact on the German society in general.

Positive effects can be concluded from the establishment of various new positions in the public administration and in Third Sector Organisations, such as refugee and integration counsellors or integration guides, who foster social integration of newcomers of refugee background but also aim at empowering them. The latter is reflected, for instance, when it comes to empowerment and knowledge transfer, e.g. in terms of establishing a pool of lay interpreters for recently arrived migrants. However, the positions are bound to the duration of the funding schemes and are thus only limited in time, despite the fact that integration is addressed as a continuous task. Unlimited positions drawing on budget funds are scarce and only affordable for richer districts. Funding bodies also often define target groups of integration measures narrowly, e.g. to forced migrants with a good prospect of staying, and neither fail to acknowledge the diversity of TCNs nor follow a whole-of-society approach (Papademetriou & Benton 2016). Rural districts and municipalities make use of the legal margin left and try to provide services to as many inhabitants as possible – irrespective of their legal status (Aumüller 2009). Accordingly, also EU migrants may benefit from certain measures such as counselling or language courses (BBSR 2018).

In the social realm, the importance of volunteers has to be highlighted, especially in small towns and villages. Despite general critics on the neoliberal outsourcing of social inclusion of immigrants to civil society, the

proliferation of volunteering activities, e.g. as refugee relief groups for this specific target group, contributed to the mobilisation of local communities. However, it is unclear how sustainable this development is. The fields of action of both civil society and local administration encompassed the access to housing and mobility as well as the establishment of meeting opportunities. The latter is crucial to diminish prejudices and becomes most effective once the wider local population can be involved, e.g. when immigrants are made visible during a local feast.

In terms of housing, recent immigration unravelled challenges associated to the specific structures of rural housing markets as well as discrimination processes in terms of access to housing. For the specific group of asylum seekers, decentralised accommodation, even in peripheral locations, was a common strategy to mobilise vacancies (residential buildings or hotels) or take pressure of the housing market, while courses for tenant qualification and rental mediators supported the acquisition of appropriate private accommodation (Weidinger & Kordel 2020). Specific policies to regulate relocation, i.e. the Residence Rule is mostly evaluated positively by stakeholders, since it offers a better predictability to plan and implement integration measures on-site and more easily warrants minimum amounts of participants, demanded, for instance, by language course providers (Kordel & Weidinger 2019, see also conclusion for economic policies). On the other hand, however, the Residence Rule is evaluated negatively as it leads to a reduced labour market integration and a limited access to the private housing market.

In terms of mobility, the issue of accessibility of certain infrastructures is commonly addressed as a core issue for social integration and participation of TCNs in rural areas. For those who cannot afford an own car, volunteers or neighbours provide lifts to overcome limited public transport. However, the reimbursement of travel costs is easier for volunteers than for TCNs attending language and integration courses, but is only sought occasionally by the further group. To obviate the need to travel, another important pillar represent decentralised consultation-hours of counselling services.

GOOD PRACTICES

Since 2015, **VIA - the Association for Intercultural Work in Bavaria** (*Verband für Interkulturelle Arbeit in Bayern e.V.*) hosts the project NIKO (*Netzwerk interkulturelle Öffnung Kommunen in Bayern*), which is an acronym for Network for intercultural opening of rural districts and municipalities in Bavaria, and is part of the

IQ Network Bavaria / MigraNet (see also Good Practice below). The project aims at fostering intercultural opening, welcoming and recognition culture as well as integration management especially in small and medium-sized towns and rural districts, drawing on information material, counselling, staff training, seminars and conferences for local practitioners. Regarding the latter, VIA organises annual Bavarian Integration Conferences for rural districts and municipalities, which bring together the most important stakeholders of the administrations involved in integration in the Free State of Bavaria.

The small town of Hofheim in the rural district of Haßberge in Northern Bavaria proactively engaged with the topic of refugees and nominated a Commissioner for Asylum even before the first allocations of asylum seekers in 2014. Together with the six other municipalities of the **intercommunal alliance Hofheimer Land** and the newly founded refugee relief group, they organised accommodation and addressed the specific needs of asylum seekers by means of providing lay language courses and lifts to courses, supporting recognised refugees to find appropriate housing, making use of an existing vacancy monitoring, or matching migrants' skills with the labour demand of local enterprises (BBSR 2017; Rhein 2017; Galera et al. 2018). In this respect, the so-called "asylum coordinator", who was hired in 2016 funded by the Office for Rural Development Lower Franconia (*ALE Unterfranken*), drew on successful measures of the rural development and reused them for asylum purposes, leading Galera et al. (2018) to term the Hofheimer Land as "exemplary integration laboratory for migrants" (ibid. 18). Later, the position of the asylum coordinator was redesigned to a "contact point for newcomers" that takes into account also EU-citizens. While so-called welcome centres or one-stop shops were previously established only in metropolitan areas, the Hofheimer Land provides a successful example in rural areas. Most recently, the programme "We and Here" (*Wir & Hier*) was launched, aiming to establish a welcome and staying culture and to foster intergenerational and intercultural participation. Accordingly, a de-migrantization is encouraged by applying a whole-of-society approach.

The **Integration Council Oberallgäu** (*Integrationsbeirat Oberallgäu e.V.*) with its 177 members is the "voice" for migrants' interests in the rural district. It aims at establishing and retaining good relationships between local inhabitants and individuals with a migration history, at supporting migrants in socially, culturally and educationally challenging situations, and at capacity building. Founded in 1979, its activities expanded from the small town of Sonthofen to the Southern and more recently also to the Northern part of the district (Allgäuer Zeitung 2020) as well as from foreigners to expatriates and Germans with a migration background (Landkreis

Oberallgäu 2020). As a result of the Integration Council's attempt, in 2001, the rural district administration created the position of a **Commissioner for Migration and Integration**, which was staffed with the chairwoman of the Integration Council. Together with a working group, the Commissioner launched an annual integration monitoring (since 2009), an annual naturalisation event and an integration conference (both since 2011) as well as an integration plan that defines the most important fields of action (2011, renewed in 2014). To provide respective offers for migrants, the implementation of the integration plan is underpinned by an integration fund. The field of action "employment", in particular, was brought forth further by means of the participation in the project "Arrived and now? Labour market integration of refugees" funded by the Bertelsmann Foundation and the IQ-Network (2016).

CONCLUSION FOR ECONOMIC POLICIES

EFFECT OF POLICY RELATED FACTORS ON MIGRANTS' IMPACT INTO THE GERMAN ECONOMY

In addition to the social perspective, immigration and integration of TCNs must also be seen from an economic perspective, where the maximisation of net gains is negotiated with the maintenance of distributive justice. In the course of the proliferation of a meritocratic element in German migration policy (Schammann 2018, 2019), it became obvious that labour and performance appear as new structural principles. Embedded in discourses around demographic change and labour shortage, an eased access to the labour market for most of the TCNs – including forced migrants – was recorded in the last couple of years (Thränhardt 2015; Grote 2018; Laubenthal 2019)¹⁴⁵.

While a comprehensive evaluation of the Skilled Labour Immigration Act is too early, the Western Balkan Regulation instead is monitored positively. Yet, it became clear that waiting times in German embassies are still too long and the regulation itself is not based on a clear-cut policy that takes into account both needs of

¹⁴⁵ Nevertheless, Germany maintained a deterrent-based approach to forced migrants and continued to increase restrictions to reduce the numbers of asylum seekers (Crage 2016).

Germany and the countries of origin. Despite processes were adapted, the recognition of foreign credentials is still considered too bureaucratic and expensive. The same is true for the introduced Toleration for Education and Employment Act, where legal obstacles prevent companies from hiring forced migrants, though positive effects are reported. Contract work is another important entry point for TCNs to the labour market. Due to the restriction of contract work to 18 months and the obligation to warrant equal pay after 9 months, contracts are often terminated then, preventing sustainability. Besides the regular system of active labour market policy (Social Act Second and Third Book, Tangermann & Grote 2018), there are a variety of measures to foster TCNs' access to the labour market. Economic policies, however, lack a specific focus on migrant entrepreneurship, despite the fact that one fourth of all new companies are founded by migrants (Metzger 2020). Due to the political structure of Germany with both federal and *Länder* level, disharmonised and inconsistent processes are observable (see also Přívvara & Rievajová 2019).

In terms of language courses, which serve the basis for further education and employment, the eased access to language courses is evaluated positively. External events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, however, unravelled inconsistencies in educational policies, for instance, with regard to rural specificities. (Infra)structural disadvantages, e.g. bad internet connection, lacking technical equipment of TCNs as well as lacking technical capabilities among TCNs, negatively affected the change to virtual courses and hampered their long-term language acquisition. Similar to social integration, however, mobility is a core issue for the educational and labour market integration of TCNs in rural areas. While reimbursement of travel costs was previously acknowledged for teachers, it is still a major issue for participants of such courses. To overcome limited public transport connections, especially in the beginning when TCNs do not have an own car, lifts are provided by volunteers as well as work mates, while companies may offer the use of a company car.

Positive effects can be concluded from the establishment of various new positions in the public administration, in chambers and in Third Sector Organisations, such as refugee and integration counsellors, welcome guides, canvassers of vocational training for refugees, job mentors or coordinators of educational offers for new immigrants, who foster economic (and social) integration of newcomers but also aim at empowering TCNs. The latter is reflected, for instance, when it comes to empowerment and knowledge transfer, e.g. in terms of establishing a pool of lay interpreters for recently arrived migrants. However, the positions are bound to the duration of the funding schemes and are thus only limited in time, despite the fact that integration is addressed

as a continuous task. Unlimited positions drawing on budget funds are scarce and only affordable for richer districts. Funding bodies also often define target groups of integration measures narrowly, e.g. to forced migrants with a good prospect of staying, and fail to acknowledge the diversity of migrants nor follow a whole-of-society approach (Papademetriou & Benton 2016). Rural districts and municipalities make use of the legal margin left and try to provide services to as many inhabitants as possible – irrespective of their legal status (Aumüller 2009). Accordingly, also EU migrants may benefit from certain measures (BBSR 2018).

GOOD PRACTICES

The **IQ (Integration through Qualification) Network Bavaria / MigraNet**, funded by the Federal Ministry for Labour and Social Affairs (BMAS) and the European Social Fund (ESF) hosted at MATILDE local partner TAT, aims to improve the employment opportunities of people with a migration background. Therefore, firstly, MigraNet launched counselling centres to provide advice on the recognition of qualifications obtained abroad (see also figure 1). Secondly, job training schemes in the context of the Recognition Act is provided, e.g. bridge training in order to support the full recognition of foreign professional credentials. Thirdly, the IQ Network Bavaria develops intercultural competence of key labour market stakeholders and offers training and advice in *Jobcenters*, employment agencies, municipal administrations and small and medium sized enterprises. Fourthly, so-called “regional skilled workers networks – immigration” (*Regionale Fachkräftenetzwerke – Einwanderung*) connect relevant stakeholders and advice both companies and skilled workers. In cooperation with the Bavarian Association of Rural Districts (*Bayerischer Landkreistag*), the Bavarian Municipal Newspaper (*Bayerische Gemeindezeitung*) and the Bavarian State Ministry of the Interior, for Sport and Integration (StMI) as well as interested municipalities and regional or local offices for economic development, MigraNet organises “Bavarian Skilled Workers Forums” (*Bayerische FachkräfteForen*). In most cases, the one-day event is implemented as a fair to make the variety of rural economies visible to potential employees in general and immigrants in particular. Apart from the four priority areas, the programme “company coach” (*Unternehmenscoach*) aims to support companies willing to recruit international employees, while the Xenex

programme provides advice for immigrants keen to setting up businesses and has a special emphasis on forced migrants.

Figure 1: Priority areas in the IQ Network Bavaria

Good practices that aim at enhancing the economic participation of immigrants firstly address the preconditions for accessing the labour market, i.e., their educational attainment. In order to identify specific needs of immigrants¹⁴⁶ and match them with existing offers in the district as well as connect all relevant actors such as kindergartens, schools, educational providers, companies, municipalities, administrations, *Jobcenter*, associations and volunteers, the previously mentioned **coordinators for educational offers for newcomers** are key stakeholders in the Bavarian MATILDE districts (except for NEA). In the rural district of Regen, for instance, the coordinator who was hired in 2017 initially wrote an extensive report about the current educational situation drawing on statistical data gathered, established a pool of interpreters and cultural

¹⁴⁶ Initially targeting only immigrants of refugee background, the coordinators currently are able to follow a more holistic approach and take into account all (international) newcomers.

mediators and organised parent-teacher conferences for international parents. Lately, she took over the management of the local “working group school – economy” (*AK Schule – Wirtschaft*), which aims at strengthening the cooperation between schools and companies, and initiated and implemented cooperative projects with the districts of Rottal-Inn and Passau, e.g. a summer vacation school for children targeting German language acquisition and a series of workshops for pedagogic professionals that were held digitally due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

To tackle the shortage of skilled nursing staff, the rural district of NEA recently decided to firstly create a network of relevant actors on nursing and elderly care and to secondly implement a new generalist vocational training at the district school for nursing profession. While the core aim of employers such as hospitals, rehab clinics, old-age homes and providers of mobile care is to recruit apprentices from the region, i.e. school-leavers and career jumpers, also international applicants like TCNs are taken into consideration. A newly hired **coordinator for care** supports the implementation of the training course, e.g. by means of assisting the recruitment and integration process. So far, she was involved in marketing efforts, the organisation of accelerated visa procedures, which were enacted in the course of the new Skilled Labour Immigration Act earlier in 2020, as well as the elaboration of an integration plan (Nordbayern.de 2020). In addition, she accompanies international migrants to visits to the authorities and fosters their housing search. With regard to the latter, she can draw on regional expertise, which the district administration gained after having to search for accommodation for asylum seekers and recognised refugees in the last couple of years.

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MATILDE

6. ITALY

Country: Italy

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1.1 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC POLICIES REGARDING THIRD COUNTRY NATIONALS INTEGRATION AND THEIR IMPACT IN ITALY SELECTED REMOTE AREAS

This overview considers national, regional and provincial policies for the two Italian MATILDE regions: South Tyrol and the Metropolitan City of Turin (MCTurin), dividing them into four main categories: 1) Migration, Reception and Integration 2) Social 3) Economic and 4) Territorial policies.

MIGRATION, RECEPTION AND INTEGRATION POLICIES

The Italian State exerts exclusive jurisdiction for the **entry, staying and legal status of non-EU citizens, including international protection and citizenship**.¹⁴⁷ Based on the Consolidated Law on Immigration (D.Lgs. 286/1998), the central level has a coordinating role on **integration policies** that are implemented by Regions, Autonomous provinces and local administrations. Resources for implementation include the National Fund for Social Policies. Following the 2001 constitutional reform, Regions, Autonomous Provinces (such as South Tyrol) and Local Administrations consolidated their in “removing obstacles to housing, language and social integration”¹⁴⁸. Both MATILDE regions have adopted *ad hoc* legislation on the integration of foreigners, although with a significative time gap: for **Turin**, the legal frame is the **Piedmont Regional Law on Immigration adopted in 1989 (Law 64/1989)**, while for **South Tyrol** it is the **Provincial Law 12/2011 ‘Integration of foreign nationals’**. Both measures recognize the important role of local administrations, favour the knowledge of Italian language (for South Tyrol, also German and Ladin), and define the framework for TCNs access to social provisions including housing, education and vocational training.

¹⁴⁷ Consolidated Law on Immigration (D.Lgs. 286/1998), as amended in particular with Law 189/2002.

¹⁴⁸ Art.3, § 5 of D.Lgs. 286/1998.

Reception policies for Asylum Seekers and Refugees (ASRs) reflect the decentralized institutional setting of the country. Until two years ago, the standard channel for reception was the System for the Protection of Asylum Seekers and Refugees (*Sistema di Protezione per Richiedenti Asilo e Rifugiati*, SPRAR). Established with Law 189/2002 and amended with Law 132/2018, the SPRAR was grounded on cooperation with the National Association of Italian Municipalities (ANCI) and local authorities, that implemented reception projects with the financial support from the central level¹⁴⁹. Local authorities, with the collaboration of the third sector, guaranteed integrated reception interventions that went beyond the mere distribution of food and accommodation, providing complementary information, accompaniment, assistance and orientation measures, through the construction of individual paths to socio-economic integration¹⁵⁰. However, Extraordinary Reception Centres (*Centri di Accoglienza Straordinaria*, CAS) have been recurrently established to compensate for the underdevelopment of SPRAR, following a top-down approach. The CAS prevailed in quantitative terms, despite their temporary and emergency features. Following the North Africa Emergency, the “National Reception Plan” (Legislative Decree 142/2015) established **dispersal policies for ASRs** (with a threshold of 2,5 ASRs every 1000 inhabitants), significantly increasing the number of ASRs in rural and mountain areas. With Law 132/2018, the SPRAR has been replaced by the System of protection for holders of international protection and for unaccompanied foreign minors (*Sistema di protezione per titolari di protezione internazionale e per minori stranieri non accompagnati*, SIPROIMI), restricting the access to integrated reception services to recognized refugees only. SIPROIMI was amended again with D.L. 130/2020, which makes the current frame for ASRs reception under redefinition.

In 2018, South Tyrol reception system provided 1,800 places for ASR in 30 facilities. At the end of 2016, 10 CAS were located in the city of Bolzano, which hosted 77% of the total ASRs in the Province (Mitterhofer and Wisthaler 2018). With an important change compared to previous years, in September 2017 the eight Bolzano

¹⁴⁹ Art. 32 Law 189/2002.

¹⁵⁰ SPRAR/SIPROIMI Official Website: <https://www.siproimi.it/lo-sprar>

District (*Comunità Comprensoriali*) joined the SPRAR network and submitted to the Ministry of Interior applications for 223 places, which will then be approved at the end of December 2017¹⁵¹. Following the National Reception Plan, with the **Circolare Critelli** the provincial Department for Social Policies excluded from temporary reception ASRs arriving autonomously in the province, i.e., all persons who were not part of the redistribution flows determined by the Ministry of Interior. The out-of-quota were thus left on informal settlements, which found support from local NGOs and civil society only (Antenne Migranti 2019).

At the end of 2018, the **MCTurin** hosted a total number of 4720 ASRs in its reception structures, 1027 of them through SPRAR system, with more than a half located outside the Municipality of Turin (Osservatorio stranieri, 2018). Financed by AMIF 2014-2020, Piedmont region has also been involved in the setting up of human corridors to facilitate the arrival of Syrian refugees from Lebanon, as well as a series of projects aimed at fostering the integration of refugees already present on the territory¹⁵².

SOCIAL POLICIES

Despite the universalistic character of the Italian welfare system, several reforms undertaken since the 80s and the 2008 financial crisis paved the way for a residual model of welfare and social protection, marked by an increasing role of the private sector. At National level, the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies coordinates and funds policies to promote the labour and social integration of TCNs, that are implemented by Regions, Autonomous Provinces and Local Authorities. The central level also promotes initiatives aimed at preventing and fighting **discrimination, xenophobia and racism**. The National Office Against Racial Discriminations (UNAR) monitors discriminatory phenomena, assists victims, and promotes initiatives for inclusion. Links at territorial level are provided by Regional Anti-discrimination Centres.

¹⁵¹ Consiglio Comunale di Bolzano, Relazione sull'attività della Referente per i richiedenti asilo e rifugiati, available at: https://www.comune.bolzano.it/UploadDocs/21198_RELAZIONE_REFERENTE_per_CONSIGLIO.pdf

¹⁵² The list of projects supported by the Piedmont region through AMIF 2014-2020 are available at: <https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/temi/fondi-progetti-europei/fondo-asilo-migrazione-integrazione-fami>

The **access to healthcare** for TCNs legally staying in the country is guaranteed through the compulsory registration with the National Health Service (SSN) and extends to family members (DLgs 25 July 1998, no. 286, Art. 34). Undocumented TCNs are insured urgent and essential health-care services. However, no structured social policies are in place at national to guarantee concretely the access to health services for TCNs. Law 132/2018 prevented regular inclusion of asylum seekers in the municipal records, with negative impact on the access to national and regional provisions for ASRs, including the right to healthcare. Many local authorities reacted elaborating *ad hoc* provisions to handle the uncertainties of the new legal framework¹⁵³.

The **access to education** is guaranteed to foreign minors regardless their legal status. In 2014, the Ministry of Education has adopted guidelines to enhance the inclusion of foreign pupils at schools, providing up-to-date instructions on school guidance, evaluation, education and training of young people and adults¹⁵⁴. At University level, the Ministry of the Interior provides a limited number of scholarships (100 yearly) to beneficiaries of international protection¹⁵⁵.

Other social inclusion measures such as the **Inclusion Income**, later **Citizenship income**, are accessible only for TCNs holding an EU residence permit for long-term residents with a 10 years long staying in the country, and to holders of international protection (refugee status and subsidiary protection only)¹⁵⁶. Similarly, **family**

¹⁵³ For Piedmont, see for instance: <http://www.piemonteimmigrazione.it/normativa/novita-legislative/item/1438-iscrizione-al-servizio-sanitario-dei-richiedenti-asilo-privi-di-iscrizione-anagrafica>

¹⁵⁴ MIUR, Linee guida per l'accoglienza e l'integrazione degli alunni stranieri, 2014. Available at: https://www.istruzione.it/allegati/2014/linee_guida_integrazione_alunni_stranieri.pdf

¹⁵⁵ For the application for academic year 2019/20 see: https://www.interno.gov.it/sites/default/files/bando_protezione_internazionale_2019_eng_def.pdf

¹⁵⁶ For the criteria of access to the Inclusion income (REI), see: http://www.piemonteimmigrazione.it/images/news_materiali/Nota_Ministero_del_Lavoro_prot_50702018.pdf; While for

welfare measures such as the “birth award” have been extended to all mothers legally residing in the country, only following the intervention of the judicial¹⁵⁷.

The Italian Constitution favours “the access [...] to home ownership”¹⁵⁸, yet **access to social housing** is reserved to TCNs with regular visa (Art 40 TUI) and parameters are determined by local authorities. In **South Tyrol**, the allocation of social housing reflects the proportionality of language groups. TCNs can access to social housing provided they have resided in the Province for at least 5 years without interruption and have been working there for 3. The Provincial Institute for Social Housing (*Istituto per l’Edilizia Sociale*, IPES) also provides the so-called “workers’ houses” (524 places in Bolzano and Merano), i.e. temporary accommodation for workers of the provincial territory¹⁵⁹. Social Districts can then provide an economic contribution for “home subsidy” and/or “additional costs” to residents who meet the requisites required¹⁶⁰. The Regional Law on **social housing** in Piedmont (n.3/2010) also requires a minimum residence period to benefit from this housing service (from a minimum of 3/5 years, at the discretion of the Municipality). In addition, regular migrants who live in Piedmont for at least 5 years have access to a National Lease Support Fund, which was established by Law no. 431/98, article 11, but has no longer been paid out since 2015¹⁶¹.

the extensions to TCNs of the citizenship income, see:

http://www.piemonteimmigrazione.it/images/news_materiali/Decreto_Reddito_di_Cittadinanza_stranieri_.pdf

¹⁵⁷ See the relative note by the National Institute for Social Provisions (INPS) of February 2018:

<http://www.piemonteimmigrazione.it/images/Messaggio-numero-661-del-13-02-2018.pdf>

¹⁵⁸ Art 47 § 2 of the Italian Constitution.

¹⁵⁹ EURAC, Rapporto sulle migrazioni 2020, pp. 56-57. Available at:

http://www.eurac.edu/en/research/Publications/Documents/dossier/migration-report/Migrationsreport_it_full_ok.pdf

¹⁶⁰ Art. 20 del Decreto del Presidente della Giunta provinciale 11 agosto 2000, n. 30

¹⁶¹ For further details: <http://www.piemonteimmigrazione.it/diritti/vivere-in-italia/abitare>

ECONOMIC POLICIES: LABOUR MARKET INTEGRATION

The access to **work related permits of staying** is ruled by Law 189/2002 (Law Bossi-Fini), that allows labour visa (seasonal and non-seasonal) for TCNs to the quotas set up annually by the government (*Decreto Flussi*) and through the sponsorship mechanism.

Public job placement is provided by provincial Public Employment Service (*Centri per l'impiego*) that can be accessed by TCNs, including ASRs, but specific services for them are not offered. Some municipalities have a migrant desk, where migrants may receive support, *inter alia*, for their needs related to employment (SIRIUS 2019: 417). Temporary tax incentives favour the hiring of ASRs: Budget Law 2017 has established tax incentives for social cooperatives which will recruit beneficiaries of international protection with a permanent contract in 2018.

To contrast the widespread **phenomenon of “Caporalato”**, a form of labour exploitation through illegal intermediation particularly rooted in the agri-food production chain, administrative and criminal sanctions has been adopted in the last decade (Legislative Decree no. 109/2012 and 199/2016), tightening sanctions against employers and intermediators. In 2019 the **Quality Agricultural Work Network** (*Rete Lavoro Agricolo di Qualità*)¹⁶² was created to promote agricultural enterprises which are distinguished by compliance with labour and social legislation.

Within MATILDE regions, **South Tyrol** participates in the quotas only for seasonal workers, i.e. authorisations to work in the tourism-hotel sector and in agriculture for a maximum of 9 months per year. After that, the applicant

¹⁶² For further details: <https://www.inps.it/nuovoportaleinps/default.aspx?itemdir=50213>

must return to his/her country of origin. With **resolution no. 414 of 8 May 2018**, the Autonomous Province of Bolzano established that seasonal work quotas are issued only to non-EU citizens who have worked at least once in South Tyrol in the seasonal sector in the last three years¹⁶³. The Province supports the employment of foreigners through the services of *Ripartizione Lavoro*, with the mediation of private social sector and fiscal assistance centres. The Project "Alba" offers a special form of assistance for labour integration targeting trafficked and exploited people. The **Piedmont region** has approved a Memorandum of Understanding promoting regular work in agriculture (*Protocollo d'intesa per la promozione del lavoro regolare in agricoltura*) and a set of provisions for **temporary accommodation of seasonal farm workers** (Regional Law n. 16 2016). In addition, a model of **social agriculture** is developing in both provinces with the aim to include disadvantaged people who are involved in social and working inclusion paths in the agricultural sector¹⁶⁴.

To counter the effects of the **COVID-19 crisis**, the emersion of irregular job relations involving TCNs was included in the *Decreto rilancio* (Art. 103 Decree Law n. 34/2020), limitedly to employees in the agricultural and caregiving sectors.

TERRITORIAL POLICIES

In the field of territorial policies aiming to support the repopulation and revitalization of rural and mountain areas, three main policy that redefine the economic resources and the access to welfare provisions in rural and mountain areas seem relevant.

¹⁶³ The Autonomous Province of Bolzano: http://www.provincia.bz.it/it/servizi-a-z.asp?bnsv_svid=1005680

¹⁶⁴ For MCTurin: Regional Law Piemonte n. 1 del 22 January 2019; For South Tyrol: Law on Social Agriculture n. 8 22 June 2018.

The first, the **National Strategy for Inner Areas** (*Strategia Nazionale Aree Interne, SNAI*)¹⁶⁵, was established in 2013 by the Ministry of Territorial Cohesion. For the first trial, it identifies 72 territories in need of intervention and developed a set of tools to improve their access to basic services (health, transport and education) and to reverse their current negative demographic trend by attracting new inhabitants. The SNAI has a financial capacity of ca. 90 million euros for the period 2019-21.

The 2017 **Law on Small Municipalities** (*Legge Piccoli Comuni* Law No. 158 6.10.2017)¹⁶⁶ aims to enhance the potential of marginalized territories. It establishes a fund of 100 million euros - 15 million for each of the years 2018 to 2023 - for the structural, economic and social development of municipalities with less than 5000 inhabitants.

Other initiatives to repopulate and revitalize internal areas are carried out at regional and provincial level: financed by FEASR (2014-2020), both South Tyrol and CM Turin **Rural Development Plans**¹⁶⁷ aim to contribute to the economic and social growth of the provincial rural areas, tackling the competitiveness of the agricultural sector; the sustainable management of natural resources; and the balanced territorial development of rural economies and communities. The Turin Strategic Metropolitan Plan is also another crucial policy document to

¹⁶⁵ See Interministerial Committee for Economic Planning, Resolution 9/2015 for the establishment of SNAI, available at: <http://ricerca-delibere.programmazioneeconomica.gov.it/media/docs/2015/E150009.pdf> [accessed November 12, 2020] and resolution 52/2018 for the latest funding allocation to the Strategy, available at: <http://ricerca-delibere.programmazioneeconomica.gov.it/media/docs/2018/E180052.pdf> [accessed November 12, 2020].

¹⁶⁶ Law No. 158 of 6 October 2017 "Misure per il sostegno e la valorizzazione dei piccoli comuni, nonché disposizioni per la riqualificazione e il recupero dei centri storici dei medesimi comuni", G.U. 2.11.2019.

¹⁶⁷ http://www.provincia.bz.it/agricoltura-foreste/agricoltura/downloads/Programme_2014IT06RDRP002_1_3_it.pdf

https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/sites/default/files/media/documenti/2020-06/programme_2014it06rdp009_9_1_it_copmod.pdf

overcome the asymmetries between mountain and urban areas. In this regard, a Permanent Roundtable for monitoring the mountain development was established in 2018 (*Tavolo Permanente per la Montagna*)¹⁶⁸.

It is worth mentioning that an overall strategy supporting widespread mountain habitability and intensive touristic exploitation has been carried out through the years in South Tyrol: as part of a policy in favour of local ethnic minorities (Membretti & Ravazzoli 2019), one of the aims of this intervention has been to support the German speaking population, mainly living in the inner valleys; on the other hand, the Dolomites mountain range has been the object of a massive strategy investing in touristic facilities. The abovementioned strategy also promoted the widespread presence of services, economic and productive activities and supports traditions such as closed farmsteads (the so-called *Hof / maso*) that link people to the rural territory, guaranteeing a quality of life that is able to both keep the natives there, but also to attract new inhabitants (Ravazzoli 2020).

¹⁶⁸http://www.cittametropolitana.torino.it/cms/risorse/agrimont/dwd/tavolo-permanente-montagna/decreto_692_30025_2018.pdf

1.2 OVERVIEW ON EXISTING ANALYSES AND ASSESSMENTS OF ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL POLICIES

This review considers scholarship on migration, asylum and integration policies with a multilevel perspective. It also presents studies on social, economic and territorial policies that may condition the possibilities of integration of foreigners in Italy and their impact on the reception context. Where sources are available, regional policies for South Tyrol and the Metropolitan City of Turin are considered, along with national ones.

THE MULTILEVEL GOVERNANCE OF MIGRATION, ASYLUM AND INTEGRATION

Migration policies in Italy are regarded as marked by an inconsistent set of multiple measures and actions, neither supported by a unitary strategy and governance nor by sufficient financial resources (Schierup et al. 2006, Fullin & Reyneri 2011). Policies are characterized since the 90s by a security and emergency approach, affected by the fragmentary stratification of primary and secondary sources, often reverted by the judicial power (Sciortino, 2003; Campesi 2011; Marchetti 2012; Dal Zotto 2014). According to Zincone (2006) these limits remain regardless of changes in the governing coalition. Integration has been conceived for long as a *de facto* process deriving from the participation in the (informal) labour market (Caponio, Zincone, 2011). In sum, King et al. (1997) defined the Italian “Mediterranean model of immigration” as characterized by the combination of restrictive admission and citizenship policies with frequent amnesties. Consequently, scholars define the Italian system as “institutionalized irregularity” (Calavita 2007:33, Ferraris 2009, as quoted in Pannia 2018: 32-33). The Territorial Councils for Immigration (*Consigli Territoriali per l’Immigrazione*) established by Law 286/1998 have been marked in their functioning by severe deficiencies (SIRIUS, 2018:322): programmatic documents foreseen by the law have not been adopted regularly across the years (Pannia et al. 2018: 26) and yearly plans, the so-called Decreto Flussi have failed to answer the actual needs of the labour market, opting instead for the progressive reduction of quotas since 2011 (Fullin & Reyneri 2011: 143).

The legal frame for **reception and integration services for ASRs** substantially developed on the basis of a bottom-up process in which experimentations started by local authorities and civil society were later on institutionalized in the legal framework (Bona 2016; Campomori & Caponio 2016; Marchetti, 2012). The SPRAR model is regarded as an example of European best practice because it creates “a system in dialogue with the territorial context that support the establishment of relations between ASRs and the community” (Cittalia-Fondazione ANCI, 2019; OECD, 2018, SIRIUS 2019:428). However, the asylum field is characterised by the emergency approach. The CEASEVAL project assessed the expansion of the reception system since 2011, noting the lack of coordination mechanisms among State, Regional and Local Authorities relating to the governance of CAS, SPRAR and today’s SIPROIMI tools (CEASEVAL 2019).

Law 132/2018 goes in the opposite direction to the integration services offered by SPRAR, firstly because asylum seekers are not any longer hosted in the new SIPROIMI reception system, but only in the first-line governmental centres or CAS (SIRIUS 2019). Restrictions to the validity of the asylum requests to obtain the municipal records caused restrictions in the access to public services, violating the principle of equality laid down in Article 3 of the Constitution (ASGI 2018). Finally, the abolishment of humanitarian protection restricted access to the reception system and increased the number of people in an irregular situation.

Scaling down to the regional level, Caponio et al. (2019) examined the governance of ASRs reception in the **Metropolitan City of Turin** highlighting the establishment of the Roundtable on Asylum as a best practice: its aim is to coordinate local authorities with the Third sector and Civil Society organizations (CSOs) managing SPRAR centres and public-private integration services for asylum seekers and refugees. Within this institutional space, conflicts between municipalities and the central state arising from the imposition of CAS centres have been solved by protocols entrusting Municipalities, rather than the private/third sector, with the tasks of setting up and managing CAS. As a consequence, several cases of good reception practices in rural and mountain areas were reported in Piedmont (FIERI 2017; Perlik et al. 2019). Reception policies in **South Tyrol** have been recently analysed by Degli Uberti (2019) and Sempredon et al. (2020), particularly regarding the challenges deriving from the transit of ASRs along the Brenner route, that from 2013 became a new, contentious “space of transit”. Both authors consider the phenomenon of the so called “out of quota”, ASRs autonomously arrived on the territory of South Tyrol, and as such excluded from the support services guaranteed to those who arrive through the national redistribution plan. Shelter problems and the impact of the 2018 national reform are considered in the

2020 dossier by Fondazione Langer and Antenne Migranti, that exposes the persistent lack of mechanism for the inclusion of asylum seekers who have arrived autonomously in the province. Finally, the 2020 EUMINT report addresses the challenges related to labour integration of ASRs in the provincial labour market, focusing on the plurilingual context, bureaucratic rigidities and the matching between supply and demand of labour (Raffaele-Addamo and Membretti, 2020).

Foreign immigration to rural and mountain areas has gained prominence in the social sciences as a trend “that helps to counter the continuous depopulation of remote rural areas” (Osti & Ventura 2012, Balbo 2015, Bock et al. 2016; Membretti *et al.* 2017; Perlik et al. 2019). The issue has been addressed from different perspectives by scholars. ForAlps (Foreign immigration in the Alps) international network conducted pioneering research work on immigration and local development.¹⁶⁹ Corrado (2017) considers the increasing relevance of foreign migration to rural and mountain destinations by their integration in sectors such as agriculture, tourism, construction, personal and care services. Membretti et al. (2017) have collected experiences of migration and its direct and indirect contribution on local economic and social development of mountain areas. Carrosio and Lo Presti (2018) consider immigration as a potential driver for regenerating the identity and economies in rural and marginal areas assessing the approach of National Strategy of Inner Areas (SNAI). The PlurAlps project (2016-2019)¹⁷⁰ identifies pluralism as an element fostering social innovations in mountain areas. Both point to the need for enabling policies and public administrations that strategically integrate and empower newcomers in processes directed to sustainable local development. Similarly, Balbo (2015) analysed how **small municipalities** cope with growing diversity of the demographic, economic and institutional contexts as a result of migration processes and policies. Differently from scholars, Caritas Italy (2019) looks at the lack of acknowledgment by the public opinion and political actors of the contribution of foreign immigrants to the Italian economy and society, exacerbated by the political climate and the resurgence of racist and nationalist discourses that unfolded during the centre-right government in 2018-19.

¹⁶⁹ ForAlps website: www.foralps.eu

¹⁷⁰ <https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/pluralps/en/home>

Considering in particular **forced migration**, Di Gioia, Dematteis and Membretti (2018) analyse how dispersal policies for ASRs brought about 40% of all asylum seekers to be hosted in these territories and 10% of the country's reception centres to be located in Alpine municipalities. As a result, in some cases across the Italian Alps the ratio of ASRs to overall residents reached 10% (Perlik et al., 2019:158). Ponzo (2017) elaborates on the fragilities and potentialities for innovation by reception projects for refugees as a result of the dispersal policies of ASRs. The study recognizes that reception projects for refugees in suburban areas resulted in triggering inter-municipality cooperation. Galera et al. (2018) provide concrete examples of reception projects and related local strategies for ASRs contributing to the revitalization of rural areas.

SOCIAL INCLUSION

On migrant social inclusion, most policy analyses relate to the regional and municipal level as the most relevant level where social policies are adopted and implemented.

Caponio and Campomori (2017) shed light on the multi-level governance relations that shape immigrant integration policies in three Italian regions: Lombardy, Piedmont and Emilia-Romagna, while Cutello and Weiß adopt the same approach to look at the whole Alpine region (2019). Caneva (2014) assessed the policy instruments for migrants' social integration, regarding the relevant fields of housing and education. Large metropolitan areas are those where the problems of housing distress are concentrated, but rural areas are also not free from housing difficulties for migrants. They are caused by the economic restrictions in which most migrants lay and discrimination towards this population group (Demaria and Lagravinese 2015). Social Housing policies have been considered by Ponzo (2010) as a potential answer to these difficulties, in which municipalities play a central role and which combine housing with social inclusion through the use of space. In the field of **education**, ISMU recently published two reports focusing on the integration of migrant students in Italy, the obstacles faced by students of immigrant origin and the favourable policies that could enable their integration (ISMU, 2020 and 2019).

Scholars from different disciplines have assessed regional policies for migrants' integration adopted in South Tyrol. Mitterhofer and Wisthaler (2017) analyse the integration of foreigners in South Tyrol in light of demographic trends and their spatial distribution. Carlà (2018) makes a critical analysis of policies targeting

foreign migrants by juxtaposing the 2008 document “Foreigners in South Tyrol” to the 2011 Law on Integration. Cutello and Weiß (2019) and Mitterhofer et al. (2016) assess that local administrations (i.e. municipalities and districts) have been given relevant competence on the integration subject since the adoption of the Law on Integration in 2011. Third sector organizations play a crucial role especially when they make up for national budget shortages. Finally, the recent Migration report from EURAC (2020) provides a multidisciplinary profile of the people migrating to South Tyrol and their integration in the region’s schools, employment, housing and political systems. The specific field of education policies has been widely addressed by scholars such as Wisthaler (2015), Medda-Windischer (2011), as being influenced by the plurilinguistic context. The existence of separate and parallel state school systems for the three official linguistic groups¹⁷¹ is assessed as creating strong barriers to integration in the educational system by migrants with cascading effects in other fields (Membretti & Cultello 2019).

Relating to the MCTurin, a 2017 report by FIERI, Dislivelli and other local actors selects and analyses 22 “best practices” related to reception projects for asylum seekers and refugees both in urban and rural areas of Piedmont (FIERI, 2017). Other concrete examples referred to this region are analysed in a collective publication by the ForAlps network (Membretti et al. 2017).

ECONOMIC POLICIES AND LABOUR MARKET INCLUSION

Assessments of national policies for the **entry and staying of labour migrants** highlight two main aspects: they fail to answer the needs of the Italian labour market¹⁷² and create the conditions favouring employment in the grey market and consequent labour exploitation of TCNs workers.

¹⁷¹ German, Italian, Ladin linguistic groups.

¹⁷² The Leone Moressa Foundation’s Annual Report offers a wide corpus of statistics concerning the quantitative and qualitative evolution of the demand for immigrant labour: <http://www.fondazioneleonemoressa.org/category/libri-in-biblioteca/>

SIRIUS project provides an overview of the legal frame, policy elements and social actors, assessing their role as enablers or obstacles for the labour integration of migrants, asylum seekers and refugees. The project finds that the number of TCNs admitted to the country through the quota system introduced by the Decreto Flussi have been systematically far below labour demand. Moreover, the opportunities to regularly enter in the Italian territory have been substantially limited to high-qualified workers, entrepreneurs and few seasonal workers in the fields of agriculture and tourism. Thus, the Decreto Flussi has been assessed to be an unrealistic, inefficient and inadequate system to tackle both labour demand and immigration needs (SIRIUS 2018, 2019). The exploitation of migrant workers through illegal or irregular, illicit intermediation and exploitation of labour is a long-debated and inquired issue in Italy (Fullin & Reyneri 2011, IDOS 2017, Corrado et al. 2018, FLAI/CGIL 2019).

The SIRIUS project provides a systematic assessment of the post-2014 migration policies in terms of capacity of the country to integrate migrants and ASRs in the labour market. SIRIUS findings point to the fact that foreigners are largely employed in labour-intensive sectors (agriculture, construction and family care) (SIRIUS, 2019: 340). Along these lines, Ricciardi et al. (2018), reflect on the potential role of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) to support firms and institutions in integrating migrants in agriculture labour market avoiding irregularities and exploitation. Differently, the SPRAR system has been considered as a “best practice” by the Italian Roadmap (2015), as it foresees compulsory language courses and the registration to Public Employment Service, allowing migrants to get employment, although with some limitations¹⁷³.

Regarding the impacts of Covid-19 on migrants’ labour integration, Faleri (2020) and Macrì (2020) examined the impact of the pandemic on agricultural workers. ISMU monitored the outcomes of the procedure for the emergence of employment relationships launched by the government during summer 2020, showing the prevalence of emersions concerning domestic work and personal assistance (85% of the total, 176,848), compared to the applications for the emergence of subordinate work (15%, 30,694).

¹⁷³ The Italian legislation recognizes the asylum seekers the possibility to work, however it ensures the right to stay in reception centres only if they have a wage that does not exceed 4.800 euro per year

1.3 STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS OUTPUT: ASSESSMENT OF THE STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF POLICIES THROUGH SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

Interviews for this assessment have been conducted with stakeholders involved in policies formulation and implementation at the national, regional and provincial level. Experts from the academia have also been included, as well as coordinators of reception and integration services. Overall, 13 informants have been contacted, out of which three at national level; five for the Turin and 5 for South Tyrol. Due to the Covid-19 pandemics, all interviews have been conducted online.

ASSESSMENT OF THE SOCIAL POLICIES

At national level, policies for social inclusion such as the Citizenship income maintain discriminatory access criteria. According to the latest report by the National Institute for Social Provisions (INPS), non-EU citizens access to this support to an even lower extent than the percentage of foreigners present on the national territory (8.5%).¹⁷⁴ Yet, according to ISTAT, the share of TCNs families over the total number of poor families varies (from north to south) from 27.7% to 42.6% (1.6 million out of a total of 5.5 million).

LOCAL DIMENSION AND SOCIO-TERRITORIAL INEQUALITIES

Looking at rural and mountain regions of Italy and considering the **local dimension of integration**, it seems, in the words of some interviewees – like the former coordinator of SNAI – that *“usually, migrants live the rural*

¹⁷⁴ INPS, Osservatorio statistico sul reddito di cittadinanza e sul reddito di inclusione, January 2020. Available at: https://www.inps.it/docalleqatiNP/Miq/Dati_analisi_bilanci/Osservatori_statistici/Osservatorio_REI/Report_trimestrale_ReI-RdC_Aprile-Dicembre_2019.pdf [Accessed November 19th, 2020]

and mountain areas with more serenity and security than the local population” (Former coordinator of SNAI, Informant 10).

Nevertheless, at the level of regional and provincial policies, as a journalist from Turin argues, “there have been no measures to encourage the presence of migrants in rural and mountain areas of Piedmont, except through virtuous municipal administrations” (Informant 2). This happens despite “the impact of migration in rural and mountain areas is not only related to the economic development of the territories, but also the social one. They keep kindergartens or hospitals open; they help to keep small shops alive; and they contribute to the social life of small villages” (Informant 4). The former coordinator of the Italian National Strategy for Inner Areas (SNAI) adds that: “Immigrants are a key resource for the inner areas of the country. SNAI has always considered the presence of immigration as an indicator of dynamism. This is because the abandoned areas are often characterized by very small communities where there is a lack of young people and innovation” (Former coordinator of SNAI, Informant 10).

When considering social inclusion of migrants, several interviewees outline as stratification and **spatial distribution of TCNs** varies significantly across Italy and even within the MATILDE regions: different national groups arrived at different times, following different trajectories. As a consequence, “*territories and communities need diversified interventions and policies, in order to overcome inequalities*”, as affirmed by a Senior official at the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies (Country level interview, Informant 5).

In particular, access to social services reflects **territorial inequalities in welfare policies**: as pointed out from a member of the provincial council for integration (South Tyrol), “*The peculiarity in Italy is that social assistance is provided at local level, so the social worker has a great margin of manoeuvre. In Bolzano there is a social integration service where you have 3 social workers for thousands of people. In Aurina valley the same social worker has much fewer people to follow. There is a very strong social network so the social worker knows that if he or she talks to a certain person, things work out*” (Coordinator of reception services for ASRs in South Tyrol, Informant 1).

Even schools, usually a mean of integration, tends to reflect these territorial disparities: “Rural and mountain schools are not always prepared to welcome these children with low language skills, especially when they are first generation immigrants”, as states the former coordinator of SNAI.

Housing is another dimension of territorial and **spatialised inequalities**. In South Tyrol the touristic sector, based on large hotels, attracts staff, which is often of foreign origin. *“The municipalities are asked, when they ask for building permits, where they intend to accommodate the workers who will be employed in those structures. But this is not yet an issue. The result is that these people are there, not all of them seasonal, filling places with little attraction for residents, less desirable, less expensive areas”* (South Tyrol, provincial manager, Informant 8).

PARTICIPATION

In terms of social inclusion of migrants, and of concrete exercise of the **rights of citizenship**, civic and political participation seem crucial, in particular with respect to the places in which people live. As pointed out by a sociologist living in South Tyrol, *“On the associative level, with the disappearance of political and ideological schemes of the past, religious associationism gains prominence, as the only one that manages to have a structured presence in buildings, with a spokesman, etc.”* (South Tyrol, Informant 9). This happens while, on the other hand, social associationism of TCNs remains quite weak, in particular in some regions. In fact, as the coordinator of reception facilities for asylum seekers in a small village of South Tyrol argues, *“there is a lack of interaction at community level. There are these parallel communities, and everyone does their own things”* (South Tyrol, Informant 10).

The existing **public bodies for the participation** of foreigners do not seem responding to the actual challenges: in South Tyrol, the Provincial Integration Council (Consulta)¹⁷⁵ *“does not effectively exercise its consultative power, not even on the recent proposal for the Integration Pact. We see that the recent municipal elections in Bolzano brought 4 people of foreign origin elected to the council, voted on lists of different political signs. This*

¹⁷⁵ The Provincial Integration Council (Consulta) is an advisory body directly appointed by the Provincial Council. Its main objective is to strengthen the inclusion of new citizens, presenting to the Provincial Council opinions, proposals and concrete input for the development of integration policies. Eight of the 18 members are represented by foreign citizens and are elected on the basis of a fair representation of the different countries of origin; the other members come from various departments of the provincial administration, municipalities, trade unions and other voluntary associations.

is proof that some sections of the population, who have been arriving for a longer time, already act in the territory and participate, and make the Consulta mechanism obsolete” (South Tyrol, Informant 9).

Moreover, considering in particular asylum seekers and refugees, there is the perception that “there is no time to prepare people to integrate in the territory. Once out of the CAS (centre for reception), people are quite lost, also because here in Italy language courses do not work very well”, argue a social worker (South Tyrol, Informant 10). This seems particularly evident for the most fragile categories of migrants, as: “there are about thirty illiterate people in contact with Caritas and no provincial service takes care of them. How can they participate if they cannot read or write?” (South Tyrol, Informant 1).

SOCIAL TENSIONS AND COVID-19 PANDEMIC IMPACT

“Certainly, the attitude towards migrants is less hostile compared to the urban peripheries, but this phenomenon is not seen as an opportunity yet. Such a perception has to be developed through good practices and policies” (Informant 3), these are the words of the President of the Italian Mountain Municipalities Union, that put in evidence the difficulty of transforming non-hostility at local level in a **positive attitude** toward migrants.

With regard to the **tensions** generated in local communities by the opening of reception centres for asylum seekers and refugees, in South Tyrol and in Turin, the lack of involvement of local authorities and communities in the set-up of reception projects is seen as a key element in the rise of hostile attitudes, later diminished when opportunities for contacts are created among newcomers and locals. As a journalist from Turin states, *“there are methods to involve the population more, and the lack of this participation is what caused negative reactions. The case of Lanzo Valley, as other small municipalities in Piedmont, shows that episodes of supposed racism in mountain areas are often driven by fear and the lack of citizens’ involvement and participation in the decision to set up a reception project” (Turin, Informant 2).*

As pointed out by several interviewees, in times of **pandemic** there is the risk that racial hatred increases. “We must be careful that the lack of broadband, income and the worsening of social tensions do not leave more space for populist policies. It is necessary to prevent it with careful instruments that have not yet existed in Italy” (National level, Informant 3), says a member of a social cooperative.

ASSESSMENT OF ECONOMIC AND LABOUR INTEGRATION POLICIES

TERRITORIAL CLUSTERS OF MIGRATION: THE CHALLENGES OF VERTICAL AND HORIZONTAL COORDINATION

Interviewees indicated sectoral and territorial clusters as qualifying elements of TCNs participation in the Italian labour market. This is the case of jobs in the tourism and agricultural sectors that are crucial for rural and mountain areas: *“The economic system of Italian inner areas finds tourism and agriculture the two main historical pillars (Informant 3). Here, “the support of immigration to the local economic and social structure is even stronger” (Social enterprise, Informant 4).* As a result, informants describe **migration as a highly “territorialized” phenomenon**, requiring regional approaches to labour integration policies, built on local labour market specificities:

“Obviously, territories in which communities carrying out certain specific tasks settle need very different policy responses” (Country level interview, Informant 5).

To answer the need for **vertical coordination**, since 2015 the Directorate-General of the Ministry of Labour and Social policies sealed Regional plans of integrated action with 17 Italian Regions to coordinate the management of European funds¹⁷⁶. The Plans worked positively in terms of providing a mid-term planning (2014-2020) and fostering an integrated approach in the provision of services targeting socio-economic inclusion for TCNs. On the other hand, the effectiveness of their implementation and the ability to draw on third-party, mainly European, funds to enhance integration activities in the Region depended heavily on the experience, organizational culture and skills of local administrations. Since 2019, coordination between the Ministry for labour and social policies and the local dimension moved closer to the territories, through

¹⁷⁶ Piani integrati di intervento regionali. For the plan drafted by Piedmont, see

<http://www.integrazionemigranti.gov.it/leregioni/Documents/Piani%20di%20intervento%20FAMI/Piemonte-Piano%20di%20Intervento%20Regionale.pdf>

cooperation protocols involving Metropolitan Cities, Regional capitals and cities where the migratory presence is concentrated. This is promising as Metropolitan cities have their own employment services making it easier to coordinate social and labour interventions.

A significant bottleneck in the implementation is the **horizontal coordination** between different departments. “This is a fundamental criticality: the social speaks little and badly with labour and vocational training, plus we have further subdivisions in many regions between training and labour services” (Informant 5). This points to the need to include migrants in qualifying training pathways that would accompany them into the world of work through integrated actions involving labour, vocational training and social affairs departments.

RECOGNITION OF COMPETENCES, VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING

Informants point to the difficulties for TCNs to have their skills recognized: “There is a difficulty in making the skills of these people valued and this is an obstacle to decent work, that remains the main road to integration” (Informant 5). Lack of recognition of TCNs qualifications reinforces the clusterization/segmentation of TCNs participation in the Italian labour market: “Immigrants have the skills to be employed in different sectors; labour integration is just an issue of training and planning the economy” (National level, SNAI, Informant 7). A local level informant based in South Tyrol, further notes “There is an over-representation of foreigners in the sectors related to fundamental economy, because they are the only sectors that foreigners can access, and this should not be looked at as a model. (Coordinator of reception services for ASRs in South Tyrol, Informant 1).

This points to the **need for more flexible and effective recognition of competences** on the one hand, and for **vocational education and training** on the other: “*We need training and supporting activities to enhance the great development potential of migrants*” (Social enterprise, Informant 4). Informant noted that public initiatives offering vocational training for highly demanded profiles, such as nurses, failed to keep into account the opportunity to integrate the skills of TCNs already working in this field. Linguistic aspects certainly matter and are further complicated in plurilinguistic settings such as South Tyrol where the high demand for labour force, coupled with strong social networks facilitate labour integration: “*Even if there are currently no policies that promote the recruitment of migrants in the industrial sector, labour integration works a lot with word-of-mouth between TCNs*” (Informant 11). Further on: “*Job placement here occurs spontaneously, especially in industry, agriculture and tourism. Farmers turn to CAS operators to find staff for apple harvesting, especially this*

year, due to the lack of workers from Eastern Europe due to Covid-19. The local inhabitants turn to us personally, this is the advantage of living in a rural area (Informant 10). Yet a job does not equate with social integration, due to language barriers: “From a linguistic point of view, bilingualism complicates matters: foreigners who learn German first because of the working environment, then find themselves in difficulty with the Italian exam. In addition, German is not enough, because the dialect is spoken in rural areas” (Informant 10).

Positive assessment is expressed for measures that reach people directly: “Great satisfaction comes from internships that guide TCNs into the labour market: this quickly improves the language; develops social networks, soft skills, security and dignity” (Informant 5).

HOUSING REMAINS A KEY OBSTACLE

Even for hired people, the **housing problem** remains a key obstacle for integration of TCNS and it affects not only the main urban centers but also remote valleys, where rents are very high. “We talked about it with the administration, with the districts, but there is not much interest from the public body: if the person loses his job, another one will be hired” (Informant 10). This problem derives from the combination of the scarcity of residential buildings on the one hand, and discriminatory attitudes on the other and forces some companies rent houses for their employees. “There is a tendency not to want to see that many people are not willing to rent their house to a foreign person” (Informant 10). Workers’ houses have been created in major cities, but not in rural places where there would be the need to host both workers employed in the tourism sector and seasonal workers: “I met people who, while picking apples, slept in their cars” (Informant 10). Social housing proves to be of little help and are not an option for particularly vulnerable groups such as holders of humanitarian protection: “People with humanitarian protection are not entitled to social housing. Only those with subsidiary and international protection can access it (Informant 10).

THE IMPACT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMICS

When it comes to measures in place for containing the impact of the economic crisis provoked by the Covid-19 pandemics, interviewee agree that TCNS are the most fragile in the labour market, as already demonstrated

in the aftermaths of the 2011-2012 crisis. They are most likely to have fixed-term contracts and to be employed in sectors that exclude smart-working arrangements. Informants then point to the **need to consider the long-term effects**: “We will suffer the effects of Covid-19 in the forthcoming months. We are buffering with welfare measures, like the extension of the redundancy fund or prohibition of dismissal” (National level, Informant 5).

The limits to mobility caused by the Covid-19 pandemics caused labour shortages especially in the agricultural field. The **regularization of TCNs from May till August 2020** is regarded as a “positive thing for some people who had slipped into illegality” (Informant 10). What is perceived as innovative and positive is the provision included in the regularization that also TCNs could activate the request. However, there were problems due to legal uncertainties that in some case prove hard to be clarified: *“We organized two seminars to clarify some questions, but the lawyer himself said that there were points of ambiguity.”* (Coordinator of reception services for ASRs in South Tyrol, Informant 10). Even the technical procedures to file the request could sometimes not be properly carried out by the specialized staff of the fiscal centres (*patronati*). This ambiguity favoured employers, such as local farmers’ leagues, who have sometimes abused their position imposing their own interpretation of the decree. In many cases, TCNs have been forced to assume the entire cost of the emersion: *“few employers were willing to take the initiative and assume the costs for the request”* (Informant 10). In worse cases, TCNs have been blackmailed and had to pay extra-fees to employers in order to gain their support in filing the request of emersion.

1.4 CONCLUDING REMARKS ON SOCIAL POLICIES (WP3)

The dynamics of social integration in mountain and rural areas appear at a first analysis less complex than in urban and metropolitan contexts: the relatively small numbers of people, the possibility of face-to-face interactions, the persisting communitarian dimension, are all factors that to a certain extent seem to limit the possible social tensions between old and new inhabitants.

Yet, as the most critical cases of the reception system for refugees and asylum seekers show, social integration is only possible where civic and collective participation dynamics are activated. In the absence of this, the risk is as much that of the creation of separate communities living in the same territory as the possible manifestation of conflicts, often provoked also by xenophobic political forces, coming from outside the contexts considered. Therefore, innovative tools are needed to foster migrants' real participation in the social life of local communities, overcoming institutional forms of the past and developing different channels of involvement, focused for example on shared care of the territory or on the promotion of forms of socio-economic cooperation between new and old inhabitants, as the community cooperatives.

Although migrants represent - according to the interviewees' shared opinion and considering the data available - an indisputable resource for rural and mountain economies and societies, policies for the re-launch of these territories usually do not focus on the role of foreigners to fight depopulation and population ageing, to maintain essential services in remote areas, to foster social and cultural innovation processes. In Italy, on the other hand, there is a general lack of policies to revitalize internal areas (with the exception of the SNAI), just as it would be necessary to invest in active demographic policies to counter the decline that is affecting many mountain and rural regions of the country.

The demographic theme and the issue of territorial inequalities must therefore be put in relation with migration policies (and new peopling, more in general), within a vision of development of the country centred on a mutual relationship between the centre and the peripheries, and between the different populations living in these territories.

The Covid-19 pandemic undoubtedly represents a new threat with respect to the prospects of inclusion of migrants in rural and mountain regions, both in economic and labour terms (they are in fact among the most fragile categories affected by the economic crisis), and with respect to ghettoization phenomena (this is the case of asylum seekers forced to stay in remote locations) and possible intolerance or open racism (in the face of political forces that identify foreigners as a scapegoat).

More than ever, therefore, action is needed to combat these phenomena, within the framework of more general policies aimed at fostering the resilience of rural and mountain communities as a whole, including the foreign component.

GOOD PRACTICES FOR SOCIAL POLICIES

1. **MorusOnlus** is an association born from the union of Cooperativa Babel and Cooperativa Pessinetto, that were already managing two CAS projects in Val di Lanzo (MCTurin) since 2014 and 2015. They hosted 18 ASRs in Ceres and 42 in Pessinetto and involved them in different activities related to the social development of territory. For example: the foundation of 'CoroMoro', a mixed choir in local dialects and Mandingo, a football team and African fashion exhibitions. All these activities were carried out by volunteers. Thanks to this experience it seems that the territory has become progressively more available and open with respect to reception initiatives (Fieri 2017).
2. The integration-and social work of the **House of Solidarity** in Brixen (South Tyrol) offers housing for migrants/refugees and local people in difficult situations. Three employees and 15 volunteers are involved in the initiative since 2002, which hosted 120 vulnerable people every year and satisfy their basic needs. They do that without public funds, bureaucracy, political, religious or other dependence.

The project "The 6th continent" of the House of Solidarity won first prize at the Alpine Pluralism Award in the category "Social Integration"¹⁷⁷.

3. **HIPPY**¹⁷⁸ is a programme that aims to support parents with children from 3 to 6 years old living in the territory of the Isarco Valley (South Tyrol). Services are addressed in particular to families with a migration background but also to who may live in situations of structural and/or social disadvantage. The objectives of the programme developed by IMPULS Deutschland Stiftung e.V. are the promotion of equal training opportunities for children, strengthening their language skills, the support of their cognitive, motor and socio-emotional development and cultural inclusion regardless of the children's belonging to a specific social stratum. The children are supported in learning German language and acquiring pre-school skills that help them to develop their writing and reading skills with a view to future schooling.
4. **InterAzioni in Piemonte 2**¹⁷⁹ is a European project funded by AMIF 2014-2020 and carry out by Piedmont region in cooperation with other private and public entities. The project (2018-2020) aims to answer the needs of people of foreign origin through a strategy based on the coordination of different policies, including the adaptation of school system to multicultural contexts; the increased accessibility to services for integration and the strengthening of information services through territorial channels.

¹⁷⁷ For further details: <https://www.alpine-space.eu/project-news-details/en/4119>

¹⁷⁸ The official website page of the Autonomous Province:

http://www.provincia.bz.it/famiglia-sociale-comunita/integrazione/esempi-di-buona-pratica.asp?bpb_action=4&bpb_article_id=642753

¹⁷⁹ The Official website page of Piedmont Region:

<https://www.regione.piemonte.it/web/temi/fondi-progetti-europei/fondo-asilo-migrazione-integrazione-fami/integrazione-piemonte/impact-consolidare-pianificazione-dellintegrazione-migranti>

5. In 2014, the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies and the CONI (Italian National Olympic Committee) signed a Programme Agreement for the implementation of activities aimed at fostering the integration of migrant citizens through sport and at combating forms of discrimination and intolerance¹⁸⁰. The Agreement was renewed in 2015, 2016 and 2017. Schools, professionals and associations are involved. In 2018 an educational-information campaign has been launched in schools, called "Champions of Fair Play", in order to stimulate moments of reflection on integration and encourage class participation in the creation of graphic and textual works on the theme; At university level, a pilot teaching module on the themes of sport and integration has been created, on an experimental basis, within the Degree Course in Motor Sciences at the University of Rome Tor Vergata; For the sports' societies and federations, a public campaign called "Fratelli di Sport" has been set up and a "Good Practice Call" has been promoted to enhance the value of social work.
6. In Ormea (Piedmont), the agricultural and **community cooperative "La volpe e il mirtillo"** (The Fox and the Blueberry) was founded in 2018 as a result of a reception project - opened as a CAS - that was initially opposed by the local population. Thanks to the Professional Forestry School in Cuneo, about twenty asylum seekers, mostly from sub-Saharan Africa, have learned the basic rules of safety at work and the practice of using the necessary tools to clean the chestnut groves. Over time, these results have cooled residents' anger and suspicion towards immigrants. The project provided a path of integration in the green sector with the funding of a "community cooperative" that currently employs TCNs with the national employment contract in agriculture.
7. **Unitedbz** is an integration project for the education of refugees and asylum seekers in South Tyrol. The Project was born in 2016 on the initiative of professors and employees of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, in collaboration with institutions and voluntary associations in South Tyrol that deal with the processes of reception of migrants. It gives asylum seekers and refugees the opportunity to attend the courses offered by unibz for four semesters, sitting its exams as extracurricular students, i.e., students who are not regularly enrolled in the university. Candidates who have attended school for

¹⁸⁰ All further details and information on the Programme Agreement are available here:

<http://www.integrazionemigranti.gov.it/Progetti-e-azioni/Pagine/Sport-Integrazione.aspx>

at least 12 years and are in contact with an association active in the area can participate in the project. The selected students can attend courses free of charge and the credits they obtain can be recognized if they enroll in one of the university's degree programmes in the future.

1.5 CONCLUDING REMARKS ON ECONOMIC AND LABOUR INTEGRATION POLICIES (WP4)

The **Italian legislation on work visas** maintains the possibility of legal entry and stay of TCNs below the needs of the Italian labour market, contributing to relegate them in the informal economy. On the one hand, this increases the risk of exploitation, reducing their chances of socio-economic integration in the long term. On the other hand, it feeds the basin of exploitation of organised crime, subtracting a considerable amount of economic resources, taxes by workers and companies, from public finances.

The Covid-19 epidemic has also highlighted the strong **dependence of certain sectors of the economy, particularly agriculture, on the contribution of foreign labour**. The emergency measures implemented to foster the emergence of employment relationships proved insufficient and further highlighted the exposure of foreign workers to work-related blackmailing: in many cases, TCNs had to pay additional amounts to employers in order to obtain the necessary support to regularise their position.

Due to the complexity of the procedures for the **recognition of qualifications and skills**, TCNs are often forced to work in positions for which they are over-qualified. This implies the waste of their skills on the one hand and relegates TCNs in low-qualified positions from where they can hardly aspire to improve their social position. As pointed out by interviewees, highly qualified TCNs often find a career path in the social sector, particularly in the reception of asylum seekers and refugees reception sector, working as cultural mediators. The reduction of funds for this sector, following the reform introduced by Law 132/2018, has dismantled many jobs in this field, reducing the quality of services offered and eliminating this important channel of employment for many highly qualified foreign workers.

The public offer of **education and vocational training** fails to meet the needs of the labour market on the one hand, and the specific needs of foreigners on the other. This has prompted many private companies to seek mediation from the private sector. In particular, temporary employment agencies intervene to qualify TCNs to meet the demand for specific profiles. A significant challenge here can be identified in the lack of coordination between different sectors of the public administration. To answer this, some territories (including South Tyrol), the experimentation of innovative forms of institutional coordination is ongoing, but their effectiveness will have to be assessed over time.

The sectoral and territorial segmentation of TCNs settlement across the country indicates the need to strengthen regional approaches to labour integration policies, based on the analysis of regional and local labour market specificities. **Vertical coordination** between the central state and local authorities have been tested with the Regional agreements implemented since 2015 between the General Directorate of the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies on the one hand, and the Regions on the other. New agreements with local authorities are currently being implemented. This form of coordination is positively evaluated as it adapts the interventions to the specific needs of the territories and an integrated approach in the provision of services aimed at the social and labour inclusion of TCNs. However, there are some difficulties.

First of all, **capacity and commitment vary across Regions** when it comes to activate effective interventions and to make full use of available European funds. This depends on the considerable gap in the management capacities of local authorities, which could be remedied by activating more exchanges of good practices between virtuous administrations and those lagging behind. Strengthening the competences of local administrations shall be tackled in a long-term planning perspective. Beyond capacity-building, the political orientation of Regional governments is to be kept in mind as it exerts significant impact in a decentralized country such as Italy. Changes in the political orientation has sometimes reversed the virtuous paths undertaken until then, with consequent waste of resources and frustration of what was previously constructed.

Secondly, **diversity of approaches persists among the Italian Regions**. While some of them pursue an approach to integration pathways oriented towards the achievement of autonomy by TCNs (through the inclusion in training and apprenticeship activities that allow to access the labour market), other Regions go after policies more oriented towards economic and social assistance, with limited view to social and economic integration in the medium and long term.

Lack of **horizontal coordination at the local level** proves to be an obstacle to the implementation of social and labour market integration policies. Different organisational cultures across specific departments (e.g. Social Policies, Employment services, Education and Training, Housing Services) hinders dialogue and the identification of common objectives. Here it is worth recalling that capacities and possibilities of internal coordination vary significantly between urban contexts and small towns. While cities are in the position to activate integrated plans and forms of coordination among different public services, rural and mountain

municipalities depend on neighbouring urban centres for services such as employment offices and vocational training centres. On the other hand, interviews point to the fact that in rural and mountain municipalities, intermediation is less time consuming, as it is mainly based on existing social networks and word of mouth. Proximity and personal contact in these cases compensates at least partially, for the lack of direct capacity to provide services.

The issue of **housing** emerges as crucial for job integration: the scarce availability of housing solutions, high costs and the persistence of discriminatory attitudes towards foreigners prevent them from finding decent and sustainable solutions. This can even become an obstacle to maintaining the employment relationship. Experiences of "worker housing" and co-housing have been found to be effective but remain quantitatively insufficient.

With regard to **reception services for asylum seekers and refugees**, scientific literature and interviews agree in identifying a wide disparity between the integration services offered by the two different reception systems in the country. While SPRAR/SIPROIMI projects homogeneously promote territorialized integration pathways, CAS centres perform differently, depending on the actors coordinating them and their dimensions. As they are established upon decision of the Ministry of Interior, in many cases they are perceived as imposition, raising frustration in peripheral municipalities as a consequence of the lack of participation and consultation. Law 132/2018 considerably reduced the resources available for reception projects targeting asylum seekers and refugees. This led many actors of the third sector to withdraw from this field of activity, despite their consolidated experience accumulated over the years. The closure of reception projects located in rural and mountain areas reduced the income of small municipalities, the jobs that had been activated in this area and the social innovation initiatives experimented within them.

GOOD PRACTICES FOR LABOUR INTEGRATION POLICIES

Good practices in the field of labour integration concern the improvement of working and life conditions, the organization of training activities as well as other services to boost the economic autonomy and integration of migrants.

1. **Prima Accoglienza Stagionali (PAS)** has built a network of territorial services to offer decent accommodation to TCNs seasonal workers in Saluzzo, a small town in Piedmont known fruit production. Since 2018, the partnership between public and private sector enabled the accommodation and monitored the living and working conditions of the migrants (Ippolito et al, 2020: 9-14). Due to the Covid-19 emergency, the PAS has not opened this year, causing complications for some workers who have no other accommodations.

Since most of the TCNs are employed in low-skilled jobs where their expertise and potential remain often unexpressed, the enhancement of their competences and training activities is another crucial aspect to boost migrants economic integration in the territory:

2. Financed by AMIF and the European Social Fund, **PUOI** is a national project by the Italian Ministry of Labour and Social Policies providing integrated services for social and occupational integration to holders of international and humanitarian protection and Unaccompanied Minors.¹⁸¹ It provides mentoring, guidance and job search assistance, financial support, certification of skills and a 6-month extracurricular internship.
3. The **EUMINT** project developed experimental tools supporting labour integration of ASRs in Südtirol-Alto Adige (IT), Tirol (AT), Friuli Venezia Giulia (IT), Kärnten (AT), Veneto (IT) and Trentino (IT).¹⁸² In collaboration with Provincial Districts and local authorities, innovative evaluation check for practical, hard and soft skills were developed and tested in South Tyrol.
4. **Job fair/Fair Job** was a 2-days event offering job interviews between 60 refugees and local enterprises taken place in South Tyrol in December 2018. Organized by Assoimprenditori, the

¹⁸¹ PUOI project website: <https://www.lavoro.gov.it/notizie/Pagine/Politiche-attive-del-lavoro-al-via-il-progetto-PUOI-Protezione-Unita-a-Obiettivo-Integrazione.aspx> [Accessed November 20, 2020]

¹⁸² EUMINT project webpage: <http://www.eurac.edu/it/research/projects/Pages/projectdetail4477.aspx> [Accessed November 20, 2020]

association representing manufacturing and service companies in South Tyrol. About 130-140 job interviews were held and some of the refugees had been hired in the following weeks.

In line with the objective of achieving economic autonomy of migrants, good practices in TCNs **entrepreneurship support** have been found at national and local level.

5. The **FUTURAE project**, started in July 2020, is financed by the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies and coordinated by Unioncamere Nazionale.¹⁸³ It supports the start-up of migrants-owned enterprises. It involves 14 Italian provinces and offers a guided path for the opening of new companies. The service starts from a first orientation and information support and then provides training courses and accompaniment in the drafting of the business plan. In MCTurin, FUTURAE project kicked-off in November 2020: they identified the first 20 beneficiaries and started the 56 hours of training course.
6. The **Colibrì project**¹⁸⁴, in the Valle Sacra (a small valley in the upper part of the MCTurin), involved the Turin Chamber of Commerce for the development of new businesses in the area. With the coordination of the *Rete Italiana di Cultura Popolare*, business ideas were identified among natives and new inhabitants, including ASRs, and supported through the use *social bonds*. The Projects involved a relevant number of local partners. Among them: municipalities, the Diocese of Ivrea, the Canavese GAL, Coldiretti, Confcooperative Piemonte, Confartigianato and the territorial consortium of Social Services..

¹⁸³ FUTURAE project webpage: <https://www.unioncamere.gov.it/V1P42AOC4344S2689/imprenditoria-di-migranti-progetto-futurae.htm> [Accessed November 20, 2020]

¹⁸⁴ COLIBRI' project web page: <https://www.portaledeisaperi.org/valle-sacra.html#progetto> [Accessed November 20, 2020]

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MATILDE

7. NORWAY

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1.1 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC RELATED POLICIES REGARDING TCNS INTEGRATION AND IMPACT IN THE COUNTRY AND ITS SELECTED REMOTE AREA(S)

Following the guidelines for assessment of policy measures, we report in this first section on our identification of existing policies that directly and indirectly affect migrants' integration in remote and rural settings. We focus mainly on policies that affect integration of refugee immigrants as this is the focus of our case studies, and the dominant group of TCNs in rural Norway. We understand policies as government white papers, formal acts and legislation and strategic documents on regional or municipal levels. The selected policies (see the appended taxonomy) were also guided by what informants highlighted as prominent policies in the interviews. We present first central policies at the national level, and secondly identified strategic documents at the regional level.

RELEVANT LAWS ON IMMIGRATION AT THE NATIONAL LEVEL

The relevant laws included are the Immigration act (Utlendingsloven), the Norwegian Nationality act (Statsborgerloven), and the Introduction act (Introduksjonsloven). Our interviews pointed out the need to also include the bill for a new Integration law which is planned to take effect from January 2021. We also give a short brief on act's regulating the social welfare system, labor market policies and education.

IMMIGRATION ACT

The immigration act has been active since 2008 and regulates foreigners' access to Norway. The overall immigration and refugee policy are largely regulated through this act and related legal documents. The Act provides the basis for regulating and controlling the entry and exit of foreign nationals and their stay within the national borders, in accordance with Norwegian immigration policy and international obligations. Political priorities and goals on immigration are continuously changing in accordance with external circumstances and the direction of the political leadership. In the aftermath of the refugee crises with increased refugee and asylum seekers influx in 2015, the government has followed a stricter immigration policy for asylum seekers and refugees (see Brochmann et al.2017).

THE NORWEGIAN NATIONALITY ACT

The Norwegian Nationality Act is the law that determines how people can obtain citizenship and become Norwegian citizens, and how the citizenship can be lost. The act contains provisions on obtaining citizenship at birth, at adoption and upon application. Applicants need to clarify their identity, have a residence permit, have lived in Norway for at least 7 of the last 10 years, and intend to stay in the country. Furthermore, applicants need to meet requirements for participation in a Norwegian-language course. New from 2020 is the opportunity to be both a Norwegian citizen and a citizen of another country at the same time.

Figure 2: The Process of refugee settlement, presented in Høibjerg, G.R. (in press).

ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

The complete immigration process involves several government agencies. Below is an overview of the different agencies and their roles in the immigration and settlement process for UNHCR resettlement refugees and asylum seekers. (The model is adapted from a report prepared by the directorate of integration and diversity (IMDi) and appears in a PhD thesis currently prepared for publication (Høibjerg, G.R., in press).

THE INTRODUCTION ACT

The Introduction Act was introduced in 2003. The law has been the government's most important tool for integrating refugees arriving in Norway. The purpose of the act is to strengthen the opportunity for newly arrived immigrants to participate in working life and society, and to support their financial independence. The purpose is also to facilitate immigrants process of becoming acquainted with the Norwegian language, culture and social life.

The program consists of three main components (§4):

- to provide basic skills in the Norwegian language.
- to provide basic insight into Norwegian society
- prepare for participation in working life

The act defines a minimum of 600 hours of teaching in Norwegian and Norwegian culture and society (point nr. 1 and 2), and those who participate in the program must participate in vocational training or education directed towards getting a job and thus strengthen the economic independence. The municipalities are obliged to provide the introduction program in line with the national guidelines, and settled refugees have the rights and obligation to participate. Participants receive a fixed monthly salary (introduction benefits) and the benefit is cut in case of invalid absence.

The municipalities are compensated for the expenses they have in implementing the Introduction Act. There are several different types of compensation, and the financing scheme has been changed several times, most

recently for 2020, where the integration compensation to municipalities (per settled immigrant) was changed from 5 years to 3 years.

INTEGRATION ACT

From January 1st 2021 the Introduction Act is replaced by the Integration Act as part of a major integration reform. The new act places more emphasis on education, training and work, where expectations and responsibilities to national authorities, regional/ county authorities and municipalities is more clearly specified. Requirements and expectations for immigrants are also made clearer and somewhat stricter. In the new Integration Act, the counties regional responsibility for the integration work is legislated.

This imposes the county to develop plans for the qualification of immigrants, recommends how many immigrants each municipality shall settled, and provides immigrants career guidance, and training in the Norwegian language and social studies for participants in upper secondary education. New is also that asylum seekers who live in reception centres are required to participate in training in Norwegian language, culture and values. The course emphasizes that the Norwegian society is built on humanistic values such as freedom, equality and respect for the individual.¹⁸⁵

Asylum seekers in reception centres has now also both obligations and rights to mapping of his/ her competence, and preparations of an “individual plan”.

We also need to mention the Temporary act on adaptations to the Introduction Act. This act was put in action the 26th of May 2020 to remedy consequences of the Covid 19 pandemic for participants in the introduction

¹⁸⁵ For more details on the description of the course:

<https://www.kompetansenorge.no/English/norwegian-culture-and-values--training-course-for-asylum-seekers/>

program. The act contains measures to strengthen integration, related to language skills, prolonged integration and introduction program, and secondary education.

POLICIES WHICH IMPACT IMMIGRATION AND INTEGRATION

LABOUR MARKET POLICIES AND SOCIAL POLICIES

The public social security system in Norway is called the Norwegian National Insurance Scheme (folketrygden). As a rule all persons resident in Norway are members of the Norwegian Insurance Scheme. To be entitled to benefits, you must be a member of the Norwegian National Insurance Scheme.

This applies to:

- all benefits from the labour and welfare services
- health service benefits (treatment by a doctor, psychologist or expenditure on medicines of major importance in long-term use).

If you have legal employment in Norway, you will, as a rule, become a member of the National Insurance scheme from your first working day even if you are not deemed to be resident here. Membership is automatic.

¹⁸⁶

The responsibility for labour market and social policies rests with the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs. The Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration (NAV) is the agency mainly responsible for the implementation

¹⁸⁶ For more details: <https://www.imdi.no/globalassets/dokumenter/andre-filer/new-in-norway-engelsk>

of these policies. The NAV office in each municipality provides most of the main social security benefits and services available to residents.

The social service Act: The purpose of this act is to improve the living conditions of disadvantaged citizens; contribute to social and economic security, and promote the transition to work, social inclusion and active participation in society. The overall social policy objectives defined for municipal services and in NAV is open for discretion in decision making and municipal prioritizations. The social services and social security benefits provide vital supplement to the introduction program because it gives financial security if participants are not able to gain employment after completing the program, and in other transition periods. The Social service act also provides an opportunity to fund children's participation in leisure activities if the parents do not have the financial resources. This is important for integration of families with children in rural municipalities (Solheim & Røhnebæk, 2019).

The NAV offices also administers a range of labour market measures, such as the qualification programme and the programme 'job opportunity'. Immigrants aged between 18 and 55 years who require basic qualifications, who have no links with working life and who are not covered by existing schemes are in the target group for this measure. The NAV offices administer also other labour market measures enabling formal educational programs, vocational training through internships and various forms of guidance and follow-up.

HEALTH CARE

Municipalities are responsible for providing necessary health services for their inhabitants – including immigrants, refugees and asylum seekers. Among other things, the municipalities shall provide:

- public health centres for children and young people, and school health service,
- care during pregnancy and post-natal care,
- a general practitioner (GP) service,
- an accident and emergency service,
- rehabilitation,
- health and care services, such as home nursing care, personal assistance, nursing homes and respite services.

County authorities are responsible for ensuring that dental health care services, including specialist services, are available to all permanent or temporary residents of the country. The regional health authorities shall ensure that everyone who lives or is staying temporarily in the health region has access to health services at hospitals and from specialists.¹⁸⁷

ACT RELATING TO PRIMARY AND SECONDARY EDUCATION AND TRAINING

The Act regulates primary, lower secondary and upper secondary education and training. The act also applies to education and training designed specifically for adults, for which the municipality or county authority is responsible.

The law regulates adults' right to primary and lower secondary education, which includes immigrants with legal residence in Norway. The county council is responsible for upper secondary education (from about 16 years and up) while the municipalities are assigned responsibility for primary and lower secondary education (10 year of education, from 6 years of age). The county's facilitation of secondary education is divided into two main directions. One further education course that qualifies for admission to University / college (3 year), and vocational education course that leads to vocational education and possibly a craft certificate. In the latter education, there are 2 years in school and two consecutive years in practical training in a workplace.

STRATEGIES AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL

There are various strategic planning documents developed at the regional, county council level (see policy taxonomy). These plans have both direct and indirect implications for integration of immigrants in the rural and remote municipalities located in Innlandet. The documents highlight the problems of population decline in many of these municipalities and highlight the importance of ensuring immigration to curb the negative effects of aging and declining populations. The strategy document for Innlandet (2020-2024) highlights inclusion (in broad terms) as one of four strategic areas. Also, strategic documents related to transport, infrastructure, skills and competence, and regional economic development have implications for integration in the municipalities,

¹⁸⁷ For more details: <https://www.imdi.no/globalassets/dokumenter/andre-filer/new-in-norway-engelsk>

and immigration is mentioned as running theme throughout these documents even though they are not devoted merely to immigration and integration.

The regional policies in Norway have placed emphasis on keeping settlement in rural and remote areas throughout the country. This is also reflected in the geographical dispersal policies which have guided the refugee settlement policies. This means that the regions and rural municipalities have important and comprehensive responsibilities when it comes to immigration and integration of (refugee) immigrants. The municipalities have also a tradition for strong self-governance, and the national policies tend to provide leeway.

1.2 OVERVIEW ON EXISTING ANALYSES AND ASSESSMENTS OF ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL POLICIES

This part of the policy brief is meant to briefly synthesize Norwegian research on economic and social policies that impact immigration and integration at the municipal level, especially in rural areas. To gain an overview of the literature, we have searched for existing meta-studies and literature reviews. This gave a few results (i.e. Brochmann et al., 2005; Brochmann et al., 2017 [green paper] and Djuve and Kavli, 2015; Midtbøen, 2017; Strøm et al., 2015). Reviews of existing knowledge are otherwise found within and as part of empirical research papers and reports. There is a comprehensive body of commissioned research on immigration and integration in Norway, an overview of the field is provided through green papers such as the official Norwegian report “Integration and trust” (Brochmann et al. 2017). Somewhat simplified, we can say that evaluations of specific policies and programs are largely carried out through commissioned research, and Statistics Norway. Scholarly debates on integration, inclusion, exclusion and social tensions and racism have been more dominant at the universities and especially within social anthropology and sociology (Midtbøen, 2017). However, from being a relatively marginal topic confined to specific disciplines (such as anthropology), immigration and integration issues have become a more mainstream field of research, increasingly dominated by sociology and economics (Midtbøen, 2017). This implies that the field of research has become more open and pluralistic, but also comprehensive and fragmented, which makes it difficult to synthesize existing knowledge.

As the aim of this analysis is to summarize findings from existing assessments of economic and social policies, it is mainly the recent commissioned research that evaluate specific programs and policies that we are focusing on. Moreover, we focus on areas most relevant for the overarching aims of Matilde, i.e. immigration and integration in rural areas, and as related to TCNs. This makes the government introduction program provided for refugees and persons granted asylum the most important policy, and we place emphasis on summarizing research on this, which is also related to language tutoring, education, qualification and labour market policies.

THE INTRODUCTION PROGRAM

The introduction program (see description in section 1) has been in receipt of a range of evaluations and assessments since it was introduced in 2003. It has been a stated target since 2011 that at least 70 percent of the participations should be enrolled in employment or education one year after completing the program. The municipalities have struggled to meet this target, yet there has been considerable variation in terms performance across municipalities and regions. While some have performed above the set target, several municipalities have performed considerably below the 70 percent aim. (To get an idea of employment rates in Norway, numbers from Statistics Norway from 2018 show that registered employment among those in the age 20-66 was 76,2 percent for the total population, and 78,5 percent for the population excluding immigrants. Registered employment for immigrants in total were 66,6 percent).

Various research reports have focused on how the results can be improved, and various projects have aimed to understand factors that lead to programs with good results (Brochmann et al., 2017; Djuve et al., 2017).

For instance, a comprehensive commissioned study, carried out in 2015-2017, aimed to understand ‘what works’ and for whom regarding the introduction program through a mixed methods study (Djuve et al., 2017). The report gives nuanced conclusions. On one hand the study finds that there is no doubt that central measures of the program such as language training, user involvement, work-orientation and full-day programs clearly contribute to integration in the sense that it facilitates the participants’ transitions to work. This is found through comparisons and analysis of variations in the municipalities’ implementation of the program and their varied results. The analysis shows also that the impact of different kinds of measures depend on the characteristics of participants, such as age or educational background. This means that tailoring of measures to individual participants is important for the programme to be effective. The report also points to the needs for new kinds of measures which contributes to provide participants with formal competence in relation to the introduction program. Since the thresholds for entering the Norwegian labour market is high, and formal competence and education is increasingly demanded, this may be a necessary strategy for ensuring long term labour market inclusion among settled refugees. A concrete strategy discussed is to develop vocational education programs adapted to immigrants that does not have Norwegian as their first language. (This is also discussed and called for in interviews, summarized in section 3).

Statistics Norway also run yearly studies (from 2007-2020) of what participants in the introduction program do one year after completion. The last study (Lunde and Lysen, 2020) examines the status of participants enrolled in the program in the period 2013-2017. This shows that 58-63 percent are employed or in education one year after the program, but it also shows that the percentage increases in the subsequent years. 67 percent of participants that completed the program in 2013 were employed or in education five years later. A higher percentage of men compared to women gain employment or start education after the program, but the difference is reduced in the coming years. (For the total population, 74 percent of the women age 20-66 were registered as employed in last quarter of 2018, while 78,3 of the men were registered as employed. For the population excluding immigrants, 76,7 percent of women were registered as employed, compared to 80,2 of the men. For immigrants, 70,4 percent of the men were registered as employed, and 62.3 percent of the women.

Even though the introduction program does not reach the set target outcome of 70 percent, it is nevertheless deemed a relatively successful policy measure for integration and labour market inclusion (Djuve et al., 2017). What contributes to good results have been explored through several studies. For instance, even though there are national guidelines and a formal act that regulates and directs the implementation of the introduction programme, the municipalities have leeway to choose between different organizational models, and there exists a large variety of different local models (Røhnebæk & Eide, 2016; Tronstad, 2015). The effects of differences in formal organizational models has been examined, for instance according to the public service office that organizes the program. Statistical analysis concludes that differences in formal organizational models cannot (statistically) explain differences in results across municipalities (Blom & Enes, 2015; Rambøll, 2011; Tronstad, 2015). It is still found through various studies that the way in which different actors collaborate and coordinate measures in the program has implications for the results (Djuve & Kavli, 2015; Djuve et al., 2017; Rambøll, 2011; Røhnebæk & Eide, 2016; Skutlaberg et al, 2014; Tronstad, 2015). Hence, the internal collaboration between different government agencies has gained considerable attention in previous studies, but the external inter-organizational collaborations, such as with third sector organizations and businesses, have gained less attention. This kind of research is called for (Djuve & Kavli, 2015; Hernes & Tronstad, 2014) and represents a knowledge gap. Djuve et al. (2017) finds that municipalities with formal collaborative relations with volunteer organizations seem to have a positive effect on the program. Moreover, Djuve & Kavli (2015) exemplify how municipalities that collaborate with volunteer organizations help participants to establish broader social networks.

Collaborations with business and employers have also gained limited attention. This knowledge gap is highlighted by Søholt et al (2014) in a study focusing on immigration and labour market inclusion in a regional perspective. The study explores the intersection between regional labour market and integration policies and points to potential synergies across the policy areas. The report highlights the importance of collaboration and partnerships across the public, private and third sector as means for regional development and for facilitating immigrant networks and building of social capital (regarded as prerequisite for employment).

LABOUR MARKET POLICIES

Labour market measures aim at improving the individual's chances of finding employment through qualification and work training. A broad range of studies examine the effects of such measures, but studies focusing specifically on effects on immigrant groups are more limited. However, a study reviewing existing studies synthesizes findings from six Nordic studies on place-then-train approaches aimed at immigrants (Strøm et al.,2015). 'Place-then-train' are measures targeted at employers and imply that participants are placed in the workplace and receive training and follow-up there. The main findings indicate first that wage subsidies and direct employment programmes most likely increase the probability of employment compared to no measures for unemployed immigrants, but special employment programmes do not seem to increase employment compared to no participation in programmes (Strøm et al,2015).

Røed et al. (2019) also provide a review of research on active labour market policies and its effects for refugees based on 9 studies with data from the Nordic countries. The summarized findings from this review show that four of the studies evaluate the effect of different types of active labour market policies and in all four studies, some of the policies have a positive effect. However, in general, the measures seem to have a more positive influence on the labour market performance of unemployed immigrants compared to newly arrived refugees. Moreover, three studies indicate positive effects of tailoring of programs to the individual participants' situations. The review also points to studies which show specific positive effects of wage subsidies (in line with studies referred to in Strøm et al (2015)). (There are also more comprehensive meta studies that explore effects of active labour market policies in further detail but without specific focus on immigrants (Card, Kluve & Weber, 2010)).

GEOGRAPHICAL DISPERSAL POLICIES

The settlement of refugees has been guided by geographical dispersal strategies, which correspond to the broader regional development policies in Norway (Søholt et al, 2014). Policies and regional strategies highlight how settlement of refugees and immigration in rural and remote districts are perceived as valuable for curbing the tendency of population decline in small and remote municipalities in rural areas. However, settlement in remote areas can create problems for refugees when it comes to integration through labour market inclusion. Refugees settled in remote areas have considerably less chance of getting employed compared to those that are settled in more centralized or urban areas, especially around the capital. Those settled in the most remote areas are also those that most often relocate to more urban centres (Hernes, Arendt, Joono og Tronstad, 2019; Svendsen, Valenta & Berg, 2017).

However, various studies show that rural and remote areas provide other qualities in terms of well-being and social inclusion of immigrants. Children's' well-being and their access to school and social activities are emphasized as attractive features of rural and remote municipalities, safety and 'slow-life', beautiful surroundings and access to nature, access to low-cost housing, local social networks and a feeling of being seen and included were all mentioned as factors that make rural areas attractive for settlement when seen from the immigrants perspective (see Solheim & Røhnebæk, 2019; Svendsen & Berg, 2012; Søholt, Aasland, Onsager & Vestby, 2012). The same studies highlight limited job opportunities, access to higher education, and risk of feeling isolated as negative aspects.

LONG TERM EFFECTS OF INTEGRATION POLICIES

Assessments of the long-term effects of Norwegian integration policies rely on analysis of how the children of immigrants are doing in terms of integration. A comprehensive research project has analysed how children of immigrants (TCNs) perform in terms of education and in the labour market, and the analysis shows that the results for this generation is more in line with the majority population compared to their parents (see Midtbøen,

2020 for a summary of central findings). However, there are considerable differences, depending on the country of origin. A larger portion of children of immigrants take higher education, compared to the majority population of the same age, but children of TCN immigrants are also overrepresented in the group that do not complete the obligatory education (10 years). Descendants of TCN immigrants are overrepresented in elite professions such as medical doctors, law and economy, but the employment rates are also lower for this group than for the majority population. Interestingly, within this group, a higher proportion of women compared to men take higher education. The overall findings give a basis for claiming that the Norwegian welfare state model, with free access to education, a regulated labour market and clear norms for gender equality provide structures which enable social mobility for second generation immigrant groups. Still, there are also studies that show that children of immigrants' experience discrimination at work, and that they face hindrances in recruitment processes (Midtbøen, 2020).

1.3 ASSESSMENT OF THE STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF POLICIES THROUGH SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

This chapter is based on the information from six interviews. One interview was conducted with state / national authorities (directorate) and three interviews at the regional level (Innlandet). We have also interviewed head managers in two municipalities regarding their experiences with settlement and integration policies. An adapted interview guide was used as a basis for the interviews. The interviews were conducted as videoconference and lasted about 1 hour each and recorded with an offline recorder and transcribed.

TCNs settlement to rural areas in Norway is dominated by settlement of refugees (those granted asylum and UNHCR resettlement refugees) and refugees' relocation within the national borders. Thus, the interviews focus mainly on refugee settlement and integration policies and reunited family member. A key trait throughout the interviews was that the informants could not fully distinguish between economic and social integration, and several informants found that these policy areas could not be clearly separated. The blurry distinction is reflected in the presentation of findings.

ECONOMIC INTEGRATION AND IMPACT

There was clear agreement among the informants that the national introduction program constitutes the most important policy measure for economic integration of TCNs (refugees). The program support refugees in the process of qualifying for (paid) work, which reduces the dependence on public welfare schemes. The importance of the program is clearly articulated in the following quote:

Norway has been at the fore front when it comes to integration of refugees and immigrants. We have invested a lot, and we have a specific act for this; the introduction act. We have built capacity [for settlement and integration] in all municipalities, so I really think we have laid the ground for integration. I think it has been shown that Norway performs quite well (Regional level, Informant 1)

The same informant highlights the needs for a detailed mapping of introduction program participants [background, skills, competence etc.]. The participants have varied backgrounds that affect their prerequisites for integration. This relates to differences regarding attitudes and values, clothing, language skills and educational background. The informant finds among others a difference in the integration of immigrants from Syria, in which the first wave of Syrian immigrants was more easily integrated than those that came later, which is assumed to be linked to the differences in educational level. Those that came first had generally higher educational levels, which provides an important foundation for learning the language and acquiring competence that enable labour market inclusion.

All informants also accentuate language skills as the most prominent factor when it comes to labour market inclusion. This implies that policies focusing on language training becomes especially pertinent, which is the dominant part of the introduction program. The informants also agree that they find that the private sector is generally positive to employ persons with immigrant backgrounds, but they also find that employers are very clear that good language skills is a clear prerequisite for being able to take part in work life. Acquiring sufficient language skills take time, and the informants find that the teaching provided within the ramifications of the introduction program is often not enough for reaching the level needed for coping in Norwegian workplaces. One informant explains: 'We are often told from private companies that the Norwegian language skills are too weak' (Regional level, informant 1). However, while mastering the language constitutes a central threshold for gaining employment in the private sector, it was also noted that the threshold is even higher for employment in the public sector. This was pointed out by one informant on the regional level (from the labour and welfare services) that explained that 'It is easier to get in contact with leaders of private companies than with managers in the public sector' when they try to support persons with immigrant backgrounds with getting employment. This is linked to the comprehensive bureaucratic rules that regulate the recruitment processes in the public sector, which is meant to ensure that the most qualified applicant gets recruited and that the process is transparent. The consequence is that this often implies that someone with higher formal competence and experience will be favoured at the expense of applicants with immigrant background. Private companies are not facing the same kind of constraints and are more flexible when it comes to recruitment. This means that private companies can provide important arenas for immigrants to gain work experience, and they can often get positions starting as vocational training which develops into temporary positions that prolong over time.

Formal competence is another vital aspect for gaining employment in Norway. In most sectors, formal education and competence is needed and there are decreasing number jobs available for unskilled workers. Permanent employment often requires formal education, and many sectors require either higher education or a 'craft certificate'. This can be obtained through vocational education at the level of upper secondary education, or a combination of learning and work experience. Several informants stress the need for developing adapted programs that enable immigrants to complete the vocational education (which is under the responsibility of the regional county). In one of the municipalities interviewed, the head manager explained that they had good experience with providing adapted programs for immigrant women to complete vocational education. They found that this enabled immigrant women to gain employment and become more economically independent, which is a central aim of the introduction program.

There are also other important policy measures available for supporting labour market inclusion and economic independence for immigrants, in addition to the introduction program. These measures are often needed as supplements to the introduction program, for participants that are distant to the labour market, have meagre formal education and need additional qualification and training. Examples of vital measures are those that enable vocational training through internships in companies [the government pay the employer to provide internships], the qualification program [a program based on close, individualized follow-up of participants that gain qualification through participation in different kinds of measures and activities suited to the individual's prerequisites] and the program 'job opportunity' [A program targeting all immigrants aged between 18 and 55 years who require basic qualifications, who have no links with working life and who are not covered by existing schemes such as the introduction program or qualification program].

Both head managers from the municipalities interviewed are set in rural mountain areas, and they have long term experience with settlement and integration of refugee immigrants. The informants in both municipalities found that the immigrants' relocation across municipalities was mainly driven by job opportunities. Three trajectories for relocations were discussed: First, the main tendencies of relocation towards more urban centres with more viable labour markets and better employment opportunities. Second, there is the tendency of relocating from the areas with dispersed populations in the peripheral areas of the region towards centres with more dense populations (2-3000 inhabitants). The third stream are secondary location from other regions. While the first stream is driven by 'economic needs' in terms of employment opportunities, the other two

streams are assumed to be more linked to social aspects and social belonging, and to the fact that the small communities, the social environment is limited.

The head managers from the two municipalities also explain in the interviews that they have experience with immigrants that have a strong drive to start their own business. They find that the individual motivation of the immigrants is more important than providing access to guidance and support for establishing businesses aimed at immigrants. The informants underline while there are comprehensive bureaucratic rules that entrepreneurs need to be familiar with and providing support for, gaining this competence, in navigating the bureaucracy, seems to be important for supporting start-ups and local development of businesses. The immigrants seem to mainly start business such as cafes, grocery stores, rather than innovative businesses.

MIGRANTS' SOCIAL INCLUSION

Those interviewed stress that there are close relations between language skills, employment, financial independence and social inclusion. Through labour market participation, immigrants get to meet others and to establish social networks beyond their close relations. Other arenas that are mentioned as enabling social connections beyond close personal ties are schools and nurseries, participation in recreational activities and sports, and through involvement with the local community more generally. Hence the informants' perspectives on concrete policy measures such as introduction program and related labour market measures discussed above is also relevant for understanding social inclusion mechanisms.

But social inclusion is nevertheless a broader concern; labour market inclusion may not always imply social inclusion, and social inclusion can take place through other arenas than the workplace. This was also pointed out by the informants of this small interview study. Indeed, they highlighted the important role of the third sector, and volunteer organizations in integration and social inclusion. The local chapters of international NGOs such as the Red Cross and Save the Children was singled out as important contributors to integration, but also local associations and clubs, and even individuals in the local community were stressed as important facilitators for integration. The role of the third sector and resources embedded in volunteers and volunteering

organizations have been increasingly highlighted in government white papers in recent years (see also the policy taxonomy).

According to the informants, volunteers have an impact on integration by providing support to individuals and families. This takes for instance place through arrangements where volunteers provide language tutoring and homework tutoring for children and youth. The municipalities also emphasise the importance of local organizations, for instance sports clubs that invite people with immigrant background to participate in their activities. Happenings arranged by the host community, or in collaboration with immigrant groups, is also highlighted as valuable. In an area of one of the municipalities the organization of a 'Syrian evening' has become very popular, and the whole local community is invited.

It is also mentioned that associations and the volunteer organizations are important arenas for participation, which makes it possible for immigrants to be profiled as good role models: *'If you have a good role model among immigrants, I think it may change perceptions among the majority population, or the majority population perception of immigrants'* (Regional level, Informant. 1). Developing good role models requires that immigrants are not only participants, but they also need to be invited to sit on the boards, and to be granted an active role in organizations' work.

The informants at the county level also point to municipalities in the region that stand out in terms of their ability to involve the resources in the volunteering sector as an active part of the municipalities' collective integration work. The informant representing the county governor (Informant 2) also underlines that there is a huge difference across the municipalities when it comes to engaging the third sector, and s/he argues that the small municipalities tend to be better at this than the bigger ones. The informant explains further that she believes that smaller municipalities are more aware of the resources embedded in voluntary organizations because they are fewer people and more dependent on bringing together all people in the community. She explains: *'They have to think more in terms of 'dugnad', but I have not really thought these things through'*¹⁸⁸

¹⁸⁸ Dugnad is a core concept in the Norwegian culture and refers to customs of communal work which has a long historic legacy. It literally translates into support or help, but it is a collective endeavour.

WHICH POLICIES ARE WORKING, AND WHICH ARE NOT?

The general perception among our informants was that the introduction program for refugees in Norway by large works quite well. There is some political disagreement regarding the decisions on the volume of immigration flows, but there is largely political agreement around integration measures.¹⁸⁹ It is also acknowledged that the immigration constitutes cross-sectional a *'wicked issue'* (National level, informant 3), which is reflected at the national policy level, where the integration department is shifted around across ministries, and it is currently located in the Ministry of Education and Research. The informant at the national level sees this as purposeful since there is increasing policy focus on ensuring a minimum of formal competence in form of educational programs among immigrants (see also descriptions in the first section).

The settlement policies emphasise as mentioned a dispersed strategy, in which all municipalities have been expected to settle refugees, and the municipalities are largely given the responsibility for working with integration. At the same time, there is a division of labour and responsibility between the national and local authorities which requires collaboration. This collaboration is generally perceived as well working according to the informants, but the informants in the municipality call for more flexibility when it comes to the local implementation of the introduction program. They stress the need for more flexibility which allows for more tailoring of the program to the participants' background and situation. This has for instance to do with the duration of the program, the option of combining and alternating between different kinds of measures. The need for developing vocational education that leads to certificate which is better suited to immigrants was also called for. There were also weaknesses mentioned in available labour market measures; since these measures are not only targeting immigrants or refugees, but all members of the population that struggle with labour market inclusion, many are in need of these measures. This creates situations of competition over scarce resources in the municipalities and the need to prioritize between different marginalized groups. Often there is lack of benefit schemes which prevents immigrants to take full advantage of these measures. The informant

¹⁸⁹ Integration is the main term used, not assimilation

at the national level explains: *'These measures are of little use if participants have no income while they take part in the training'* (Informant 3).

The same informant explains that there are some tensions between the municipalities that are responsible for the introduction program, and the counties which are responsible for the upper secondary education and vocational education. The county municipality is not required to provide vocational educational programs that are adapted to students which lack Norwegian language skills. Additionally, an arrangement in which students are free to choose which school to apply for when getting enrolled in upper secondary education is seen as hampering opportunities for immigrant students because they tend to have lower grades and thus often fail to qualify for the schools in the area where they live. This often force them to move, and this is assumed to increase the number of dropouts. This arrangement also affects the immigrants' ability to take part in the vocational education at the upper secondary level, as they compete for access alongside Norwegian students which tend to have better grades since Norwegian is their first language. These issues are impediments to inclusion which currently have not clear policy solutions.

The refugee crises led to an upscaling of the public service system, (mainly in terms of having sufficient staff that could assist in providing housing, counselling, guidance, and tutoring, but also access to housing, access to opportunities for vocational training etc) in order to tackle the increasing pressure from immigration that peaked in Norway in 2015. While the numbers of applications for asylum in Norway has fluctuated over the years, with peaks in different periods, the number of applicants reached an all time high in 2015 with more than 31100 applications. 7135 were in 2015 granted refugee or humanitarian status, 12871 were granted refugee or humanitarian status in 2016. (around twice as much compared to 'regular years'). In the previous years, the number of applicants were around 10 000 (2012:9785, 2013:11983, 2014: 11480). In subsequent years the numbers have significantly dropped: 3460 for 2016, 3560 for 2017 and 3054 for 2018).¹⁹⁰

¹⁹⁰ The numbers are from The Norwegian Directorate of Immigration and reported here: <https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/6a652e6b53594e42ba9aecedacc73a68f/immigration-and-integration-2018-2019-report-for-norway.pdf>

As the immigration policies have become more restricted and the numbers of applicants for asylum are reduced, there is an accompanying downscaling of the public service system. The informant at the national level (Informant 3) is concerned with the future dynamics of integration as the municipalities are downscaling their services and resources, while there is a reform for enhancing qualification measures and integration at the same time. She also points out that many municipalities are eager to settle more refugees than what they are allocated from the central authorities. The same was pointed out by both informants at the municipal level. The informants in the municipalities explained that they want to have a service system with adequate capacity and competence to follow up those that are settled. Close physical proximity to a service office locally was deemed vital for successful in the settlement and integration process. The informants on regional and national level expect that the future settlement policies are likely to prioritize settlement in larger municipalities as they are perceived as most resilient when it comes to maintaining competence and quality in the service system. Smaller municipalities will need to rely on inter-municipal collaboration, and the informants pointed to several examples of such arrangements in the region Innlandet.

While the general impression from this review and expert interviews is that the integration policies in Norway overall works quite well, there are also a range of tensions and problematic aspects of immigration and integration, which is not covered in this report. The expert informants are somewhat 'biased' in they sense that they represent government agencies that seek to promote integration and social inclusion to strengthen social cohesion. Hence, they may be more focused on what works and on highlighting the positive aspects of immigration, than emphasizing tensions, conflicts and perceptions of negative impact of immigrations. When asked questions regarding tensions and conflicts, one of the central government informants explained:

Our agency takes the positive approach. Instead of focusing on racism, we talk about diversity. I have learned that when we talk about negative social control, we don't say that; we talk about the right to be free to choose how you live your life. But we have this 'integration barometer' which assess the population's attitudes. This indicates that only one out five believe that integration in Norway works well. You find far more insights on attitudes to integration in society in this, than I can explain to you just now.

Hence, we add some numbers from the integration barometer to provide some context and expand on sentiments and attitudes to immigration and integration in the population. The survey numbers from 2020 show that:¹⁹¹

- 40 percent of the population perceive immigration as positive for Norway
- 27 percent believe that immigration is negative for Norway
- 20 percent believe that the integration works well
- 47 percent believe that the integration works poorly

Attitudes are linked to gender and educational background. Women and those with higher education is more positive to immigration than men and those with low education level. However, the barometer does not differentiate between attitudes in rural areas and urban areas. As discussed in this report it is likely that immigration is perceived more positive in rural areas because immigration helps curb population decline, it creates jobs and it contributes to strengthen the local economy at least if the local integration measures are successful in supporting immigrant in gaining and maintaining employment. On the other hand, the population in rural areas is characterized by lower education levels than in urban areas, so this may also affect attitudes towards immigration in rural areas. When it comes to local government decision makers, the attitudes may be positive as reflected in the interviews with the representatives from rural municipalities. They seem motivated to settle refugees because it helps address problems of population decline; it can strengthen the municipal economy and immigrants play a part in rural municipalities strategies to attract new residents and sustain local service provision.

As a backdrop to nuance the positive bias reflected in the interviews we should mention the 2011 Norway attacks at Utøya summer camp for the youth section of the labour party, and the related attacks on the executive government quarters in Oslo. In this attack 77 people were killed by a white, male, right wing extremist. This is a national trauma, which have affected acts on radicalism and the dialogues and practices around immigration and integration in Norway. The terror attack has also contributed to reveal widespread

¹⁹¹ <https://www.imdi.no/om-imdi/rapporter/2020/integreringsbarometeret-2020/>

problems of racism, radicalism and anti-immigration sentiments in the population which perhaps has not been sufficiently addressed and captured prior to 2011.

THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Covid-19 has affected the integration work in various ways, both for those enrolled in the introduction program and those that have completed it. The teaching in the introduction program takes normally place in a physical classroom, but this has shifted to digital platforms due to the pandemic. At the outset, the managers of the program did not expect this to be feasible (Municipality level, informant 6). They expected that participants would lack access to necessary technological equipment and that they would lack necessary digital skills. However, it turned out that some had access to computers, and some could borrow I-pads from the municipality. Half a week after the lockdown (in March) the participants were able to log on to the digital platform and continue with the education. So, in fact the lockdown seemed to have limited impact on the progress of the teaching. The county (informant 1) and the county governor (informant 2) also pointed out that the municipality handled this shift swiftly. Still, at the national level, it is expected that the pandemic will have a negative impact for those excluded or marginal at the labour market for many years. The national authorities have tried to counteract the negative short-term effects of the pandemic by allowing the municipalities to provide more language training, they allow extended time frames in the introduction program and the offer career guidance.

An unfortunate effect of the pandemic is linked to how the lockdown created distance between immigrants and councillors/ case workers in the public services, since face-to-face meetings were not possible. Also, many companies have had to downsize and those with looser connections to the labour market lost they jobs first, which largely affect immigrants (Regional level, informant 1). There is also a concern that the infection control measures amplify isolation and feelings of loneliness among immigrants that tend to already have limited social networks. This may also have long term negative effects, as pointed out by the informant from the labour and welfare services (NAV): *This is not just about NAV, it is about access to health service, health services for the kids. Suddenly there are these huge changes, not just for you but for the whole family - it affects everyone.*

You are disconnected from society - you are not really involved. And you add this to the fact that you have problems understanding everything that goes on in the first place (Informant 4).

Yet another negative affect of the pandemic is that the number of applicants for asylum is reduced and it is mainly UNHCR transfer refugees that are settled. With fewer people being settled, this accelerate the downscaling of the services allocated to work with qualification and integration of refugees in the municipalities discussed above. This means fewer jobs in the municipalities and less financial transfer from the central to the local government. The informants were also concerned with the lack of continuity in the local service provision when rates of refugee immigration drops.

1.4 CONCLUSION

This section summarizes the findings from the identification of policies; review of research on policy impact on integration; and insights from the expert interviews. The summary is structured in two parts: A and B emphasize economic impact and C and D emphasize social impact. As reflected throughout this report, the social and economic dimensions cannot be easily separated, which was also pointed out in the expert interviews. This has perhaps also become increasingly the case in the last decades given the fact that understandings of integration, and policy measures for integration, has come to largely focus on labour market inclusion. This trend in Norwegian social policy, which is linked to a focus on activation and conditionality in relation to integration policies, is in line with tendencies in most western European countries (see Djuve, 2011). Djuve identifies and discusses a change of discourse on integration from an emphasis on social citizenship towards a focus on activation and employment as prominent paths to inclusion and integration. This forms an important backdrop for the summarized findings along the two dimensions social and economic impact. We should also repeat that our report focuses on integration policies aimed at refugees.

FINDINGS ON HOW POLICIES INFLUENCE THE IMPACT OF IMMIGRATION ON THE ECONOMY IN NORWAY.

First, we are asked to summarize findings on how policies influence the impact. This is an extremely complex question to answer and it is dependent on whether we consider short term effects of specific policy measures (for instance labour market measures) or the more long-term effects of broader programs and combination of policies and societal infrastructure. Since our focus has been mainly on TCNs in terms of refugee immigration, it is the introduction program provided as 2-3 years mandatory program for settled refugees that constitutes the most important policy tool for integration. The program has been closely and regularly evaluated through different methodologies, so we know a lot about the results and effects, and we have also knowledge about what contributes to more or less successful programs. The set policy target in terms of results is that 70 percent

should be employed or in education one year after completing the program, and even though this target is not reached throughout the country (average results have been around 58-63 percent) it is still regarded as a highly valuable policy instrument for integration. It is a costly investment for the government at the outset of settlement, but it seen to pay off in the long run. For instance, a study documents that 67 percent of the participants were in work or enrolled in education five years after completion (Lunde and Lysen, 2020). Looking at the results in a long-term perspective show that differences between the genders when it comes to employment evens out over time.

The importance and relative success of the introduction program when it comes enabling refugee immigrants to be economically independent and included in the labor market, was also recognized by all expert informants. However, in line with discussions in studies and evaluations of the program, they also find that there are rooms for improvements. Both research reports and the informants highlight the importance of tailoring of the program, and individual follow-up. This is also accentuated as strategy to be implemented in future development of the program, as it is expressed in a new Act (the integration Act) to be implemented in January 2021. The corresponding discussions in studies and evaluations of the program, the expert interviews and the planned new policies show that the policy making are based on insights from research-based evaluations.

We have also reviewed studies that examine the results of more specific labour market measures which can be used as part of the qualification efforts in the introduction program, or as measures that give extra support to participants subsequent to completion if they are still in need of more training and qualification to get employed or to start education. These studies show that place-then-train measures aimed at employers such as wage subsidies and direct employment programs seems to have a positive effect on enabling unemployed immigrant groups to gain employment, but such programs can also have a negative effect (lock-in) if they are design as special employment programmes.

Additionally, studies and evaluations discuss that the while many labour market measures in use seem effective, the Norwegian labour market is increasingly characterized by high thresholds for inclusion, as formal competence tend to be a requirement across sectors. Thus, it seems like there is need for investing more in programs with longer duration that lead to formal education, especially vocational education. The need for developing such programs, that are adapted to the prerequisites of immigrants with Norwegian as second

language, is elaborated in research reports and in the expert interviews at all levels. It seems also to be a planned element in the new integration Act to be implemented next year.

An issue which has gained limited attention in policy discourse and in research in Norway is incentive and support for immigrants to start their own business and develop career paths as entrepreneurs. This is a clear lacuna when it comes to policy instruments and research attention. This issue was somewhat thematized in the expert interviews, especially at the municipal level. Immigrants were perceived as often being motivated and having a drive to start their own businesses, but the bureaucratic rules on how to register, pay tax and in different ways report to the government can be complex and provide hindrances for start-ups. Moreover, the interview indicate that immigrants seem to be able to start their own businesses based on their own drive and motivation, not due to incentives and stimulation for the government.

We have also examined regional development policies and how this links to immigration and integration policies. Norway has emphasized on geographical dispersal when settling refugees, so there are settlements in rural and remote areas. This implies weakened employment opportunities for immigrants, and employment rates are lower among refugees settled in remote areas compared to those in more centralized urban areas. Settlement of refugees is still attractive for rural municipalities, because it counteracts population decline; it creates public service jobs locally and the municipality receives financial compensations from the central government to cover cost for settlement and integration. Thus, the interviews, and regional strategic documents highlight that it is attractive for rural municipalities to settle refugees (and get them to stay permanently) because it is perceived as having a positive impact on the local economy and regional development.

We have also dealt with the question of what we know about the more long-term effects of the Norwegian integration policies in general, which we can respond to by looking at the situation of second-generation immigrant groups. Results from a comprehensive study show that the children of TCN immigrant groups are provided with opportunities for social mobility (Midtbøen, 2020). A larger portion of children of immigrants take higher education, compared to the majority population of the same age, and they are overrepresented in elite professions such as medical doctors, law and economy. However, children of TCN immigrants are also overrepresented in the group that do not complete the obligatory education (10 years). And the employment

rates are also lower for this group than for the majority population. Overall, it still seems that the Norwegian integration policies is relatively 'successful' in the sense that it provides structures that enable social mobility for the next generation. Looking at the effects of integration policies in this way, does imply also that these policies are seen as interlined with the broader societal structures which in Norway is marked by free access to education, a regulated labour market and clear norms for gender equality. The expert interviews also pointed in the direction that the Norwegian integration policies seemed relatively successful, even though problematic aspects were identified. However, the general question of impact of immigration (and refugee immigration in particular) on the national economy is a highly controversial and contested issue, which cannot be easily responded on the sole basis on the studies conducted for this report. Different perceptions on this controversy is among others referred to in the government green paper 'Integration and Trust' (Brochmann et al., 2017).

GOOD PRACTICES FOR INTEGRATION IN TERMS OF LABOUR MARKET INCLUSION:

Considering how the impact of integration on the national economy largely depend on labour market inclusion we present in this section what the review of research and expert interviews bring forward as good practices in this area:

- The national introduction program in Norway (2 years of language training and more) has proved successful when it comes to providing refugee immigrants with a foundation for labour market inclusion or continuing education after the program. The programme puts pressure on all municipalities to invest in integration, and it provides immigrants the opportunity to invest in qualification and training that pay off in the long run in terms of labour market inclusion.
- Active labour market measures within and subsequent to the introduction programme, such as 'place-the-train' measures, seem to have positive effects for employment among immigrants. However, some programs can also have negative 'lock-in' effects if they are designed as special employment programs because they may prevent job seekers to apply for jobs in the regular labour market.
- Introduction programs, and the use of labour market measures, work better if they are tailored to and adjusted to the situation and background of individual immigrants. Individualized follow-up and user involvement are also highlight as a positive influence.

- Norway has an increasingly specialized and high-skilled labour market, in which formal competence and education become ever more important. Development of vocational education programs that lead to craft certificates for immigrants seem to provide a promising strategy for strengthening this group's prerequisites for taking part in an increasingly competitive labour market.

SOCIAL INCLUSION: HOW POLICY RELATED FACTORS ACT ON THE MIGRANTS' INCLUSION OF NORWAY

The economic and social dimensions of integration are largely overlapping, so the aspects of integration that are linked to education, training and qualification for labour market inclusion described above, apply also to questions of how policy measures affect integration in terms of social inclusion. However, the shifts in research and policy discourses in which employment and labour market inclusion is increasingly equated with integration, tend to shadow that integration embeds several interlinked dimensions (i.e. Ager & Strang, 2008). Employment can provide important means for social inclusion, but employment may not always be accompanied by social inclusion, and social inclusion may also take place on other arenas. This becomes especially evident when studying integration in rural and remote areas with less employment opportunities and in which access to social networks become especially important. This is reflected in the expert interviews which highlight the importance of involving civil society and volunteer organizations in integration work. Involvement in volunteer organizations and associations can give access to important networks and 'bridging' social capital and reduce feelings of isolation in remote areas (Putnam, 2001). Several research reports also point to the importance of bringing together resources in the third sector with the formal programs and measures implemented by the government. There is also research that shows that municipalities where the public services establish formal collaborations with volunteer organizations, produce better results from the introduction program compared to those that do not have such collaboration (Djuve et al., 2017). There are, however, still relatively limited studies focusing on the role of the third sector and especially the importance of collaborative relations between government agencies and volunteer organizations. Our review show that

research on this; the conditions for and impact of inter-sectorial and inter-organizational collaboration, represent an important knowledge gap.

GOOD PRACTICES REGARDING SOCIAL INCLUSION

Good practices for integration linked to concrete policy measures are presented above (B) but our research highlight also the importance of considering integration in a broader perspective. In the Nordic countries in which the government takes a major responsibility for integration (for a Nordic comparison see Tronstad & Hernes, 2014) activation of resources in the third sector is highlighted as good practice.

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MATILDE

8. SPAIN

Country: Spain

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1.1 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING ECONOMIC-RELATED POLICIES AND SERVICES REGARDING TCNS' INTEGRATION AND IMPACT IN SPAIN AND ITS SELECTED REMOTE AREA(S)

Spain is a highly decentralised state in political and administrative terms, leading to different "migratory mosaics" (Cachón, 2008; 2009a). The national government is responsible for migration policies governing entry into Spain, entitlement to Spanish nationality and the conditions for staying in Spain, family reunification, and for applying for refuge or asylum. The Autonomous Regions, on the other hand, are responsible for managing all the other sector-specific policies (housing, employment, education, social services, etc.) that affect immigrants' lives, always within the framework of national guidelines.

There are also other policies concerning: 1) the integration of foreigners; 2) raising public awareness and fighting rumours and hoaxes; 3) territorial policies, which lay down measures for territorial development and attracting immigrants to rural areas. Yet it must be stressed that sector-specific policies comply with the standardisation and mainstreaming principle, which implies that there is no specific legislation or regulations for immigrants, but rather general ones that apply to the entire population as long as they meet certain criteria.

ENTRY AND STAY POLICIES

Responsibility for entry, settlement, family reunification and nationalisation policies currently lies with the Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration, which liaises with the Ministry of the Interior (Directorate General of International Relations and Foreigners) (**Basic Law N°. 4/2000 of 11th January on the rights, freedoms and social integration of foreigners in Spain**); this Law has been amended several times to bring it in line with the current state of migration and economic cycle (most notably in Laws 8/2000, 14/2003 and 2/2009), and was last amended on 04/09/2018. Other major measures include the six extraordinary regularisations that took place in Spain between 1985 and 2005.

Another milestone was the Basic Law N°. 14/2003, of 20th November (reforming Basic Law N°. 4/2000 and Law 7/1985, of 2nd April amending the Immigration Law approved in 2000). The Law granted undocumented aliens access to the basic benefits of the national health system, education system and social services system for all foreigners in an irregular situation (Lobo Abascal, 2007) as long as they were registered at a town hall, which only involves presenting proof of a fixed address¹⁹².

The *"Intensive Nationality Plan"*, for processing residence-based nationality applications, enshrined in the Ministry of Justice's **G.E.N. (Nationality Application Management)** Project (2012-2013) has provided a more favourable legal framework for naturalisation policies. More specifically, it has positively impacted nationals from Latin American countries who need to have been legally resident for two years, whereas other nationalities need ten years' legal residence (Martín & Moreno, 2012).

There have been two national plans to foster the foreign population's integration (1st and 2nd **Strategic Citizenship and Integration Plan (Spanish acronym: PECE)**; PECE 2007-2010 and PECE 2011-2014). These plans were the linchpin for drafting the sector-specific integration policies for which the Autonomous Regions are now responsible.

Another key nationwide policy regards **applications for international protection**. The first legislation on the right of asylum was enshrined in Law N°. 5/1984, which was amended by Law N°. 9/1994 and then by Law N°. 12/2009. This Law was passed to establish the terms and content of international protection in Spain (Law N°. 263, in 2009).

¹⁹² In Spain, this is called *Empadronamiento* and it involves being registered in the local council's register, and being given a certificate to justify that you live in Spain on a more or less permanent basis. This allows the local government to calculate how many people are living in an area and helps them to petition for grants to improve local facilities.

ECONOMIC AND LABOUR ASPECTS OF INTEGRATION

A quota system is used to organise migratory labour flows in line with the Spanish job market's requirements (**art. 2b of Law N°. 4/2000**), but this national job market consideration only applies to people applying for their first work permit, but not to work permit renewals or to permanent residents seeking jobs, people who hold family reunification-based resident permits, or to relatives of people naturalised in Spain (CES, 2019).

Labour integration has been positively impacted by two important legislative amendments. If immigrants were unemployed and their contributory unemployment benefit period ended, they could have their work and residence permits renewed; this enabled foreigners to get new employment contracts and therefore avoid being considered undocumented immigrants (**Section 38.6 of Basic Law N°. 2/2009, of 11th December, amending Basic Law N°. 4/2000**). The employment requirements necessary for renewing a work permit were also eased in 2011 (**Royal Decree 557/2011 of 20th April, approving the Regulations of Basic Law N°. 2/2009**).

Hiring workers in their countries of origin has allowed sectors that need large numbers of workers to hire them on a seasonal basis. Known as 'circular hiring', this was restricted exclusively to seasonal agricultural campaigns from 2012 (**Ministerial Order ESS 1/2012**) until 2018, when collective management of hiring at origin was resumed (**Ministerial Order TMS/1426/2018, of 26th December**).

SOCIAL & HEALTH DIMENSION ISSUES AND INTEGRATION

Each **regional social services Law** includes the basic principles of integration of the Aliens Law (**Basic Law N°. 4/2000**) and grant legal immigrants access to the system's benefits under the aforementioned standardisation and mainstreaming principle. Accordingly, undocumented immigrants who have registered with their local authority are entitled to some basic emergency benefits (economic benefits), but other benefits (i.e. Minimum Insertion Income, see two paragraphs below) are more restricted.

The **National Strategy for the Prevention and Fight against Poverty and Social Exclusion 2019-2023** (Ministry of Health, Consumer Affairs and Social Welfare, 22/03/2019) refers especially to the provision of

comprehensive care of unaccompanied foreign minors (Spanish acronym: *MENAs*) to meet their accommodation, education, food and guardianship needs in order to ensure they are properly integrated into Spanish society. It also calls for the promotion of active employment policies to make it easier for vulnerable people, including immigrants, to find jobs.

The **Minimum Insertion Income**, another measure that the Spanish government approved in 07/2020, is intended to alleviate cases of extreme poverty in households and seeks to protect families that suddenly lose their source of income, whether they are natives or of foreign origin. Another measure that the government has implemented in 2020 to limit covid-19's effect among the poorest people has been to limit evictions and cuts in basic services, and immigrants can benefit from both.

On the issue of **health care**, although Law N°. 4/2000 extended the right to health care to all foreigners regardless of their administrative status, between 2012 and 2018 health care was limited to legal immigrants (Royal Decree-Law N°. 16/2012). In the summer of 2018, the authorities restored this right to health care with limitations for foreigners in Spain who are no legal residents (Royal Decree Law N°. 7/2018).

One interesting initiative in **Aragon** was the **Immigration Forum**, which the Aragon Regional Government set up in 2002. This advisory body enables immigrants in Aragon to take part and be represented in devising social policies, as well as a powerful mechanism for debating and putting forward proposals on how to improve social policy management. The Forum has discussed the **four major migration-related plans passed in Aragon** in the last decades, all of which have been of a global, mainstreaming nature:

- Comprehensive Aragon Immigration Plan, 2004-2007
- Comprehensive Plan for Intercultural Coexistence in Aragon, 2008-2011
- Plan for Inclusion and Intercultural Coexistence in Aragon, 2014-2016
- Comprehensive Plan for the Management of Cultural Diversity in Aragon, 2018-2021

These plans have been drawn up by right-wing and left-wing governments alike, and have sought to promote a comprehensive policy for integrating immigrants, to guarantee the conditions for coexistence and participation, and to give immigrants equal access to general services, on the same terms as the rest of the population.

One of the sector-specific policies that affect immigrants the most are **housing policies**. The Aragon regional government is working on legislation to grant housing aid to all the population. In particular, it has earmarked €1.8 million a year to help young people to rent housing (Order VMV/1289/2018, dated 26th July). Provincial authorities can also approve other plans to supplement the regional housing aid plan. For instance, in May 2020 Huesca Provincial Council approved the €3 million **Housing Promotion Plan**, which offers interest-free loans to towns and villages, which normally have fewer than 1,000 inhabitants, to encourage new inhabitants to settle in the province's smallest municipalities and keep the population from shrinking even more.

It is also worth mentioning the two **equality and cooperation laws** that the Aragon regional government passed during the 2015-19 legislature; both laws were the first of their kind because they extended rights and freedoms for LGBTI people, and include measures to protect migrants and refugees:

- Law N^o. 4/2018, of 19th April, on gender identity and expression and social equality and non-discrimination (the Trans Act).
- Law N^o. 18/2018, of 20th December, on equality and comprehensive protection against discrimination on the grounds of sexual orientation and gender identity in Aragon (the LGBTI Equality Act).

Both laws refer to the protection of vulnerable groups, including migrants and refugees. In 2019, the Aragon regional government also approved the '**Aragon Cooperation Master Plan**' (11/2019), which addresses efforts to promote the rights, freedoms and equality of LGBTI people, including foreigners and refugees.

EDUCATIONAL AND CULTURAL ASPECTS OF INTEGRATION

The law guarantees equal schooling for schoolchildren, but the problem comes when children who cannot speak the language spoken at their school need support to adapt.

The 2nd Strategic Citizenship and Integration Plan featured four types of educational measures: reception measures, attention to linguistic and cultural diversity, attention to families, and teacher training.

Certain religious affiliation-related actions, regulated by **Basic Law Nº 7/1980, of 5th July**, focus on the recreation of the culture of origin. The Law allows immigrants to receive religious education and assistance, establish places of worship and associations, use public land for religious cemeteries, etc.

In 2002, the Aragon Regional Government's Department of Education set up the Aragon Centre of Intercultural Education Resources (Spanish acronym: CAREI), which in 2020 was renamed the **Aragon Centre of Reference for Equity and Innovation**. Its mission is to support schools in aspects related to innovation and educational research, educational inclusion and attention to interculturality.

OUTREACH POLICIES

Both the Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration, and the Autonomous Region are responsible for these policies. The Ministry has implemented comprehensive measures socio-residential intervention measures to promote diversity management, intercultural coexistence and prevent racism and xenophobia through the **Secretariat General of Immigration and Emigration**. Spain's nationwide social organisations, like the Spanish Red Cross, can also develop outreach and awareness-raising plans and campaigns.

The Aragon Regional Government has launched several plans and campaigns to raise awareness about immigration. The most recent was the '**1st Aragon Anti-rumour and Anti-Discrimination Strategy**' (2020), with actions and measures to prevent unfounded rumours, stereotypes or prejudices about the migrant population and cultural diversity. In 2020 it has also launched the 'Campaign against Racism and Xenophobia' to fight against stereotypes, prejudices and racist and xenophobic discriminatory behaviour, and is planning an 'Awareness campaign on immigration and the rural environment' for the end of 2020.

TERRITORIAL AND DEMOGRAPHIC POLICIES

Migratory issues and immigrants moving into rural areas is closely linked to Spain's territorial depopulation problem. Several regional schemes are underway to attract immigrants to rural areas.

In order to stop **depopulation**, there have been some general schemes for attracting immigrants into rural areas, although demographic issues have only recently begun to arouse the interest of national politicians. On 27th January this year, the Spanish government passed Royal Decree 40/2017, creating the **Government Commissioner for the Demographic Challenge**, which regulates its operation and the drafting and development of the **National Strategy for Demographic Change**, in addition to other tasks in response to the problem of the progressive population ageing and territorial depopulation. In November 2020, this Strategy was still being finalised prior to its approval.

In Aragon, and in terms of demographics, several measures and regulations have been developed to combat depopulation since the end of the 90s. It was at that time that the first '**Land Management Act**' (*Ley de Ordenación del Territorio*, LOTA) (1992) and in 1998 the '**General Guidelines for Land Management**' (*Directrices Generales de Ordenación del Territorio*) were passed. This was the first territorial intervention instrument in the region, and although it paid particular attention to population imbalances by establishing a regional system of cities, it did not provide the necessary economic funds for its development.

The second land planning Law (**The Aragon Land Planning Law Nº. 4/2009, of 22nd June**, also known by its Spanish acronym, LOTA) was passed in 2009 and is still in force in 2020; the Law was later amended by Law Nº. 8/2014, of 23rd October, to permit the strategic design of the model for using and transforming the Aragon region in the short, medium and long term (Aragon 2025). This Law led, in 2014, to the passing of the **Aragon Territorial Planning Strategy** (Spanish acronym: EOTA) (Decree 202/2014), a land planning instrument that addresses Aragon's demographic and depopulation problems.

Apart from laws and plans, important documents have been written on demographic matters in Aragon. A first report entitled 'Towards demographic policy in Aragón' sparked debate in 1999 on demographic policy, while urging the regional government to develop the '**Comprehensive Plan for Demographic Policy**' (*Plan Integral de Política Demográfica*) in 2001 (Government of Aragón, 2001). Their measures were intended to boost the birth rate, keep the population in rural areas and even encourage migration into rural areas, although these objectives were not met.

Subsequently, the Aragon regional government passed the Decree 165/2017, of 31st October, and the **Special Directive on Demographic Policy Land Planning and against Depopulation**; the Directive laid down the

goals and strategic lines of the Aragon's depopulation policy, which include attracting and integrating immigrants to alleviate the negative demographic situation of rural areas, and envisaging the creation of the 'Aragon Observatory of Demographic and Population Dynamisation' (2017).

These are not the only institutional instruments implemented by the public administration, because other bodies have launched other initiatives. In 2017, the **Depopulation and Creativity Chair** was set up at the initiative of Zaragoza Regional Council and the University of Zaragoza (<http://catedradespoblaciondpz.unizar.es>) to address depopulation issues. It was the first of its kind to be set up in Spain and works to put forward proposals against depopulation based on scientific knowledge. The Chair has already conducted several studies on new tax schemes for rural areas, the housing market, innovation and entrepreneurship, and has put forward highly original proposals such as a recent programme of university placements in rural areas (*Rural Erasmus*).

In addition to these efforts, it is important to highlight the role of various **associations**, whose objective is to help people who wish to establish themselves in rural areas. The '**Association of Municipalities against Depopulation**' (*Asociación contra la Despoblación Rural*) (<http://contraladespoblacion.com>) has nationwide coverage and is made up of a group of people mainly from Aragón and also other Spanish provinces that help people create small businesses in rural areas. Its aim is to keep young people in villages and to settle new families.

Another similar project is '**Embrace the Earth**' (*Abraza la Tierra*) (www.abrazalatierra.com), which is a network for territorial cooperation to facilitate the arrival of new inhabitants. 'Embrace the Earth' has set up a network of offices to welcome new settlers, accompanies new neighbours during the process of selecting a village to live in, puts them in touch with local residents and follows up their arrival and integration in village life.

One similar project is '**Lively villages**' ('*Pueblo's vivos*' in Spanish; <http://pueblosvivosaragon.com/en>), which aims to help put a stop to depopulation and encourage new inhabitants to settle in rural areas of some of Aragon's districts. The project is being financed with a LEADER 2014-2020 grant, co-financed by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (FEADER) and funds from the Aragon regional government. The project's partners include 7 of the 20 rural development groups that are working with LEADER funds in Aragon's three provinces.

1.2 OVERVIEW ON EXISTING ANALYSES AND ASSESSMENTS OF ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL POLICIES

The fact that, over the last 30 years, Spain has become a country that receives foreign immigrants with different profiles and reasons for migrating has given rise to wide range of literature on the economic and social integration of the foreign population. Of particular note are the studies that relate policies, the situation, and integration strategies of the foreign population, such as those by Aja et al. (2010), Cachón (2009a, 2009b, 2011; 2016), Checa et al. (2016), Izquierdo (2008, 2011) and Laparra & Cachón (2010). Especially worth mentioning is the literature that analyzes multilevel management in Spain, such as Izquierdo & León (2008), Zapata-Barrero (2011, 2012, 2013, 2015), in addition to the literature that, since the 2008 economic crisis, reflects on and puts forward proposals regarding integration policies, such as Laparra & Izquierdo (2015) and also Izquierdo (2016; 2019a; 2019b). Yet very few authors analyse the implementation of concrete sector-specific policies and their social and economic impact.

The sector-specific policies on education, health, housing social policies, employment and social services that are the responsibility of Autonomous Regions, have been analysed from a joint perspective, and shown that this decentralised model has led to highly different levels of integration and to what has been called a 'patchwork' model of integration (Martínez de Lizarrondo, 2009a). This model of integration is mainly oriented to documented migrants, except in some sectors like health that has also paid attention to indocumented migrants, in some autonomous regions (Laparra & Martínez de Lizarrondo, 2008; Godenau et al., 2014).

A review of the literature on policies for assisting foreign schoolchildren has shed light on two fundamental problems: school failure rates and how schoolchildren are distributed. As several researchers (Moreno & Bruquetas, 2012; Murillo & Belavi, 2018) have shown, 82% of the foreign schoolchildren were attending state schools, and only 14.1% were at subsidised schools. The new Basic Law that amends the Basic Education Law (Spanish acronym: LOMLOE, 2020) intends to distribute schoolchildren in state and subsidised schools in line with each neighbourhood's social make-up. Other authors highlight the differences between regions that develop policies ranging from assimilationism to overemphasising interculturality. The implementation of

these approaches/theories remains at a theoretical level (Martínez de Lizarrondo, 2009b), although emphasis is placed on public immigration policies based on interculturality as a cornerstone for integration (Zapata-Barrero, 2011).

The analysis of social service policies first – during the 2000s – underscored the need to reorient these policies to tackle the migration phenomenon (del Olmo Vicén, 2008). Subsequently, and in the context of the economic crisis, the focus has been that social policies are responding to a growing demand for social needs (Alemán 2011; Alemán & Soriano, 2014; Maldonado, 2012), but there is no focus on analysing the impact they have on migrants' social and economic integration, and at the micro level, this field of social policy remains underdeveloped.

The most recent literature on policies that affect the economic and labour dimension of migration focuses on seasonal workers. In this regard, the policies of recruiting non-EU nationals in their country of origin is said to have promoted the territorial anchoring of people between their places of origin and destination. That is, this hiring allows seasonal workers to remain living in their countries of origin while traveling regularly to work for a few months in a specific country, impacting the economy of both countries. However, those policies point to two realities: firstly, they are designed to meet basic needs (clothing, food, showers, housing and other financial aid schemes) and secondly, despite being financed by Autonomous Regions, it is the local entities, together with employers and small farmers, along with trade unions, NGOs and town councils, who make it possible for recruitment policies in origin to be successful and to favour these workers' inclusion (Macías et al., 2016; González, 2019; López Sala & Sánchez, 2014). The spatial segregation problem prompted by these recruitment policies has appeared in the literature time and time again for years (Checa, 2009; Checa & Arjona, 2003; Checa et al., 2016; Checa et al., 2018).

As mentioned earlier, each Autonomous Region is responsible for its own active employment promotion policies, but it can be local entities that actually implement programmes and other measures (Law N^o. 7/1985, of 2nd April, regulating the bases of local government) aimed mainly at: job training; professional certification of work experience; providing information, advice and tutoring in active job hunting; granting incentives and/or economic sanctions for workers conditional upon active job hunting; retraining or continuous training. These policies are aimed at the entire population, including legally resident non-EU foreigners. The main conclusion

of the literature review is that these policies generate a dual horizontal and vertical stratification. (Cachón, 2009b; Carrasco, 2014). In other words, they normally are concentrated in the most precarious sectors and occupations with the worst working conditions, which makes them especially vulnerable to changes in the economic cycle and social precariousness (Godenau et al., 2014). Indeed, immigrants can change jobs from one productive sector to another, but always within certain sectors (that is, construction, care, agriculture) and always keeping their professional categories at the most precarious levels.

In Spain, the migratory boom took place since 1994, related to economic development and the aforementioned regularization measures that allowed the establishment of a large immigrant population. During this period of increment of migratory flows occurred from 1994 to the 2008 economic crisis, a large number of research articles on foreign immigration were published in **Aragon**. Most of them were publications on migratory flows and referred to specific groups (Senegalese, minors, women, etc.), to specific aspects (integration, care, education, etc.), or to specific territories (rural areas or provinces), or case studies and empirical analyses. Outstanding examples include the article on immigrants' educational inclusion in Aragon and social and industrial repercussions (Gómez Bahillo, 2004), and the article on integration challenges in the educational system (Eito Mateo, 2003; 2005); yet very few analysed the issue of migration policies at a regional level.

One good example from that first period is a report published by Lázaro et al. (2008) on the **effects of immigration on employment in Aragon**. The report raises the question of whether the presence of foreigners has resulted in native workers losing their jobs, or whether it has made it difficult for unemployed people to find work. The results point to a non-negative impact of immigration on the Spanish job market, and that immigrant workers' jobs may have supplemented, rather than substituted, native workers' jobs. This article also suggested that the increase in per capita income and social networks were important pull factors to explain the arrival of immigrant workers; this explains more than 70% of the foreigners living in Aragon in the 2000s.

During those years, the majority of publications were of a very general nature, and basically addressed the flows and territorial distribution of immigrants in Aragon. This is the case of the articles published by Pinos (2001; 2002; 2007) and Lardiés (2004) on the socio-demographic and territorial characteristics of foreign immigration in Aragon. Lardiés et al. (2012) also published a chapter of a book on an issue that receives very little attention in the literature on migration in Aragon, namely immigration in the region's rural areas. Certain local publications

also dealt with the immigrant population's rooting processes (Eito Mateo, 2015) and local integration plans in the city of Huesca (Eito Mateo, 2011).

Most of what was published in those years focused on **territorial demographic policies** as a result of the demographic problem identified in Aragon, and in particular on rural depopulation (Pinilla & Sáez, 2002). Some reports have addressed this problem at a national level (FEMP – Spanish Federation of Municipalities and Provinces-, 2017) and others focus on Aragon, namely the report by Sáez et al. (2011) on public intervention against depopulation as a local policy, and the more recent one by the Aragón Ombudsman (Justicia de Aragón, 2017) about depopulation in Aragon (2000-2016) which includes proposals for designing policies to prevent depopulation. However, these reports are not binding and have not resulted in any legislation so far.

The migratory boom took place from 1994 to 2008, and it ended with the beginning of the economic crisis in 2008. Since 2010, and parallel to the decline in the arrival of immigrants, the number of publications about immigration also dropped significantly, such that now there are very few and on very partial aspects. Despite the phenomenon's importance and significance, this could be due to a factor that is quite repeated, namely that very few researchers in the region are concerned with this issue.

Even so, some recent publications on migration in Aragon highlight the situation of **foreign minors**. The Aragón Ombudsman (Justicia de Aragón, 2008 to 2020) produces annual reports to establish comprehensive, ongoing measures to guarantee the rights of foreign minors, wherever they live in Aragon. Along the same lines, Gimeno (2014) has analysed the situation of migrant minors, and other articles by him (Senovilla & Gimeno, 2020) also deal with the issue of the welcome that young immigrants receive until they come of age. The same authors (Gimeno-Monterde & Gutierrez-Sánchez, 2020) deal with the issue of family reunification and specifically of minors; reunification is also one of the most frequent legal migration routes for minors, and it is the responsibility of local administrations to offer integration policies for these children and teenagers. This research proposes the implementation of successful programmes, and to this end diagnoses the situation in Aragon and proposes a route for integration in the host society with measures to accompany these people.

1.3 STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS OUTPUT: ASSESSMENT OF THE STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF POLICIES THROUGH SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

METHODS AND ETHICS ASPECTS RELATED WITH THE INTERVIEWS

Before conducting the interviews, interviewees were sent the list of questions to let them collect and arrange the information. The interviews were recorded with the interviewees' consent, and the interviewers took notes with which to draft a preliminary summary of the interview. Generally speaking, the questions were asked as in the script, although the interviews spontaneously touched on other related subjects.-The interviews have had a variable duration of between one hour and almost two hours and a total of seven interviews have been collected. The interviewed people were: two public officers working on migration, a politician from the migration Department, a social worker, a responsible of a Labor Union, a Local Development Agent (from an European projects office) and a representative of a non-profit organization.

Both the University of Zaragoza and the CEICA (Research Ethics Committee of the Aragon Autonomous Region) gave their permission for the information, including the field work-related information, to be processed. That is why care has been taken with the information about the interviewees and the interview questions, on their recording - always offering them the chance to interrupt the recording if they wished to make any remarks off the record - and guaranteeing their anonymity throughout the research.

INTERVIEW ANALYSIS

In order to address the issues at hand, the interview questions were asked in this approximate order: information about the interviewee (current and previous jobs), and characterisation of the migration phenomenon (phases, evaluation...), integration-related policies and services that have had the greatest impact, type of impacts generated, extent to which the policies have managed to revitalise the area and opinion about current needs.

ABOUT THE EXISTING POLICIES AND SERVICES REGARDING MIGRANTS' ECONOMIC INTEGRATION AND IMPACT

When asked about migration governance, the interviewees positively highlighted the fact that the State and Autonomous Regions share responsibility for these policies, but the fact that several ministries are involved in drafting legislation leads to a wide range of different policies.

The national regularisation processes carried out until 2005 are judged positively, as they permitted the initial legal and administrative integration of foreign TCNs; this has been a fundamental step for accessing the job market and welfare system benefits. However, one interviewee complained about the legal loopholes that prevent the full integration of all kinds of foreign immigrants. The two basic models for regularising foreign TCNs, which are 1) regularisation due to family ties – reunifications – and 2) regularisation due to social ties, result in immigrants suddenly becoming irregular and not being to access the system's basic benefits in the meantime.

"there are legal loopholes in the Aliens Act"(ES006).

Regional governments are responsible for implementing the national legislation framework, and in this respect, the interviewees positively underscored the huge amount of social legislation passed by the **Aragon** Regional Government. All the policies are included in the integration and citizenship plans that have been drawn up large every four years since 2008. However, it is up to local authorities to implement these policies, and it mainly the districts that develop integration plans, while the associated services are managed and executed by third-sector institutions. Social organisations are responsible for delivering the services and goods to the local population, a fact that conditions immigrants in rural areas, who cannot access the services because very few social organisations work in those areas. Except for the Red Cross, Caritas and Accem, most social organisations are based in towns and cities, and are mainly to be found in the three provincial capitals and in some of the larger regional capitals:

"Third sector organisations play a key role (...) although few work in rural areas, except for the largest ones like Caritas, the Red Cross, Accem and Cepaim"(ES006).

"Social organisations play an important role in the rural world by offering services but most of them are based in the demographically larger centres of population, in provincial capitals... and some larger county towns" (ES005).

The interviewees stressed that benefits are governed by the principle of standardisation, that there are no specific policies for immigrants, and that they benefit from them because they are usually the ones with the lowest income and the most vulnerable:

"The policies... have been at a more local level, social services tried to facilitate their integration and acceptance... yes there were integration programmes and projects but there has never been any specific financial aid for immigrants...; the financial aid that native citizens (...) can access are the same as those that immigrants can access, as long as they meet the requirements"(ES003).

However, and in view of the wide range of different regulations, one interviewee appreciated the fact that, in Aragon the different social actors liaise and work together:

"Yes, the social agents, the DGA (Aragon regional government), the districts, plus the town councils, the NGOs and also the immigrants' associations, are all on good terms (...); coordination is a key factor"(ES002).

The specific schemes that help most to further TCNs' integration are the **reception and information initiatives and socio-labour integration measures** such as Spanish language courses, vocational training and employment information courses. Other important measures help people get to know their surroundings (especially women who have arrived for family reunification purposes from 2000 onwards), and measures for schooling minors.

"They arranged digital literacy courses, courses to help minors on their arrival, and worked closely with schools to facilitate the reception of minors, with specific programmes for minors, and awareness-raising campaigns (...). The subsidies were financed by the IASS -Aragon Institute of Social Security- for disadvantaged groups" (ES003).

Asked about **integration**-related measures, they had very positive opinions about the work done by municipal and district public social services, the NGOs working in the area and trade unions. Offering immigrants

guidance and helping them with their legal paperwork is the first step towards effective integration and settlement in the region. One interviewee spoke very highly about the work done by the Foreign Workers' Information Centre (CITE, run by the CC.OO. Trade Union), and the Legal Assistance and Guidance Service for Immigrants (SAOII, run by the Aragón regional government):

"The CITE offers guidance on legal paperwork and basic employment information, i.e., employment rights, how the job market works, ..., information on social benefits; we also refer immigrants to specialized services depending on their profile or whatever they need, even if we find out that they want to join a job placement scheme. We refer them to the Aragon Institute of Employment (INAEM), or to an agency, as we do with any Spaniard...; in other words, the CITE does not provide any service that immigrants do not ask for...; that is because we believe that they do not know enough about the job market. If they need help with any other matters, they must come to us just like any other worker"(ES004).

Importance is also attached to the fact that all the policies to allow regular and irregular (registered or not) immigrants alike to access basic health, education and social services, has ended up attracting a significant contingent of foreigners. These foreigners tend to arrive due to the presence and active work of networks, a lure effect that is also triggered by the job market's heavy demand in critical sectors. The most immediate consequence has been further stratification of the job market. Spanish workers are in the top segment of the job market, while TCNs are in the second or bottom segment with insecure jobs, low wages, harsh working conditions, working on a temporary or even seasonal basis. This issue has become particularly evident during the health pandemic:

"They occupy job market niches because they are being hit either by the closure of the hospitality industry or are on furlough (...). In the care sector, women employed as housekeepers are semi-reclusive (...), because the perimeter closures mean they cannot go home at the weekend, (...), and because they are undocumented immigrants, they are not allowed to move"(ES001).

In this regard, one interviewee emphasised the work done in Aragón, where the authorities are committed to improving benefits such as healthcare access, which central government had limited from 2012 onwards; they are also committed to equal access to the education system, and providing extra support for immigrant schoolchildren as mentioned above:

“Some Autonomous Regions only wanted immigrants as a labour, but others have opted for integration and the generating of models of coexistence” (ES002).

From the **economic integration** viewpoint, the measures that have had the biggest impact are employment-related and due to private initiative. The interviewees believe that the main way to get population to settle is with policies that favour the growth of fixed and regular employment, which is why certain livestock sector-related schemes (pig farms) have led to immigrants settling in rural areas, for two reasons: because it is an expanding sector, and because the harsh physical conditions make it a niche of employment that Spanish workers reject.

Immigrants enjoy the same access to active employment policies as the local population, although immigrants attend training courses much less than their local counterparts. In the interviewees' opinion, this has to do both with not having enough time and with the type of work they do, which is usually physically demanding.

When asked about **social inclusion**, the most successful policies are considered to be the campaigns to raise awareness about living with foreign immigrants, who are now seen in a much better light. In this regard, there is a notable difference between urban and rural areas, with integration being easier in the latter. This is because immigrants feel closer and are better known in rural areas; there, the rural population knows them better, and also the role they play. However, immigrants living in urban areas are more unknown and the population does not have as much contact with them. Even so, some interviewees said that one cannot speak of integration but rather of “coexistence”, to quote the anthropologist Giménez Romero (2005), in reference to a stratified use of public space.

“You have to work hard at getting people to live together...; if you wonder what time they go to the park..., you'll see that quite often the foreign women go from 3 to 5, when it is sunnier, and then the Spanish women go there at 5 or 6” (ES001).

Broadly speaking, immigrants and native population are said to mix well, without there being any major discriminatory attitudes. The Latin Americans are regarded to be one of the most readily accepted groups. However, work still needs to be done in Aragon on removing certain prejudices and stereotypes among the locals towards the immigrants that do not correspond to reality. One solution would be to draw up plans to

raise the population's awareness and prevent discrimination, in line with the anti-rumour strategy on which the Aragón regional government is already working.

Interestingly, some of the interviewees stressed the importance of training and awareness-raising in public administration bodies too; even though immigrants' rights of access are recognised, sometimes certain civil servants limit or ignore these rights, and this can lead to institutional racism setting in:

"...anyone who does not have the right papers is still entitled to an education (...) because education has to do with minors. That is why the Aragon Regional Government's Department of Education has admitted that a passport entitles its holder to education, even adult education, and guarantees access to vocational training. Immigrants are also entitled to health care if they have been registered for three months, and the right to emergency assistance from social services. That's the theory, because in practice, I might come across a civil servant who tells me that I'm not entitled to ... and in practice, I don't have the right papers, so "I'm going to believe it"... Civil servants have such power that sometimes they breach instructions, rules, laws...; sometimes there is low-intensity racism"(ES001).

Finally, on the issue of **participation policies**, in rural areas the foreign population still participates very little in immigrants' associations, although they have a presence in the Interdepartmental Commission and in the Aragon Immigration Forum.

"Immigrants' associations are present in the Interdepartmental Commission, but they have very limited resources...; they are defined by their needs, but they are frustrated by the lack of means (...). Sometimes, there are individual actions and they join other associations like women's associations"(ES006).

The main shortcoming of the policies that impact immigrants' economic and social integration is that they are poorly coordinated and implemented, and not monitored and assessed often enough. One serious problem that several interviewees pointed out is precisely that nobody knows how policies are implemented, and that the failure to **monitor and assess** policies makes it impossible to know their real impact on immigrants' integration; lots of analysis, a little bit of development and no assessment whatsoever.

IMPACT ON THE TERRITORY. BALANCE ON THE INFLUENCE OF POLICIES ON THE REVITALISATION OF RURAL AREAS

The majority of interviewees said that the social and economic impact for the region is very positive, from different points of view. From the social viewpoint, one of the interviewees stated that Aragon's society has become richer and that immigration has generated a greater ability for people to live together:

"society has gone from grey to colour"(ES005).

It was also acknowledged that there has been a shift in the stratification of the classes of native workers with the most insecure jobs - normally from the countryside (from the agricultural and livestock sector). This is because social groups in the countryside have moved up a step on the job ladder, and their place has been taken by economic immigrants. Another reason is that immigrant workers have moved into jobs in agriculture and the construction industry.

From the **economic viewpoint** all the interviewees agreed how important immigration is to the development of certain economic sectors in Aragon, namely the agricultural and livestock sector, the service sector (hotels, logistics and transport) and the care services sector (both in old people's homes and at home and on a private basis).

"Our autonomous region's development over the last 10 or 15 years could not be explained without the foreign population's participation. In this sense, it must be emphasised, which is why it must be made visible, both from an economic and a cultural diversity point of view"(ES004).

Immigration has an indirect impact on the **care** sector, since the presence of women carers in the rural area has allowed native women to join the job market and to keep many jobs thanks to the support and cover provided by immigrant women with children and dependent relatives.

The interviewees also stressed that this kind of work is done by immigrant women who either have no need for a work-life balance, or who come from an urban environment. In rural and depopulated areas, immigrant women who have children to look after and have come for family reunification purposes do not usually work outside the home. These female immigrants who work in the cared sector have had a very positive impact in

sparsely populated areas whose younger inhabitants have emigrated; it also allows the elderly to stay where they live, and is a clear example of rural-urban interaction.

The interviewees also mentioned certain **barriers** to enforcing policies. One of the main barriers to revitalizing rural areas is the lack of any council housing policy in smaller municipalities, where privately-owned housing available to rent does not meet appropriate living conditions (Camarero et al., 2012). There is not usually much housing available in these rural areas and most buildings are rundown and would be expensive to renovate.

Various – interviewees- informants made observations related to the mimicry of the social and relational behaviors of the foreign population, indicating that few time after the arrival and in a short period of time, foreigners follow the same guidelines as the native population. Within a few years of settling, foreigners behave in the same way as local inhabitants, so getting population to settle in certain areas depends on the services offered and not on whether the inhabitants are locals or immigrants. In other words, if there are no services, there will be no population either, foreigners or locals:

“It is not so much that they are lead to those areas, but rather that the job market lures the immigrant population (...). Immigrants move around the region to wherever where they can find work (...) and yes, years ago there were public announcements ... and they were hired at origin to work in harvests, but today (...) it is quite clear that the crisis had an impact on the drop in the number of immigrants as many returned home...”(ES004).

In short, employment, housing, communication and service infrastructures, especially education, are what encourage or stop the local or immigrant population from settling in rural areas.

1.4 CONCLUSIONS

CONCLUSION: IMPACT INTO THE ECONOMY

Numerous studies have shown the advantages of immigration at different times of history and that foreign-born citizens use social expenditure much less than the local population. The arguments that the population overuses and abuses the social protection system are unjustified, to the extent that immigrants receive less from the State than what they contribute to the Treasury (Doomernik & Bruquetas, 2016; Moreno & Bruquetas, 2012). According to this report, foreign immigrants inject more into the public accounts than what they consume. Firstly, on average immigrants are much younger than the local population, so they cost the health system much less than locals do. Secondly, their relative cost in terms of pensions is very low. In economic terms too, the arrival of immigrants has a very positive impact on the housing market.

According to some empirical studies, the induced effects of immigrants' arrival on the local population's working conditions is limited (Carrasco et al., 2004). Cuadrado et al. (2008) argue that immigrants occupy different sectors and jobs in the job market, which limits their possibilities to compete for the same jobs; besides, **immigrants do jobs that locals no longer want to do** (Garrido, 2006). Yet if most immigrants do **low-skilled** jobs, it is not so much because they are poorly qualified at origin, but because their skills are not recognised on the Spanish job market, and because they often work in a segment of the job market that was empty or that the local population has left.

So when immigrants have joined Spain's job market, they have done so without causing hardly any **labour unrest**. However, there has been some empirical evidence that **friction** can occur more in terms of wages than in levels-of-employment terms, and also because competition from immigrants is stronger for certain activities and jobs (Carrasco et al., 2004).

As for immigration's impact on **economic development** in Spain, it is agreed that immigration is associated with **positive effects on GDP** per capita, although its magnitude is limited (Izquierdo et al., 2007). Immigration has been proven to contribute positively to job creation processes (Prime Minister's Office on Economic Affairs,

2006), and this has been particularly so for certain activities and types of jobs. The working immigrant population is also making a very important contribution to the national **social security**. In addition, they are bringing **flexibility to the job market**. Other works highlight that immigrant workers have more flexible **job mobility** patterns than local workers. Restricting the analysis to immigrant women, they register much less for work in the social security system than Spanish women, and therefore work less (Cebrián et al., 2007).

There is also evidence that the large number of immigrants living in Spain would explain why Spain's inflation rate has steadied (Bentolila et al., 2008), since the arrival of immigrants has had a positive effect on the Spanish economy in economic welfare terms (lower prices in the care sector, small businesses, etc.).

In short, the immigrant population's employment and labour patterns converge very little with the local population's patterns, so there does not seem to be any significant assimilation. There is a clear **segmentation** in the job market for immigrants, as they preferably do low-quality, low-skill jobs. Existing studies on productivity-related consequences in Spain conclude a slightly negative effect, at least in the short term (Cuadrado et al., 2008). This result would be based on the immigrant population's qualification and their employment in labour-intensive sectors of activity (Izquierdo et al., 2007). In particular, the immigrant population may have contributed slightly negatively to labour productivity developments (Prime Minister's Office on Economic Affairs, 2006).

The immigrant population more often do low-skilled jobs subject to high turnover and high seasonality. Therefore **policies** should correct the clear tendency to segment the immigrant population in the job market. If there is segmentation in the labor market among different groups, policies would always be necessary to avoid this segmentation. The immigrant population's employment situation is often accompanied by poor social protection, in addition to lower wages than local workers, as a rule. All this means that in times of economic crisis in the job market, the immigrant group is hit very hard, as we are seeing in the Covid-19 pandemic crisis. The possible existence of an adverse scenario in the job market poses new challenges in terms of coverage and protection for immigrants.

As well as immigration policies, attention should be paid to the impact of **territorial policies** devised to keep the rural population in place and attract immigrants. It is hard to accurately assess the different territorial actions and measure their effectiveness, due to the funding overlap that stems from the different schemes

implemented by different administrations (EU, State, provinces, counties and municipalities); also, because the final result is the sum of public and private initiatives. Considering the depopulation situation that affects large rural areas of the country and Aragón, it is hard to be too optimistic about the outcome of these initiatives. It cannot be denied that introducing these measures has managed to get a certain number of people and some families to settle, but their quantitative significance is limited and they have not reversed the regressive trend of these areas. In addition, no one can ensure that, in a few years' time, these new settlers will still be living in the villages in which they settled first.

Most of the initiatives can be criticised for only considering financing and economic aid for the settlement of people, but trying to change and redirect the depopulation problem calls for something else. For example, the measures of Aragón's 'Comprehensive Plan For Demographic Policy', introduced to prevent depopulation, can be criticised for almost always being based on regulations and actions that did not assume new financial scenarios but instead relied on current economic capabilities; hence these measures based on economic aid are often criticised as usually just being a collection of good wishes for the future (Pinilla & Sáez, 2002). Furthermore, most of these policies have tried to improve rural areas' material conditions (which are a 'condition' for developing and settling population, but not the only thing), with the financing and construction of infrastructures, but pay little attention to cultural and social capital aspects.

INVENTORY OF GOOD PRACTICES RELATED TO ECONOMY

Governance of migration policy in Spain is characterised by the fact that the State and the Autonomous Regions share public administration powers. As mentioned earlier, some policies are national, but the Autonomous Regions are responsible for developing and managing integration and many sector-specific policies on a mainstreaming basis (for all the population: immigrants and natives); subsequently, immigrants access goods and services with the help of social organisations distributed throughout the country. Therefore, each Autonomous Region can define its own model of integration; indeed, Aragón is an example of where integration policies are developed and applied properly, although the same cannot be said of the other Autonomous Regions Aragón is also a good example of commitment to the government of diversity, multicultural policies and intercultural dialogue, as a positive resource for cohesion in local policies; this is the path to follow.

As for **good practices**, and in the economic and international sphere, countries must promote and improve dialogue and cooperation between sending and receiving countries, so that migrants benefit from both. For policies to be coherent and complementary, the close ties between international development migration and other key issues, including trade, aid, state security, human security and human rights, must be recognised.

Governments, such the Spanish government and Aragon regional government, must also take further steps to ensure that workers' rights are not violated, comparable wages are ensured, there is no correlation between status and salary, and there is an explicit and strong system of sanctions if this is not met; they must also pursue and prosecute any exploitation of immigrants in the job market and employment of indocumented workers.

The previous section mentioned that the Spanish job market is hugely segmented, and that this justifies job market protectionism (Ullán de la Rosa, 2016). Native skilled labour is protected by legislation requiring an official validation of foreign universities degrees, and applicants are discouraged by long waiting times and high rejection rates. That is why the number of skilled jobs on offer is very low. Some scholars see the system as empirical proof of the dysfunctional nature of rigid, bureaucratic policy regulation in open economies. The job market should therefore be made more flexible and opened up to skilled workers, in an open and globalised economy.

Therefore, within each Autonomous Region, each level of administration has its own competences, and each one can develop sector-specific regulations or plans that affect immigration (a district, a municipality...). All this means that Ministries and Departments face an important **challenge of coordinating the different levels of administration**, but do not always do so. Sometimes there are too many initiatives and plans, which can make them less effective and deplete funding.

Also in economic matters, but also in social matters, some **good practices** have been successful to a certain extent. Local and provincial administrations, or rural action groups (financed by LEADER funds), have arranged initiatives and programmes to attract and settle immigrant populations in rural areas, while helping them to find jobs and with their social and local integration. Undoubtedly, several of these bottom-up measures, implemented in the immigrant's close environment, have been successful.

Finally, on the issue of territorial and demographic policies to keep population in rural areas, immigrants who settle there clearly not only need policies that ensure they have jobs, but also that they settle and take root. That is why education and health services and amenities are also needed, and in particular **sufficient and appropriate housing** for a family group. Today, housing is one of the main demands and problems (it is scarce and old).

CONCLUSION: SOCIAL IMPACT

Spain's current existing **immigration entry** and **settlement policies** have prompted different integration models, depending on the group of economic migrants to which they belong (Morén-Alegret & Wladykala, 2020)¹⁹³, giving rise to different levels of social and spatial segregation and relationship with institutions.

When social policies are analysed, it is possible to visualise a theoretical integration of (regular and irregular) immigrants into the welfare system. Yet it is only theoretical because this group of registered immigrants is often subject to institutional xenophobia, mainly because civil servants do not know about welfare system benefit entitlement requirements. The principle of standardisation guarantees equal access to the system's benefits, so in practice, integration is limited to documented immigrants (naturalised or not), and partially to registered undocumented immigrants.

According to the information obtained in the field, it seems that social policies on housing, emergency economic benefits and periodic economic benefits (i.e., Minimum Insertion Income) have sufficed to meet primary needs, but only residually and insufficiently. Their impact on the immigrant population's socio-economic integration has been residual.

¹⁹³ Legal immigrants, immigrants who are undocumented but registered and therefore in an administratively legal situation, and undocumented -not officially- immigrants.

Furthermore, each immigrant's situation varies, depending on what papers they have, and this determines different ways of settling in the territory. Firstly, seasonal workers – with temporary work permits for the first sector – tend to settle outside city centres, in the outskirts; this implies that they are physically cut off from the rest of the population, making it very difficult to deal with institutions and the public administration, such as social services, and with third-sector organisations. Consequently, this spatial segregation has repercussions on social and cultural integration processes (Checa & Arjona, 2003). There is less interaction with society as a whole –both with natives and other immigrants– because they spend far less time socialising in public. Nor are they hardly ever to be seen in shops, open leisure and sports spaces, educational establishments, cultural associations or places of worship.

Secondly, the **reception policies** promoted by local authorities –and partly implemented by third sector organisations– have a direct impact on integration processes. Firstly, because they provide immigrants with the main tool: literacy in the region's language; that is why Spanish courses, even for Spanish speakers, are the instrument that lets them socialise and communicate, facilitating their social and institutional inclusion. Secondly, because the advice they get helps them to understand their working environment (legal-labour advice), legislation (help with paperwork for permit renewal and family reunification purposes), education and training (social and labour integration courses), social and health care (information about the system's resources and what they are entitled to), etc. Hence, the importance of local governments in the integration of immigrants is once again confirmed (Zapata-Barrero et al., 2017).

Thirdly, policies to facilitate the **integration of foreign minors into the school system** take a two-pronged approach: adapting the children to the educational system, and providing guidance on how to live a multicultural society. Both approaches trigger their acculturation because they receive the host country's culture; yet these policies have not been shown to affect the loss of the culture of origin; and even though children of one same school spend time and study together, current policies have not avoided a high degree of school segregation, since most immigrant pupils go to state-subsidised schools (Franzé, 2003; Murillo & Belavi, 2018).

Fourthly, there are a set of **outreach and coexistence-oriented policies** devised to improve interaction between the local population and immigrants. However, they are still a long way from promoting an inclusive

coexistence, since both groups coexist more in time than in space (Giménez Romero, 2005). These policies have not solved the spatial integration issue because, as mentioned earlier, use of public places is stratified, preventing effective integration.

As a general conclusion, social integration is limited to a process of inclusion that stems from the development of an organic solidarity, based on a reciprocal need: economic dependence, in the primary productive sector and in the service sector, especially in care services; and also demographic need. Migration produces processes of assimilation into lifestyles typical of the host society, such as reproductive patterns, showing a reduction in the fertility rate with respect to the country of origin (Pérez Díaz, 2019).

That is why what are needed are new proposals involving local governments in particular, if we do not want to reduce integration to a stimulation of economic growth (Hadj Abdou, 2019).

INVENTORY OF GOOD PRACTICES RELATED ON THE MIGRANTS' INCLUSION

Social and spatial inclusion in rural and mountain areas needs to be designed in a way that takes into account not only their population's diversity, but also the existing territory and communication infrastructures, as well as the orography of the terrain and the climate.

In this respect, the Aragon Regional Government, with its 'Comprehensive Plan for the Management of Cultural Diversity in Aragon, 2018-2021' has laid down the general principles that should govern all the strategies: equality, standardisation, globality, interculturality, integrality and accessibility.

Specifically, work has been underway since 2000 to guarantee access to the system's benefits, sometimes over and above state legislation provisions, as is the case with health care. Emergency measures are also being taken in the current pandemic situation. The social integration policy highlights include awareness-raising policies like the '1st Aragon Anti-rumour and Anti-Discrimination Strategy, 2020', or the 'Campaign against Racism and Xenophobia', and also the educational policies oriented at everyone –families and teachers alike– involved in the cultural and language integration of different individuals.

However, it is important to highlight a few ideas that encourage new practices tailored to rural and mountain areas. As we have seen, third sector organisations need to move to and stay in the rural environment, because

they would be closer to immigrants and be able to resolve their issues more effectively. Social acceptance, and therefore migrant integration, is easier in rural areas; however, it would be necessary to have more help in these areas to solve their problems (for example, reunification processes, renewal of documentation, etc.).

The analysis has also spotlighted a need to give civil servants ongoing training on immigrants' rights when they apply for welfare system resources. Also, in the immediate future, training must be provided on migrants' rights to recreate their culture of origin, in order they can keep their customs.

On the other hand, the right to become fully-fledged 'citizens' necessarily implies immigrants participating much more, which is not always something that they understand or do; that is why they need to be encouraged to set up immigrants' associations in rural environments. Along the same line, immigrants should be encouraged to join or take part in local social fabric associations, as this would facilitate joint social dynamics.

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MATILDE

9. SWEDEN

Country: Sweden

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1.1 POLICY OVERVIEW

Sweden has long been an attractive destination for voluntary and forced migrants, partially due to its liberal labor migration and asylum policies (Parusel 2016). Its asylum regime has become more restrictive in the wake of the 2015 refugee “crisis” (Migration policy institute 2018).” The Swedish authorities were not prepared to accommodate the arrival of 163,000 asylum seekers, which constituted the largest number of asylum seekers per capita of any European state (Swedish Migration Agency 2018). In November 2015, the government approved measures to reduce the number of asylum seekers (Government Offices of Sweden 2015). This response can be interpreted as a reaction to the large number of asylum seekers as well as a lack of solidarity among European Union member states on refugee reception (Shakra et al. 2018). The Swedish authorities implemented temporary border controls and identity checks in January 2016 and enacted the Temporary Aliens Act on July 20, 2016 (Law 2016:752, extended to July 19, 2021). Since then, persons whose asylum claims have been approved receive temporary residence permits, while the authorities previously granted permanent residence permits to recognized refugees and beneficiaries of international protection (Shakra et al. 2018). The requirements for family reunification and permanent residency have also been sharpened (Swedish Migration Agency 2020c).

The Swedish Migration Agency provides temporary accommodation for asylum seekers or they can arrange their own housing, for example by staying with relatives or friends (Reception of Asylum Seekers and Others Act, Statute 1994:137). In the latter case, asylum seekers are entitled to a daily allowance but no compensation for rent. Since 2016, municipalities are required to settle residence permit holders according to a quota system (Reception of Certain New Arrivals Act 2016:38). The placement of permit holders takes into account the labor market conditions, population size, previously settled permit holders and unaccompanied minors (ibid.).

The rights of migrants are stipulated in the Aliens Act (*Utlänningslagen*, Statute 2005:716), which includes provisions on long-term residence status, work permits, temporary protection, and refusal of entry and expulsion. The Aliens Ordinance (*Utlännings-förordningen*, Statute 2006:97) covers travel documents, identity documents, travel visas, residence, and work permits.

Foreign-born persons who reside in Sweden are eligible for generous education benefits, including free courses in Swedish for Immigrants (Education Act 2010:800). They can also apply for grants and loans from the Swedish Board of Student Finance (CSN) to enroll in adult education or at institutions of higher education (CSN 2020). The benefits for non-EU students, however, were considerably restricted when institutions of higher education started charging tuition fees in 2011. This measure reduced the enrollment of non-EU students from approx. 13,000 to 6,000 per year (Swedish Migration Agency 2020d).

Sweden has a universal welfare system that aims to provide high-quality welfare services to all its citizens “from cradle to grave” (Government of Sweden 2017). Migrants with residency permits can also qualify for these services, including child allowance, parental benefit, a housing allowance (if they have a low income), benefits during sickness, and old-age pensions (European Commission 2020). Since 2013, persons without a residence permit are entitled to the same emergency healthcare as asylum seekers (Swedish Migration Agency 2020d). Children without a residency permit have a right to full healthcare- and dental coverage (ibid.).

County Administrative Boards provide funding to civil society actors and adult education to develop early initiatives for asylum seekers (County administrative board 2020). These initiatives include Swedish language training, knowledge about Swedish society and the labor market, and health promotion.

Individuals from outside the EU/EES wanting to work in Sweden need to apply for a work permit via their employer. What is required - amongst other things - is a valid passport, an application made prior to arrival and the position needs to have been advertised in Sweden and the EU. Furthermore, the salary ought not to be below what in Sweden is referred to as '*kollektivavtal*' ('negotiated salary' or 'established/set salary'). An applicant cannot combine two jobs. The employer is responsible for the various forms of insurance. For the employee this means that the work-permit is only valid as long as the employment contract is valid. A contract can be renewed up to two years at a time while after four years an individual can apply for permanent residency (Swedish Migration Agency 2020e).

In an effort to circumvent the exploitation of migrant labor, the Swedish Migration Agency has demanded since 2012 that employers have to show that employees have guaranteed salaries and are able to document payments (ibid.). New legislation was introduced in 2017 to ensure that a work permit did not have to be rescinded when an employer made a minor mistake (Government Offices of Sweden 2017). In light of this, the

Migration Court of Appeal also concluded that minor mistakes should not warrant extradition. In 2019, almost 22,000 work permits were granted. The most common country of citizenship was Thailand followed by India and the most common occupational categories among labor migrants were berry pickers followed by IT specialists (Swedish Migration Agency 2020a).

Before 2009, the municipalities were responsible for new arrivals. The Act on Establishment Initiatives for Certain Newly Arrived Immigrants (2010:197) moved the responsibility to the Swedish Employment Service.¹⁹⁴ The latter has the overall responsibility for the establishment of certain newly arrived persons in the labor market and in society. From 1 January 2018, a new set of rules applies for immigrants with regards to working life and society. These rules are to a greater extent harmonized with the regulations for other jobseekers. In short, the rules mean that more provisions are included in regulations instead of laws; migrants will be assigned to a labor market program, the so-called '*Etableringsprogram*,' and have to create an individual action plan in collaboration with a case worker in the Swedish Employment Service. A proportionate action system was also introduced, which includes, among other things, warnings and suspensions (Regulation 2017:1172). An asylum-seeker is allowed to work (employed or self-employed) after he or she has applied for and has been granted 'AT-UND' status (an exemption for a work-permit), which in turn would allow the individual to receive a '*samordningsnummer*' (coordination number) as well as a tax-code (Swedish Migration Agency 2016).

The Swedish government runs business development support through ALMI, a national organization with regional offices. ALMI offers information about how to run a business, business development, innovation, and digitalization. ALMI also offers loans and connections to venture capital companies (www.almi.se). Besides ALMI, the Swedish authorities for business administration, the Swedish Companies Registration Office, the Swedish Tax Agency, the Swedish Agency for Economic and Regional Growth and the Swedish Public Employment Agency run the webpage verksam.se where all information regarding business and entrepreneurship and its relation to the authorities is gathered.

¹⁹⁴ The Act applies to new arrivals between 20 and 65 years old who have been granted a residence permit. It also applies to persons between 18 and 20 years old who do not have parents in Sweden (Act 2010:197).

CHALLENGES IN IMMIGRANT INTEGRATION IN SWEDEN

This section discusses several integration-related challenges that Sweden is facing. In particular, the section addresses issues related to the reception of asylum seekers, housing, education, language, and employment. These five topics emerged as the most addressed topics in the meta-analysis and were discussed in interviews with migration experts. Like other European states, Swedish immigration policy shifted from assimilationist to multicultural goals, and then reverted back to assimilationism when immigrants were deemed to be “insufficiently adapted to Swedish society” (Hoekstra, Kohlbacher, and Rauhut 2018: 10). The coalition government of the Social Democrat Party and the Green Party under Prime Minister Löfven (2014-18) supported the assimilationist agenda, illustrated by the abolishment of integration-related portfolios (ibid.). The Ministry of Justice is now responsible for issues related to migration and asylum policy (Ministry of Justice 2020).

When asylum seekers first arrive in Sweden, a number of state agencies as well as civil society and voluntary actors provide basic services. The cooperation between these actors, however, has been criticized by a government-issued report: “A lack of a holistic perspective and system thinking leads to long wait times, delayed establishment or return, as well as a high cost for society and the individual” (SOU 2018:22: 21). Asylum seekers have access to rudimentary language- and civics courses, but they spent most of their time waiting for a decision (OECD 2016). Since the number of asylum seekers in Sweden has declined considerably since 2016, the Swedish Migration Agency is now closing down asylum reception centers (SVT Sweden’s Television 2020a). This decision is a challenge for smaller (and often rural) municipalities, who are losing funding for basic services such as schools, bus lines, and other infrastructure.

Municipalities also struggle to maintain a high quality of social services for unaccompanied minors (Seidel and James 2019). For example, therapeutic care is lacking and unaccompanied minors have little everyday contact with supportive adults (Lundberg and Dahlquist 2012). While Sweden has a coherent policy concerning guardianship (Hedlund and Salmonsson 2018), the role of the guardian, who should only take care of legal questions, might be unclear to unaccompanied minors and the guardians themselves. This unclear role may contribute to insecurity on both parts (ibid.).

The availability of housing, both for asylum seekers and refugees, is another key integration challenge. When refugees have been granted a residence permit, they are assigned to a municipality. But they often have to wait until the municipality has secured suitable housing. During this period, refugees are not eligible for language courses and labor market preparation activities, as these are the responsibility of municipalities that have accepted the refugees. Refugees are disproportionately placed in remote locations that are facing high unemployment rates and population decline (Wennström and Öner 2019).

In an effort to more equally distribute refugees among municipalities, the Law on the Reception of Certain New Arrivals Act (Government Bill 2016:38) implemented a quota system to allocate refugees. This system has, however, had unintended consequences. Several municipalities have engaged in social dumping of refugees. The municipalities receive compensation from the central government for 24 months.¹⁹⁵ Toward the end of the two-year period, some municipalities with housing shortages have secured housing in another municipality with vacant rental properties. These tend to be located in less affluent, often remote, municipalities, sometimes far away from the cities where the refugees were initially settled (Tenant's Association 2020a). The refugees then become the financial responsibility of the recipient municipality (Tenant's Association 2020b).

Refugees are assigned to a municipality after they have been awarded a residence permit, but they tend to relocate soon after resettlement. This results in a high level of internal migration of refugees in Sweden (Statistics Sweden 2016; Laine and Rauhut 2018). The majority of refugees has moved five years after their arrival in Sweden, and most settle in Stockholm, Gothenburg and Malmö, Sweden's three largest cities. The majority of refugees who arrange their own housing are also residing in these cities (Statistics Sweden 2016) (for more research on refugees' residential patterns, see (Vogiazides and Mondani 2020; Kadarik 2019; Åslund and Rooth 2007).

¹⁹⁵ Municipalities are reimbursed by the central government for the reception of asylum seekers and newly arrived immigrants, including the provision of housing, SFI, and civic orientation courses. The reimbursement system, however, is cumbersome and expensive (Swedish National Audit Office 2017). Municipalities receive reimbursement for 24 months (Swedish Migration Agency 2020b). After that period, if refugees are not able to provide for themselves, they become the financial responsibility of the municipality in which they reside.

In order to reduce residential segregation in socio-economically disadvantaged neighborhoods, the Own Housing Proposition (commonly known as *EBO law 2019/20:10*), now includes a provision that asylum seekers who move to these neighborhoods may lose their daily allowance (Swedish Migration Agency 2020f). The decision for this provision was justified by the Minister of Justice and Immigration, Morgan Johansson, as “It is necessary to come to terms with the increasing segregation and other programs that the own housing for asylum seekers can entail, especially in areas with socioeconomic challenges” (Government Offices of Sweden 2019). It is currently too early to assess the outcome of this new law.

It is important to note that the Temporary Aliens Act (2016:752) has had severe humanitarian consequences. According to this law, refugees and beneficiaries of humanitarian protection are now awarded temporary permits, and the requirements for permanent residency and family reunification have been sharpened. The uncertainty of being able to stay takes a toll on refugees’ mental health. The new regulation is particularly taxing for beneficiaries of humanitarian protection, who are awarded 13-month, renewable permits. The temporary status makes it difficult to access healthcare services, and the restrictions on family reunification have resulted in long-term separation of children from their parents (Swedish Red Cross 2018).

The Temporary Aliens Act requires a minimum level of income and standard of housing in order to qualify for permanent residency. This regulation pushes many refugees to prioritize employment over continuing education, resulting in a loss of competence for Swedish society (Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions [SUHF] 2020). SUHF calls for a change in the requirements for permanent residency, and advocates for a faster validation of migrants’ knowledge and skills.

Courses in Swedish for Immigrants (SFI) are available free of charge to all foreign-born persons who reside in Sweden, but the learning outcomes have been disappointing (Lundgren, Rosén, and Jahnke 2017). According to the Education Act (2010:800), SFI courses should provide freedom of choice and flexibility, adjusted to individual needs (Ministry of Education 2013). The heterogeneity of immigrants (in terms of f. ex. country of origin and level of education) makes it difficult to cater to all immigrants’ needs (ibid.). In addition, recent arrivals have a lower level of education compared to previous arrivals (Swedish government inquiry 2019). Refugees with low levels of education tend to experience difficulties with learning in general, often live in segregated areas, speak

their native language at home, and tend to have a large linguistic distance between their own language and Swedish (Ek, Hammarstedt, and Skedinger 2020). These factors make it difficult for them to learn Swedish.

The Swedish labor migration regime was reformed in 2008. The new system is described as the most liberal labor migration regime within the OECD (OECD 2011). Emilsson (2015) has highlighted Sweden's uniqueness as its migration system does not differentiate between high and low skilled labor migrants, highly and low-skilled occupations or occupations with and without labor shortages. It does not provide preferential access to more or better economic or social rights, or easier access to permanent residence permits. Emilsson also found that labor migrants more often work in low-skilled occupations where there is a surplus of labor, compared to native-born workers.

Research has also highlighted the difference in salaries between Swedish-born and people born elsewhere (Joyce 2015) as well as a gap in gainful employment. Similarly, Gustafsson et. al. (2016) highlighted that individuals who are born in middle- or low-income countries who immigrate after age 50 do not seem to get a foothold in the Swedish labor market. Sandberg (2017) refers to Sweden's 'poor record' regarding to labor market integration as have others, such as Parusel (2020) and Joyce (2015). They highlight factors such as language, age, education, etc. as factors that contribute to low labor market outcomes.

However, Larsson (2017) has highlighted that early interaction with the Swedish Employment Service has paid off.

Regarding poverty, a high share of immigrants lives under the poverty line. This issue was already identified in the 1990s (Rauhut and Lingärde 2014). Poverty among immigrants continues to exist as Statistics Sweden has noted that a larger percentage of employees born outside of Sweden risk falling beneath the poverty line, based on income and after tax (Statistics Sweden 2020). Gustafsson et al. (2018) also highlight the fact that migrants tend to enter the labor market later or in some cases never and therefore have not been in the position of accumulating savings. Poverty among immigrants is also the case in Dalarna, our study region (Broström and Rauhut 2017).

1.2 STAKEHOLDER INTERVIEWS

METHODS AND ETHICS ASPECTS

We conducted semi-structured interviews with five key informants at the regional and national level.¹⁹⁶ All interviews were conducted digitally due to corona restrictions. Before the interview, respondents were provided with a one-page information sheet about the project and contact details for the involved researchers, a letter informing about their rights and how the collected material would be used, and a consent form. At the beginning of each interview, respondents were asked to fill in the consent form and they had the opportunity to ask questions about the project and the consent form. The interviews were recorded, and the researchers took notes during the interview. The notes were analyzed using the framework provided by MATILDE.

LOCAL ECONOMIC STRUCTURE

Tourism is a very important employment sector, and Dalarna accounts for the fourth largest number of 'guest nights' behind the three largest regions in Sweden – Stockholm, Goteborg and Malmö (Swedish Agency for Economic and Regional Growth (*Tillväxtverket*) 2017). The agency also highlights the fact that Dalarna –in comparison with the rest of Sweden – has fewer small enterprises.

Both in Dalarna and in Sweden as a whole, the proportion of employed persons has increased in recent years. The difference in employment rates between those born in Sweden and abroad is large, which can largely be explained by the fact that it takes time for new arrivals to establish themselves in the labor market (Region Dalarna 2020).

¹⁹⁶ We planned to conduct interviews with six informants and numbered them 1-6. Informant 1 had to postpone the interview, therefore the interviews included in this report are numbered 2-6.

The healthcare sector employs most people in Dalarna, followed by industry, retail, education and financial/business services. Employment in healthcare, education and the private sector has increased during the years 2008-2016. Employment in the public sector also increased, one reason is the increase in refugee migration to the region (Swedish Public Employment Service 2018). Immigrants are also employed in the forestry sector, mainly from Europe but also Ukraine and Thailand.

ARRIVAL AND ARRANGEMENT OF HOUSING

As a result of the increase in asylum applications in 2015, many individuals who were granted a residence permit were experiencing long waiting times to be settled in municipalities. As discussed previously, municipalities are required to settle permit holders within two months of being granted residency (Reception of Certain New arrivals Act 2016:38). One informant argues that this measure was necessary to even out the reception of asylum seekers, even though it interfered with municipalities' autonomy. The informant also confirmed migrants' tendency to move onward, either to other rural municipalities or mostly to more urban settlements (Governmental organization, interview 4).

The law on government benefits stipulates that the benefit follows the individual. When a person moves to another municipality within the 2-year establishment period, the "new" municipality will receive the remaining benefit. Some smaller municipalities miss out on this opportunity because they don't have a designated person who is knowledgeable and has time to apply for this funding. Thus, rich communities have an advantage (Governmental organization, interview 5).

ECONOMIC INTEGRATION AND IMPACT

Two stakeholders in our study primarily regard the third country nationals' (TCNs) effects on the economy in the municipalities as positive (Governmental organization, interviews 4 and 6). One representative mentioned

that shops and schools have been “saved” or even established because of the arrival of migrants in some places (Governmental organization, interview 6).

More important is however that the newcomers fill vacancies in the labor market and contribute to the maintenance -or even growth- of the local population (Governmental organization, interviews 4, 5, and 6).

“The importance of the migrants for maintaining local services and a local economy is clear. This, together with humanitarian reasons and prospects of turning a negative trend regarding the population, is probably an important reason for welcoming migrants”(Governmental organization, interview 6).

“In some municipalities in-migration is decisive for population development” (Governmental organization, interview 4).

Informant 2 also stressed that individuals should find employment to be able to ‘secure their own income,’ but acknowledged also the barriers that migrants face when seeking employment.

The effects of the Reception of Certain New Arrivals Act counteract such strategies to some extent. Several municipalities want to take in more refugees, especially if they are experiencing declining populations. But according to the new law they are not allowed to do so, as refugees should be more equitably spread among municipalities. Other municipalities want fewer refugees, but are supposed to receive their share (Governmental organization, interview 5).

However, one informant also emphasizes that it should be recognized that Sweden might be the country in Europe with the highest barriers to work if one has limited education and a lack of language proficiency. So called “low threshold jobs” have disappeared in the processes of streamlining and labor market regulations, even though the situation differs between municipalities (Governmental organization, interview 6). A report from Region Dalarna (2020) states that the employment rate in the region is significantly lower for persons with a foreign background. However, it is possible to identify an effective integration process over time, in the sense that persons born in Sweden with foreign-born parents are employed to a much greater extent than foreign-born. Their employment rate is higher in places with a larger share of tourism-related work opportunities according to the same informant (interview 6). This relationship has also been highlighted in

national media exemplified with a case in Dalarna, with the headline: “More refugees find a job in the countryside compared to those living close to metropolitan areas.” Figures by Statistics Sweden, reported by Swedish Television, show that rural municipalities with a base in tourism have the highest labor market participation among refugees who arrived in 2015 (SVT Sweden’s Television 2020b).

One policy that is aiming at increasing migrants’ participation in the labor market is “*instegsjobb*” (step-in-jobs) (Regeringskansliet 1997). This labor market measure was introduced in 2007, targeting newly arrived migrants. An employer can apply for a subsidy covering 80 percent of the salary (limited to 800 SEK/day). The employment should be combined with language training (SFI). The Swedish Public Employment Service manages this support, which targets both immigrants and established entrepreneurs. One informant means that politicians have a responsibility to create a basis for integration. She tells about her own experiences of hiring individuals with a migrant background using the step-in-job program. She argues that information about this opportunity needs to be improved, and cites a humanitarian and economic incentive to participate:

“The municipality needs to inform about these favoring conditions. It might be a large step to employ someone. /.../ You need to have an interest to make it work. To realize that someone who will come and work with subsidies is not a 100 percent worker. /.../ You can make a contribution as an entrepreneur; it is a win-win-situation”(Regional organization, interview 3).

The Federation of Swedish Farmers (LRF) also works with integration. A recent project is “*Nya nätverk för jobb på landet*” (New networks for work in the countryside). The aim is to find positions for vocational training or employment for young adults. They initiate processes where entrepreneurs within the agriculture sector and local public employment agencies cooperate.

The overall impression regarding economic integration is summarized by an informant representing a governmental organization. When migration streams are low, there is a positive attitude, and many municipalities would like to receive a larger number of migrants. This is because there is a need for workers in some sectors, to increase the population, and they know that they have a good record in helping newcomers find employment. When streams are large, the receiving capacity might not be strong enough and some municipalities say that they cannot manage. Another aspect is that a certain number of migrants is needed in order to uphold certain activities (Governmental organization, interview 4).

MIGRANTS' ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Migrants start businesses to a higher degree compared to Sweden-born. In rural areas and smaller towns all kinds of restaurants and food-shops are run by individuals with a migrant background, *"You can see that it works"* (Regional organization, interview 3). The migrants thus fill an important role in increasing access to private service and creating meeting places. Another informant adds that migrants start businesses with low pay, integrating the business with life in general (Governmental organization, interview 6). Research has shown that foreign-born entrepreneurs have a higher level of education compared to Swedish-born, and that their jobs require relatively low qualifications. This research indicates that foreign-born entrepreneurs are overqualified for the jobs they perform (Eklund et al. 2016).

SERVICES: BARRIERS AND/OR ENABLERS

Access to services of good quality varies. The problems are due to an uneven geographical distribution and access to information, rather than a lack of resources, one informant says. Good service exists, but not necessarily in the place where the migrant lives. This can also explain why the process of establishing oneself takes a long time (Governmental organization, interview 6).

Before 2009, the municipalities were responsible for the new arrivals. The Act on Establishment Initiatives for Certain Newly Arrived Immigrants (2010:197) moved the responsibility to the Swedish Employment Service and most of the resources were also transferred (Governmental organization, interview 4). At that time the Swedish Employment Service had local offices in almost every municipality. This shift is described as bit "messy":

"They turned their backs on the municipalities and took over everything. Rather than expressing that both are of equal importance. The municipalities have a responsibility for reception, SFI (Swedish for foreigners) and the local perspective"(Governmental organization, interview 4).

“The municipalities experience that they are a bit lonely with the responsibilities for new arrivals, and they do not have the mission in formal terms, and not the resources.” (Governmental organization, interview 4).

A disadvantage when the Swedish Employment Agency is decreasing its presence on the local level is that: *“...knowledge about the local labor market, the local business life and the local employers risk to get lost.”* According to an informant, this local knowledge is crucial for being able to implement smart and individual solutions. Close contacts with different actors are necessary, in addition to knowledge about the character of the local labor market. These kinds of relations and local conditions do not appear in statistics, it is about meeting each other and discussing needs and matches (Governmental organization, interview 4).

There is a need for people to fill vacancies in many municipalities, and if people do not find employment, they need support from the municipality and the municipality will lose tax income. Despite these incentives, it is not always possible to find employment. One reason might be the lack of local anchoring by the responsible institution (The Swedish Employment Agency) and a centrally governed authority does not necessarily work under such incentives (Governmental organization, interview 4).

SOCIAL INCLUSION

Social inclusion is discussed in relation to work and leisure. A job is seen as a pathway to social inclusion because it offers a social context, colleagues and daily routines. Knowing the language is the road to get a job and to be socially included. One informant means that the combination of language classes and vocational training is the preferable way to reach inclusion (Governmental organization, interview 4).

Inclusion is probably easier to reach in already existing activities, rather than through new initiatives (Governmental organization, interview 4, Regional organization interview 3). Ordinary associational life, especially sports associations, are thought of as contributing to inclusion. The range of civil society activities vary geographically, but generally rural areas host more activities compared to urban areas. Examples of activities are language cafés, leisure activities and other social activities. However, one informant says, these activities should be seen as complementary. The linchpin is all public (state, region, municipal) activities and

measures. Sometimes the media exaggerate the role of civil society, which is not to say that it is unimportant (Governmental organization, interview 6).

In Dalarna, civil society has shown to be important, particularly in the initial phases of reception and welcoming into the local community. This is shown for example in the arrangement of language cafés (Dalademokraten 2016) and the collection and distribution of furniture and clothes. An informant noted a strong mobilization of civil society in the wake of 2015, and that it continues to play an important role in language training and other types of support (Government interviewee 2). Another issue concerns the participation/engagement of TCNs in voluntary organizations, information regarding this issue is limited.

One informant means that there is a strong regional identity in Dalarna, and that it involves proudness and a will to cherish this identity. This might also lead to social barriers and to difficulties in accessing the labor market. In addition, peoples' everyday life is busy and it might prevent from establishing new contacts.

"Someone said; 'first there is [the work with] the wood, after that comes the potato harvest and then the elk hunt!' And this is essential. That you are busy and there is no interest for getting to know someone else. It might also be fear for what is new."(Regional organization, interview 3)

In relation to the question whether migrants contribute to integration processes, one informant adds that migrants (if we think about asylum seekers) probably are very busy with their own process of establishing themselves. Thus, they are less active in finding ways to contribute to integration processes in the society in a broader sense (Governmental organization, interview 6).

COVID-19

The Covid-situation has had an impact on language training (SFI) as lessons are now offered online. Also, activities offered by the Swedish Employment Service are carried out digitally. This is not an ideal situation for the target group, which often has limited educational backgrounds. Informant 2 highlighted an issue with the digital divide, i.e. that not everyone had good access to Wi-Fi, etc. In addition, relevant agencies struggle to get

the information about Covid-19 out to a range of groups in the appropriate languages. Some municipalities have decided to offer the participants another opportunity to participate in the course. This means that the establishment period is extended (Governmental organization, interview 4).

Many newly arrived work in services that are heavily affected, such as restaurants and hotels, with a high competition for these jobs (Governmental organization, interview 4) (but see also (SVT Sweden's Television 2020b), which reports that refugees are more likely to be employed in rural areas than in commuter cities).

PUBLIC POLICY AND TENSIONS ABOUT MIGRATION

Many municipalities experienced tensions during the years 2013-2015 when the number of immigrants reached a peak. The Swedish Migration Agency established asylum centers / housing for asylum seekers, and entrepreneurs could establish housing companies as the Swedish Migration Agency needed places to rent. In some places, inhabitants expressed fear while in many others they organized collection and distribution of clothes and furniture. Some municipalities experienced these opposite expressions at the same time. (Governmental organization, interview 4)

When problems occur, they often relate to a large reception volume compared to the size of the population in place (Governmental organization, interview 6). In some municipalities, competition regarding access to resources and services is causing the tensions. Substantial consequences might occur in the wake, for example that health centers are increasingly burdened (Regional organization, interview 3). When schools are crowded and there is a lack of teachers the whole population is affected, and the municipal economy is weakened.

"Suddenly people experience that it is a year's waiting time to get a dentist appointment" (Governmental organization, interview 6).

"Housing is sought where there is a supply and where it is cheap and where it is empty. For a period, the population may consist of 10-20 percent asylum seekers. Of course, it has an impact" (Governmental organization, interview 4).

“They [the Swedish Migration Agency] has never had as their mission to defer to such circumstances. /.../ From the state perspective, perhaps it is not motivated to consider such factors /.../ it is for a limited time. Time-limits are stretched out, people are rooted, they might stay when they have received a permit and it might be hard to absorb that many.”(Governmental organization, interview 4)

One aspect of the tensions is the time frame and the “moment of surprise.” A preparing dialogue was missing between the state and the municipalities. If the inhabitants and civil society were informed beforehand and would be able to prepare, it would probably contribute to a smoother process (Governmental organization, interview 4). Part of the solution is also to work for a more even national distribution (Governmental organization, interview 4 and 6) increase the possibilities to dialogue, and making sure that the local context and local possibilities are both recognized and used in a fruitful way (Governmental organization, interview 4).

Social polarization is an expected outcome from in-migration according to one informant. Labor market participation is crucial to counteract this process. A weak socio-economic position needs to be handled immediately, and at this point civil society is an important actor for example by providing second-hand consumption alternatives or “libraries” offering sport equipment (Governmental organization, interview 6).

SOCIAL ECONOMY

Knowledge about the social economy is scarce among the informants. They know that it exists, but it seems to be a sector one either is involved in and informed about, or not. One interpretation is that the links between the social economy actors and public (regional and national) actors could be improved. One informant mentioned that a colleague is working with these aspects and that the organization has arranged a conference on the theme. (Governmental organization, interview 4). The county is also organizing activities to promote the social economy (Governmental organization, interview 2).

During site visits in our case study municipalities in Dalarna we learned that social enterprises exist, but they are not common. Some social entrepreneurs have been involved in integration activities. We expect to gather more information when we approach the local level.

1.3 CONCLUSION - SOCIAL POLICIES

In the wake of the 2015 refugee “crisis,” Sweden has become a less-welcoming country for asylum seekers. It has become more difficult for forced migrants to obtain permanent residency and to bring their family members. In addition, anti-immigrant sentiments have intensified, illustrated by the rise of the Sweden Democrats party. Despite this unfriendly context of reception, Sweden continues to provide generous welfare benefits for immigrants. Once a TCN has obtained a residence permit, he or she has the same right to welfare services as Swedish-born persons. This social security net, as well as a high quality of life, continues to attract immigrants to Sweden. The number of asylum seekers, however, has declined considerably since 2016.

Sweden is facing several migration-related issues, especially since the rapid rise in asylum applications in 2015. One of the key policy challenges concerns the housing situation for refugees. Many municipalities have struggled to provide accommodation within two months after a person has been granted a residence permit, as they are required to do by law. In addition, the newly implemented housing law has had unintended consequences. Municipalities who want to welcome more refugees are not allowed to do so, while some municipalities try to relocate refugees who have been assigned to them. In addition, refugees tend to move away from their initial place of residence, especially if they were placed in remote locations with high unemployment rates. Over time, they tend to move to cities, settling in low-cost housing areas where immigrants are over-represented. This is also the case for refugees who arrange their own housing. A new law aims to discourage refugees from settling in residentially segregated areas by withholding their benefits. It is, however, too early to assess the outcome of this measure.

Our interviews have identified three center-periphery challenges in migration governance. First, larger municipalities tend to allocate funding for staff who work with migration issues, while smaller municipalities are less able to afford this service. The imbalance in staffing contributes to inequalities in funding and reimbursement between larger and smaller municipalities. Staff members who work on migration-related issues tend to be more informed about funding opportunities and reimbursement rules, generating revenue for larger municipalities that are already better-funded. Second, the settlement of refugees in rural areas has

helped to offset population decline, and generated funding for schools, shops, bus lines, and other local services. The closing of reception centers in rural areas, as a result of the decline in the number of asylum seekers, is likely to negatively affect the provision of services in rural areas. Third, migrants may experience a lack of high-quality services in remote areas and may have to travel to access these services.

Another policy challenge concerns language education. While many Swedes speak English, Swedish language proficiency is necessary for many types of employment. Municipalities offer Swedish for Immigrants (SFI) for all non-Swedish speaking residence permit holders, free-of-charge. The quality of the language courses, however, has long been an issue of concern. For smaller municipalities with fewer SFI students, it is more difficult to offer individual and flexible course options. Sweden's largest cities, on the other hand, offer profession-specific language courses that cater to highly skilled migrants.

In Sweden, the national government funds most social policies, allocated at the national scale, and distributed to agencies at the regional and local scale. Municipalities are in charge of language courses and civics courses and are financially responsible for refugees if they are not self-sufficient after the two-year establishment period has ended. Regions are in charge of healthcare services and transportation, and the county and administrative boards play a coordinating role in the delivery of services and allocation of resources. This system requires a large bureaucracy and coordination efforts, with some gaps as discussed by our expert informants. Voluntary organizations try to fill some of these gaps through language cafés, sports teams, clothes- and furniture donations. These efforts tend to be more prevalent in rural areas, but asylum seekers and refugees may experience social barriers in joining these organizations.

The covid-19 pandemic has turned Sweden's gaze inward, as in other European countries. The primary concerns are now about health and the high unemployment rate. The integration of immigrants currently receives less public attention, except for media attention to immigrant criminality and residential segregation. The funding for integration efforts may be negatively affected by budget reallocations in the near future, but it is yet too early to tell.

1.4 CONCLUSION – ECONOMIC POLICIES

While migration certainly changed the economic landscape in Sweden, the country is facing an array of challenges with regards to integration. Employment and integration into the labor market are some of these challenges. Research cited in this report and elsewhere has highlighted the salary-gap between native-born and foreign-born, as well as the difficulties for migrants and asylum seekers to get a foothold in the labor market. The gap in employment between native-born and foreign-born individuals in Sweden is larger than in most other high-income countries. Research has highlighted a range of factors such as the prospects for migrants -regardless of their background- to find employment, such as knowledge of the Swedish language and the challenge of availing themselves of Swedish for Immigrants classes (SFI), as highlighted in the section above. Similarly, for highly skilled migrants such as doctors and nurses, acquiring the necessary credentials can be a laborious process. The age of arrival is also a significant factor in employment rates as well as level of education.

The introduction of new legislation for labor migration in 2008 resulted in a shift from supply-driven to demand-driven labor migration from countries outside of the EU. Whereas other countries have tended to limit the inflow of low-skilled migrants, competing for highly educated migrants through various forms of supply-driven policies and programs, Sweden did the opposite by shifting to a non-selective demand-driven labor market migration model. The reform aimed to ease labor shortages while meeting the demographic challenges of an aging population. Migrant workers tend to work as computer programmers, civil engineers, and berry-pickers, as well as in low-skilled professions. Emilsson (2016) has noted a slight overrepresentation amongst professions where there already is a surplus, such as kitchen staff and cleaners.

As highlighted in the interviews, initiatives such as '*instegsjobb*' (step-in-jobs) are not widely advertised, and more information is needed in immigrant communities as well as participating agencies. Here it is also worth highlighting the current restructuring of the Swedish Employment Agency and whether the agency will remain in place. Some of the agency's work will be complemented by private actors who prepare job seekers for employment.

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MATILDE

10. TURKEY

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AFAD	- Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency
AFIP	- Act No. 6458 on Foreigners and International Protection
CCTE	- Conditional Cash Transfer for Education
COVID-19	- Coronavirus Disease 2019
DAFI	- Albert Einstein German Academic Refugee Initiative
DGMM	- Directorate General of Migration Management
ESSN	- Emergency Social Safety Net
EU	- European Union
FRIT	- Facility for Refugees in Turkey
FRiT	- Facility for Refugees in Turkey
GDLL	- General Directorate of Lifelong Learning
GDP	- Gross Domestic Product
ILO	- International Labor Organization
IPA	- Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance
IPC	- Istanbul Policy Center
MoH	- Ministry of Health
MoNE	- Ministry of National Education

- NGO - Non-Governmental Organization
- PEC - Public Education Center
- PIKTES - Promoting Integration of Syrian Children into the Turkish Education System
- RWPFTPS - Regulation on Work Permit for Foreigners under Temporary Protection Status
- SOYBİS - Social Assistance Information System
- SPI - Small Projects Istanbul
- TCN - Third-Country National
- TEC - Temporary Education Center
- TL - Turkish Lira
- TÖMER - Turkish and Foreign Languages Center of Ankara University
- TPR - Temporary Protection Regulation
- TPS - Temporary Protection Status
- TRC - Turkish Red Crescent
- UNDP - United Nations Development Programme
- UNHCR - United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
- UNICEF - United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
- WHO - World Health Organization

1.1 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC RELATED POLICIES REGARDING INTERNATIONAL MIGRANTS¹⁹⁷ (PARTICULARLY SYRIANS UNDER TEMPORARY PROTECTION) INTEGRATION AND IMPACT IN TURKEY IN GENERAL AND KARACABEY, BURSA IN PARTICULAR

Turkey has always been a country of migration. The population movements from rural to urban which started in the 1950s have continued; migration to European countries began in the 1960s in the form of labour migration and was followed by various forms of commercial migration. Thus since the early 1990s, Turkey has also been experiencing in-flows of transit migrants, refugees, asylum-seekers, diverse forms of irregular migration and increasing number of foreign residents. Turkey has now become both a country of emigration and immigration (İçduygu & Kirişçi, 2009; Erdoğan & Kaya, 2015). This overview generally considers existing national policies, although the province of Karacabey, Bursa is the selected MATILDE region. Considering the highly centralized governance in Turkey, any separate urban-rural/mountain linkages with the national policies is hard to be raised at this level.

Since 2011, with Syrians, Turkey for the first time has to adopt its policies as a migration receiving country. Syrians, escaping from an internal war and searching for a safe place since 2011, were accepted as “guest”, with no legal status (Uyan-Semerçi & Erdogan, 2016). Contrary to right-based approach, humanitarian support to Syrians were first maintained by charity, most of the time with religious references, by state agencies and NGOs. Thus, as the numbers and duration of their stay increase, their status and the rights including access to basic rights had to be rearranged and Syrians are granted the “temporary protection” status in 2014 by Act No. 6458 on Foreigners and International Protection and Temporary Protection Regulation (AFIP). Syrians under

¹⁹⁷ TCNs are not an applicable term in the Turkish context. Therefore, instead all international migrants are considered.

temporary protection status benefit from health, education, access to labour market, social assistance, and interpretation services which will be provided according to these regulations.

As of 07.10.2020, the number of Syrians under temporary protection is 3,627,481, and then almost a decade after, in line with their legal status, they are still regarded as “temporary”. The table provided in the Annex (Annex I) contains selected social and economic policies on international migrants, particularly Syrians under temporary protection status. With the rising anti-immigrant attitude, there is still a long way to reach harmonization, integration of migrants, especially Syrian refugees, to education system since 2014 and access to minimum healthcare for all residents, including the undocumented should be noted as positive developments, as part of Turkey’s new integration policies. Thus still, international migrants are excluded from conventional political participation in Turkey.

Overall, regarding the high increase in human mobility due to the instability in the region and therefore the flow of Syrians towards Turkey and, therefore the intensive policy-making process in last ten years; this review centre mostly upon the policies and regulations on Syrian population. Nevertheless, although most of the policies and regulations seem to be indexed for Syrians under temporary protection, some determine the rights of foreign population, either resident or under international protection, and provide for general rules for the functioning of related policies.

HEALTH POLICIES

Access to health care is a constitutional right, in parallel with the international consensus on the recognition of health as a fundamental right (Diker, 2018). The General Health Insurance Scheme, introduced in 2006 with its new version (Act No. 5510) to create a unified health insurance, covers most of the population in Turkey, including foreign residents who do not have social security coverage in their home countries (Bilecen & Yurtseven, 2018).

The health care for foreign nationals has gone through a comprehensive change over the last ten years with a number of regulations specifically for Syrian migrants. At first, since Syrians were regarded as “guests”, the issue was handled in terms of an emergency (Uyan-Semerçi & Erdoğan, 2016). In this conjuncture, Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency (AFAD) was the initial authority responsible of regulating all services, including health, for Syrian migrants (Bilecen & Yurtseven, 2018).

The major step was the adoption of the Act No. 6458 on Foreigners and International Protection (AFIP), which provides that those under international protection status who are not covered by any medical insurance and do not have the financial means to do so to be covered by Turkey’s general health insurance scheme. So, asylum-seekers and persons under international protection status has currently covered within the General Health Insurance coverage (Act No. 5510) with a change adopted in AFIP (AFIP 4/4/2013-6458/123 art.). Although the AFIP does not specify the case of Syrians, the Article 91 introduced a legal basis to the adaption of Temporary Protection Regulation (TPR) which applies to migrants arriving from Syria. The Article 27 of TPR (Regulation No. 29153) specifies the health services to be provided to those under temporary protection. Accordingly, all Syrian refugees both inside and outside the camps can have free access to medical treatment, but only on the condition that they have to be registered by Directorate General of Migration Management (DGMM) (Bilecen & Yurtseven, 2018; Syrians in Turkey, 2018).

Primary health care services are provided by existing Public Health Centers (PHCs) and Family Health Centers (FHC). The system based on the long-term residence seemed essentially insufficient for irregular migrants and asylum seekers who frequently had to change their residence places. In this sense, establishment of the Migrant Health Centers (MHC) as an additional unit to PHCs was the subsequent step to follow in 2015 (MoH, 2015c). Each MHC is envisaged to serve 4,000-7,000 Syrians in places where Syrians under temporary protection live collectively (Özkul, 2020; Yıldırım et al., 2019). Each of these centers have a translator to ease the health service delivery.

When the COVID-19 epidemic broke out in March 2020, the most important development in access to health care is that testing for and treatment of the virus was included in the ‘emergency’ scope on April 9, 2020.

Afterwards, by the President's Decision No. 2399 dated April 13, 2020, all personal protective equipment, tests, kits and medicines to be supplied and distributed under the scope of pandemic are included in the scope of exemption on healthcare spend as of March 1, 2020.

EDUCATION POLICIES

Turkish education system, briefly, points to a strong authority of the state (McCarthy, 2018; Sunata & Abdulla, 2020), despite long-standing controversial issues such as native language education, religious education, and privatization (Sunata & Abdulla, 2020, p. 4). The Ministry of National Education (MoNE) is responsible for planning, implementing, monitoring and inspecting education and training services at all levels.

Within the already-vulnerable context for children in Turkey (Uyan-Semerici et. al., 2013; Uyan-Semerici & Erdogan, 2017; 2018), more than 1,500,000 Syrians under TPS are children. Whereas the school age-population for Syrians for the 2019-2020 academic year was 1,082,172 (DGMM, 2020). The total number of Syrian children in formal education was 684,728 (UNICEF & MoNE, 2019).

Following the first wave in April 2011, the socio-political discourse of temporariness was reflected in the manner towards the access of Syrian children to the education in Turkey (Sunata & Abdulla, 2020, p. 4). Through the early regulations issued by MoNE, the education for Syrian refugee children was only envisaged for those in the camps. The courses were also conducted in Arabic through the Temporary Education Centers (TECs).

However, upon the prolongation of Syrians' guest status, MoNE issued two separate circulars in 2013 to make regulations on the education facilities in and out of camps. Education is defined as a right for those under TPS by the Temporary Protection Regulation. In order to eliminate the barriers in front of the foreigners in accessing formal and non-formal education services, MoNE issued a Circular No. 2014/21 on "Education and Training Services for Foreigners" on 23 September 2014. This circular set the standards for educational services to be offered to Syrians which will be evaluated in the part of literature review.

Moreover, in order to coordinate and respond the education needs of Syrians, the Department of Migration and Emergency Education was established and the MoNE has adopted the approach through which it ensures that all children under temporary protection receive the same standard and quality within the formal Turkish education system (UNICEF & MoNE, 2019). To this end, TECs established for Syrian children have been gradually closed since 2017.

The numbers of Syrian students under temporary protection in higher education/universities during the 2018-2019 academic year were 27,034. The majority of those enrolled in higher education are following a BA program in universities (75%) (UNICEF & MoNE, 2019). Albert Einstein German Academic Refugee Initiative (**DAFI**) and **IPA scholarships** are scholarship programs that have been provided to Syrian students who are having formal education at the level of bachelor's degree at the state universities (in total only around 15% of Syrian university students receive a scholarship) (Erdoğan, 2020).

There are a number of projects concerning educational support for the Syrian children. The Project on "Promoting Integration of Syrian Children into the Turkish Education System" (**PIKTES**) is implemented by the MoNE and funded by a direct EU grant within the scope of the Facility for Refugees in Turkey (FRIT) agreement.¹⁹⁸ A national social assistance program implemented since 2003, The **Conditional Cash Transfer for Education**¹⁹⁹ (CCTE) was extended to Syrian and other refugee families in mid-2017. In addition to formal education, several channels have been provided by both the MoNE and also municipalities as well as civil society organizations. **Public Education Centers (PECs)** are the ones operating across the country and conducting age-specific Turkish language modules for foreigners and developing modules for language proficiency levels. Free vocational trainings are provided by PECs and funded by the General Directorate of Lifelong Learning (GDLL) in the MoNE.

¹⁹⁸ See more <https://piktes.gov.tr/Home/IndexENG>

¹⁹⁹ Conditional Cash Transfer for Education (CCTE) Programme for Syrians and Other Refugees, <https://www.unicef.org/turkey/en/media/10876/file> (latest access, 15 October 2020).

POLICIES ON SOCIAL SUPPORT AND SOCIAL ASSISTANCE

Currently, social support activities for refugees and migrant groups are carried out by different ministries and municipalities. Moreover, since the early period of Syrian crisis social assistance has also been one of the largest domains of NGO emergency field activity, while their social assistance programs differ in their perspective and scope (Yilmaz, 2018).

The launch of the aid program called **Emergency Social Safety Net (ESSN)**, an EU-funded cash assistance, is considered a shift in the center of gravity from NGOs to domestic public actors (Yilmaz, 2018). The ESSN is a multi-purpose cash transfer program for vulnerable refugees living outside of the camps across Turkey to cover their basic needs.

Humanitarian assistance programs are still provided in sense of emergency support for Syrian refugees in Turkey, although the current situation in Turkey can no longer be treated simply as an emergency situation (Yilmaz, 2018). With the fragmented structure of social services in Turkey, there has still been a structure in lack of integrity or a holistic approach. This problem has been tried to be solved by the Ministry of Family, Labour and Social Policies through SOYBİS (Social Assistance Information System). However, the absence of municipalities in this system continues the risk of duplicates in social aids (Temel & Tüfekçi, 2018, pp. 88–89), as municipalities have been at the forefront of providing public services and support for the Syrian refugees and they developed varied responses (Betts et al., 2020; Coşkun & Uçar, 2018). To overcome financial constraints, actively engaged municipalities seek external funding through establishing partnerships with NGOs and international actors.

ECONOMIC POLICIES: PARTICIPATION TO LOCAL ECONOMY AND LABOR

In terms of migrants' participation in the local economy and the labour force, TCN's are not part of the natural actors in the labour market. Therefore, they need to pass through a formal recognition procedure to be able to enter into the labour market regardless of their residence status. The recognition of the right to work, covering both employment relationship and self-employment, may be deemed as the primary policy device in this regard.

Under Turkish law, there exists different category of rules applicable to different migrant statuses: migrants with Turkish origin, regular economic migrants, migrants under international protection regimes such as refugees, conditional refugees, subsidiary protection status, temporary protection status beneficiaries , turquoise card for qualified foreigners.

Regarding the access to the labour market, the Regulation on Work Permit for Foreigners under Temporary Protection Status (TPS) issued in 2016 is one of the major policy instruments that directly condition the impact of Syrian migration on the economy. To access the labour market, temporary protection status beneficiaries need to obtain either a work permit or a work permit exemption. An overall look at the access of Syrian immigrants to the labour market under an employment contract reveals a multilayer restriction mechanisms:

Spatial restrictions: Work permits may be granted only in provinces wherein they are allowed to reside. Therefore, the right to have access to the labour market is restricted with their right to reside.

Quota system: There exist different quotas aiming to control the number of temporary status beneficiaries at workplaces and sectors. Thus, the number of temporary status beneficiaries cannot exceed ten per cent of the number of Turkish citizens working at the workplace. If the number of employees is less than ten at the workplace, maximum one TPS beneficiary may be granted a work permit. Quotas also exist for work permit exemptions.

Seasonal agriculture and live-stock works are exempted from the work permit requirement. TPS owners also need to proceed with a formal exemption certificate. These works fall, in principle, out of the scope of Labour Act providing the most extended protection to workers. Nevertheless, the Ministry is also authorized to set quotas to the number of TPS beneficiaries wish to work in seasonal agriculture and live-stock works (art. 5/5 of RWPFTPS). Unlike EU regulations, not all seasonal works but seasonal agriculture works are exempted from work permit. Therefore, for example, those who wish to take a seasonal job in the tourism sector need to have a work permit. And not all TCN but only TPS beneficiaries may benefit from this exemption. Therefore, we could detect an implicit policy of placing TPS beneficiaries in jobs less preferred by locals.

TPS beneficiaries do also need a work permit to start a business as self-employed, however restrictive regulations do not apply to self-employed TPS owners.

To sum up, forcibly displaced migrants and TCNs are subjected to similar rules in respect of their access to the labour market under an employment contract. Nevertheless, reading between the lines of regulations, we may detect the aim of protecting local workers against the vast Syrian recruitment at workplaces and sectors. Thus, the main economic policy may be deemed the “controlled integration” of TPS beneficiaries into the labour market.

1.2 OVERVIEW ON EXISTING ANALYSES AND ASSESSMENTS OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC POLICIES

This review handles the existing analyses and assessments of social and economic policies within a general and centralized perspective without making a separation between central and local policies. This is mainly because, as briefly emphasized in the first section, the Republic of Turkey has a unitary structure in terms of public administration. Local administrations were established to provide services by the governors and other senior public officials appointed by the central government and the mayors, who govern the municipalities, are elected. Formal social policy in Turkey includes, basically, the state-provided free education at primary, secondary and tertiary levels, and a combined public health and pension system associated with employment status (Buğra & Keyder, 2006, p. 213).

RIGHT TO HEALTH

The existing literature (Önder, 2019; Bilecen & Yurtseven, 2018) focus on three main stages for Syrians' access to health services from the beginning: (1) initial responsibility of AFAD to regulate all services including health for those living in camps, (2) expansion of Syrians' access to the health services to those locating in the eleven provinces bordering Syria²⁰⁰ (AFAD Circular, 2013/1 No. 374), and (3) in the final stage, broadening to cover all 81 provinces (AFAD Circular, 2013/8 No. 12816). But the field researches in that period revealed that especially access to follow-up visits was problematic except for the emergency services (Dinçer et al., 2013). During this period, several NGOs were involved in providing health services mainly to those non-registered and living outside the camps (Dinçer et al., 2013; Önder, 2019).

²⁰⁰ Hatay, Osmaniye, Kilis, Kahramanmaraş, Gaziantep, Şanlıurfa, Adıyaman, Adana, Mersin, Malatya, Batman.

In the meantime, as mentioned above, the major step was the adaption of the AFIP in 2014 introducing a legal basis to the adaption of TPR which applies to migrants arriving from Syria (Diker, 2018). Under the regulation, Syrians have direct access to medical treatment for primary and emergency health services without paying patient contribution fee. But to access secondary and tertiary services, Syrians can be treated with referral certificates (MoH, 2015b; Alp et al., 2018; Assi et al., 2019; Bilecen & Yurtseven, 2018).

Residence location is an important determinant to access healthcare services for Syrian migrants. Those under temporary protection and living outside the camps can go to healthcare institutions in the city of residence where they are registered. This obligation prevents refugees living outside the city where they are registered for any reasons such as job opportunities, family visits and education, from accessing health (Özkul, 2020). **Lack of information** is another problem because the rules change frequently. For these reasons, Özkul (2020) indicates that many refugees prefer to apply the health care when their health situation deteriorates rather than accessing routine health check. Assi et al. (2019) also states effectiveness of healthcare services for refugees is limited by **language barriers** (Mardin, 2017), **mobility** of the refugees and some **legal restrictions**. They conclude that the current migration rules do not enable refugees to access all human rights, mainly due to the increase in number of refugees. They suggest a multi-dynamic refugee-friendly system, the provision of preventive health care and increasing the number of both national and international organizations may help improve the health of refugees. The field report conducted by the Association for Migration Research (GAR) with the support of Citizens' Assembly (Sevinin, 2020) indicates the complications of the Turkish healthcare **bureaucratic system** and the lack of multilingual and multicultural rights-based approaches. Accordingly, this makes it more difficult to navigate the system for those unfamiliar with the system. Their observations also show that the current healthcare system systematically excludes **migrant communities except for those who are under temporary protection**. Faced with these problems, immigrant communities that seem to be deterred from applying to formal health services develop their own alternative strategies. Also, Önder (2019) states the necessity of a permanent solution, alternative to the temporary protection policy, in the long run. She points out that by ensuring that Syrians also take responsibility for their lives, integration can be accelerated. Specifically, in the field of health, it will be possible to reduce costs.

Besides the obstacles, Sevinin (2020) remarks **migrant networks** which play a crucial role not only in providing and disseminating information about healthcare services but also in establishing solidarity networks such as

creating an informal insurance fund for healthcare expenses, accompanying each other to hospitals and offering translation services. Also, Özçürümez & İçduygu (2020), in their study, draw attention to the contributions of **MHCs** in terms of overcoming the language barrier through the translation service and, of providing employment to the migrants by employing Syrian health personnel.

As regards to the **pandemic process**, right before the COVID-19 pandemic, a bill (Law No. 7196) amended the Article 89(3)(a) of the AFIP. Accordingly, those who have no medical insurance and do not financial means to pay, are subject to the provisions of General Health Insurance (GSS) as to be limited to one year after the registration for international protection. This decision **differentiated access to health care** between those who have international protection status and those not. Upon the amendment, many national, regional and local associations prepared a joint assessment (MÜLTECİ-DER, 2019) to indicate that such a provision would limit the right to health of thousands of individuals who cannot obtain work permits, have no regular income, and who are subject to physical and psychological problems because of forced migration; and it will cause serious injustice and violations.

Many migrants who has not currently have work permit and regular income did not have access to health when the epidemic broke out in March 2020. Although COVID-19 testing and treatment was included in the 'emergency' scope on April 9, 2020, and protective equipment, tests, kits and medicines to be supplied and distributed under the scope of pandemic are included in the scope of exemption on healthcare spend as of 1 March by the President's Decision No. 2399, fieldwork researches displays that irregular migrants are afraid of being deported, being fired or dispossessing, so they do not want to go to health institutions (MUDEM, 2020; Özkul, 2020). However, in their field research, Sevinin (2020) finds out that the main problem migrant communities faced during the pandemic was less health-related than economic.

RIGHT TO EDUCATION

Turkish education system, briefly, points to a strong authority of the state. Research findings display that the **highly centralized governance** does not allow much rapid response to external changes as it has been at play during the Syrian refugee crisis and the lack of local-to-national policy alignment causes hindering refugee education development (McCarthy, 2018; Sunata & Abdulla, 2020).

The main issue is how the existing rights and provided facilities turn into **actual capabilities**. Considering the financial vulnerability of refugee families, as Uyan Semerci & Erdoğan (2018) indicates, **material conditions** in which the child lives define her propensity to fail to start, to continue and to complete her education. The conditions such as income and education levels of Syrian families, employment status of parents and language ability play a role even in immigrant children's school participation.

The **language barrier** is among the serious obstacles to integrate the Syrian refugees into the education and social cohesion as well as social integration (Özçürümez & İçduygu, 2020). In addition to formal education, several channels has been provided by both the MoNE and also municipalities as well as civil society organizations. Each channel targets different groups in a broader sense. For instance, Public Education Centers (PECs) are the ones operating across the country and conducting age-specific Turkish language modules for foreigners. Nevertheless, access to Turkish language courses in PECs is seemed to be limited. The main problem is stated that most children who have participated in language courses have only reached the first stage of basic proficiency and therefore require further support (UNICEF & MoNE, 2019). Nimer (2019) also emphasizes the capacity rarely meets demand, also resources are often limited, and the waiting times between the courses are long. According to her research results, students find the duration of the courses too short, especially in more advanced levels. More importantly, the certificates provided by the centers are recognized nationally but not by universities, in higher education. On the other hand, accessing language education in private centers (e.g. TÖMER, Turkish and Foreign Languages Center of Ankara University) is costly and so it is inaccessible for many Syrians, especially for those who have difficult financial situation and those supporting family members by working. Nimer (2019) states that this is particularly difficult for those who needed to study at TÖMER centers to pursue their studies. Although the duration of courses is longer and provide enough time to learn Turkish in advanced level, the course duration does not offer enough time flexibility and opportunity for those who work.

Civil society organizations (CSOs) are also involved in language education through supporting the formal channels (Nimer, 2019). At first, in an ad hoc manner, a variety of CSOs offered language instruction at the beginning as part of emergency response. However, particularly due to the state of emergency in 2016, on one hand many CSOs were shut down and the government began to control all educational activities provided to Syrians, including language instruction. According to a circular issued in 2017, all educational activities by CSOs

with international funding require approval from the ministry (Ibid., pp. 13–14). Permission for the language courses for foreign organizations is given for only one year; it requires renewal for every year while for the local ones this period is up to three years. Collaboration with CSOs can take different forms in collaboration with municipalities or PECs. However, this is believed to be inefficient, because the new procedure resulted in a loss of funds and lack of quality control; on other hand it seems to be under better control though. This process is also described “as a shift toward a more centralized system” through protocols and “more support to existing organizations seems to be favored by actors in state institutions” (Nimer, 2019, p. 15). This brings a criticism on that once the funding stops, the state’s centralization efforts are not sufficient to ensure **long-term sustainability** (Ibid., p. 16).

Regarding the **unaccompanied minors** and education, access to up-to-date statistics on unaccompanied minors is currently not possible. Although there is no information about the current numbers of unaccompanied children in Turkey, especially with regard to highly predictable increase in following the Syrian flow to Turkey, Düzcel and Aliş (2018, p. 261) indicates the number of unaccompanied minors who sought asylum between 2005 and 2012 is 352 mostly from Afghanistan, Somalia and Iran. According to an information provided by a stakeholder, in February 2018, the vast majority of unaccompanied children applying for international protection in Turkey originate from Afghanistan. Unaccompanied minors over age 18 remains outside the protection system provided to unaccompanied children in Turkey. They fall in more disadvantaged position for both extending protection and therefore for their education. The related law on the placement of Turkish children under protection into a job (Art. 66 of LFIP) also does not cover unaccompanied children after the abolition of their protection. In that sense, Beyazova (2019) emphasizes the importance of providing **vocational education** to the unaccompanied minors before the age of 18. Despite this fact, there is a considerable need for capacity building for vocational education and a need for raising awareness in this sense among the unaccompanied youth. This seems a challenge for accessing vocational education.

Considering **education during COVID-19 pandemic**, the overall analysis on the distance education indicates the main problems arising from the difficulties in accessing television, computer and/or the internet to participate in distance education and also having no suitable studying environment at home. According to a survey, 48% of the children enrolled in schools did not have access to distance education (SGDD-ASAM, 2020). In another research (Beyazova et al., 2020) conducted during the first quarter of 2020 during the pandemic, it

is observed that refugee families are under intense pressure due to unstable economic conditions, cannot afford food and rent expenses, and feel high anxiety about their near future. Refugee families, who generally live on the ground floors of apartments with insufficient ventilation and sunlight, often share their homes with others due to high rents. These conditions make it difficult for Syrian refugees to take the protection measures taken during the Covid-19 process. These conditions also negatively affect the children to follow distance education from home. Also, one of the mentioned difficulties during this process is that Syrian children have not been able to get enough support from their parents because their Turkish language levels are not good enough. Özkul (2020) also states that problems in education also negatively affected those who took the High School Transition System (LGS) exam in Turkey.

SOCIAL SUPPORT AND ASSISTANCE

Social assistance have traditionally been one of the least developed policy domains of Turkey's welfare system (Yılmaz, 2018). Buğra & Keyder (2006) describes that in the absence of meaningful social assistance schemes, many have no choice but to rely on family ties in risk situations. The family still continues to be the pillar of Turkish welfare regime; however, the state, too, historically an important player as employer and provider. Formal social policy in Turkey includes, basically, the state-provided free education at primary, secondary and tertiary levels, and a combined public health and pension system associated with employment status (Ibid., p. 213). Since the early period of the 2000s, there has been an increase in the share of public expenditure on social assistance schemes, and their scope has been extended. Still, Yılmaz (2018, p. 8) defines that "the main feature of social assistance programs in Turkey is their categorical feature targeting 'the deserving poor'", which implies a targeted social policy.

In terms of the social support for migrants and refugees, it is difficult to talk about the existence of an institutional social support regime until 2011. Temel and Tüfekçi (2018) examines the changes and transformations in the social assistance policy for immigrants and refugees in Turkey. They states that social aids provided to migrants and refugees were carried out in tandem with poverty assistance programs in terms of welfare state regime. The legal status of migrants and refugees is considered for the first place in the field of social assistance. Priority is given to cognates who migrated to settle in Turkey (Ibid., pp. 93-94).

Temel and Tüfekçi (2018) point out the **fragmented structure of social services**; and from a legal perspective, they underline that the social assistance system is not regulated through the lenses of absolute right. In this sense, while it is observed that there is an effort to build a system for social aids provided by different units for migrants and refugees, there has still been a structure in lack of integrity or a holistic approach. The existence of many different institutions leads to the recurring of aids.

Municipalities have been at the forefront of providing public services and support for the Syrian refugees and they developed varied responses (Betts et al., 2020; Coşkun & Uçar, 2018; Kaya & Kırac, 2016). The services covering a wide range of activities have already been provided by many municipalities under the poverty aid for Turkish citizens living in their district; and, with the arrival of Syrians, they were extended to Syrians (Kale & Erdoğan, 2019). In time, the emergency response activities turned into local efforts in order to support social cohesion between the local people and refugees. In the absence of a clearly defined understanding of social cohesion, Kale & Erdoğan (2019, p. 229) states the general understanding was to keep *solidarity* among fellow citizens or avoid tensions.

However, due to the vagueness of their specific mandate towards refugees, or non-Turkish citizens broadly (Betts et al., 2020; Kale & Erdoğan, 2019), municipalities affected by the Syrians' arrivals have faced two main challenges (UNDP, 2018; Betts et al., 2020; Coşkun & Uçar, 2018; Kale & Erdoğan, 2019). The first challenge is the **ambiguity of the legal framework**. The political authority of municipalities concerning refugees are not formally laid out in the legislative framework. To respond to the needs of refugees, many municipalities have acted with reference to the maximalist interpretation of Art.13 of the Municipality Law (No. 5393), defining any resident of a town as a "fellow citizen" (hemşehri) who has the right to get municipal aid. The second challenge is about the lack of a specifically delegated central-government funding for refugees. Since the amount of the budget allocations from the national budgets are indexed to the Turkish population, the presence of refugees does not lead to an increase in allocations. Moreover, in terms of their own budgets as the second way of revenues for municipalities, the handicap is that refugees do not contribute to the municipalities' budgets because they do not pay local taxes since they are not citizens (Coşkun & Uçar, 2018). So, the limitation on the **financial resources** becomes a critical issue. The researches have pointed out, for instance, an increase in demand for infrastructure services such as garbage and wastewater that have to be compensated without any extra budget (Coşkun & Uçar, 2018); and the concerns of municipalities about criticisms from local residents

who do not feel comfortable with the usage of municipal resources for non-citizens (Kale & Erdoğan, 2019). As emphasized earlier in the first section, through establishing partnerships with NGOs and international actors, actively engaged municipalities seek external funding to overcome financial constraints.

ECONOMIC POLICIES

Even though no study has been done on the impact of the Syrian migration on the overall economy of Bursa, the research so far seems to indicate that the impacts are similar to those on the Turkish economy in general. A recent econometric analysis by Tunaer-Vural (2020) shows that the overall impact of the Syrian migration on the GDP of Turkey is positive. A one per cent increase in the population is found to be associated with a rise in production by nearly 1,2 %. The impact of forced migration on general employment is found to be insignificant. This result is in line with the findings in some previous work (Akgündüz et al., 2015; Del Carpio and Wagner, 2015).

The inflow of Syrian migrants in the labour market seems to have no significant effect on either the wage rate or the unemployment rate in Bursa (Saraç & Keskin 2019). This seems to confirm the general conclusion that there is no serious competition between the Syrian migrants and the domestic workers in the formal economy. However, the availability of a cheaper alternative in the market is always a factor that creates downward pressure on wages.

The main reason why the formal employment figures seem unaffected is that more than 95% of the migrant workforce are employed in the informal sector (Erdoğan 2019). As of May 2019, employment in the informal sector makes up 34.3% of the total employment in the Turkish economy (Ibid). The informal economy renders all above-mentioned restrictions useless. Also, the informality endangers migrants' social security needs not only for today but also for the future. Act No. 5510 describes long term insurance branches as those of invalidity, old-age and survivors insurances. To be entitled to old-age, invalidity or survivors' pensions, Act No. 5510 foresees a system mainly based on two variables: the duration of the insured period; and the numbers of days that the insured person paid contributions. The absence of contribution payments will certainly make their

entitlement to pensions more difficult. That will affect not only their income level but also their access to health care in the future, while pension receivers and their dependents are considered as universal health insurance holders and receive health care services without being obliged to pay any health insurance contributions.

We must emphasize the fact that the two major policy tools that condition the impact of the Syrian migration on the economy, namely, the Regulation on Work Permit for Foreigners under Temporary Protection Status and The Emergency Social Safety Net (ESSN) seem to have a direct bearing on the scope and extensity of informal migrant labour. ESSN aid is given to each member of the migrant family provided that none has a formal employment. This is believed to prevent many Syrian refugees who are eligible for ESSN aid from applying to jobs in the formal sector. In a similar vein, the spatial limitation imposed by the work permit regulation prevents many refugees from applying to jobs outside the provinces they are registered in. This is especially the case for the Syrian migrants who are employed in the seasonal jobs in the agricultural sector.

Saraç & Keskin (2019), analyzing primarily the impact of Syrian migrants on the textile sector in Bursa, argue that the migrants entered the sector both as workers and entrepreneurs and both were highly welcomed. Even though no data is available, the interviews mentioned below in this policy analysis implicate that the employment of Syrian migrants in the sector is substantial. The main reason for this is the unwillingness of the local population to work in the sector. The working conditions in the sector are considered to be rather harsh and the noise pollution and widespread use of chemicals in almost every stage of the production are important factors that create the unwillingness of the local population. It is also argued that local population prefers to be employed in the services sector (mostly in malls) where the wages are not lower than they are in the textile sector. Another factor that contributed to the substantial employment of Syrian migrants in the sector is the fact that many are already skilled and had been working in the textile sector in Syria. The employers in the sector are reported to say that they are extremely happy with the coming of the Syrian migrants because they close the deficit not only in the supply of unskilled labour but of the skilled labour as well.

Saraç & Keskin focus on the Syrian migrant entrepreneurs in the textile sector as well. Again it seems that many of them preferred Bursa specifically because it has a developed textile sector. With 77 foreign firms with Syrian partners, Bursa is the fourth province, as of 2019, among those that host the most Syrian-invested firms. As

mentioned before, the Syrian entrepreneurs brought not only capital but their business web as well. As a result, most of the firms they set up are exporting textiles to the Arabic countries. Furthermore, the inputs of these firms are mainly supplied by domestic firms.

1.3 ASSESSMENT OF THE STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF POLICIES THROUGH SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

To assess the strengths and weaknesses of policies with regard to the integration in Turkey and the selected case Karacabey, Bursa, semi-structured interviews with eight actors were conducted in November 2020 (Annex II). Applying purposive sampling, interview persons were selected based on their competence regarding the themes of the policy brief and comprised policy makers, public officers and representatives of professional associations as well as practitioners and organizations working on migration-related fields. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, four interviews were conducted by using the conferencing tool Zoom and the remaining four were conducted as face-to-face interviews. After having received the interviewees' consent, all interviews were audio-recorded. Afterwards, they were transcribed verbatim and were analysed using thematic analysis.

FINDINGS

MIGRANT POPULATION IN KARACABEY, BURSA

Bursa, fourth most populous and industrial city located in north-western Turkey, is a city of migration. With its closeness to Istanbul, not only with the current Syrian migrants but different migration flows from the Balkans, the Crimea and the Caucasus and internal migrants have been part of city as stated in almost all the interviews.

Thus the current migrants, profile of Syrians, are described with low levels of education and rural background in all interviews. The place of origin, the qualifications and the jobs they had in Syria play a role in their current capabilities and network:

“The Syrian population entering Turkey from the border is a population coming from the north of Syria, already from the rural area, and this population’s relation with means of living has always been based on rural activity. It’s based on agriculture, on farming; only very few of them, especially those who come from Aleppo are able to get into trade. Of course, we can see that the traders are establishing a trade network here. But for the

agricultural workers, we see that they are in a partial idle state. Because they don't have their own land, or a land which they can cultivate. Those who can work as seasonal agricultural workers do work but this has no social security nor guarantee.”(Country & Regional level, INGO, Informant 4)

The business sectors Syrians work in Bursa are textile; automotive and furniture. However, as Syrian workers mostly work informal and unregistered, they are working in the workshops or small ateliers, or in seasonal agriculture.

LOCAL ECONOMIC STRUCTURE AND THE ROLE OF MIGRANTS IN SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

With its developed industrial, agricultural and service sectors, Bursa's economy is among the top four cities in Turkey. This is one of the main reasons why the province has historically been very attractive to immigrants. There are three big companies; Tofaş, Renault and Bosch. These big companies feed sub-industries. Gemlik district has the free zone which has its advantages. There is industry and agriculture in Karacabey, Kemalpaşa regions.

Thus, immigrants particularly prefer Karacabey, the Matilde local region, due to the availability of job opportunities. Whereas rural Karacabey hosts Syrians who come to the region to work as seasonal agricultural workers, mainly tomato, the rural area mainly hosts permanent migrants who work in factories and workshops. Some immigrants also work in jobs which locals do not want to. However, lack of exact data is underlined in the interviews, stating that there are recently Afghans who have started to come to work in husbandry.

“As for Karacabey, it's a place that receives seasonal agricultural labor migration. But they have conducted this through the workers mostly from Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia, such as Diyarbakır, Urfa and Mardin. However, it is said that Syrian refugees are also included within this population recently. But I will remark again, unfortunately there's no clear data. We don't know this clearly; are these Syrians currently resident in Bursa or are they the ones who come with local people from Diyarbakır, Urfa and Mardin, who are resident there?”
(Country & Regional level, INGO, Informant 4).

None of the interviews provides any facts or narratives regarding a negative impact on the economy of Karacabey or Bursa. Thus, this can be explained with the profile of the interviewees, e.g. policy implementers affiliated in Provincial Directorate and Metropolitan City of Bursa, or in local level, Karacabey. The positive economic impacts, on the other hand, are more visible. The interviews make it clear that the availability of migrant labor for those sectors not preferred by the locals, such as agriculture and textile, seems to have been very fortunate for those sectors.

“It is said that Syrians are the drivers of the furniture industry there. They say that before they came, the shortage of intermediate staff was very serious; that they couldn’t find a person to work anymore but now this gap is closed. (...) Syrian people prefer to establish small independent businesses in their own way. Or they prefer to participate in small activities that will revitalize Arab tourism, such as translation. This is also valid in other provinces. Apart from that, we can say that they almost closed the intermediate staff gap in textile industry. (...) Arab tourism has been developed.” (Regional level, Provincial Directorate, Informant 1)

“The blow to the textile industry that started gradually after the crisis in 2012 affected Bursa very much, many workshops and people were also affected. But I can say that with the migration, Syrians have made them a little more active. (...) The Syrians’ engagement in this process, either as an additional job or as a resource, has mobilized the textile industry. They have made positive contribution. (...) With the Syrians, an alternative workforce was established in all those areas. (Regional level, Bursa Metropolitan Municipality, Informant 2)

Another channel through which Syrian migrants positively affected the local economy is their transfer of capital and business relations to Turkey. It is also raised during the interviews:

“They have entered the textile industry with their own capital. This also provided mobilization, contributing to the dynamism of this process” (Informant 2). The entrepreneurial capacity, particularly in trade is really high. With a technical and legal support, some establish their own company and have a comparative advantage of having access to Middle Eastern network.

The unitary and centralized character of the state and non-inclusive character of policy-making are noted in the interviews. Furthermore, as elaborated in the quote below, both public and private perceptions and implementation of regulations are shaped and reshaped through this:

“In fact, the processes related to migration are very connected with the central policies. I saw that it was the same in other provinces within the framework of some other projects. I mean, especially the Syrian migration continues in a more political conjuncture. That is why, within the framework of the state policy and the expansions it envisioned, I think that both the provincial administrators and economic leaders, sectoral leaders don’t act outside the vision of the state policy. This situation is the same in terms of both public and private sectors. Therefore, it cannot develop a policy as a city. In other words, there is no policy regarding the dynamics of your own city, neither in the context of adaptation nor attitude...” (Informant 2)

The limited resources and their distribution, with the existing number of Syrians and also local population who need social assistance and social services, is stated as one of the key problems:

“(...) perhaps a more holistic and long-term planning is required to be sufficient (...) But it is important for the European Union to move forward with a long-term projection and a more sustainable financing..

Each municipality has its own resources. The needs of using this resource may differ, at this point prioritizing the needs of the local people, more precisely voters, may be a political choice since they are the groups that come to power through an election.” (Informant 4)

NGOs therefore are crucial for providing support in Bursa, similar to other localities in Turkey.

Work permits are crucial as it means a real integration to labor market with social security, however as the following quotes demonstrate neither small business owners nor farmers can go over the procedures, financially and/or bureaucratically. Particularly in agriculture, workcover insurance does not exist:

“Of course, informality is the common practice in terms of employment. Governorships and district governorships are working on this. Last year, as best practice, a study was carried out, there was a circular of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in order to raise awareness about Syrians, employers were reached together with the personnel from the institution, and they were reminded that work permits should be obtained. It was said

that administrative sanctions would be applied to those who do not have work permits, but the pandemic started in the following process. (...) Of course, there are different reasons for this informality. What are the reasons? It is difficult to get a work permit. A process is required to get work permit. Also, the places where Syrians work may not be very institutional. They usually work in the service sector, and therefore small businesses. There may be cases that the employer does not want to deal with it. Generally, employing informally can be in favor of the employer; this is the situation.” (Regional level, ISKUR policy implementer, Informant 8)

DIFFICULTIES OF HARMONIZATION

As summarized in the second part of the report, temporary protection status provides legal foundation for accessing the rights, however there are obstacles to turn the rights into the capabilities, real opportunities people enjoy. In the conducted interviews; language, competition among the poor, and social exclusion have been stated as obstacles.

The most stated obstacle, at least in four interviews with respect to different policy areas, including health, is the language. The following quote reflects an example of a good practice “health mediators” for overcoming language barrier:

“When we say health mediators - who are selected among Syrians, who are Syrians and who provide that information flow, that is, bringing out the problem in the region where they are located and translating our language to them... that makes them trust us in the field, reaching more people in the field ... “ (Country & Regional level, INGO, Informant 3)

The tension between the locals and the Syrians, particularly among the most vulnerable groups is an issue that needs be carefully handled:

“At first, there was tension between those who lived on social assistance, saying “they get our bread, what we need to buy”. Were they wrong in that? Frankly, we tried to deal with that, but they were actually right. Because in the first wave of migration, all social assistance was directed to Syrians. And local people in need of social

assistance could not benefit from this. But it has been overcome immediately after a year, with the transfer of other sources.” (Informant 2)

For the harmonization, there is still a long way to go. Although the Provincial Directorate of Migration Management prioritizes, there is still a long way to social cohesion. The emphasis on how Syrians are living in a closed circle, with limited or no contact to locals demonstrates the lack of social cohesion.

“They are very comfortable, but not with the locals. They are with their own inner groups..

It is not possible to talk about a harmony or coexistence, but they do not have any trouble creating their own space. There is no pressure. So I think Bursa has that culture from the past, too. Because the city is used to different cultural groups anyway.” (Informant 2)

Although the common culture is underlined, the lack of contact is also stated as “living as two separate groups”²⁰¹, “no such thing as getting used to them”:

“There are small grocery stores and shops selling clothes. They are very nationalists and always go there. For example, there are Turkish grocery stores here, but they go to theirs even if it is far away.” (Local level, Karacabey, Informant 5)

Education is an important policy area for social cohesion. Thus, as observed in the field, education can be inclusive or exclusive. PIKTES is an example of good practice whereas bullying, combined with discrimination, is an example of reasons for drop-outs. An expert from Bursa Provincial Directorate also indicated the effectiveness of the project as well as the need of its improvement in approach by stating that *“There is a PIKTES project for education and it has been effective for a long time (...) maybe one further step could be done about the trainers. Children who need social adaptation, who cannot learn languages persistently, may be approached with more care than forcing them to continue to school, because there are children who are still*

²⁰¹ For more debate about the relevance of cultural similarities between the Syrians and the locals in Turkey see (Rottmann & Kaya, 2020).

traumatized, or the effects of the trauma emerge long afterwards. Counseling activities in schools can be expanded.” (Informant 1)

Furthermore, all the tensions and the problems are resulted in further exclusion and sometimes blaming the Syrians (Uyan-Semerçi & Erdoğan, 2020).

1.4 CONCLUSION

CONCLUSION FOR SOCIAL POLICIES

Inequalities and regional development gaps in Turkey cause limitations on the capabilities of the citizens (Karatay et. al, 2016). Poverty; informal economy; child labor and access to qualified education for all have been major problems prior to the arrival of Syrians (Uyan-Semerçi et. al, 2013; 2014 and Uyan-Semerçi & Erdoğan, 2017). 1950s onwards, rural-to-urban migration developed and caused the informal sector to expand. From the 1990s onwards, more urban problems have also emerged due to forced migration, mainly from Southeastern Anatolia (Erder, 1995). A number of very basic infrastructural problems still remain especially for socially excluded groups which also threaten child well-being (Uyan Semerçi et al, 2012; 2013; UNICEF, 2013).

Turkish welfare regime, similar to the Southern European model, regards the family as main actor, with different informal supports. The family still continues to be the pillar of Turkish welfare regime; however, the state, with its unitary character, too, historically an important player as employer and services provider (Buğra & Keyder, 2006). Although the current situation in Turkey can no longer be treated simply as an emergency situation with respect to Syrians, humanitarian assistance programs and the implementation of different policies and projects are still provided in sense of emergency support in the public view. And as expected, competition among the most vulnerable groups with respect to social assistances and job opportunities in the informal labor market create tensions, however the increasing anti-immigrant attitude is not only a result of this economic threat perception.

Although with the temporary protection status, the rights are legally defined, still access to these rights is limited with the existing conditions in the field. Not only in terms of availability of resources, which is definitely crucial, but also the perception of people at every level is important for developing and implementing policies for harmonization. The current situation in Turkey can no longer be treated simply as an emergency situation but meanwhile the change from emergency aid policies to integration policies is not easy.

Humanitarian assistance programs are still provided in sense of emergency support for Syrian refugees in Turkey (Yılmaz, 2018). The role of the public sector increases especially in social assistance and health care.

Despite the vagueness of their specific mandate towards refugees, or non-Turkish citizens broadly, municipalities also take active role.

Local authorities cooperate with civil society organizations in order to provide free services and orientation to Syrians about education, health services, and training opportunities. To overcome financial constraints, actively engaged municipalities seek external funding through establishing partnerships with NGOs and international actors. In other words, they have found out some “bypass methods” (Betts et al., 2020; Coşkun & Uçar, 2018). Local governments have no legal, financial, or political-administrative responsibility and authority. Although they are not active in the formulation and implementation of policies to tackle the refugee issue (Coşkun & Uçar, 2018), they are still important actors in the field.

Schools are crucial for current and future social cohesion, however, the conditions such as income and education levels of Syrian families, employment status of parents and language ability play a role in immigrant children’s school participation. Similar to the competition among the most vulnerable groups for receiving social assistance, the schools that are mostly populated with children of Syrian families are located in most disadvantaged neighborhoods and have limited resources. In order to realize the goal of inclusive education, there is a need to support schools at every level, from supervision to teachers to curriculum change.

Right to health is crucial, considering the vulnerabilities and existing risks even before COVID- 19, thus particularly those Syrians who work informally in seasonal agriculture or in other sectors, most of the time work in other cities than they are registered. The risks one faces by going to a hospital might seem to be more than by living with an illness and/or not getting health care. COVID-19 already puts enormous pressure on the available resources to health, including health workers. Another aspect to be underlined is the claim causing great tension that Syrians enjoy more rights and that they, without payment, have access to healthcare, whereas citizens of Turkey have to pay more. Non-Turkish citizens, mostly Syrians, are regarded as scapegoats (Uyan-Semerçi and Erdoğan 2020). They are to blame for the unemployment or insufficient social support.

Overall, Syrians are still not accepted as permanent part of the current and/or future society in Turkey and this dominant perspective has an effect on policy making and policy implementation. Thus, it is urgent to develop short, middle and long-term strategies for harmonization and the policy-making process should also be inclusive.

GOOD PRACTICES

The following two projects are good practices that are observed in the field and also underlined in the interviews:

“Health for Rural, Support to Rural” Project for refugees- Ministry of Health and UNFPA: Language barrier and lack of information are some of the key deterrents to the access to the right to health. Here, health mediators can be given as an example of good practice, as the right to health does not guarantee access to the right. Health mediators, chosen from the Syrian population, do not only make translations but also act as a mediator to solve communication problems and reduce socio-cultural barriers.

The Project on “Promoting Integration of Syrian Children into the Turkish Education System” (PIKTES) is a project in education sector/an education project implemented by the MoNE with a view to contribute to the access of Syrian children to education provided in state schools /to education. PIKTES is funded by a direct EU grant within the scope of the Facility for Refugees in Turkey (FRIT) agreement. The project was launched on October 3, 2016 and is still in operation in 26 provinces. PIKTES Project, which started its second phase in December 2018, will continue until the end of 2021. Within the large scope of the project, supports are provided to children, families, and schools in a variety of forms as well as cross-cutting services such as social cohesion activities²⁰² are enabled.

CONCLUSION FOR ECONOMIC POLICIES

Nation states have wide sovereign power not only in deciding on who will enter and stay in their territories but also on who will work in their labour markets. The protection provided by international law as well as national legal regulations contains subtle differentiations and restrictions as regards the labour rights of forcedly displaced persons. Work permit regulations applicable to Syrians under temporary protection status reveal the priority of local workers over displaced migrants in the labour market except for seasonal agricultural and live-

²⁰² See more <https://piktes.gov.tr/Home/IndexENG>

stock works. However, in terms of independent commercial activities, receiving independent work permits seems much less compelling. These observations confirm the argument that among many reasons causing the vulnerability of migrants in the labour market, the most striking is the law, itself, is becoming a source of vulnerability. (Mantouvalou, 2015, 49-51; Doğan Yenisey, 2019, 271).

As mentioned in the report, the impact on Turkey's GDP of the Syrian forced migration has been calculated to be positive as the theory predicts. Even though there is no calculation for the local level, the available research and the fieldwork carried out for this project implicitly show that GDPs of Bursa and Karacabey, too, were positively affected. This is especially true for the textile, furniture and agricultural sectors in which the Syrian migrant labor covered a deficit in labor supply. Similarly, the field work makes it clear that the contribution of the Syrian migrant entrepreneurs in the textile sector and some services like tourism and shopping is substantial.

The impact of the Syrian migration on the general price level, or more particularly on inflation, is positive and significant. The food and housing sectors are especially important because the demand shock hit those sectors directly and immediately. Even though the housing inflation in Turkey turned out to be affected by the shock, food prices do not seem to have been affected. It seems that the supply shock in the agricultural sector has played a compensatory role to stabilize the food prices. This also seems to be the case for Bursa and Karacabey because there is no mention of a rise in the food prices as a result of the migration of Syrians but one interviewer mentions that the rents have increased in districts where the migrants settled in great numbers.

As emphasized above, the impact of the Syrian migration on the formal labor market has been rather limited due to widespread shadow employment. The unemployment figures and wage rates in the formal sector have been found to be unaffected by the inflow of Syrian migrants. This seems to be the case for the local economy as well. Even though some interviewers expressed concern over a possible negative effect of migrant employment on local workforce, many have explicitly acknowledged the employment enhancing investments by the migrant entrepreneurs and the positive contribution of the migrant labor on the employment rate in the sectors not preferred by the local population.

An overwhelming proportion of the migrant workers are employed in the informal sector. The controlled integration policy does not work in practice. This may have important consequences both in the short run and

in the long run. Some of the short-run effects seem to be advantageous to both the migrants and to the local population. Firstly, the migrant workers can avoid the restrictions imposed by the work permit regulations. Bypassing the spatial restriction, sectoral restrictions and the quota system they can find work more easily and almost in any sector and in any region. Secondly, the informal sector generally comprises jobs that are not much attractive to the local population. Hence there occurs less competition in the labor market and hence less friction in social life between the migrants and the locals. However, not all Syrians benefit from good job opportunities even in the informal sector, the majority of them find themselves working dirty, dangerous and demeaning jobs under highly precarious and unsafe work environment. In the long run, such informality may also affect all social security rights of migrants, once the “temporary” nature of their stay is ruled out.

GOOD PRACTICES

To support refugees and host communities gain a living in decent working conditions, the ILO in Turkey is implementing the “Refugee Response Programme”. It is guided by a Programme of Support spanning from the years 2017 to 2021. The achievements of the programme include:

- Supporting employability of more than 23,000 refugees through skills development
- Gender equality supported through provision of gender-sensitive training
- 900 entrepreneurs trained and 150 micro grants awarded to support innovative business ideas
- More than 600 SMEs supported through business advisory services
- 2,340 Syrians. In total over 4,500 refugees and host community members have been employed formally with the support of the ILO
- 15% of all social security auditors, 20% of all labour inspectors and 20% of all labour and social security judges trained in the legal framework protecting refugees in the labour market.
- Another practice that needs mentioning is the “Turkey Resilience Project in response to the Syria Crisis (TRP)” financed by the EU Trust Fund in Response to the Syrian Crisis (EUTF). It is a two-year project with €50m budget focusing on promoting job creation, strengthening local government capacities and municipal services and delivering Turkish language training for Syrians in 11 provinces of Turkey. The Project will benefit 2,000 Syrians and host community members for employment and livelihoods,

52,000 Syrians for Turkish language training, and more than 307,000 Syrians and host community members for improved municipal services.

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MATILDE

11. UNITED KINGDOM

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1.1 OVERVIEW OF EXISTING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC RELATED POLICIES REGARDING THIRD COUNTRY NATIONALS INTEGRATION AND IMPACT IN THE UNITED KINGDOM AND SCOTLAND

MIGRATION POLICIES

The migration policies are reserved matter of the United Kingdom parliament²⁰³.

The Scottish Government is presently calling for greater influence over immigration policy arguing that the current system cannot respond to Scotland's specific migration needs notably in terms of migrants contribution to the population growth, specifically working age population in shrinking areas.

The existing main entry policies for TCNs include the Tier Points-Based Immigration System, the Overseas Domestic Workers (visa), the Asylum policy and the Resettlement schemes.

The **Tier Points-Based system (TPBS)** is a visa scheme aimed at workers and students: it regulates the migration to the country for highly-skilled workers (Tier 1), skilled workers with job offers (Tier 2) and low-skilled workers to fill specific labour shortages (Tier 3). A Shortage Occupation List defines jobs in short supply in the UK (and Scotland), these jobs can be filled by migrants under the Tier 2 route more easily than others. The Tier 3 was never implemented as all non-UK low-skilled labour requirements has been met by EU workers. The TPBS also allows the stay of Students (Tiers 4) and young people and temporary workers (Tiers 5), such as people whose primary interest to join the UK is not directly connected with the economy. Initially points were awarded on the basis of the characteristics of the applicants (e.g. qualifications) – more desirable migrants were awarded more points – but the system has evolved away from points towards requirements e.g. minimum pay threshold. This system developed in the logic of “Making migration work for Britain” aimed at identifying and

²⁰³ The Scottish Act (1998) regulates the devolution to the Scottish Government and lists the reserved and the devolved matters.

attracting “migrants who have most to contribute to the UK” and was supposed to “help deliver high-level benefits for the UK including increased economic competitiveness and cultural exchange” (HO 2016, p.1).

This structuration implies that highly skilled and potential healthier migrants are more likely of being allowed into UK; the system does not take into account regional differences in wages; it is demanding in terms of administrative requests as migrants (worker and students) must have a sponsor, being a sponsor requires a license and migrants must obtain a Certificate of Sponsorship (CoS), a form of work permit.

It is important to add that after December 31st 2020, the TPBS became the main gate for EEA migrants to enter and work in the United Kingdom (HO 2020). The EEA migrants who were in the country before December 31st 2020 are entitled to apply for the EU **Settlement scheme** and ask for a settlement or Pre-settlement status that allow them to access to health cares for free, enrol in education or study in the UK, access public funds such as benefits and pensions, and travel in and out of the UK without visa.

The **Overseas Domestic Workers** (ODW) intend to regulate the stay of Domestic workers travelling with their employers. The scheme that exist since 2012 has been recently discussed in the House of Commons because of the concern that the existence of a tie to a specific employer and the absence of a universal right to change employer and apply for extensions of the visa could potentially put ODW at risk of exploitation while in the UK (Gower, 2016).

Since the 1980s the **Asylum** seekers enter and access to welfare has been regulated in a progressive more restricting way (Asylum Act 1999 and its following amendments until The Immigration, Nationality and Asylum EU Exit Regulations 2019).

A person can claim asylum upon arrival in the UK at border control or after-entry to the UK and once made the asylum claim they have the legal right to remain whilst their application is considered. In order to be eligible for asylum in the UK, a person must either meet the 1951 Refugee Convention’s definition of a refugee or they should be at risk of suffering “serious harm” if returned to their country of origin. If an application is refused there is a time-limited right of making an appeal that will be considered by an Immigration Judge, who is independent of the Home Office. According to the Migration Observatory, of all applications received between

2012 and 2016 (116,390²⁰⁴), 55% resulted in a grant of asylum, humanitarian protection, or another form of leave, of those 38% at initial decision, the rest after the initial decision was appealed (Welsh 2020).

People whose asylum claims are granted are given permission to stay in the UK for five years with the same rights to work, study and access welfare benefits as British citizen/permanent residents. At the end of those five years the refugee must make a further application for permanent permission to stay in the UK. People whose asylum claims do not succeed are expected to leave the UK – refused asylum seekers may be put on regular reporting restrictions or be held in immigration detention to assure their removal.

Resettlement Programmes In 2015 the Home Office in collaboration with UNHCR, Local Authorities and NGOs launched the **Syrian Vulnerable Peoples Scheme (SVPRS)** aimed at resettling 20,000 Syrian refugees from refugee camps in Jordan, Lebanon, Iraq, Egypt and Turkey by 2020. It is numerically significant as it corresponds to about one third of all the Asylum granted between 2012 and 2016 (see previous analysis). After a suspension, due to Covid pandemic, the Home Office announced the programme will resume in 2021 until the 20,000 quota²⁰⁵. Resettlement schemes purposefully targets those in greatest need of assistance, they are not selective on the basis of employability or integration potential. The resettled population – as they hold the status of refugee – is allowed to work and eligible for mainstream welfare benefits. Local authorities and other partners receive funding to support SVPRS refugees in accessing education, employment, healthcare and other key services, as well as to encourage social mixing and integration.

A twin programme, the **Vulnerable Children's Resettlement Scheme (VCRS)**, has been launched in 2016 to resettle 3,000 vulnerable and refugee children and their families by 2020.

The scheme is aimed at children at a high risk of harm and exploitation along with their families, identified by the United Nations in refugee camps and other unsafe environments across the Middle East and North Africa.

²⁰⁴ Applications with a known outcome as of May 2019, excluding withdrawn applications.

²⁰⁵ The refugees resettled were 19,353 at the end of December 2019 (Wilkins 2020).

1,747 people had been resettled under the VCRS (end of December 2019) of them 57% were under the age of 18 at the time of resettlement.

Under the VPRS and VCRS schemes, a **Community Sponsorship Scheme** has been introduced by the Home Office as civil society wished to play a greater role in refugee resettlement, and with the expectation that the community-led approach will lead to positive integration outcomes for refugees and communities.

A further and pre-existent resettlement scheme, the **Gateway Protection Programme** (2004 – ongoing) aimed at offering a safe and legal route to the United Kingdom for the most vulnerable refugees – notably to people living in protracted refugee situations – allowed to resettle in the country about 9,862 people since its launch, mainly from Sub-Saharan Africa and the Middle East (Wilkins 2020).

Finally, the **Mandate Scheme**, the longest running refugee resettlement scheme caters for recognised refugees who have close family members living in the UK. It allowed a very small number of refugees to settle in the United Kingdom: only 430 people were resettled since 2004 under this programme (ibid.).

The British Government is currently discussing about the creation in 2021 of a global resettlement scheme that will incorporate VPRS, the VCRS and the Gateway and the community sponsorship scheme, as recommended by the UNHCR in 2017 (ibid.).

INTEGRATION POLICIES

Integration policies in the United Kingdom originates in the 1960s when they notably aimed at migrants from New Commonwealth countries and focus at addressing discrimination and racial hatred and on mechanisms to manage community relations (Broadhead 2020). The British approach to integration (see next section) produced few policies aimed at migrants – targeted notably through citizenship policy – and particularly focussed at the larger society.

In 2000, the Home Office established a **Refugee Integration Strategy** to support recognised refugees (i.e. not including asylum seekers) in their access to labour market, accommodation, welfare benefits, healthcare, education and language services and to encourage participation (Home Office 2000).

The 2001 British riots in Bradford, Harehills (Leeds) and Oldham (Greater Manchester) and the consequent Community Cohesion Report (2001) for the Home Office (known as Cattle report) affirming that “separate educational arrangements, community and voluntary bodies, employment, places of worship, language, social and cultural networks, means that many communities operate on the basis of a series of parallel lives.” (ibid. p.9) set the context in which the **Community Cohesion Policy Framework** has been developed.

This framework aims at building shared common values and cross community interactions, as well as to tackle inequalities. Community Cohesion has been defined as a common vision and a sense of belonging for all communities, positively valuating the diversity of people’s different backgrounds, similar life opportunities; and strong and positive relationships are being developed between people from different backgrounds and circumstances in the workplace, in schools and within neighborhoods (LGA, 2002).

At Scotland level the **New Scots Strategy** (2014-2017 and 2018-2022) – built with the Local Authorities and third sector organisations – aims at addressing the key issues of employment, education, housing, health, communities and social connections, and at coordinating the efforts of all organisations involved in supporting refugees and people seeking asylum. Its principles are: integration from day one (and not just once leave to remain has been granted), rights (empower people to know about their rights and how to exercise them), involvement of refugees and asylum seekers in shaping the strategy and its delivery, inclusive communities. The Scottish Government provides funding through its equality budget to support a range of projects run by third sector organisations aimed at integrating refugees and asylum seekers in their local communities.

SOCIAL POLICIES

Until 2016 social policies were Reserved matters of the British parliament then the Scotland Act 2016 devolved significant new welfare powers to the Scottish Parliament. The implementation of this devolution process is currently ongoing (Kennedy, McInnes, Bellis, O'Donnell, Steele 2019).

Among the welfare related policies, **Universal Credit - Welfare Reform** (Act 2012) is the largest benefit umbrella - it aggregated the former benefits aimed at children, housing, income-related, unemployment related. People who are in work and on a low income are the eligible population, as well as those who are out of work, among them EEA nationals with settled status; people with indefinite leave to remain (ILR), refugee status or humanitarian protection. Many EEA people with pre-settled status can also claim benefits at the condition of having the "right to reside" as well as some other EU and Commonwealth citizens who are habitually resident in the UK and have right of abode²⁰⁶.

Migrants "subject to immigration control" and whose granted leave states that they cannot claim public funds²⁰⁷ are not eligible. Among them, People seeking asylum are generally not eligible for mainstream welfare benefits (see previous note), nor are they allowed to work whilst waiting for a decision on their claim. Instead they can apply for **Asylum support** that includes accommodation and/or financial support (Immigration and Asylum Act 1999 - Section 95). A standard weekly subsistence amount of £39.63 intended to cover essential living needs including food, non-prescription medication, communications and travels. 'Dispersed accommodation' are also

²⁰⁶ Having right of abode means you are allowed to live or work in the UK without any immigration restrictions, which means no need of visa to come to the UK and no limit on the length of time you can spend in the country.

All British citizens automatically have right of abode in the UK, some Commonwealth citizens may also have right of abode.

²⁰⁷ A "person subject to immigration control" is a person who falls into one of the following categories: someone who need leave to enter or remain in the UK but do not have it (e.g. asylum seekers with temporary admission) or someone who overstayed their leave to enter or remain; someone who have leave to enter or remain in the UK on condition that they have no recourse to public funds; someone who have leave to enter or remain in the UK as a result of someone providing a maintenance undertaking.

provided, flats or houses located outside of London and the South-East on the base of an agreement with willing local authorities. Private sector providers are responsible for providing those accommodations for asylum seekers. Concerns about accommodation standards under the former COMPASS contract (cit) were finally addressed by the government in 2019 with a new Asylum Accommodation and Support Services Contracts (AASC) intended to follow its engagements with local authorities and non-governmental organisations. A person's financial and accommodation support ends a few weeks after the final decision has been made on their asylum claim. Refused asylum seekers have support options only if there is a temporary obstacle preventing the person's departure or if the household includes children under 18.

At Scottish level, the **Fairer Scotland Action Plan (2014-2020)**, through two funds supports communities to design and delivery a community-led initiatives that tackle poverty, inequality and exclusion (The Aspiring Communities Fund) and supports third sector organisations to create jobs and developing and expanding services to disadvantaged individuals, families and communities. It also encourages and supports social innovation approaches to tackle social problems (Growing the Social Economy).

Concerning the **access to healthcare**, a health surcharge (between 470 and 625£ per year) was introduced by the UK Immigration Act 2014 for non-European Economic Area (EEA) students (international students), non-EEA migrant workers, those from outside the EEA who are joining their families in the UK. From 2021, EEA migrants that did not have applied for the settlement or pre-settlement status need to pay the health surcharge. The NHS provides free care for refugees and asylum seekers, and for those whose application for asylum was rejected but are supported under section 4(2) of the Immigration and Asylum Act 1999, children looked after by local authorities, victims of modern slavery or human trafficking, those receiving compulsory treatment under a court order, or who are liable to be detained in an NHS hospital or deprived of their liberty²⁰⁸. In Scotland free healthcare is also guaranteed to asylum seekers who do not receive support from the Home Office or have

²⁰⁸ UK Government, *NHS entitlements: migrant health guide*, updated 8.09.2020, consulted on 20.11.2020

<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/nhs-entitlements-migrant-health-guide#free-for-all>.

been refused asylum. The NHS Scotland website states that “The Scottish Government decide how healthcare is provided in Scotland. This is not linked to immigration control, which is a matter for the Home Office. NHS Scotland does not pass patient details to the Home Office for the purpose of immigration enforcement”²⁰⁹.

Regarding **equal opportunities**, the British Parliament legislates while the Scottish Parliament encourages them (Scotland Act 1998). The British **Equality Act** (2010) consolidates a unified equality legislation – while before different antidiscrimination policies aimed sex, race, and disability. It prohibits direct and indirect discrimination, harassment and victimization and protects people from discrimination on the basis of age, disability, gender reassignment, marriage and civil partnership, pregnancy and maternity, race, religion or belief, sex and sexual orientation.

At Scottish level the **Race Equality Framework & Action Plan** (2016 – 2030) aims at supporting community cohesion and safety – good race relations and community cohesion across all communities, and all minority ethnic individuals feel safe, protected and included, and experience less racism; participation and representation; education and lifelong learning – without disadvantage in relation to racial inequality or racism; employability, employment and income – minority ethnic people have equal, fair and proportionate access to employment and representation at all levels, grades and occupation types in Scotland’s workforce, and experience fewer labour market, workplace and income inequalities; health and home – minority ethnic communities in Scotland have equality in physical and mental health, have effective healthcare appropriate for their needs and experience fewer inequalities in housing and home life.

The **Promoting Equality and Cohesion Fund** (2017-2020) allocates funding to organisations working to tackle inequalities in Scotland by addressing issues related to housing, ESOL classes (English courses for foreigners), mental health, skills development, fighting racism, in particular with refugees and minorities.

²⁰⁹ NHS Scotland, *Healthcare for overseas visitors*, updated 15.09.2020, consulted on 20.11.2020

<https://www.nhsinform.scot/care-support-and-rights/health-rights/access/healthcare-for-overseas-visitors>.

The Home Office maintains that the health provisions in the Immigration Act 2014 support immigration policy, which is a reserved matter for the UK Government (ibid).

EDUCATIONAL POLICIES

In Scotland, education and training is managed by the national government since 1998. In the general framework of the Community cohesion strategy, the language became a central matter as strictly associated with ethnic and national identity. An **English for Speakers of Other Languages (ESOL)** has been developed (2007). It is delivered by a range of providers including Community Learning and Development (CLD) services through local authority partnerships, colleges, schools, voluntary organisations, universities and private language providers. ESOL learners are very diverse, ranging from highly educated and proficient learners tackling a new language, to individuals who have little or no experience of schooling and are not literate in their first language. Specific programmes are in place to make the programme inclusive, like Workplace ESOL.

Modern Apprenticeship Programme and **Graduate Apprenticeship Programme** aim at enhancing Scotland's work-based learning system and reducing youth unemployment. Migrants may have already the skills for which they enrol in an apprenticeship, but they do not have those recognized or they need to adapt them to the Scottish context (ex. Regulations). Therefore, OECD recommended to "Develop a non-apprenticeship route to apprentice qualifications"²¹⁰

Education Maintenance Allowances (1999) provide financial support for 16 to 19 years old (four years) from low-income households who are undertaking full-time study at a school, full or part-time study at an FE college or education center, or are taking part in an 'activity agreement'. Are eligible people aged 16 to 19 that meet household income as well residency criteria. Recent migrants or refugees without leave to remain are not eligible due to residency criteria.

In 2018, the **Migrant and Refugee Skills Recognition Pilot Project** (2018), a 15-months pilot, was launched to explore processes for recognition in order to maximise on the skills migrants bring to employers and the

²¹⁰ OECD, 2020, Strengthening Skills in Scotland. Review of the apprenticeship system in Scotland, OECD, Paris http://www.oecd.org/skills/centre-for-skills/Strengthening_Skills_in_Scotland.pdf

employment market. The project strategically targeted four sectors – Social Care, Construction/Engineering and IT and Hospitality – each experiencing skill shortages and under-employment.

ECONOMIC POLICIES: LABOUR MARKET INTEGRATION

Access to labour market is one of key issues of British migration policies since the 1990s.

TCNs are entitled to work in the United Kingdom if they arrived through the **Tier Points-Based system** as highly-skilled workers (Tier 1), skilled workers with job offers (Tier 2) or temporary workers (Tiers 5). Since 2020 the **Entrepreneur visa** (Innovator visa and Start-up visa) took some of the TPBS (and notably the Tier 1) tasks. Entrepreneur VISA allows overseas entrepreneurs and early stage technology business or start-ups to relocate their business in the UK. It is reserved at entrepreneurs from outside EEA who want to set up or run a business in the UK, have at least £50,000 in investment funds and have enough personal savings to support themselves while in the UK.

Among the displaced migrants, **refugees** have the right to work while **asylum seekers** can apply for permission to work after they have been waiting for a decision on their asylum claim for over a year and the permission is restricted to jobs on the Shortage Occupation List (Asylum and Immigration Act 1999), that should be related with the imaginary of asylum seekers as economic migrants in disguise ‘pulled’ to particular countries by economic opportunities that informed the asylum policies (Mayblin 2019).

The previously illustrated **Equality Act framework** includes also measures aimed at contrasting direct and indirect discrimination, harassment and victimization at work.

The **Modern Slavery Act** (2015) gives law enforcement the tools to fight modern slavery. It also states that leave to remain must be provided for Overseas Domestic Workers who apply as recognized victim of slavery or human trafficking.

Job Centre Plus was formed in 2002 from the Employment Service merged with the Benefits Agency. It is a government-funded employment agency and social security office that aims at helping people of working age

to find employment in the UK and to facilitate recruitment for employers. Job seekers among all residents including refugees and migrants with indefinite leave to remain as well as recruiters.

New Enterprise Allowance (2011) is aimed at people (among them refugee and other categories of migrants e.g. those with indefinite leave to remain) who get different kind of benefits and it helps them to establish a business through a mentorship programme, weekly allowance (up to £1274 as total for 26 weeks) and the possibility of applying for a loan to help with start-up costs.

Training has been a devolved matter since The Scotland Act 1998 and the new Scotland Act (2016) transferred also responsibilities in providing employment support for people at risk of long term unemployment. Different training and employability programmes have been activated since for all the Scotland population including migrants.

Before 2016, the **Employability fund** (2013) was intended at improving learner progressions along the skills and employability pipeline and at providing a **Certificate of Work Readiness**, a qualification through employability training and a work placement, which results in a nationally recognised qualification upon completion. **Fair Start Scotland** (2018) employment support service (2018) aims at helping people living in Scotland (including migrants) who are disadvantaged in the labour market. In the Western Scotland it is reserved for supported businesses that provide permanent employment for those disadvantaged in the labour market. **No One Left Behind** (2019-2020) Employability fund is aimed at helping those members of society who face challenging barriers to finding and maintaining employment, reach their true potential

A Local Authorities lead and founded programme, the **Business Gateway** (2013) provides support to people that would like to start or run a business. It provides professional resources, support and tools to help you learn new skills, create new opportunities and develop sustainable strategies for growth.

In the framework of **EU Cohesion policy**, such as the European strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth and to the achievement of economic, social and territorial cohesion, Scotland had access to the ERDF and ESF, destined for more than half (55%) at Highlands & Islands as transition region to increase digital connectivity, improve employment opportunities, make Scotland more competitive in business, ensure communities are healthy and sustainable, building a sustainable, low-carbon Scotland, tackle poverty and inequality.

In 2012, the Scottish government with the local Authorities designed the **Empowering Communities Policy**, a community-led Regeneration strategy. Through the Investing in Communities Fund and Aspiring Communities Fund (previously described), local communities are supported in building community capacity, increasing active inclusion and developing opportunities, developing local assets, services and projects that respond to the needs of the people in their communities, delivering community-led solutions that tackle priorities that matter most to communities, and/or develop local interventions which offer opportunities and pathways for social and community integration.

In 2018, the Scottish parliament approved the **Islands (Scotland) Act** that sets out the main objectives and strategy of the Scottish Government in relation to improving outcomes for island communities by increasing population levels; improving and promoting sustainable economic development, environmental wellbeing, health and wellbeing, and community empowerment; improving transport services and digital connectivity; reducing fuel poverty; and enhancing biosecurity, recognizing common interests shared by the population and their environment. The Islands Act objective was ensuring that there is a sustained focus across government and the public sector to meet the needs of island communities now and in the future with the aim of improving outcomes for islands communities. One of the first provisions introduced was a duty on Scottish Ministers to prepare a National Islands Plan, delivered in 2019. The **Island Plan** defined the following strategic objectives: addressing population decline and ensure a healthy, balanced population profile; sustainable economic development; improving transport services; improving housing; reducing levels of fuel poverty; improving digital connectivity; improving and promoting health, social care and wellbeing.

The Islands (Scotland) Act as Scottish legislation does not apply to the Home Office legislation for immigration. That means that there is no formal consideration of the specific challenges that the migrant population living on islands meet to travel to the mainland to fulfil VISA or other obligations.

According to the Scottish government “early assessment of what the outcome of the EU-UK negotiations means for Scotland”, Scotland will lose access to all of the EU’s pre-allocated programmes that provide for example funding for agriculture, fishing, or rural development²¹¹.

²¹¹ Scottish Government, “Early assessment of what the outcome of the EU-UK negotiations means for Scotland”, Publications, published on December 31st 2020, consulted on January 13th 2021

<https://www.gov.scot/publications/eu-uk-negotiations-outcome-analysis/#EU%20programmes>

1.2 OVERVIEW ON EXISTING ANALYSES AND ASSESSMENTS OF ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL POLICIES

In this section we focus on the recent literature that explores the main themes that emerged from the previous description of the policies, notably integration and segregation, migrant access to labour market and welfare, regional approach to migration and post-Brexit migration.

The British **integration policies** aim predominantly at the second (or sequent) generations of migrants and only in very limited cases at newcomers (Broadhead 2020), it is this the case of asylum seekers and refugees. In the last twenty years, two major narratives²¹² emerged – the idea of communities leading “parallel lives” (Cantle 2001) and of the country “sleepwalking into ghettos”. In the wake of those analyses British policies – traditionally adopting an approach based on the importance of minority groups and recognition of multiculturalism – experienced a “assimilationist turn” (Bertossi 2007).

According to Mason (2018) the first narrative – that of the “parallel lives” – emerged from the critic to multiculturalism as an approach that refers to an essentialist idea of culture, gives unfair advantages to minority cultural and religious groups and encourages cultural communities to form separate societies, discouraging integration.

The second narrative – that of British ghettos, formulated in 2005 in a paper at the conference of the Royal Geographical Society – stated that ethnic **segregation** was increasing and ghettos had formed in some British cities, and was shared by the Director of the Commission for Racial Equality at that time (Peach 2009). In the following decade, many scholars (Peach, Simpson 2009; Peach 2010; Finney, Simpson 2009) – enabled by the statistics on ethnicity and on religion introduced in the census by the Office for National Statistics (ONS) in 1991 and in 2001– denied the hypothesis of ghettos in British inner cities and discussed the re-spatialisation of “racialised geographies” as more peripheral regions are increasingly ethnically diverse (Rhodes, Brown 2019).

²¹² See Boswell, Geddes, Scholten (2011) for the role of narratives in migration policies.

Furthermore, considering that living near people of the same background could be also an active choice aimed at preserving cultural traits and identity (Peach 1996), they also suggested that connections with fellow migrants reinforced by **residential proximity** may strengthen social capital, the sense of being settled and at home (Ager and Strang 2008).

Those studies support the necessity of exploring the relation between spatial and social patterns as British ethnic groups' spatial concentrations cannot be considered by default as an indicator of the lack of integration. Nonetheless, in the very recent years, assimilationist and dispersion inspired policies have been implemented in particular with the asylum seekers and refugee's programmes.

Since the Immigration and Asylum Act 1999, according to Spencer (2011), the British government began a process of separation between the categories of 'asylum seeker' and 'refugee' and decided who was to be considered eligible to integrate and who was not (ibid.). Refugee populations were understood as a group in need of integration support and according to Phillimore (2012), this was meant – in an assimilationist way – on the one hand as a stress on the attainment of English language and culture skills accompanied, on the other hand, with the end of funding for clusters of refugees to establish their own refugee community organisations (RCOs) to enable the retention of cultural identity and encourage self-help.

Concerning **Asylum seekers**, they were not considered 'refugees' unless they were granted status by the UNHCR, or they gained 'leave to remain' in the country. As a result, states Spencer (ibid.), they were not seen as eligible for integration support in the UK. Meer, Peace and Hill (2018) reformulate the issue in terms of which is the "**starting-point** of the integration process", an issue that remains disputed, not least by the Scottish Government which maintains that it begins from the point of arrival. Furthermore, they point out that the Immigration and Asylum Act (1999) placed responsibility for arrival, housing and welfare provision with central government that allowed asylum seekers access merely to cash-only support and to accommodation in a no-choice location and removed local government from service provision. The introduction of **no-choice accommodation** is to link with policies that established **dispersal** as a key immigration policy. In this sense, describing the different dispersal programs implemented for asylum seekers since 1967, Hynes (2011) point out that in the early 2000s, the Home Office abandoned a key feature of its previous programmes which enabled the clustering of small groups, fearing that this approach would lead to the creation of 'ghettos' (ibid.). A new

policy – introduced by the New Labour government – aimed at “sharing the burden” saw dispersal (away from south-east England) as a solution to the increasing number of people seeking asylum in the UK. Stuart (2012) notices that the majority of literature on the UK dispersal has focused upon critiquing the policy for being driven by void housing and concentrating vulnerable populations in deprived, inner city neighbourhoods. Although recent research seems to analyse dispersal asylum seeker condition in a more holistic approach, e.g. Parker (2020) writes on asylum policy-imposed liminality and highlights how, in asylum seekers accounts, restrictions from the asylum system are indicated as the reason for not developing feeling of belonging. Along with dispersion, he suggests that **exclusion from work** is a key element of this condition of liminality and that allowing asylum seekers to work would be a key step forward and contribute to generate a greater sense of belonging.

The narrative behind those policies – stated in the white paper *Fairer, Faster and Firmer* – is the idea of an ‘**economic pull factor**’ such as that economic migrants in disguise of asylum seekers were attracted to the United Kingdom because of economic opportunities (Mayblin 2019), the existing literature agrees that there is no evidence that can confirm this hypothesis (ibid.). Current asylum policy in the UK is thus recognised to be a barrier to social integration, preventing their progression from benefits into work. Furthermore, Bloch (2008) affirms that UK integration strategies prove to be contradictory by focusing on the employability as a key aspect towards refugees’ broader integration, while at the same time being restrictive and negatively impacting their access to labour market. Furthermore, even when asylum seekers have granted the refugee status, Strang, Baillot and Mignard (2018) identified structural failures in the delivery of their new rights which result in disruption and disempowerment in refugees’ lives. “Instead of increasing independence and contribution, it is clear that for most, the immediate impact of receiving refugee status is to interrupt, and even reverse aspects of integration and to increase dependency” (ibid. p.211). In particular, the 28-day time period between the granting of leave to remain and the removal of asylum support is widely considered to be insufficient to support refugees into paid employment or to enable them to access to general welfare benefits and housing support.

According to Meer, Peace and Hill (2020) if the ban on working for asylum seekers was lifted it would significantly reduce the costs of keeping people on asylum support as well as allowing people seeking asylum to contribute economically through consumer spending and paying tax (campaigning groups for the “**Lift the ban**” campaign estimated a gain of £42.4m per year for British economy). In this sense, they describe a potential

pilot project in Glasgow (result of the collaboration of Glasgow City Council, the Home Office and the Scottish Refugee Council) and analyse how the regional policies have tried to address this issues, notably the New Scots strategy. “Emphasis in New Scots is placed upon developing refugees’ employability and skills, a service that is almost unanimously provided by the third sector in Scotland. However, despite demand, there are very limited specialist refugee employment services in Scotland. Existing services are oversubscribed and subject to time-limited funding. Funding streams are especially vulnerable in a post-Brexit environment” (ibid. p. XI).

More generally, migrants **access to labour market** is strongly dependent on the entry system established by the UK Government, a large revision of this system is currently undergoing because of the challenges of the post-Brexit reforms. In this sense relevant literature has been produced in the very last years by the Migration Advisory Committee (MAC) and by the Migration and Population Expert Advisory Group (EAG) at Scottish level, the two expert groups of migration advising the British and Scottish government. In 2018 MAC produced two reports – Government commissioned – to advise on the economic and social impacts of the UK’s **exit from the European Union** and on how the UK’s immigration system should be aligned with an effective economic strategy. Among the recommendations, MAC (2020a) included the general principle to make it easier for higher-skilled workers to migrate to the UK than lower-skilled workers, maintain existing **salary thresholds** for all migrants in Tier 2, review how the current sponsor licensing system works for small and medium-sized businesses and pay more attention to managing the consequences of migration at a local level. Eventually, to fill low-skilled roles by extending the Tier 5 Youth Mobility Scheme. MAC (2020b) also reviewed the Shortage Occupational Lists advising to add senior care workers and nursing assistants among the occupations to consider. The MAC has also recommended additions to separate lists for all of the devolved nations, allowing additional flexibility and reflecting the different needs of each.

The EAG (2019) estimated that the 2018 White Paper changes to Tier 2 might result in a reduction of net migration to Scotland of between 30 – 50%. This figure has been calculated as result of two consideration. Firstly 78% of EEA nationals entering under free movement would not meet the Tier 2 threshold. Secondly, with the removal of the cap, a lower skills threshold, and reducing the administrative burden on employers might lead to an increase in non-EEA nationals entering via Tier 2. The combination of these two effects were estimated as a 70% reduction in current EEA inflows for work. In this report EAG analysed the **effects of the salary threshold by gender, by local authority and by sector**, showing how migrants (and notably migrant

women) would be ineligible for many jobs in local authorities like the Outer Hebrides and for certain sectors like notably agriculture, caring, office and customer related occupations (ibid.). A further report containing recommendation on regionally tailored migration policy advises is yet to come.

In January 2020, the Scottish Government published a paper (Scottish Government 2020a) which defined options for a **tailored approach to immigration** for Scotland within the context of the broader UK immigration system.

One of the proposals was a '**Scottish visa**', which would operate in addition to other UK visa categories. The paper envisages that Scottish Ministers would set the eligibility criteria and associated rules for the visa, which would provide a route for migrants to live, work and ultimately settle in Scotland.

Another option envisaged by this paper was a visa with a more specific focus on **ensuring settlement by migrants in remote and rural areas**, whether in Scotland or in other parts of the UK. The Migration Advisory Committee (MAC) has recommended pilot projects be established to look at retention of migrants in remote and rural areas, the paper analyse this tool in the Scottish context and how the Scottish Government would support the Home Office in their delivery.

The paper state that the Scottish Government's preference would be for devolution of migration policies with shared responsibility with the UK Government for delivery.

1.3 ASSESSMENT OF THE STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES OF POLICIES THROUGH SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

METHODOLOGY AND ETHICS

Interviews have been carried from the 14th October to the 16th November. As the Covid-19 pandemic did not allow us to travel to Scotland and meet the interviewees personally, the interviews have been carried through Teams video calls. Eight interviewees consented in being recorded and agreed at us using their anonymised transcript, but only seven interviews have been recorded due to a technical issue. Their decision to be recorded has been often related to the will of facilitating the task for a non-English mother tongue speaker. Only one person preferred the researcher to take only notes.

The interviews have been carried out by Dr Maria Luisa Caputo and for two of them jointly by Dr Caputo and Prof. Baglioni. The transcriptions have been compiled by MATILDE team member Dr Martina Lo Cascio and proofread by Dr Caputo.

The profiles of the interviewees were differentiated: two interviewees were policy experts, one was a Member of Parliament, one a representative of the Scottish government, two representatives of the Convention of Scottish Local Authorities, two representatives of the Local Authorities, one a member of a large organisation aimed at supporting asylum migrants. The interviewees were chosen to represent different scales of government (UK, Scottish national, local) and to include different types of actors who contributed to the definition or the discussion of the current migration and/or integration policies; and/or managed those policies implementation at local scale; and/or were in charge of discussing the impact of the policies effective from January 2021.

Because of the broadness of the questions of our interviews, only for some topics we found our interviews saturated – notably the general impact of migrants in demographic and economic terms and the post-Brexit scenario, the current social and economic policies with the important exception of the Island Act that we need to further investigate. Some other topics notably the migrant entrepreneurship and the role of social economy

were very marginally approached by the interviewees we selected and need to be further investigated. Those topics as well as Scottish islands Act are not discussed in this part of the report.

All of the interviewees were familiar or very familiar with interviews as research tool and fully understood the aim and the structure of the performance, moreover they provided their informed consent and were aware that their transcript was going to be anonymised.

The interviews were carried in October and November 2020, such as before the Brexit agreement between the United Kingdom and the European Union (EU-UK Trade and Cooperation Agreement²¹³) with big changes of December 24th.

DEFINING POLICIES FOR POST-BREXIT ERA DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Our interviews took place at the historical juncture which saw an overlapping between the country exiting the EU (Brexit) and the diffusion of the Covid-19 pandemic, a situation that a policy expert interviewed defined as “*the perfect tempest*” (WP3WP4UK09). On the one hand, the end of the Brexit transition (or implementation) period on December 31st 2020 implies the need of reviewing a large number of policies. Among those immigration policies are particularly relevant for our project: the end of 2020 will very likely mark the end of the EEA free movement in the United Kingdom and a significant impact is expected notably at regional level.

On the other hand, an analysis of the potential effects of the new proposed policies has been highly difficult as the pandemic radically affected the demographic and economic trends and made it impossible to accurately foresee how those trends will evolve in the next future. This lack of horizon has been stressed by the same interviewee, who underlined how it was difficult for experts to propose even only principles for potential policies (ibid.).

²¹³ European Commission, 2020, “EU-UK Trade and Cooperation Agreement. A new relationship, with big changes”

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/brexit_files/info_site/6_pager_final.pdf

SCOTTISH BACKGROUND

Scotland has been for long an emigration country, since at least the post-WWII until the last two decades his net international migration rate was negative. While from the 2000s (EAG 2019) its net migration rate became positive, its population natural growth stayed negative. Coherently with this picture, many interviewees stressed the importance of migrant population in Scotland from a demographic point of view, and especially in relation to the need to increase the **part of working age persons** in the general population (WP3WP4UK02, WP3WP4UK04, WP3WP4UK06, WP3WP4UK08, WP3WP4UK09).

In 2019 there were 155,000 EU nationals in employment (they were 56,000 in 2007), 5.8% of total Scottish workforce and 63,000 TCNs (they were 47,000 in 2007), 2.4% the workforce. About 1/5 of all EU nationals (21.6% or 23,000 people) works in the public sector – including administration, education and health, representing 4.4% of the all health and social cares' workforce. TCNs are more likely than EU nationals to work in the public sector (31.9% or 20,000 people). Hospitality and tourism sectors' workforce is constituted for 12.7% by non-UK nationals (about 1/3 of the EU workforce and 1/3 of TCNs work in this sector), followed by manufacturing 9.3% (11.4% of EU workforce, while only 3.5% of TCNs work in this sector). There are 79,000 non-UK nationals working in Scotland's six growth sectors, with 33,000 working in Sustainable Tourism alone, accounting for 17.6% of all the workforce in this sector (Scottish Government 2020b)

The positive net migration of the last decades is the result notably of the **EEA free movement** (WP3WP4UK06): the EEA migrants from 2006 to 2017 represented about half of the all in-migration in Scotland and as 87% of the increase in the workforce. "While cities enjoy a higher share of immigration, rural and remote areas have also seen a substantial rise in immigration. This has been enabled by the free movement framework, which allows flexible patterns of movement and employment for EU nationals. The absence of a skills threshold has also meant that EU migrants have filled lower-skilled jobs in areas such as agriculture, tourism, manufacturing, health and social care, across Scotland" (EAG 2019 p.3). In this sense, with the EEA free movement it became easier for migrants to settle in Scottish rural and remote areas, including those places in which population is notably shrinking. The flexibility of this scheme – no need of a skilled job, no salary threshold, possibility of

exploring this life choice and easily go back, no VISA costs, etc.) – and the access to British welfare comparable to that of a UK citizen e.g. work benefits to bridge jobs, were the two main pull factors for seasonal workers according to a policy expert (WP3WP4UK08). Because of free movement there was much more diversity about where people came from and where they went – in the sense that settlement patterns showed no clustering (ibid.). In addition to EEA migrants, in the last 5 years the **refugee families of the Syrian Vulnerable People Scheme** contributed to this immigration flux towards rural and remote areas of Scotland.

All the interviewees generally agreed on the positive demographic impact of migration in Scotland rural and remote areas. Additionally, an interesting shared but differentiated narrative rose from the interviews about why even **small numbers of migrants do matter**. From a representative of the Scottish government point of view, “*notably in rural communities, small numbers have a disproportionate impact*” as those small numbers of people allow services’ sustainability, because they fulfil key positions (e.g. 3 out of 4 anaesthesiologists in the Outer Hebrides is a migrant according to the interviewee) or because those migrants contribute to the population threshold (e.g. to keep schools open) (WP3WP4UK06). This latter affirmation need to be further investigated, as other interviewees did not shared it indicating on the one side a general restructuring of the services in relation notably to resources and information technology (WP3WP4UK04; WP3WP4UK09) and on the other side mentioning other dynamics operating at local scale, like for example urban and rural dynamics, with schools at risk of being closed in rural and in remote areas while migrants would mainly settle in more urbanised areas (WP3WP4UK07). From a strictly economic point of view small numbers of migrants can be also particularly relevant: it is the case of specialised workers like e.g. migrant veterinarians working in the abattoirs who according to the interviewee are for the 90% non-UK nationals (WP3WP4UK06). That means that, apart from the number of immigrants working in a specific sector, it is important also to consider the proportional share that those migrants represent of the sector work force. High number of migrants do not necessary correspond to high shares and vice-versa.

Detailed evidences have been provided by the Scottish government to the Migration Advisory Committee on the effects on the different sectors reliant on migrants of the new migration policy recommendation (WP3WP4UK06, WP3WP4UK09): it is the case notably of the social care sector, education, agriculture, abattoirs, shell and fishing sector, transports (notably EU citizens, ex. in the link with island), hospitality, transportation sector, warehousing and logistics, and gaming sector (prominent in Scotland but limited by the difficulty of

recruiting internationally). Those sectors are notably filled by EU migrants and not TCNs – because of the skills and salary thresholds set by the Tiers Point Systems – those migrants are more likely to be found in the health sector (e.g. doctors), finance and university (as students and staffs) (ibid.).

The beginning of 2021 marked the end of EEA free of movement in the United Kingdom. From Scottish perspective this is very concerning as the population is aging and there is a need of migration to grow the Scottish population, notably working age population. According to a Scottish government representative the decrease of migration to Scotland (after Brexit) is estimated at 50% (70-80% less EU migrants), that will translate in a decrease of 3-5% of working age population in the next 25 years according to the Expert Advisory Group (EAG 2019, also cited in WP3WP4UK06).

DEVOLUTION AND MANAGEMENT OF MIGRATION (ENTRY) POLICIES POST-BREXIT

The relationships between the Scottish and United Kingdom government are regulated by the Scottish Act (1998 and following acts). The migration entry policy is a reserved matter, such as a matter reserved to the United Kingdom government.

An increasing interest has been shown by the Scotland government in being able to influence this policy. According to a policy expert interviewed, the political attitude in Scotland toward migration is generally positive “*some of the reasons why you may restrict migration such as population density and political will simply do not exist up here*” (WP3WP4UK08).

The proposed revision of migration policy envisaged by the UK government at the time of the interview and currently implemented restrict the entry and settling of migrants – as these processes became more difficult and more expensive for EEA migrants (ibid) – and the inability for migrants to enter and settle in Scotland is more problematic than in other parts of the UK (ibid.) from a demographic as well as economic point of view (as described in the previous section).

Different propositions came from the Scottish government.

Strong evidences were produced by the Expert Advisory Group about how the Tiers Points System disproportionately impacts rural areas – as well as women (EAG 2019). It considers the average salary threshold but this average is distorted by the proportional weight of Edinburgh and Glasgow working population. In this sense MAC – who shared the Expert Advisory Group concerns – recommended the introduction of a rural migration pilot. The proposal (on a Canadian model) included the possibility of awarding points in relation to where the people are going to settle, but this approach rises many questions – e.g. how long migrants need to stay in this rural place? (WP3WP4UK06) – and it seems not have had any outcome yet (ibid.).

The Scottish government also recommended to add some “low skilled”²¹⁴ job in the Shortage Occupation list, a proposal rejected by the UK government. The shortage occupation list is based on job vacancy rate and since its implementation it did not change significantly. As an explanation, an interviewee remarked that either there are not many variations or this tool is not very responsive to variations (WP3WP4UK08). But more importantly, this tool is seen to have a narrow scope. *“It is more about what you’re trying to do with immigration... to boil down economic needs for migration into what it is the vacancy rate in your labour market seems to me to narrow too much”* (ibid.).

A Scottish government representative interviewed remarked that the UK industrial strategy that puts stress on high productivity and low wages has been taken as an indicator on low productivity, commenting that there are many sectors with low wages and high proportion of migrant labour where the forthcoming immigration system will be unable to recruit migrants. From a Scottish prospective this is problematic as it concerns many strategic sectors like agriculture, hospitality and tourism. Furthermore, the duty of sponsorship will also be a brake according to this analysis: e.g. in Scotland there are very small care homes that will not be able to do the necessary administrative steps to recruit migrants (WP3WP4UK06).

According to the reviewed TPBS, seasonal workers should become part of the Tiers 5, such the tiers aimed at young and temporary migrants. Seasonal workers according to the same interviewee spend around 7-8 months in the country: they work their way across the UK in different jobs, but their family would be back in the country

²¹⁴ Different interviewees criticised the use of “low skilled” to indicate jobs that do not request high formal education.

where they are from. Some of them move towards other more stable jobs and settle. Some are returners and commit to come to work for a number of years, some others only come once. Scotland would like to keep those workers and persuade them to settle (ibid.)

Among the different proposal of the Scottish government, surely the most challenging is that of a **Scottish visa** (see previous section), which would operate in addition to other UK visa categories. A policy expert was very critical about this possibility – “*when the Scottish made requests maybe they were not given very much attention but one could see it as making requests that they know that will not be taken seriously*” – as the interviewee thinks that regionalised migration policies can be shaped without the need of regional visas (WP3WP4UK08).

In conclusion, migration entry policy seems a key theme in Scotland as likely to affect welfare and economy and more largely the maintain of sustainable rural and remote communities. Tailored solutions are currently under exam for the Expert Advisory Group recommendation. In particular, they are taking into consideration for their analysis **functional areas** – such as broader areas than those of residence that include the spaces where needs and functions are carried out (the areas must include access to jobs, schools, health care, etc.) and they are exploring the policy principle of **mitigation** – such as how to deal with the decrease of migrant population and what strategies that can be adopted to reduce the impact of it (WP3WP4UK09).

Finally, a shared point among the interviewees has been the **lack of formal mechanism for negotiation** between the Scottish and the UK government that regulate how and at what extent Scotland can influence the reserved matters (WP3WP4UK06; WP3WP4UK08 and WP3WP4UK09). “*One of the problem under the devolution settlement is the lack of formal or official mechanism for dialogue or negotiation, that’s obviously a problem that become much more difficult to negotiate when governments have different ideological positions*” (WP3WP4UK08). “*All Scotland can do is continue to make the case*”. If UK government will not support the Scottish requests, the Scottish government should continue to build the case and to produce evidences (WP3WP4UK06).

Concerning integration policies, despite the description we produced on Community Cohesion and on the evolution of the British approach to integration, interviewees agreed that in Scotland “*there are not a lot of structured integration policies*” (WP3WP4UK06) and the only policy mentioned in that case was the New Scots. A policy expert stated that apart from the New Scots “*there is no integration policy in Scotland [aimed at migrants], even if there has been consideration if this should be the case*”, such as if policies need to be aimed exclusively at the integration of migrants. Integration policies in Scotland are more focused on social inclusion while issues like “*racial equality come from the place of being non-migrants*”, such they are addressed by policies and actors that focus on **visible minorities** (WP3WP4UK08) and do not think at migrant population as a particularly prominent category. This may be understood through the relative importance of the recent European migration to Scotland, a category of migrants that is not much associated with visible minorities. Nonetheless, this point needs to be further investigated, notably in the **relation between minorities and newcomers**, as we could see already in our fieldwork networking between old and new migrants – e.g. the recent creation of a mosque in Stornoway seems to be related to the recent arrival of resettled refugees as well as to the presence on the island of Muslims since the second world war who used their homes as place of worship, both population were necessary to the good outcome of the project (WP3WP4UK07).

As regard the **New Scots** – all of the interviewees mentioned this policy, generally in positive terms even if as a policy expert noticed any deep analysis of the outcomes of this policy has been produced yet. This policy can be considered – according to a representative of the Scottish government – as a narrative of refugees being welcome in Scotland (WP3WP4UK06). A key element we found already in the literature that interviewees stressed was the principle of **integration from the day one**, an approach that try to withdraw the distinction between asylum seekers and refugees. Furthermore, important stress has been put on the fact that national and local government and third sector work together to achieve the goals of this strategy. From a founding point of view, there are **not specific resources** attached to this policy, so that the partners involved need to look for resources from different funds “*so part of the work for the strategy is actually looking at the available resources and prioritising them*” (WP3WP4UK01).

According to a local government officer, the first New Scots policy in 2015 was thought for the **central belt**, while the peculiarities of asylum migration in rural and remote Scottish areas were not taken into consideration. However, “*the second New Scots was aware about the Scottish picture rather than only the Glasgow picture*”

(WP3WP4UK07). Nonetheless, with all the its limitation, according to the interviewee, having had an integration policy already there at the beginning of the resettlement programme, meant that Scotland was ready and clear about what it meant for integration. There was a starting point and this “*made the acceptance of resettlement program across the country easier. There was a narrative around how to work with refugees, a bit of a map*” (ibid.).

For the purpose of this report, we will focus here notably on the **resettlement program** as there are no asylum seekers in the areas where we are carrying out our research. Furthermore, other existing projects – notably GLIMER or SIRIUS – work on similar issues and directly focus on asylum seekers in Scotland.

During the last five years, about 3500 resettled migrants (SVPRS) arrived in Scotland and about 200 people with the Children resettlement program with the participation of all 33 local authorities (WP3WP4UK01). The local authorities were **not experienced** in accommodating refugees, as a consequence, the **people in charge** of the programme at local level had a huge impact on its outcome (WP3WP4UK07 e WP3WP4UK05). The challenges faced at the beginning were notably having long term view – such as behind providing basic needs – and supporting migrants without “*too much of hand holding*” (WP3WP4UK06) so not to generate **dependency** on officers’ support (WP3WP4UK05). More awareness about need to translation/interpreting in public services came from the presence of refugees (WP3WP4UK06). Specific **interpretations of “positive” clustering** and migrant rate “**threshold**” has been developed in some case at local level – as portrayed by a local authority officer who explained the decision of organising the resettled families by groups of 7-8, spaced out in about 10 different areas to allow them to interact and self-help but “*to not create any cluster and let family to interact with community*” (WP3WP4UK02).

All the Scottish local authorities participated in the resettlement program, including **rural and remote ones**. Living in those areas is particularly challenging: because of the difficulty of travelling (e.g. in the island, off the island), accessing health care, accessing to job, dealing with the weather (WP3WP4UK07). And even more **challenging for migrants**, as they need to face isolation, language barrier, culture obstacles (e.g. it is not possible to respect religious needs as there is no halal butcher), the impossibility to access to comfort things that can help making isolation more bearable (like accessing home food like as it would be possible in a city)

and the lack of specific equipment (ex. Waterproof clothes and shoes). Finally, the low disposable incomes do exacerbate those challenges (ibid.).

Nevertheless, the representative of a third sector organisation interviewed underlined how the experience of the resettlement programme in Western Island changed his view on the opportunity of resettle refugees there (WP3WP4UK05). Many reasons have been mentioned by different interviewees on this point. According to a local government representative, in rural areas communities are on one side open and supportive and on the other less diverse – there are less or no services for non-English speakers (ex. shops where there are Arabic speakers) and it is more difficult to congregate by national groups – and that would help integration (WP3WP4UK01). Another interviewee stresses how **insularity does not mean isolation** but on the contrary islanders have extended connections – because they worked in the merchant navy, in the oil industry, or fishing – and wordily view. “This ability to work away and come back is vital to the island” (WP3WP4UK07). That means that islanders are used to work with people of all over the world and to diversity and this can ease the integration of newcomers. On the other side, from the migrants point of view, those remote places offer the opportunity of becoming quickly part of a community (ibid.). The opportunity to connect more easily with locals is often related by the interviewees to the fact that refugees were notably families with children of school age. Schooling has been identified as a prominent integration factor (WP3WP4UK01, WP3WP4UK05). Finally, the connections with locals have been identified as a key element for the refugees’ access to the labour market (WP3WP4UK05): “knowing people in a small community helps to find job and avoid racism” (WP3WP4UK07).

Concerning refugees’ **integration in the labour market**, two additional reflections arose from the interviews. Firstly, the need of considering for the choice of the resettlement location also the potential impact of the local socio-economic situation on refugees’ opportunities. The availability of suitable accommodations can occur in areas affected by high level of deprivation and unemployment, as in the case of North Ayrshire (WP3WP4UK02). Secondly, migrants face the challenge transferring their **pre-existing skills in the Scottish context** (WP3WP4UK01), e.g. in order to be employed as a chef or to open a restaurant a refugee needs to be aware of Scottish regulations, speak English, etc.

Concerning the **ESOL strategy** for Scotland, the arrival of refugees, according to an interviewed local government officer, brought to an increase in ESOL provisions – rethought for meeting refugees’ needs while

before it was qualification oriented – that benefited all migrant communities. The access to ESOL provision seemed to be understood notably according to the characteristics of the migrant: age and gender can act or acted as a barrier. Child responsibilities, larger families and gendered roles and duties have been pointed as obstacles in accessing English classes (WP3WP4UK01). In some case distance-learning classes put in place in the last months because of the Covid-19 pandemic had the effect of including refugee women otherwise not participating in English classes (WP3WP4UK04), opening to new reflection on how to reach those people on the long term.

COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND REMOTENESS

The impact of Covid-19 pandemic on migration is very complex and has been approached by interviewees from multiple angles, underlining not only the negative impact but also the opportunity that those troubled times are bringing for migrants.

It is shared opinion amongs the interviewees that the pandemic is affecting **migration figures**. Only one/third of seasonal workers – 98% of them EU nationals in the past years (McGuinness, Grimwood 2017) – arrived to Scotland to work in agriculture in 2020 with consequent difficulties to find workers to employ (WP3WP4UK08). Covid is also “*affecting the labour demand, as we do not know where the economy will go*” (WP3WP4UK08).

Similarly, the resettlement programs – that at the beginning of the pandemic were closed to achieve their goals – and the new joint resettlement program that was supposed to start in 2021 are currently on hold because of the pandemic (WP3WP4UK04).

Secondly, Covid-19 affected how the Home Office operates (WP3WP4UK01) and obliged to **rethink procedures and services**, with important impact on remote and rural migrant communities (WP3WP4UK07). Significantly an interviewed local government officer pointed out the need of reflecting on continuing online services after Covid-19 and how to include people who were alienated by those new Covid-adapted procedures (WP3WP4UK01).

Covid-19 impacted strategic sectors for Scottish economy like hospitality and tourism and consequently the labour demand in those sectors. Interestingly remotes areas, where the public sector is a large employer like on Scottish islands, where consequently more resilient (WP3WP4UK04).

Finally, and very importantly, Covid-19 added another argument on why it is problematic to exclude migrant groups from services and social support as excluding people from health and social security makes the response to the virus more difficult. *“There is an **argument to support everybody**, we expect opening up support in more generous way that we have seen since some time now”* (WP3WP4UK08). People who could not access services like housing can now better access them because of the necessity [in order to control Covid-19 spread] of taking people out of the street, the same for health care (WP3WP4UK01).

TENSIONS? MIGRATION AND CULTURAL ENCOUNTERING

Tensions about migration has been described as a minor issue or absent by the intervieweed, notably at local scale, nethertheless some elements of tensions have been mentioned by most of the interviewees.

Concerning potential pressure on public services, the narrative around the public services in Scotland seems more about having enough population at local level to sustain them (WP3WP4UK06). As regards housing, tensions seem not related to the presence of migrants. The difficulties of founding accommodations seem more related to the presence of many second homes (WP3WP4UK04, (WP3WP4UK06) and to the change in the composition of households, with more people living alone (WP3WP4UK06). Concerning the specific **island context**, fears have been expressed that migrants (often including here also UK nationals) coming to live on the island will **dilute culture**, change the way of life and **take precious jobs** (WP3WP4UK07).

More generally, according to a policy expert intervieweed the Scottish population’s **attitude toward migration** is more welcoming than in England (WP3WP4UK08) while underlining the difficulty of carrying reliable surveys on this topic. According to a representative of the Scottish government the attitude toward migration changed in the last decades becoming more positive (compared with England) because the migration demographic impact and the economic benefits entered in the common narrative (WP3WP4UK06). This seems to be related

to the fact that the parliament, local government and other stakeholders have more evidence based view on migration compared with England (ibid). However the link between the government attitude and the population ones cannot be supposed as “whilst the Scottish Government clearly seeks to encourage immigration into Scotland, it is unclear whether the Scottish population in general or supporters of Scottish independence in particular ‘go along’ with these aspirations”. (McCollum, Nowok, Tindal 2014 p. 98). As an expert interviewed described it there is a general “*recognition of the need of migration*”, also “*among those people who do not necessarily like it*” (WP3WP4UK08), in this sense the recognition of the Scottish need for migration – encouraged by the government – does not necessary means a positive attitude.

At local scale, in rural and remote areas, all the four local officers interviewed (WP3WP4UK01; WP3WP4UK02; WP3WP4UK04; WP3WP4UK07) appreciated the positive impact of the presence of migrants on the local population’s understanding of migration, bringing a positive change in the perception of migrants and of “otherness”. The possibility of meeting people of different cultures in very remote places have been highlighted notably in reference to the resettlement programme that can be symbolised by the attitude toward the “hijab scarf”, largely mediatised as symbol of alterity in western countries. “*Some people never saw a Hijab scarf; people were staring at the window. Now Hijab scarf is part of North Ayrshire landscape*” (WP3WP4UK02).

1.4 CONCLUDING REMARKS ON SOCIAL POLICIES

Whereas at British level we described, with the help of the literature, an “assimilationist turn” with a larger attention on migrants’ acculturation and an impact on the resources for ethnic, national and religious community, at Scottish level we found an approach based on the importance of minority groups and recognition of multiculturalism.

On the one side, no integration policies were described except those aimed at refugees and asylum seekers, while the other categories of migrants were considered part of the national inclusion framework. On the other side, anti-discrimination policies seem to aim ethnic and national groups that can be described as “visible minorities” and diversity seems valued by the national as well as local government. As a consequence, a narrative of migrants’ valuable impacts for Scotland – notably from a demographic and economic point of view – is nowadays widely shared.

As main integration policy, the New Scots strategy seemed to have provided a very important framework for understanding the path of the newcomers in the Scottish society and how to accommodate and integrate differences. Considering the limit of being a very recent policy without any deep analysis already carried out, the New Scots seems to have positive outcomes on migrants’ lives and migrants’ impact in Scottish society. With the “integration from the day one”, it contributes to avoid the limbo of asylum seeking and its effects on the refugee integration potential we explored in the literature. It has a positive impact on the cooperation of different actors – the national government, COSLA, the local authorities and the third sector organisations – aimed at building a coherent integration model.

Providing a narrative on refugees’ integration, it contributes to the voluntary adhesion of all the Scottish Local Authorities to the resettlement program that allow refugee population to safely settle around the all country – the programmes saw very few out-migration toward urban areas and very few tensions – the fact that the resettled refugees were families with schooling children has been indicated as a key element for the integration in the new community.

This programme brought new challenges to the local communities in terms of perceptions and practices. Small and close communities welcomed people of different cultures challenging their own perceptions and practices as well as those of the newcomers. This brought for example a wide transformation in the way the local authorities deliver services bringing a larger attention to inclusion through e.g. translation of official documents in other languages and using interpreters. It brought as well an encounter with new cultural praxis and new cultural traits challenging the fear of losing the “island way of life” or “diluting culture”. It is worth to explore how the presence of new migrants impacted the life of some minority groups and if there has been a minor re-elaboration or re-adjustment of their identity (role, visibility) in those community. We refer here to the decision of building a mosque after the arrival of the refugees in Stornoway, and to the pre-existing Muslim community installed there since the WWII. This impact on minority groups of the resettlement program and of refugees is worth to be further investigated.

From a demographic point of view, it was shared opinion among the interviewees that “dying communities” (WP3WP4UK09) have been happy to welcome a new population, notably if composed by children and families. Nevertheless, the link between services and migrant population seems still problematic – as resources and services change and the migrant population is likely to settle in the “centres” of the remote areas – and need to be further investigated.

GOOD PRACTICES

The following scheme is described as good practice in the interviews: **Community Sponsorship Scheme** has been introduced by the Home Office as civil society wished to play a greater role in refugee resettlement, and with the expectation that the community-led approach will lead to positive integration outcomes for refugees and communities.

1.5 CONCLUDING REMARKS ON ECONOMIC POLICIES

In Scotland, and more broadly in the UK, immigration policies seem the most important determinant in the current time in shaping the impact of migrants into the local economy and they will likely remain so in very next future.

Scotland could benefit in the last twenty years of migrants' contribution to the local economy and to the sustainability of remote communities. Migrants constituted in 2019 6.9 % of the Scottish population but 8.2% of its workforce (Annual Population Survey).

EEA freedom of movement policy allowed European migrants to work and settle in Scotland very easily. Today there are about 100,000 EU workers more than in 2007, 87% of the all increase of the all non-UK Scottish workforce. Those workers went to occupy position in strategic sectors, notably health and social cares, hospitality and tourism (in particular sustainable tourism) and manufacturing.

As we previously described, the Tiers Point-Based System currently aimed at TCNs allows skilled workers to come and work in Scotland via the award of a VISA. Consistently TCNs workers in Scotland tend to be proportionally more represented in sectors that employ notably skilled workers – like the public sector – and to be underrepresented in sectors that employ mostly routine or semi-routine workers like the manufacturing sector, so that those sectors are notably reliant on EU workers.

Furthermore, the flexibility of EEA Free movement policy has been positive for potential settlement in Scotland notably because there is not a need of a strong commitment but “you can see as you go” and in relation to the potential settlement of workers arrived for seasonal jobs.

Moreover, through the interviews we could appreciate that general figures do not allow a clear picture of the key role of migrants in remote and rural areas and in specific economic sectors – we provided the examples of the Western Isles anaesthetists and of the abattoir veterinarians. In this sense a multiscale analysis and by sector of migrant impact seems necessary. EAG (2019) breaking down sectors in Scotland that have more than

10% of their employees born outside the UK provided detailed highlights of the “role played by EU-10 workers in manufacturing food, leather products and so on. It also highlights the dependency of scientific research, computer programming, film and video production on migrants from the EU-15 countries” (ibid. pp. 20-21).

At the moment of writing the EEA freedom of movement in the United Kingdom is coming to an end. From Scottish perspective this is very concerning as the population is aging and there is a need of migration to grow the Scottish population, notably working age population, and even more so in rural and remote areas. According to the Scottish government the decrease of migration to Scotland (after Brexit) will translate in a decrease of 3-5% of working age population in the next 25 years according (EAG 2019).

These numbers will affect notably rural and remote communities and specific sectors which are more reliant than others on migrants’ work. It is the case of the social care, education, agriculture, abattoirs, shell and fishing sector, transports, hospitality, transportation, warehousing and logistics, and gaming. Tiers Point-Based Systems’ skills and salary thresholds do not allow TCNs (this category will soon include EEA migrants) to fulfil positions in those sectors, so that those sectors with low wages and high proportion of migrant labour are and will be unable to recruit workforce.

As small numbers of migrants can be particularly relevant as for specialised workers in particular sectors and in remote areas. In this sense an effort to look for tailored solutions – as encouraged by the Migration Advisory Committee and the Migration and Population Expert Advisory Group – seems particularly relevant as well as a deeper revision of the Shortage Occupation List.

In this context, it seems strategically important the inclusion of the Scottish refugee population in the labour market with programmes like the Migrant and Refugee Skills Recognition Pilot Project. As, even if this migrant group is relatively small – about 3000 people, including children and elderly people – because of its distribution in all the Scottish Local Authorities, it can significantly contribute to the economy of rural and remote areas.

Finally, the current Covid-19 pandemic on the one side, with its impact on the individual decisions of migrating (or not), showed the key role of the migrant working population through the difficulty of recruiting seasonal workers. On the other side, it does not allow to foresee how the economy and labour demand is going to evolve in the very next future, as well as how – giving new shape to national borders – it will modify the migration

strategy of individuals and groups. Concurrently the uncertainty of the way Brexit will be delivered at few weeks from the end of the transitional period troubles even more the waters, making particularly challenging for experts to propose policies' principles and frames.

GOOD PRACTICES

The following campaign can be considered as good practice – as result of the literature review and our analysis: Campaign “Lift the ban” to allow asylum seeker to work. The Lift the Ban coalition – 240 charities, businesses, trade unions, faith groups and think-tanks – asks to reform the rules so that people seeking asylum are allowed to work after waiting for six months for a decision on their asylum claim. They consider that half of the asylum seekers can be defined as “critical workers”; one in seven had previously worked in health or social care; and giving the right to work can benefit the public expenses by £98m a year.

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